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CONFERENCE-vol. 1

Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

15-17 May 2014
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Food and Tourism
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EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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ACADEMIC MESSAGE

at the 4th edition of BIOATLAS International Conference,
taking place at Transilvania University from Braşov, Faculty of Food and Tourism,
May, 15-17, 2014

The message identifies itself with a certitude of the professional prestige and of the scientific quality of excellence that this scientific event made proof of during the previous editions that took place between 2008 - 2012.

We emphasize the fact that this professional message has a triple academic meaning, as I am transmitting it on behalf of profile specialists from the Romanian Academy, from the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences and from the Academy of Scientists from Romania, having the intellectual and moral satisfaction to accomplish an honorable colleague duty towards the initiator and coordinator of this international conference, respectively Mr. Prof. Romulus Gruia, PhD, that I have met and particularly appreciated for more than three decades, as he has always been restless in seeking scientific truth and in permanent direct connection with international scientific news in the competence fields that made him known and that positively superpose with the present and of perspective complex themes approached in this volume, that I recommend with all my conviction and necessary responsibility.

Both for specialists and for consuming and beneficiary public from civil society, all news referring to alimentary safety and security, to their nutritive quality and biodisponibility, to traditional culinary diversity and to a polyvalent tourism, respectively ecologic, cultural, rural etc., are approached in this volume with high scientific and methodological accuracy at superior level of international standards, with scientific interpretations corresponding to international literature of specialty, bringing numerous and various theoretic and practical scientific contributions to the progress and development of thorough knowledge linked to agri-food biodiversity and biotechnology, gastronomic engineering, traditional foods and etno-pharmacology, agri-tourism, landscape management and development of tourism industry, IT applications and equipments corresponding to these fields.

We wish good luck to the ongoing of the scientific events of the conference.

Prof.univ.dr., Dr.HC (M) Alexandru T. BOGDAN

Correspondent Member of the Romanian Academy
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Bazele științifice ale unui proiect național, strategic și prioritar de bioeconomie agro-alimentară și de eco-economie turistică, prin valorificarea inovativă a capitalului teritorial românesc în secolul XXI

Alexandru T. BOGDAN¹, Romulus GRUIA², George Florea TOBĂ¹, Carmen PAȘALĂU³

Rezumat

România europeană și euroatlantică are în context globalizat prioritățile științifice recunoscute pentru conceptele de bioeconomie clasică (prin Acad. Grigore Antipa) și de bioeconomie modernă (prin Acad. Nicholas Georgescu-Roegen). Autorii studiului sintetizează contribuțiile acestor savanți, le coroborează cu alte contribuții științifice internaționale și, mai ales, aduc propriile lor rezultate originale prin bioeconomia rurală și agroalimentară în relație cu *integronica* (prin teoria integronicii ecoemergente și cea a modulizării sistemelor complexe, dar și prin conceptele de management integronic, alimentație integronică ș.a.), cu *biosofia* și *ecosanogeneza* (prin noile direcții și domenii de activitate cum ar fi Agricultura modulară, Zootehnia cibernetică, Ingineria gastronomică, Genetica biocenozelor), sau cu principiile moderne ale Economiei verzi sau Economiei albastre.

Analizele se fac cu exemple de tip studii de caz, referitoare la bioeconomia și integronica agro-alimentară în spațiul carpato-danubiano-pontic autohton cu deschidere europeană.

Un aspect important îl reprezintă sintetizarea recente concepții originale a savantului american Lester R. Brown (ales Membru de onoare al Academiei Române) referitoare la eco-economie, care este analizată inovativ în relație cu valorificarea turistică complexă a

Scientific basis of a national, strategic and preference interest project, of agri-food bioeconomy and of tourism eco-economy, by innovative valorization of the Romanian territorial capital in the 21st century

Alexandru T. BOGDAN¹, Romulus GRUIA², George Florea TOBĂ¹, Carmen PAȘALĂU³

Abstract

European and Euro Atlantic Romania has, under globalized context, scientific priorities recognized for the concepts of classical bioeconomy (due to Acad. Grigore Antipa) and of modern bioeconomy (due to Acad. Nicholas Georgescu-Roegen). The authors of the study synthesize the contributions of these scientists, coordinate them with other international scientific contributions and, especially, bring their own original results by rural and agro-alimentary bio-economy in relation with *integronics* (by the theory of ecoemergent integronics and the one of modulating complex systems, but also by concepts of integronic management, of integronic food etc), with *biosophy* and with *ecosanogeneses* (by the new directions and activity fields such as Modular agriculture, Cybernetic zootechny, Gastronomic Engineering, Communities Genetics) or with the modern principles of Green Economy or of Blue Economy.

The analyses are made with examples of the case study type, referring to bioeconomy and agri-food integronics in the native Carpathian-Danube-Pontic area with European opening.

An important aspect is represented by the synthesis of the recent original concept of the American scientist Lester R. Brown (chosen Member of honour of the Romanian Academy) referring to eco-

capitalului teritorial românesc, cu exemplificări privind capitalul uman, capitalul natural, capitalul cultural, capitalul agrosilvic, capitalul istoric și arheologic, inclusiv capitalul financiar-bancar.

Autorii propun în esență, în premieră tehnico-științifică și socio-economică un **Proiect Cadru de interes național, strategic și prioritar** pentru dezvoltarea etapizată bioeconomică agro-alimentară și eco-economică turistică a României, în secolul al XXI-lea, prin valorificarea intergată și eco-inovativă a potențialului bioresurselor de hrană din țara noastră corelată cu bunăstarea oamenilor, în proiecție socială și spirituală.

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economy, which is innovatively analyzed in relation with complex tourist valorization of the Romanian territorial capital, with examples concerning the human capital, the natural capital, the cultural capital, the agri-forest capital, the historic and archeological capital, including the finance-bank capital.

The authors essentially propose, as a technical-scientific and socio-economic premiere, a **Frame Project of national, strategic and preference interest** for bioeconomic agri-food and eco-economical tourist stage development of Romania, in the 21st century, through integrated and eco-innovative valorization of the potential of food bioresources in our country, in correlation with people well-being, in social and spiritual projection.

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EFFECT OF SOME THERAPIES ON POTATO PLANTLETS INFECTED WITH POTATO VIRUS X (PVX)

C. L. BĂ D Ă RĂ **

N. CHIRU ***

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to decrease the PVX (potato virus X) infection level, using electrotherapies, antiviral compounds (ribavirin and oseltamivir) in the tissue culture and several treatments (*Satureja hortensis* essential oils, H₂O₂ 1mM pH 5.6) applied to microplants acclimatised in green house. The biological material used in experiments was plants (variety Roclas, virus free biological material) mechanically inoculated using: PVX secondary infected plants from Bintje variety. Electrotherapy was applied in 9 variants: after washing and sizing explants, potato stems infected were exposed to either 40, 50 or 100 miliampers (mA), for 5, 10 or 20 minutes, followed by sterilization and immediate planting the axillary buds tip in vitro. Chemotherapy was undertaken with ribavirin (RBV) and oseltamivir (OSMV) (RBV 40 mg l⁻¹ + OSMV 40mg l⁻¹; RBV 20mg l⁻¹ + OSMV 40 mg l⁻¹; RBV 20mg l⁻¹ + OSMV 80mg l⁻¹). The first variant (RBV40mg l⁻¹ + OSMV40mg l⁻¹ added to the tissue culture medium + essential oils treatments of acclimatised plants) and the electrotherapy variant 10minutes at 100mA showed the highest rate of virus eradication, the maximum values of the therapy efficiency.

Keywords: *Satureja hortensis* essential oils, potato virus X, Ribavirin, Oseltamivir, electrotherapy

1. Introduction

Potato virus X (PVX), a *Potexvirus*, occurs throughout commercial stocks of most varieties and is responsible for many of the uncertainties and difficulties encountered in field inspections. When *potato virus Y* is present, synergy between these two viruses causes severe symptoms in potatoes.

Elimination of PVX from potato supply is essential for seed potato production. Also, in this study, the efficiency of some techniques (chemotherapy, treatments with *Satureja hortensis* oils, electrotherapy) in eliminating PVX and producing virus-free plants (cultivar Roclas) was evaluated.

Untill now, many compounds were tested for their antiviral activity but few were effective (Schuster, 1988). The most used substance is the ribavirine (Virazol), an analogue of guanosine, wich when added to the medium at concentrations of 10-50mg/l, was effective against PVX, PVY, PVS and PVM in potato (Cassel and Long, 1982, Klein and Livingston, 1982; 1983; Cassel, 1987; Griffiths 1990). However, ribavirin at active dose is usually phytotoxic causing an increase in culture time, death of some meristems, and the need for

frequent transfers to fresh media (Klein and Livingston, 1982). Regeneration of potato sprouts from meristematic cultures was delayed by 6 to 8 weeks (Cassel, 1987). To overcome toxicity, a low dose of ribavirine was supplied with another compounds (antimetabolites).The simultan use of the two chemicals alone was also beneficial, because ribavirin above 5 mg/l delayed meristem development. In our research we used oseltamivir (Tamiflu) for reducing the phytotoxic effect of the ribavirine.

The treatments with *Satureja hortensis* essential oils and antioxidants (H₂O₂ and ascorbic acid) applied to acclimatised plants (obtained planting the plantlets) could be beneficial for obtaining virus free material. The essential oils from *Satureja hortensis* L. (summer savory – Family *Lamiaceae*, order *Lamiales*) are known for its antiseptic (antifungal and antiviral) properties (Bedoux et al., 2010). Maybe some compounds of these oils could be implicated in the processus signaling against stress, in infected potato plants (Bădărău, 2012; Bedoux, 2010).

The methods employed to eliminate viruses from plants like meristem culture, chemotherapy and thermotherapy are technically demanding and time consuming. Electrotherapy, however, is a simple method of virus eradication without the

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need to use any special or expensive equipment. In this technique, the electric current is applied to plant tissues in order to disrupt or degrade viral nucleoprotein and eliminate its virulence activity (Lozoya-Saldaña et al., 1996, Sabry et al., 2009, Hormozi-Nejad et al., 2010).

The study aimed to evaluate the therapy efficiency of different chemotherapies and treatments with *Satureja h.* EOs applied to acclimatized plants and several electrotherapies, for PVX elimination in potato plants and find out the best one for virus eradication.

2. Material and method

Solanum tuberosum L. microplants cv. Roclas, tested virus free, were obtained from the Biotechnology Department of National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov. The microplants were transferred to greenhouse conditions 30 days. For obtaining positive material, a part of these plants were mechanically inoculated (Bădărău et al., 2012) using a PVX secondary infected source cv. Ostara.

The plants had previously tested positive by ELISA for PVX, to confirm the occurrence of single infection in the selected material. Tissue samples infected mother plants growing in the greenhouse were used as positive control. Stem segments excised from infected potato plants were transferred two times in MS medium with

antiviral compounds (sub-culture S1-26 days, sub-culture S2 -30 days). Plantlets obtained were divided into single node cuttings (about 1cm length) and sub-cultured on a fresh MS medium (sub-culture S3). After 28 days the plantlets were planted in pots, under greenhouse conditions.

Acclimatization, treatments with *Satureja hortensis* essential oils *Solanum tuberosum L.* plantlets submitted to chemotherapy, regenerated with roots and a well developed aerial part (5-7 leaflets), were removed from the culture medium and were acclimated in pots containing a sterilized mixture of soil, vermiculite and organic matter (2:2:1). After 7 after the injection with EOs suspension (14 days for beginning the acclimatization), the plants (excepting the controls) were sprayed twice a week with a *Satureja hortensis* essential oils suspension (1/1000, 5 ml each plant) (Bădărău et al., 2012). The survivor plants were indexed after 45 days from the transfer in the greenhouse.

DAS ELISA test. The analysis was performed following the protocol Clark and Adams (1977).

Chemotherapy was carried out on nodal cuttings with a single axillary bud and was undertaken with ribavirin (RBV, Sigma, Q0125) and oseltamivir (OSMV, Tamiflu, LaRoche) in the following variants: V1= RBV 20 mg l⁻¹ + OSMV 40mg l⁻¹; V2 = RBV 40mg l⁻¹ + OSMV 40 mg l⁻¹; V3 = RBV 20mg l⁻¹ + OSMV 80mg l⁻¹.

Table 1 Chemicals used for obtaining PVX virus-free plantlets

Chemicals	Activities	Chemicals Activities References
Ribavirin (Virazol) (1,β-D-Ribofuranosyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxamide) (Abbreviation in text RBV)	Broad spectrum anti-viral activities, ribavirin 5'-phosphate: inhibitor of inosine monophosphate (IMP) dehydrogenase	Cassel and Long (1982)
Oseltamivir (Tamiflu) [ethyl (3R,4R,5S)-5-amino-4-acetamido-3-(pentan-3-yloxy)-cyclohex-1-ene-1-carboxylate] (Abbreviation in text OSMV)	- an antiviral prodrug - used to slow the spread of flu virus (influenza A and B) by stopping from chemically cutting with its host cell. - produced from shikimic acid, an inhibitor of neuraminidase	Ward et al. (2005)

Electrotherapy treatments and regeneration of virus-free plants. Before the treatment, the greenhouse-grown inoculated plants were assayed by DAS-ELISA for verify the virus presence. Plants with similar levels of virus concentration were used to obtain stem segments containing axillary buds for electrotherapy. Each infected plant provided for approximately 3 nodal

cuttings that were subsequently used for electrotherapy treatment. From each stem one node was cut for the control (untreated by electrotherapy) and the stem segments remaining were immersed in sodium chloride solution (1M) in an electrophoresis tank and exposed to electric currents of 40, 50 and 100 mA for 5, 10 and 20 minutes using a power supply (Tehsys E250V,

fig. 1). After treatment, the stems were surface sterilized and rinsed three times in distilled water (fig. 1). Explants were prepared by dividing stem segments into nodal cuttings with a single axillary bud. The cuttings were cultured in test tubes containing MS medium (fig. 1). The experiment was repeated three times for each electrotherapy treatment.

In the aim to estimate an electrotherapy treatment leading to high rates of both virus elimination and plant regeneration, the Therapy Efficiency Index (TEI) was used (Lozoya-Saldaña et al. 1996). The TEI was estimated with the following relation:

$$TEI = \frac{\text{percentage of regenerated plantlets} \times \text{percentage of virus-free samples}}{100}$$

Fig.1. Electrotherapy treatments steps and equipment used to produce virus-free plants in potato *cv. Roclas*: Power supply and electrophoresis tank used for producing electric currents, single node explants prepared for *in vitro* culture, electrotherapy variants (intensity of the electric current) regeneration of electrotherapy treated plants on MS medium.

3. Results and discussions

Chemotherapy. Results showed that in all the variants and stage of the therapy, for both viruses, plants virus free were found (table 2).

Regarding the PVX infected plants, the chemotherapy variant V2 (RBV 40mg/l + OSMV 40mg/l) combined with treatments with *EOs* and *AO* of acclimatised plants, lead to the higher value for the virus elimination rate (100% PVX free plants) and for the therapy efficiency index (TEI): 87.5%. (table 2; fig. 2). Highest

values for the virus elimination rate (100%) were obtained in variant V3 (RBV 20mg/l + OSMV 80mg/l) combined with treatments *EOs* + *AO* too, but this treatments decreased regeneration rate (50%), also the TEI had lower values than in variant V2 (table 2; fig. 2). The absorbances values at 405nm (DAS ELISA) for the plants acclimatized obtained from the variant V2 (RBV 40mg/l + OSMV 40mg/l) and treated with *EOs* and *AO* were significantly lower (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Evaluation of chemotherapy and treatments with *Satureja hortensis* essential oils and H_2O_2 (1mM) on plants infected with potato virus X (PVX). The therapy efficiency of different variants and vegetation culture (B) The average values of absorbance in the plants regenerated from infected plants inoculated with a PVX viral strains (from cv Bintje secondary infection) Data are means \pm SD of 3 experiments (n=3). Bars with different letters differ significantly by Duncan's test ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2. Efficiency of chemotherapy, special treatments* of acclimatised plants on PVX infected material regeneration and virus eradication (cv. Roclas)

Variant of the treatment (for potato virus X infected plants)		Regeneration rate		Virus elimination rate	
		NPT/NRP	%	NPVF/NPM	%
V1	S1 (MS + antivirals)	5/6	83.3	1/5	40
	S2 (MS + antivirals)	10/12	83.3	5/10	50
	S3 (MS)	16/18	88.9	8/16	50.0
	Plants acclimatised untreated	6/6	100	3/6	50
	Plants acclimatised treated *	5/6	83.3	3/5	60
V2	S1 (MS + antivirals)	7/8	87.5	5/7	71.4
	S2 (MS + antivirals)	12/14	85.7	10/12	83.3
	S3 (MS)	22/24	91.7	18/22	81.8
	Plants acclimatised untreated	7/8	87.5	5/7	71.4
	Plants acclimatised treated *	7/8	87.5	7/7	100
V3	S1 (MS + antivirals)	5/8	62.5	4/5	80
	S2 (MS + antivirals)	7/10	70.0	6/7	87.5
	S3 (MS)	10/16	62.5	9/10	90
	Plants acclimatised untreated	4/6	66.7	3/4	66.67
	Plants acclimatised treated *	3/6	50.0	3/3	100

V1= MS +RBV(20mg/L) + OSMV(40mg/L); V2 = MS +RBV(40mg/L) + OSMV(40mg/L); V3= MS +RBV(20mg/L) + OSMV(80mg/L); MS =Murashige and Skoog medium; RBV=Ribavirine; OSMV=Osetamivir; NTP = number of tested plants (plants that survived); NRP = number regenerated plants; NPVF = number of plants virus free;

*Treatments with *Satureja hortensis* essential oils and H_2O_2 (1mM)

Electrotherapy

Application of electrotherapy on the potato cultivar Roclas resulted in partial elimination of PVX from potato tissues when the most severe treatments were applied (100 mA for 10-20 minutes). The figures 3,4 showed that the two viruses were not very different in responding to electrotherapy (excepting the variant 100mA, 10minutes). In spite of developing of many virus-free plants, diminishing levels of virus concentration were observed in all variants even if the regenerated plantlets remain infected, for both viruses (fig. 4). But the success of electrotherapy in producing virus-free plants

depends upon both plant regeneration and virus elimination rates. Usually, plant regeneration depends upon several factors, including genotype, physiological state of the explant, culture medium, the cultivation conditions and the interactions between these factors (Svetleva et al. 2003). The electric pulses are also reported as stimulants of plant differentiation *in vitro* (Hormozi-Nejad et al., 2010). It was demonstrated that regeneration of potato plant tissues could be improved by exposing explants to mild electric currents (Lozoya-Saldaña et al. 1996).

Fig. 3. Effects of electrotherapy treatments on the elimination rate of PVX in Roclas cv. infected material. Results = the mean of three experiments.

Fig. 4. Mean absorbances values of regenerated plants, using different electrotherapy treatments on potato plants (cultivars Roclas): OD in infected plants before electrotherapy (green dark bars) and in regenerated plants after electrotherapy which were ELISA positive (green bars) and ELISA negative (orange bars). Results = the mean of three experiments.

Fig. 5. Effects of electrotherapy treatments on the *Roclas* cultivar infected explants. Mean of the therapy efficiency index (TEI) for PVX infected and treated material. Results = the mean of three experiments. Bars with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test ($P < 0.05$).

Plant regeneration rate estimated as the ratio of the number of regenerated plantlets to the total number of cultured explants was 56.1- 77.2%. Usually, higher intensities of electric current affected the survival of explants and thus plant regeneration.

The results of the present research work show that the regeneration of explants *in vitro* is influenced by electrotherapy treatment and depends upon the electric current intensity. Many papers suggest that the regeneration rate of virus-free plants obtained after electrotherapy is higher than that of plants exposed to more conventional virus elimination techniques including meristem culture and chemotherapy (Jung-Yoon et al. 2003; Mahmoud et al. 2009). In our study we obtained good results regarding the regeneration rate when the oseltamivir was used or when the acclimatised plants were treated with *Satureja hortensis* EOs and AO.

Regenerated plantlets were tested for PVX infection by DAS-ELISA. A reduced concentration of virus was observed in all regenerated plantlets (fig. 4). On this basis, the mean virus elimination rates of *Roclas* cultivar explants exposed different periods to the three electric currents of 40, 50 and 100mA was 62/7%, 54.9% and 88.7% for PVX infected material (figure 3). An increase in the number of virus-free plants for both viruses was observed as the intensity of the electric current was raised. The highest virus elimination rate was obtained at the highest electric current (100mA) used in this study. Although raising the electric current

increased the mean virus elimination rate, it also decreased the mean plant regeneration rate, so TEI index has to be used as a basis in identifying the most efficient electrotherapy treatment. The TEI for the three electrotherapy treatments at 40, 50 and 100mA was estimated as 42.6, 44.6 and 64.3. The electric currents of 100 mA for 10 minutes resulted in the highest TEI value: 74.3 for PVX infected material (figure 5).

It has been postulated as a hypothesis that viral nucleoproteins may be denatured by when it is exposed to electric current (Lozoya-Saldaña et al. 1996). It has been suggested that denaturation of viral particles may occur during transport through the plasmodesmata in the apoplastic space. Inactivation of specific nucleoprotein that assist in cell-to-cell movement to three-dimensional structures leads to blockage, which prevents further penetration of virus particles to healthy cells (Hormozi-Nejad et al., 2010; Hull R., 2002). The basis of this phenomenon is still poorly understood.

4. Conclusions

This preliminary study revealed that chemotherapy (40mg/l RBV + 40mg/l OSMV), followed by treatments with *Satureja hortensis* EOs and AO of acclimatised plants on the one hand and the electrotherapy (100mA, 10 minutes) on the another hand, had effects on PVX elimination from potato plant tissues.

Further investigations are needed for combine chemotherapy + electrotherapy + treatments with EOs and AO of the

acclimatisated plants, for improvement and optimization of these techniques.

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References

- Bădăraș C. L., Mărculescu A., Chiru N., S. C. Chiru: *Benefic effects of essential oils treatments in healthy and potato virus Y infected plants of Solanum tuberosum L. (cv.Roclas) and Nicotiana tabacum(cv.White Burley)*. In: Romanian Agricultural Research, Vol. 29, 2012, p. 281-28
- Bedoux G., Mainguy, C., Bodoux, M., F, Marculescu, A., Ionescu, D.: *Biological activities of the essential oils from selected aromatic plants*. In: Journal of EcoAgroTurism, Transilvania University of Brasov, Vol. 6 (1), 2010, p. 92-100
- Cassel A. C. and Long R.D.: *The elimination of potato virus X, Y, S and M in meristem and explants cultures of potato in the presence of virazole*. In: Potato Research 25, 1982, p. 165-173
- Cassel, A. C.: *In vitro induction of virus-free potatoes by chemotherapy*. In: Biotrechnology in Agriculture and Forestry, Vol. 3. Potato (ed.) Y.P.S. Bajaj, p. 40-50, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, 1987
- Clark, M.F. and A.N. Adams: *Characterization of the microplate method of the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for the detection of plant virus*. In: Journal of General Virology, 34, 1977, p. 475-483.
- Griffiths, H.M., S.A. Slack and J.H. Dodds, : *Effect of chemical and heat therapy on virus concentrations in in vitro potato plantlets*. In: Canadian Journal Botanic, 68, 1990, p. 1515-1521
- Hormozi-Nejad, M. H., Mozafari J. & Rakhshandehroo F.: *Elimination of Bean common mosaic virus using an electrotherapy technique*. Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection, ISSN 1861-3829, 117 (5), 2010, p. 201-205
- Hull R.: *Induction of disease: Virus movement through the plant and effect on plant metabolism*. In: *Matthew's Plant Virology*, Fourth Edition, 2002, p.373-411
- Jung-Yoon, Y., S. Hyo-won, C. Young-Mee, P. Young-Eun: *Ribavirin, electric current and shoot tip culture to eliminate several potato viruses*. In: Journal of Plant Biotechnology, 5, 2003, p. 101-105.
- Klein, R. E. and Livingston, C. H.: *Eradication of potato virus X from potato with ribavirin treatment of cultured potato shoot tips*. In: American Potato Journal 59, 1982, p. 359-365
- Klein, R.E. and Livingston, C.H.: *Eradication of potato viruses X and S from potato shoot-tip cultures with ribavirin*. In: Phytopathology 73, 1993, p.1049-1050
- Lozoya-Saldaña, H., F.J. Abelló, G. García: *Electrotherapy and shoot tip culture eliminate potato virus X in potatoes*. In: American Potato Journal, 73, 1996, p.149-154.
- Mahmoud, S.Y.M., M.H. Hosseney, M.H. Abdel-Ghaffar: *Evaluation of some therapies to eliminate potato Y potyvirus from potato plants*. In: International Journal of Virology, 5, 2009, p. 64-76.
- Murashige, T. and F. Skoog: *A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassays with tobacco tissue cultures*. In: Physiologia Plantarum, 15, 1962, p. 473-497
- Sabry Y.M., Mahmoud, Maher H. Hosseney and Mamdouh H. Abdel-Ghaffar: *Evaluation of some therapies to eliminate Potato Y Potyvirus from potato plant*. In: International Journal of Virology, 5, 2009, p.: 64-76
- Schuster, G.: *Anthiphytovirale Verbindungen mit Guanidinstruktur*. In: Phytopathology Z. 103, 1982, p.44-86
- Schuster, G.: *Synthetic antiphytoviral substances*. In: Applied Virology Research 1, 1988, p. 265-283
- Steward Gray, Solke De boer, Kames Lorenzen, Jonathan Withworth, Philippe Nolte, Rudra Singh, Alain Boucher, Huimin Xu. 2010. *Potato virus Y an evolving concern for potato crops in the United State and Canada*. In: Plant Disease / Vol. 94 No. 12, 2010, p. 1384-1397
- Svetleva, D., M. Velcheva, G. Bhowmik: *Biotechnology as a useful tool in common bean (Phaseolus vulgaris L.) improvement*. In: Euphytica, 131, 2003, p. 189-200.
- Ward, P., Small, I., Smith, J., Suter, P., Dutkowski, R.: *Oseltamivir (Tamiflu) and its potential for use in the event of an influenza pandemic* In: The Journal of antimicrobial chemotherapy 55 (Suppl 1), 2005, p. 5-21.

A LABORATORY METHOD FOR THE DETECTION OF MECHANICAL DAMAGES AT POTATO SORTING

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Abstract: *Potato sorting is maybe the main technological operation in the potato industry, mainly because its role is to obtain marketable products that will respond to the consumers' expectations of aspect, size and freshness. This paper is aimed at studying the factors that could have an influence upon the technology of sorting potatoes and the biological effects of sorting the harvested potatoes that will be afterwards stored. There are studies the damages that appear at the contact between active organs of the potatoes sorting machines and the tubers and they are classified as mechanical damages. The quantifying of mechanical damages at potato sorting is a difficult element, because of the variety of the potatoes characteristics. It is being used a specific laboratory technique that can identify, quantify and also may prevent the mechanical damages at sorting potatoes.*

Keywords: *potato, sorting, damages, characteristics, laboratory technique.*

1. Introduction

To sort is an expression that is intended to explain that after its execution, the final mass will consist only is good and ready to use or ready to consume products. If the products that are going to be sorted are biological structures, the operation in cause may pose an influence on their characteristics, as to deteriorate them structurally. The deterioration process is a consequence of the contact between the products that are sorted and the surfaces of the technological equipment that does the sorting.

The technological operation of potato sorting consists in a series of phases that have the main goal of obtaining a final mass constituted only by whole, healthy and fresh potatoes. As to obtain a such type of mass, there should be adopted a specific equipment and an associated technology by which potatoes should not be damaged mechanically. Thus, the mechanical damages appear mainly as a consequence of a less controlled harvesting, because of the hard contact between the parts of the machines and the potatoes from the soil.

Potatoes are biological products or bodies that have a relative hard consistency, depending also by the variety. In all cases, potatoes are generally resistant to the damages caused mechanically. Thus, if contacts between them and other surfaces and bodies are consistent and frequent, mechanical damages are very susceptible.

Because of the fact that potatoes visual characteristics are not constant, this meaning that they have irregular forms and their color is not constant, it is very hard to find a method for the identification of several aspects, as damages caused mechanically or by other means.

Laboratory techniques used for the identification of mechanical damages at potatoes are relative simple methods as the methodology, but they are very hard to be interpreted [1].

2. Working methodology

The mechanical damages at sorting potatoes are caused mainly by the forces of contact between the tubers and parts of the sorting machine, as well as the kinetics of potatoes on the machine.

As to evaluate the degree of harmfulness (damage) at sorting, there were taken samples before sorting and after sorting. The only influence regarding the detection of mechanical damages at these samples consisted in the fact that they were harvested mechanically and this is an operation that also caused some damages [1].

The working methodology consisted in the sampling of potatoes from two varieties before sorting and after sorting and trying to evaluate the degree of harmfulness at those stages, depending on the potato variety (Fig. 1). The tests were done on the same sorting machine, at the National Institute of Research for Potato and Sugar Beet from Brasov (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

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Fig. 1 *The mechanical damages at potato sorting*

The sorting machine from the National Institute of Research for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov is composed by an elevating band that places the potatoes on the sorting table (Fig. 2) and continuously on the three sieves for separating potatoes on sizes (Fig. 3) [1].

Fig. 2 *Elevating band and sorting table*

Fig. 3 *Sorting sieves with three sizes*

The potatoes that were sampled for the evaluating of the mechanical damages were stored in specific conditions of 4...6 °C, controlled atmosphere and labelled adequately (Fig. 4) [3].

Fig. 4 *Potato stored for testing*

3. Methods and intended result

3.1. The description of the objectives

It is of interest for the research of improving of the potato sorting process the identifying of the vulnerable technological aspects or points that may have an influence upon the role of sorting potatoes that is to obtain final products that will correspond to the consumer's expectation of quality and will be able to be marketed.

After the examination of the sorting potatoes technology with the mentioned machine [2], [3] but also the potato sorting in general, it was concluded the fact that the only vulnerable point is the apparition of the mechanical damages.

Mechanical damages as a consequence of the contact between potato tubers and the parts of the sorting machine could appear, taking also into account that the machine in case has been projected and constructed also with the aim of preventing or reducing unwanted processes of damages, including the mechanical ones.

It is of interest for the specific research the identification of the degree of mechanical damages as a consequence of sorting. It should be clearly outlined that the harvest process has a strong influence upon the apparition, evolution and continues the process of mechanical damages, technologically speaking.

For the research of mechanical damages, it was adopted a laboratory technique of identifying and quantifying the mechanical damages. The technique identifies mainly the external damage, that's why it's suitable in the case of sorting [1].

3.2. The laboratory method

The testing method has the following phases:

- Potatoes that are aimed to be tested are very well washed by soil and other adherent materials; they are then measured and pondered as to be sampled for testing;
- It is being prepared a solution of 1,2 – dihydroxyl-benzene (*catechol*) of 1,5 % concentration;
- It is being measured the temperature of the solution;
- The solution is toxic and caustic, that's why it is mandatory to use plastic gloves at manipulating it;
- It is used a specific testing bin, made of plastic and endowed with a special sieve, for the immersing of the potatoes in the solution and their discharging from it [2], [3].

The **testing principle** consists in the reaction between the **wounded parts of potato tubers** and **1,2 – di-hydroxyl-benzene (*catechol*)**, with the forming of a **specific dark-red color** [2].

The dark-red color appears different as intensity, depending on:

- the degree of harming;
- the potato variety and color;
- the solutions concentration corresponding with the method and the time that followed the harvesting and sorting;
- the method adopted for harvesting and sorting, but both for the storing, after the case [1], [2], [3].

The **testing method** is presented above:

- The preparation of the potato tubers for testing: sampling, fractioning on sizes and weighing individually and globally (Fig. 5) [3].

Fig. 5 *Sampling potatoes for damages testing* [3]

- The potatoes washing of soil and other adherent elements from the soil (Fig. 6) [3].

Fig. 6 *Washing potatoes for testing method* [3]

- The preparation of the 1,2 – di-hydroxyl-benzene (*catechol*) 1,5 % solution (as specified in the method) (Fig. 7) [3].

Fig. 7 *The testing solution preparation* [3]

- The arrangement of the testing table and the measuring of the temperature of the prepared solution of 1,2 – di-hydroxyl-benzene (*catechol*); the determined temperature was 22,7°C (Fig. 8) [3].

Fig. 8 *The temperature of the testing solution* [3]

- The introduction of the weighed potatoes (the sample) in the prepared solution of 1,2 – di-hydroxyl-benzene (*catechol*) for 5 minutes (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10) [3].

Fig. 9 *Immersing yellow potatoes in catechol* [3]

Fig. 10 *Immersing red potatoes in catechol* [3]

- The discharging of the solution (Fig. 11) and the method interpreting [3].

Fig. 11 *Discharging the solution for interpreting* [3]

3.3. Method interpreting

The immersed potatoes in the *catechol* solution were arranged on the testing table:

- yellow potatoes before sorting;
- yellow potatoes after sorting;
- red potatoes before sorting;
- red potatoes after sorting.

After arranging the potatoes on the testing table, it was investigated the degree of reaction of wounded zones of tubers with the specific solution of testing [1], [3].

Fig.12 *Preparing for method interpreting* [3]

As it was mentioned in the Introduction, because of the fact that potatoes are biological bodies with irregular characteristics and that depend mainly on the variety, the interpreting of the method for mechanical damage identification is kind of difficult [1], [3].

- Method interpreting for yellow potatoes

It can be seen (Fig. 13) that there are some parts of the tubers that turned near to dark red (mainly the potato's sprouts). Taking a very good look at the samples, the surface of the tubers did not turn dark red and that can suggest the fact that there do not exist mechanical damages at a sufficient level as to create the specific reaction [1], [3].

Fig. 13 *Interpreting damages - yellow potatoes* [3]

- Method interpreting for red potatoes

Interpreting the method for red potatoes is more difficult, because of the fact that their color is very similar with the one of the specific dark red color in the case of positive reaction. One possible conclusion is that it should be adopted another method for this identification of damages or maybe potatoes are not damaged, as if they

Fig. 14 *Interpreting damages - red potatoes* [3]

4. Conclusions

Potatoes are biological bodies with irregular characteristics, depending mainly on the variety.

The process of sorting potatoes implies a direct contact between the tubers and the parts of the technological machines, including the harvesting and continuing with the storing. That's why mechanical damages at sorting have also influences from harvesting and storing.

Laboratory methods for the identifying of mechanical damages are not laborious, but are very hard to be interpreted.

The catechol test indicated that both yellow and red potatoes were not mechanically damaged. were, the specific color should appear anyhow [1], [3].

References

1. Edu, F. V.: Școala Doctorala a Universității Transilvania din Brașov – Referate din cadrul Programului de pregătire pentru doctorat. Brasov, 2011 – 2014.
2. University of Nebrasksa – Lincoln: *CropWatch, Bruise testing*, accessed March, 2014, [http://cropwatch.unl.edu/potato/bruise_testing].
3. National Institute of Research for Potato and Sugar Beet Brasov: *Notițe de laborator – Laborator Tehnologia și Calitatea Cartofului*. Brașov, 2014.

RESULTS ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF SOME POTATO VARIETIES (*SOLANUM TUBEROSUM* L.) SUITABLE FOR INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING AT THE POTATO RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT STATION TARGU SECUIESC

MIKE GABRIELLA *

Abstract: *The problem of discovering new sources of raw material for the food industry is now a major concern worldwide. This concern meets the both the diversification requirements, the improvement of the range of products offered to consumers and those of food supply to a growing global population.*

Our world is evolving at a staggering pace, time is one of the most important resources, so that the consumer society is moving towards a food market based on a superior capitalization of crop production, which ensures a high nutritional potential.

In recent decades, all over the world are taking steps to diversify and intensify main crops. The aim of the experiment was to check the potential of potato production in the case of the varieties suitable for industrial processing and to choose the most suitable varieties for processing, which can be grown in areas favorable for potato, depending on the level of fertilization.

Keywords: *potato, variety, production, dry matter content.*

1. Introduction

The extraordinary dynamics of the development of civilization that characterize modern society was determined by the results of scientific discoveries, technical and technological progress, that revolutionary changed the pace and the quality of life of mankind.

As a result of the growing demand in the quantity and quality of food offered to a growing population, agriculture suffers many changes, the major concern throughout the world is the discovery of new sources of raw materials and the orientation towards a food market based on a superior capitalization of crop production, which ensures a high nutritional potential.

To obtain high quality products, that ensure a diverse assortment it is intended the use of appropriate raw materials with superior parameters, that best meet the processing requirements.

Chemical and physical properties that the potato crop must meet in order to obtain starch:

-high dry matter content to ensure manufacturing yields

-skin as smooth as possible for easy washing with reduced water and energy

-low cellulose and albumin content

-well-developed starch granules with specific gravity

-the maturity of tubers should be ensured by harvesting after being perfected the biological and chemical process of the plant

The dry matter of the potato tubers contains a proportion of 60-80% starch. Researches has shown that for every 1% increase in dry matter content of potato is obtained with plus 1 kg finishes product per 100 kg peeled potatoes, increasing processing efficiency with 1%.

A potato tuber with a high dry matter content is floury, it gives a higher yield when processed.

It is well known, that the dry matter content of tubers increases with their maturity, except some decreases, that may occur at the end of the growing season, when losses by respiration exceed the rates of assimilation.

2. Materials and working methods

Varieties under study are: *Redsec*, *Luiza*, *Productiv* and *they* were created at the Potato Research and Development Station Targu Secuiesc. Production capacity of the studied

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varieties was determined by weighing potato tubers harvested from the field.

Experimental factors and their graduation:

✓ **Factor A – Potato variety**

- a₁ - Luiza
- a₂ – Productiv,
- a₃ – Redsec

✓ **Factor B – Type of fertilizer (NPK ratio)**

- b₁ – Ammonium nitrate(1:0:0)
- b₂ – Complex 20:20:0 (1:1:0)
- b₃ – Complex15:15:15 (1:1:1)

✓ **Factor C – Level of nitrogen (kg a.s./ha)**

- c₁ – N0, c₂ – N50 c₃ – N100 c₄ – N150 c₅ – N200 c₆ – N250 c₇ – N300

Fertilizers were applied at the seedbed preparation.

The experimental field was located according to the subdivided parcel method, on three repetitions. In all three experiments were made observations during the growing season and harvest. The calculation and the interpretation of the results were performed by the variance analysis method and to assess the significance of differences was used the multiple comparisons test.

The results obtained were statistically analyzed by linear regression and variance analysis.

3. Results and discussion

Regarding the size of the planting material, the highest percentage of commercial production, 94%, is achieved by using tubers with a diameter of 30-40 mm at planting. Compared to this size, by planting tubers with a diameter greater than 55mm, the relative commercial production significantly decreases to 92.7 %, a tendency that manifests itself in all experimental years.

Profitable potato crops can not be conceived without using chemical and/or organic fertilization. The fertilization must ensure the best possible exploitation of the productive potential of intensive varieties in the ecological condition in the area of the culture.

Potato plant, in the first period after plantation until it forms a foliar surface of abt. 200cm², extracts 96 % of the nutrients necessary for growth from the mother tuber and only 4 % from the soil through the root system (IANOSI, S. 2002). Initially the percentage of nutrients taken from the soil is very low, but this process intensifies rapidly, reaching its highest level at the beginning of flowering, when dry matter accumulation is most intense. According to the type of fertilizer, the applied dose and the assimilation rhythm of the rates among the main nutritive elements it is achieved the fertilization optimization through the optimization of accumulations. Our research has proposed this approach of potato fertilization for 3 perspective potato varieties created at the Potato Research and Development Station Targu Secuiesc.

In order to obtain a higher yield were studied 7 levels of fertilization and 3 types of fertilizers, representing ratios NPK 1:0:0 (ammonium nitrate), 1:1:0 (Complex 20:20:0) and 1:1:1 (Complex 15:15:15).

Influence of experimental factors on the total production of tubers

Levels of production achieved during the experimental years

Researches on potato fertilization with macro-elements at Targu Secuiesc in the period 2010-2012 indicate large differences in the effects of fertilization variants on potato yields in different years.

Table 1. Variation amplitude of productions in the experimental years

Year average (Tg.Secuiesc 2010 – 2012)					
Year	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
2010	30,42	16,9	51,1	9,54	31,4
2011	30,25	21,8	37,6	4,29	14,2
2012	30,90	17,5	38,9	5,50	17,8
Total	30,53	16,9	51,1	6,79	22,2

In 2010, with more favorable growing conditions for potato crop, stronger plant respond to fertilization, yields varied depending on the variety and fertilization between 16,9 t/ha and 51,1 t/ha (CV = 31,4%) (Table 1).

In 2011 and 2012, when the growing conditions were less favorable for potato crop, average yields were achieved close to that in 2010 (about 30 t/ha), due to the variants studied yield differences were much lower (CV = 14,2 and 17,8 %).

The production of tubers in fertilized variants in the case of the three varieties studied

The *Luiza*, *Productiv* and *Redsec* varieties have different behaviour due to growth conditions and differentiated fertilization.

The *Productiv* variety with an average production similar to the *Luiza* variety (about 28t/ha) exceeded with its maximum production this variety (44,5 t/ha to 38,5 t/ha).

The *Redsec* variety proved to be a variety with resistance to poor growing conditions and achieved the highest production levels in the experimental years, with a lower variation amplitude than those recorded by the *Luiza* and *Productiv* varieties. In the experiment, this variety achieved an average production of 34,7 t/ha and a maximum yield of 51,1t/ha (Table 2).

Tabel 2. Variation amplitude of productions obtained in the case of the three varieties studied

Variety average (Tg.Secuiesc 2010 – 2012)					
Variety	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
<i>Luiza</i>	28,22	16,9	38,5	5,41	19,1
<i>Productiv</i>	28,64	17,5	44,5	6,73	17,9
<i>Redsec</i>	34,72	23,1	51,1	6,20	17,9
<i>Total</i>	30,53	16,9	51,1	6,79	19,6

We can say that the *Redsec* variety has a higher ecological plasticity than the *Luiza* and *Productiv* variety.

Influence of N:P:K ratio on tuber production

The total production of tubers at Targu Secuiesc was weakly influenced, but positive due to the use of phosphorus, and phosphorus und potassium in

equal ratio with nitrogen, achieving an average increase of about 1t/ha. The favorable effect of the presence of phosphorus and potassium can be observed especially in the maximum production. The studied N:P:K ratios do not differ regarding the variation amplitude of productions due to the growing conditions, varieties studied and levels of fertilization (Table 3)

Tabel 3. Variation amplitude of productions obtained at different NPK ratios

Average NPK ratios (Tg.Secuiesc 2010– 2012)					
Ratio	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
1:0:0	29,79	16,9	46,9	6,48	21,6
1:1:0	30,57	17,2	46,7	6,57	21,4
1:1:1	31,22	17,2	51,1	7,36	23,5
Total	30,53	16,9	51,1	6,79	22,2

Influence of nitrogen doses on tuber production

On average the increase of nitrogen dose from 0 to 150 kg/ha has determined the increase of tuber production, above this level, on average were recorded decreases.

With the increase of the production up to N 100-150 can be observed a decrease of variation amplitude, at these levels the variation rate is the most reduced. Increasing fertilizer rates above these levels entails higher production variations due to the studied factors (Tabel 4).

Table 4. Variation amplitude of productions obtained at different nitrogen doses

Dose average (Tg.Secuiesc 2010 – 2012)					
Dose N kg. a.s./ha	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
0	24,66	16,9	36,1	5,10	20,7
50	29,40	19,4	38,5	4,90	16,7
100	32,98	19,9	37,8	4,48	13,6
150	34,41	23,3	44,7	5,02	14,5
200	33,63	21,1	50,4	7,85	23,6
250	30,38	17,5	51,1	8,14	26,8
300	28,48	20,6	39,9	6,23	21,8
Total	30,53	16,9	51,1	6,79	22,5

The behaviour of the *Luiza* variety at fertilization

Table 5. *Effects of fertilization on the total yield of potato in the experimental years in the case of Luiza variety*

NPK ratio	N dose kg a.s./ha	2010		2011		2012		Average	
		t/ha	Duncan test	t/ha	Duncan test	t/ha	Duncan test	t/ha	Duncan test
Ammonium nitrate 1:0:0	0	16.9	F	26.1	GH	31.3	BCD	24.8	FG
	50-0-0	19.4	EF	30.7	ABCDEFGH	33.4	ABCD	27.8	CDEF
	100-0-0	19.9	EF	32.3	ABCDE	33.1	BCD	28.4	CDE
	150-0-0	23.3	CDE	32.4	ABCD	31.8	BCD	29.2	BCD
	200-0-0	24.2	BCDE	29.4	BCDEFGH	28.9	CD	27.5	CDEF
	250-0-0	21.6	DEF	28.4	CDEFGH	34.9	AB	28.3	CDE
	300-0-0	21.4	DEF	28.6	BCDEFGH	28.6	CD	26.2	DEFG
Complex 20-20-0 1:1:0	0	17.7	F	25.9	H	28.7	CD	23.9	G
	50-50-0	20.5	DEF	31.9	ABCDEF	32.3	BCD	28.2	CDE
	100-100-0	24.2	BCDE	32.4	ABCD	32.8	BCD	29.8	BC
	150-150-0	25.5	BCD	33.7	ABC	35.4	AB	31.5	AB
	200-200-0	28.7	AB	30.1	ABCDEFGH	30.8	BCD	29.9	BC
	250-250-0	22.2	CDEF	28.2	CDEFGH	31.3	BCD	27.2	CDEF
	300-300-0	21.5	DEF	26.5	FGH	31.4	BCD	26.5	DEFG
Complex 15-15-15 1:1:1	0	17.2	F	26.4	FGH	35.8	AB	26.5	DEFG
	50-50-50	19.6	EF	29.4	BCDEFGH	38.5	A	29.1	BCD
	100-100-100	20.6	DEF	34.0	AB	34.8	AB	29.8	BC
	150-150-150	27.0	ABC	35.2	A	33.6	ABC	31.9	AB
	200-200-200	31.5	A	31.5	ABCDEFGH	35.9	AB	33.0	A
	150-250-250	21.5	DEF	27.9	DEFGH	27.9	D	25.8	EFG
	300-300-300	21.4	DEF	26.9	EFGH	31.3	BCD	26.5	DEFG
Average NPK ratio	1:0:0	20.9	E	31.7	B	29.7	C	27.5	A
	1:1:0	22.8	D	31.8	B	29.8	C	28.1	AB
	1:1:1	22.7	D	34.0	A	30.2	BC	28.9	A

DL (year)- 0.3 t/ha

DL(year* NPK ratio)- 1.5 t/ha

DL(NPK ratio)- 0.9 t/ha

DL(ratio* NPK dose)- 2.6 t/ha

As shown in table 5 the differences in production in different years can be observed both in the case of variants without fertilization and the productions obtained with different doses of N:P:K. In 2010, in the case of the *Luiza* variety,

without N:P:K fertilization there were obtained productions under 18t/ha. The increase of the fertilization levels resulted in the growth of productions with lower gains in the case of fertilization exclusively with nitrogen, the

maximum production being of 24,2 t/ha at the level of N200.

In the case of N:P fertilization at this level of nitrogen there were obtained 28.7 t/ha. It the fertilization was carried out with N:P:K, a statistically equal production level was obtained with 150 kg of nitrogen. Above the level of N200

the productions presented a tendency to decrease at all the studied N:P:K rates.

In the year 2010 there were found significant relations between the growth of the nitrogen level and the productions of the *Luiza* variety at all studied NPK rates.

Fig. 1. The influence of the nitrogen doses on the production at different N:P:K ratios in the year 2010 in the case of *Luiza* variety

In 2011 the influence of the nitrogen doses on the productions of the *Luiza* variety was similar in the absence and presence of phosphorus and that of the phosphorus and potassium, the

differences in production being smaller even when the nitrogen doses were close to the optimum (Fig.3).

Fig. 2. The influence of the nitrogen doses on the production at different N:P:K ratios in the year 2011 in the case of *Luiza* variety

Fig. 3. The influence of the nitrogen doses on the production at different N:P:K ratios in the year 2012 in the case of *Luiza* variety

Due to the climatic conditions of the year 2012, which determined the appearance of new tubers on the whole, there were registered higher productions than in the previous years at all variants of the *Luiza* variety which correlated easily with the growing nitrogen doses, especially in the lack of fertilization with phosphorus and potassium (Fig.4).

Conclusions

- The potato variety used for processing is paramount in ensuring effective returns
- The varieties used for processing must be productive and have a percentage of 20% dry matter
- The *Redsec* variety proved to be a tolerant to thermo-hydric stress
- The highest yields were obtained in the case of the *Redsec* variety, 51,1 t/ha
- The increase of fertilizer doses entails increase in the production
- The variation of the production levels in the researched ranges decreases in parallel with the increase of the fertilization levels up to N200. At higher fertilization doses can be registered increases in the coefficient of variation, which do not reach the level of those with low fertilizer doses.

- The productions with the lowest variations, due to the applied fertilizers; at these levels the coefficients of variation were 14,4 % and 10,4 % in the case of *Luiza* variety.

References

1. Banu, Constantin. *Tratat de industrie alimentară - Tehnologii alimentare*, Ed. ASAB, București, 2009;
2. Bende, I. *Tehnologia îmbunătățirea de cultivare a cartofului industrial pentru realizarea unui procent mai ridicat de amidon în tuberculi*, (manuscris) S.C.P.C. Targu-Secuiesc, 2002;
3. Berindei, Matei., Copony, W., Tofan, M. *Interpretarea unei experiențe cu îngrășăminte la cartof prin metoda funcțiilor de producție*, Anale ICCS, Cartoful vol.III, 1998, p. 183-201;
4. Berindei, M., Copony, W. *Interpretarea unor experiențe de camp cu îngrășăminte la cartof prin metoda funcțiilor de producție*, Anale ICCS, Cartoful vol.IV, 1999;
5. Borlan, Z., Hera, Cr. *Metode de aprecierea stării de fertilitate a solului în vederea folosirii rationale a îngrășămintelor* Ed.Ceres, Bucuresti, 1973;
6. Mike, *Luiza Valorisation supérieure de la pomme de terre*, Ed. Academic Press, 2009.

PLANT SOURCES USEFUL IN DIGESTIVE ENZYME PREPARATIONS

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Abstract: *Is well known that, enzymes are chemical special structures that fulfill multiple roles in the human body, from digestion to energy production, protein synthesis and toxins elimination, most metabolic processes are catalyzed or controlled by enzymes. Researchers have shown that the human body has a limited ability to produce digestive and other types of enzymes. This ability decreases with age and in certain diseases or if the diet is poor in enzymes (decreased consumption of raw foods: fruits, vegetables, etc., and increasing of industrial processed foods). In these deficiencies, the human body is subjected to additional stress and may appear different symptoms including: indigestion, flatulence, fatigue, infections, allergies, insomnia, and other serious diseases. On this reason, researchers from Research Department- Hofigal company, have been studying a variety of plant materials with an increased enzymatic potential in synergy with existing active substances from plants which supplement the body needs. The aim of the research, in this case, is to develop natural enzyme dietary supplements.*

Keywords: *medicinal plants,enzymes*

1. Introduction

Like any living body, plants have complex enzymatic equipment, with which to defend, to provide nutrition and perform synthesis. Some plants have a high content of enzymes that when they get into the human body, to improve digestion, absorption and metabolism of principal nutrients in food. These were called herbal enzymes.

Numerous studies, in the last decades, have shown that enzymes from plant organs (enzymes and microenzymes), have special effects on the human body, normalizing digestion, metabolism and tissue respiration. Plant enzymes have the advantage of being caught as in a network by vegetable fiber plant and shows a greater resistance to degradation factors and also are released slowly into the body.

2. Materials And Methods

The main plant sources enzyme studied were: Seabuckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*)- fruits (fresh and dried and ground conditions spared), Aloe vera juice, Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*)-leaves (fresh and dry ground conditions spared), flax seeds (*Linum usitatissimum*), Parsnip (*Pastinaca sativa*) - fresh root. The plant material was analyzed in fresh and dry conditions,

knowing that the plant enzymes are labile protein substances that are easily destroyed by heating to temperatures exceeding 40°C, in prolonged contact with air or even by simple centrifugation. With regard to the enzyme analyses, regardless of what stage they're in, they fulfil the requirements of the European Pharmacopoeia, complemented with those of other internationally circulating pharmacopoeias, and of the quality conditions pertaining to Hofigal's Quality Philosophy.

The Research Laboratories are furnished with modern equipment, in accordance with the practices, standards and requirements, where the raw materials were analysed.

The methods used for enzyme determinations are common methods.

Hydrolases have an important role in the metabolism of food substances in the body because they break down large molecules, contained in food, into simple molecules who are better assimilated. Hydrolases are enzymes that catalyze hydrolytic cleavage of substrates resulting in dissolution of bonds between the atoms of carbon and other atoms, by using water.

Thus:

The activity of α -amylase was determined spectrophotometrically at 540nm. This method uses the reducing groups released by enzymatic hydrolysis of starch, to reduce 3,5-dinitrosalicilic acid. An enzyme unit is represented by of 1 μ mol

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of reduced molecule per minute at 37 ° C and pH = 6.9.

Protease activity is determined by the digestion of casein used as substrate.

One unit of activity is the amount of enzyme that releases acid-soluble fragments equivalent of 0.001 absorbance units (A-280/minute at 37 ° C and pH = 7.8).

Lipase activity was performed volumetric from olive oil.

The amount of fatty acids resulting from the splitting of lipase substrate is measured by titration with standardized dilute NaOH solution. The amount of NaOH solution required to neutralize free fatty acids, is proportional to lipase activity.

One unit of lipase activity is defined as corresponding to one mole of fatty acid released by hydrolysis of triglycerides in olive oil, according to analysis at 37 ° C, pH = 7, reaction time = 60 minutes.

3. Results And Discussion

Enzymes are secreted with beautifully orchestrated precision by your digestive organs to accelerate the breakdown of food (carbohydrates, proteins, and fats) so your gut can extract and distribute the nutrients that are locked inside. They also assist you in absorbing these nutrients and eliminating what can't be used. Without enzymes, food would just sit in your gut and slowly rot.

There are several enzymes with specialized roles – too many to describe here – but they fall into general categories: lipases that break down fat, amylases that handle carbohydrates, and proteases that work on proteins.

The human body produces digestive enzymes capable of digesting the main components of food proteins, carbohydrates and fats.

Digestion of food is done in several phases starting in the mouth and continues in the stomach and small intestine.

Specific enzymes for each phase of digestion decompose different kinds of food. A enzymes

for the digestion of proteins, for example, does not have any effect on the starch; active enzyme in the mouth will not be active in the stomach. This process is balanced by the acidity.

Each part of the digestive tract has a different degree of acidity, which allows certain enzymes to act, while inhibiting the action of others.

The body's enzymes start digesting food in the mouth and continues to "work" in the stomach, plant enzymes (present in natural foods) are joined and become active in stomach, and after that contents move to the duodenum (the initial portion of the small intestine), where pancreatic enzymes break down food into simple molecules.

Final breakdown into the small fragments takes place in the terminal portion of the small intestine. Exogenous and endogenous enzymes act synergistically, digesting food and providing food for the cells to keep them healthy.

Natural diet in enzyme therapy is determined by the knowledge of the human digestion.

Therefore, studying and comparison of the results obtained from selected plant material with the highest content in digestive enzymes, will be producing plant enzyme supplements with the highest content in interest ones.

These enzymes were dosed in selected plant material:

- amylases (U/g/min),
- lipases (U/g/min),
- proteases (U/g/min),
- acid-phosphatases (U/mg/min),
- alkaline-phosphatases (U/mg/min),
- invertases (U/mg/min).

Through a correlation of R & D activities with industrial and environmental policies we could effectively use a valuable source of raw material in nature and greatly improve the management of local resources /national /world of spontaneous and cultivated.

Studies will be made to develop new products with natural enzymatic content interest.

The graphical results of compared plants were:

Fig. 1 Comparative content of amylases dosed in fresh and dried plant material

For amylases content from analyzed plants can make the following observations:

For the seabuckthorn, parsley and parsnip the amount of enzymes did not differ significantly at the fresh material and the dried one.

The significantly differences between the values of amylases from fresh and dried Aloe leaves can be attributed at the concentration process of fresh Aloe juice.

Fig. 2 Comparative content of lipases dosed in fresh and dried plant material

In this figure may notice significant amounts of lipase distinct at Seabuckthorn fruits, Parsley and Aloe vera.

-Meanwhile, for the Parsnip and Flax seeds the differences are not significant.

Fig. 3 Comparative content of proteases dosed in fresh and dried plant material

Comparing the values of proteases, is seen much better that we have higher values for Parsnip, Parsley and Seabuckthorn. These

differences are as expected and in close correlation with climatic factors, with the content of substrate content.

Table 1 Comparative content of enzymes in fresh and dried plant material

No	Dosed enzymes	Plant Material									
		Seabuckthorn-fruits		Aloe vera-leaves		Parsley-leaves		Flax seeds		Parsnip-root	
		Fresh	Dried	Fresh	Dried	Fresh	Dried	Fresh	Dried	Fresh	Dried
1	Amylases U/g/min	2.7	13.3	34.0	278	0.1	0.3	251.5	271.5	2.1	5.6
2	Lipases U/g/min	480	882	251	370	129	395.2	132	158	75	111.6
3	Proteases U/g/min	18	27	1.4	2.5	1.2	4.6	5.1	6.1	2.1	8.1
4	acid-phosphatases U/mg/min	1.2	5.02	> limit	> limit	0.5	3,5	> limit	> limit	> limit	> limit
5	alkaline-phosphatases U/mg/min	>limit	>limit	2.5	6.3	5.06	8.9	4.2	7.9	2.1	5.7
6	Invertases U/mg/min	1	4.8	0.1	9.8	1.2	4.6	0.1	0.3	12.86	18.9

Therefore, studing and comparison of the results obtained from selected plant material with the highest content in enzymes of interest, will be producing plant enzyme supplements with the highest content in interest enzymes. Plant material with the highest content in enzyme dosage are : Aloe vera > Seabuckthorn > Parsley > Flax> Parsnip.

4. Conclusions

The study presented for a group of interest plant enzymes used for digestion particularly shows significant variation in the amount of enzyme from a plant to another, as well as the fresh plant to dried plant. Thus: the lipase content in the form of interest ..Seabuckthorn>Aloe>Parsley, for fresh and dry plants; for amylase: Aloe>Flaxseeds and for protease:Seabuckthorn>Parsnip>Flaxseeds>Parsley>Aloe.

The researchers from Research Department-Hofigal company, have been studied a variety of plant materials with an increased enzymatic potential in synergy with existing active substances from plants which supplement the body needs, to develop natural enzyme dietary supplements.

Supplementing food with enzymes, from vegetable source, is eliminate risks while bringing multiple and significant proven benefits in human health.

References:

1. Dunaway-Mariano D (2008). "Enzyme function discovery". *Structure* **16** (11): 1599–600.
2. Thomas G. Villa „Enzybiotics-Antibiotic Enzymes as Drugs and Therapeutics“ 2010
3. D.C. Cojocaru „Enzimologie generala” Ed Tehnopress , 2007, Iasi
4. Arthur R. Schulz „Enzyme Kinetics”: Multi-enzyme Systems, 1995
5. P.J.F. Henderson, „Techniques in Life Sciences, Protein and Enzymes Biochemistry, Vol B1 Ed KF Tripton) Elsevier, Ireland 1995
6. Cambou, B. & Klibanov, A. M. (1984). Unusual catalytic properties of usual enzymes. In *Enzyme engineering*, vol. 5, ed. A. I. Laskin, G. T. Tsao & L. B. Wingard Jr, pp. 219-23. New York: New York Academy of Science

BULK PRODUCTS SEPARATION ON A STEPPED SCREEN SURFACE

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Abstract: *The results of analytical study of average speed of bulk product vibratory displacement during separation on steeped clothing are represented in this work.*

Keywords: *sieve separator, vibratory displacement, title angle of a step, bulk product, horizontal oscillations, deck plate.*

1. Introduction

Problem statement and its connection with the most important scientific and practical tasks. Separators using harmonic oscillations are used not much for separation of grain crops and other bulk products. Advantage of such separator is lesser electricity energy consumption in comparison with vibration machines using vertical oscillations or oscillations at an angle [1, 2]. Characteristic feature of such separator is an operative device which represents a stepped screen (Fig. 1). Speed of vibratory displacement of bulk product on a screen is the most important parameter for any sieve separator. Literature review shows that at present there is no a theory for determination of vibration displacement speed of a stepped sieve separator sufficiently close to practice that prevents full value scientific development and wide practical implementation of separating machines of such type which are characterized by the lowest electrical energy consumption among vibration oscillating separators.

The purpose of the article is to prove theoretical principals of vibratory displacement of product on steeped clothing under horizontal harmonic oscillations of an operative devise on the experimental base.

2. Materials and methods

The operational schemes of a stepped sieve separator for bulk products separation into fractions are represented in the sources [1, 2, 3]. Fig. 1 shows fragments of oscillatory displacement according to the experiment with a pattern of a bulk product particle. Frequency of sinusoidal horizontal oscillations of a deck plate during performance of the experiment amounts to 18 Hz, amplitude is 0,006 m. For analytical consideration of the stages of this process we shall accept the XOY coordinate frame associated with a deck plate (Fig 2) in which we shall consider motion of product particles with weight m at the moment of commencement of upslide motion on clothing of a step.

Fig. 1. Fragments of fast video record of the process of vibratory displacement of a particle patten on a screen surface:

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We accept a particle with weight m as a material point on which earth gravity mg has an effect (g - gravitational acceleration), normal reaction N , inertial force I , frictional force $F_{T p}$. Due to short range of throw and

sufficiently high density of the transported product we hypothesize that air resistance does not have noticeable effect on the process of particle displacement and in our case it can not be taken into account as well as we idealize the particle as a product layer of the same weight.

Fig. 2. Scheme of forces acting on a product particle.

Deck plate movement to the left from MEP (medial equilibrium position) shall be deemed as beginning of a period of oscillations, measuring phase angles and time from MEP. To the left from MEP the product moves along with a deck plate and when movement to the right after passing MEP and

when OE (operating element) $\ddot{x} > 0$ and $\dot{x} < 0$ the inertial force compels the product to negative displacement towards X axle by sliding on an angled deck surface.

Lest's compose a force equation acting on a product particle along X and Y axils on a stage of sliding:

$$\begin{cases} m \ddot{x} = mA\omega^2 \sin \omega t + F_{mp} \cos \alpha + N \sin \alpha, & (n p \sin \omega t < 0) \\ m \ddot{y} = -mg + N \cos \alpha - F_{mp} \sin \alpha, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where t - current time. Friction force $F_{mp} = \pm \mu N$. After long-term mathematical transformations we received a number of equations for various values and phase angles

which are required for receiving of the formulas of total speed of vibratory displacement of the product.

$$\bar{\xi} = \frac{\omega}{2\pi \cdot \text{floor}\left(\frac{\varphi_2}{2\pi}\right)} \left[\begin{aligned} & - \frac{A(\sin \omega t_1 - \sin \omega t_0)}{1 + \text{tg} \alpha \left(\frac{\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha}{\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha} \right)} + \frac{A \omega \cos \omega t_0 (t_1 - t_0)}{1 + \text{tg} \alpha \left(\frac{\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha}{\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha} \right)} + \\ & + \frac{g(\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha)(t_1 - t_0)^2}{\left(1 + \text{tg} \alpha \left(\frac{\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha}{\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha} \right) \right) 2(\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha)} - r + A \sin(\omega t_1) + \\ & + \left[\begin{aligned} & - \frac{A \omega (\cos \omega t - \cos \omega t_0)}{1 + \text{tg} \alpha \left(\frac{\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha}{\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha} \right)} + \\ & + \frac{g(\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha)(t_1 - t_0)}{1 + \text{tg} \alpha \left(\frac{\sin \alpha + \mu \cos \alpha}{\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha} \right) (\cos \alpha - \mu \sin \alpha)} + \\ & + A \omega \cos(\omega t_1) \end{aligned} \right] \times (t_2 - t_1) \end{aligned} \right] \cdot (2)$$

3. Results and discussions

We take values of traveltime parameters from rational parameters range: $A=0,007$ m, $v=20$ Hz (ω , rad/s) recommended by the source [2]. On the grounds of the formula (2) we determine average speed of bulk product vibratory displacement. Speed will be determined depending on α - a tilt angle of the step and μ - a coefficient of external friction. Range of values α - a tilt angle should be selected with the range of 17...40 degrees for receiving the most complete speed dependence from an angle α . Range of μ coefficient values will be selected from values interval of various grain crops on various clothings within the limits of 0,3...0,8 [2]. Time points t_0 , t_1 , t_2 in a formula (2) are determined as in [3].

Analysis of the Fig. 3 shows that changes of tilt angle values of α step and μ friction coefficient lead not only to change of bulk product vibratory displacement speed, but also to change of a motion vector of a partical into contrary one.

The reason of this, when values $\alpha=...18...21$ degree, is that the frictional force $F_{mp} = \mu N$ depends upon N , its value is proportional to α and decreases along with it that is why the product slides on angled clothing on a previous step to the right (Fig. 2),

and when deck movement to the left the product holds on it by a vertical surface of the step.

When $\alpha=35...40...$ degree the product with any μ will not have reverse motion as frictional force $F_{mp} = \mu N$ is much greater due to a greater N value therefore the product on a sliding stage on an angle surface with a deck motion to the left (Fig. 2) moves more slowly that does not admit its sliding off on a step at the right. And at the end of the sliding stage being near a step top the product is separated away from its angled surface and passes on the next step to the left.

Range of values of α angle =22...34 degree is of special interest. In a greater or lesser degree vibratory displacement speed depends upon traveltime parameters, though according to [2] graphical dependance shown in Fig. 3 change of motion speed of the product can in some degree be corrected by a step geometry and μ coefficient, that is of prime importance for reverse motion of the product at the right X axle where speed value is greater in a module (Fig. 2).

Detailed consideration of the range of values of α angle =22...34 degree (Fig. 4) proves analytically possibility of multidirectional vibratory displacement of bulk product when α constant value due to different μ values. This allows us to use μ as a separation criterion.

Fig. 3. Average speed of vibratory displacement ξ_{avg} depending on α - a step angle =17...40 degree and μ - friction coefficient ($A=0,007$ m, $V=20$ Hz).

Fig. 5 illustrates a side view of a diagram of Fig. 3 wherefrom we can draw conclusion that under traveltime parameters of $A=0,007$ m, $V=20$ Hz, the most relevant for fractional division of bulk mass is the value of a friction coefficient $\mu=0,4.....0,7$.

4. Conclusions

Under selected traveltime parameters and according to our analytical investigations the vibratory displacement speed will be no more than 0,2 m/s. But at that we can get three fractions from one stepped screen. Two will be overlaid with different μ friction coefficient and

as consequence different displacement direction and one fraction will be out-siftings. And it can be additionally operated on by change of traveltime parameters at a speed of vibratory displacement. The perspective of the further studies in this direction. In perspective it is necessary to carry out a number of experiments of vibratory displacement of grain-crops and their additions. Creating artificial mixtures in practice to check possibility of multidirectional vibratory displacement and make sure of validity of the process of screening and frictional separation simultaneously, to get corresponding photo documents.

To specify the developed theory according to the obtained results of the experiments.

Fig. 4. Average speed of product vibratory displacement depending upon α step angle =22...34 degree and μ frictional coefficient.

Fig. 5. Average speed of product vibratory displacement depending on α step angle =22...34 degree and μ frictional coefficient (side view).

References

1. Falko A.L. Expediency of use of harmonious fluctuations of working body of a separator in a horizontal plane. / A.L. Falko, A.V.Kovalenko // Modern directions of technology and mechanisation of processes of processing and food manufactures.: The edition of scientific works. Release 119, - Harkov: HNTUAC of Peter Vasilenko. - 2011. p. 161-166.
2. Falko A.L. Conceptual of a basis of creation of vibrating cars for calibration and separation of grain and vegetable cultures: the monography, DonNUET / A.L.Falko, I. N. Zapletnikov, Donetsk - 2012. - 178 p. - ISBN 978-966-385-268-3 BBK 30.605.
3. Falko A.L. Dimensional classification of loose foodstuff: the monography, DonNUET / A.L.Falko, Donetsk: 2009. - 215 p.-ISBN 978-966-385-16

STYDYING OF THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF THE CORRUGATED PAPERBOARD BY USING OF FEM BASED COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

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Abstract: FEM-based computer simulations are used to perform study on the influence of the tensile strength of corrugated paperboard by its basic geometric parameters. For that purpose, 3D model of a corrugated paperboard panel is built and subjected to tensile loading. Experimental results published by other authors are used to define the mechanical properties of the layers and to verify the reliability of the model.

Keywords: FEM-based simulations, stiffness, corrugated paperboard, tensile strength.

1. Introduction

Corrugated paperboard is the most frequently used material for making of vast variety of packages, post-displays used in the advertisement, decorative furniture, pieces of art and many others. The reasons which make this material preferred for so many designers are mainly its low price, its lightness, its capability to withstand external loads, its ability to absorb vibrations [3] and protect packed items during transportation and ability to contain heat [4] which makes it suitable for catering.

Corrugated paperboard is a multilayered structure which most often consists of 3 layers. Two external layers which are flat and one internal between them which is corrugated. The external flat layers are called “liners” and the internal is known as “flute”. Common structure of the corrugated paperboard is shown on figure 1. International standards specify several types of flute based on two geometric parameters [5]. These are the pitch of the flute and the height H. These parameters are visually shown on figure 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the multilayered structure of the corrugated paperboard with the basic geometric parameters shown

Presently the engineers who deal with the design of products of corrugated paperboard use formulas to calculate dimensions of their

structures based on the external loads which are expected to occur. These formulas however, give results which are found to be severely inappropriate in many cases when actual tests are conducted. Because of this, the engineers are left to make decisions entirely based on their personal experience and sometimes even guesses. Prototype of the product is produced and subjected to experiments. If it does not meet the strength requirements, changes are done in the construction and another prototype is produced and tested. This cycle repeats until all the requirements are met [2].

This cycle could be shortened and the number of prototypes minimized if advanced methods for design are used [2].

Such methods include the implementation of computer FEM-based simulations in order to obtain distribution of the stress and deformation of 3D geometric model of the designed structure.

The complex multilayered structure of the corrugate paperboard and the lack of information regarding its equivalent mechanical properties pose significant difficulties for the use of such methods.

Using experimental data on the mechanical properties of flat paperboard samples used to make the layers of corrugated paperboard, a FEM-based computer simulation study is conducted over corrugated paperboard geometric models with different values for the pitch P and the height H (see figure 1), subjected to tensile loading.

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2. Materials and methods

For the purpose of the study a geometric 3D model of corrugated paperboard sample is built. In order to perform stress and deformational analyze of this model by using FEM-based computer simulations, some mechanical properties of the materials which are used to make the samples are necessary. The mechanical properties of materials are determined by running experimental tests. In this case the results published by another authors who conducted an experimental studies on samples of flat paperboard and corrugated paperboard [1] are used. For that reason, the dimensions of the 3D geometric model which is built are chosen to be correspondent to the dimensions of the samples the authors tested. This model is shown on figure 2.

Fig. 2. 3D geometric model of the corrugated paperboard

The model is then meshed with *Shell* type of finite elements. This type of element is chosen because of the small thickness of the layers. The elements are quadratic. The elements of the flat layers are all the same size – 2 mm, while the elements of the corrugated layers are different in size which vary from 0,5 to 1 mm. This is due to the more complex geometric configuration of this layer. There are several reasons to chose these values for the size of the elements in the mesh. One reason is related to the lowering of the time and computer resources necessary for calculations and another reason is related to the need of having coincident nodes from the mesh of the flute and the mesh of the liners. These coincident nodes are necessary at the process of defining the contact conditions between the layers. The entire mesh consists of 7636 nodal points and 2399 elements (figure 4). Several trial simplified studies are conducted with different dimensions of the elements (all having 0,5 mm. as factor) to check if the results are independent to the density of the mesh. This check show that the difference is small enough to be ignored.

Each shell element has 8 nodal points with 6 degrees of freedom at each. These are the translations along the 3 axes and the rotations

around them. This is schematically shown on figure 3.

Fig. 3. Shell element with 8 nodal points and 6 degrees of freedom

Fig. 4. Geometric model of the corrugated paperboard sample with mesh of shell elements

Boundary conditions are defined by applying fixed restrains of all nodal points from one side of the model. This is done by setting all degrees of freedom to these nodes to be equal to 0. Loading force is applied to the nodes on the opposite side of the model. The locations of the restrains and the external loads as well as their directions are chosen in a way so they correspond to the conditions of the experimental tests described by the authors [1]. Schematically this is shown on figure 5.

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the boundary conditions and the applied external load

The magnitude of the applied load increases in steps by 8 N from 0 to 160 N.

3. Results and discussions

The results from the computer simulations are used to obtain predicted equivalent “stress – strain” curve of the geometric model of the corrugated paperboard. This curve is compared with a curve obtained after experimental test of samples of corrugated paperboard, which is published in [1].

Both curves are shown on figure 6.

Fig. 6. “Stress-strain” curves – experimental and obtained by computer simulation

The comparison shows good coincidence of the theoretically determined curve and the one obtained by the means of experimental tests by [1]. A conclusion can be drawn that the proposed model can be used for further studies.

Figure 7 shows the distribution of the equivalent stress (von-Misses) at the maximal load of 160 N. Figure 8 shows the distribution of the deformation at the same magnitude of the external loading force.

Fig. 7. Distribution of the equivalent stress [MPa] at maximal load of 160 N

Fig. 8. Distribution of the deformation

It can be seen from figures 7 and 8 that there are lower values of the stress and the deformation around the places where the contact occurs between the liners and the flute.

Figure 9 shows the distribution of the plastic deformation at the maximal load of 160 N. One can see from this distribution that the liners sustain larger irreversible deformation than the flute. The areas which are further from the places where contact occurs experience bigger plastic deformation.

Fig. 9. Distribution of the plastic deformation

The study continues by building 6 additional geometric models with different values for the H parameter but constant value for the pitch P=8 mm. The H parameter for these models differ by 0,5 mm and are as follows: 1,6; 2,1; 2,6; 3,1; 3,6 and 4,6 mm. They are then subjected to tensile loading under the same conditions. The results are used to obtain 6 additional predicted equivalent “stress-strain” curves – one for each model. These curves are used to determine the equivalent modulus of elasticity by calculating the tangent of the slope of their linear sections. It should be noted that these values of the equivalent modulus of elasticity have the meaning of predicted values at those geometric parameters. This is why the term predicted modulus of elasticity shall be used. Actual values for modulus of elasticity and other mechanical characteristics can only be obtained by experimental tests of actual samples.

Figure 10 shows the dependency of the predicted modulus of elasticity on the H.

Fig. 10. Dependency of the predicted equivalent modulus of elasticity on the H parameter

The study continues by building 8 more models with the purpose to check how the pitch of the flute influences the predicted equivalent modulus of elasticity. These models have different values for P as follows: 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9 and 10 mm. The H parameter is equal for all – 4,1 mm. These models are also subjected to tensile loading and predicted “stress-strain” curve for each one of them is obtained and predicted values for the equivalent modulus of elasticity. Graphical representation of the dependency of the predicted equivalent modulus of elasticity is shown on figure 11.

Fig. 11. Dependency of the predicted equivalent modulus of elasticity on the pitch of the flute

4. Conclusions

The conducted studies of the corrugated paperboard by the means of FEM-based computer simulations shown how the equivalent modulus of elasticity is expected to vary at the different values for the pitch of the flute and the height H.

Results show that the increase of H and P results in the lowering of the rigidity of the corrugated paperboard.

References

- [1] Allaoui S., Aboura Z., Benzeggagh M.L., Phenomena governing uni-axial tensile behaviour of paperboard and corrugated cardboard, Composite Structures 87 (1), pp. 80-92, 2009
- [2] Gospodinov. D., Hadjiiski W., Using of contemporary methods for enginery analyze for optimization of corrugated paperboard packages, University of Food Tehchnologies – Plovdiv – Scientific Works, Volume LVI, Issue 2, p. 319-324, 2009
- [3] Kirwan M.J., Paper and paperboard packaging technology, ISBN-10: 1405125039, 2005
- [4] Singh S. P., Burgess G., Singh J., Performance Comparison of Thermal Insulated Packaging Boxes, Bags and Refrigerants for Single-parcel Shipments, Packaging Technology and Science, 21: 25-35, 2008
- [5] Steadman R. Part 2. Special situations – mechanical properties of products corrugated board. Handbook of physical testing of paper, vol. 1. CRC; 2001

RESEARCH REGARDING CONVECTIVE DRYING OF FRUITS

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Abstract: *The paper presents results of research on convective drying of apples in a dryer with hot air circulating and analysis parameters that influence the efficiency of dehydration.*

Keywords: *dryng, apples, foodstuff.*

1. Introduction

The thermal processing of vegetables and fruits is a process with profound implications in technology, sensory and nutrition.

The most important operations that can be performed in the thermal processing are: preheat, scalding, boiling, drying, dehydration, pasteurisation, sterilization and roasting.

Among the advantages of thermal processing, we can mention:

- reducing the amount of moisture contained in the product, which causes slowing or temporarily stopping biological functions or physicochemical reactions, increasing resistance to storage;
- reducing the number of microorganisms and enzyme inactivation, which occurs even when the sterilization or pasteurization of the product is not intended, with a positive effect in avoiding the degradation of the product;
- changes in the structure of plant tissue: increased strength, weakening internal links (soaking), gelation, etc.;
- removal of air from the tissues, which helps prevent oxidative processes of destruction of vitamin C, the increase in pressure in sealed containers, as well as their internal corrosion;
- stabilizing the color and eliminating the unpleasant taste of some vegetables, with particular importance for conservation.

The thermal treatment has negative consequences also:

- possible infestation with microorganisms (for drying, scalding);
- reducing the nutritional value of fruits and vegetables by destroying vitamins at high temperatures and the loss of soluble substances that go into water treatment;
- loss of qualities that are linked with the freshness of the product: texture, taste, color, smell.

Drying the fruits and vegetables relates to the product's reduction of humidity, with the

selection of drying modes which depend both on the nature of the product subjected to drying and its subsequent destination, or the end-product that will be obtained from a processing operation.

The drying process is divided into two distinct periods. In the first period, the product's surface humidity is higher than the hygroscopic humidity. In this case, the rate of drying does not depend on the processed product, but rather the mode of drying and the drying agent used.

The period covers the step of heating and constant drying rate, and ends when the surface humidity becomes equal to the hygroscopic humidity. This is called critical humidity, and its value determines both the drying time and the quality of the dried product.

The second period includes the decreasing drying rate phase and the hygrometric balance phase (which should be avoided).

Fruits are especially valuable due to their high content in carbohydrates, proteins and fats, some being rich in vitamins and minerals, necessary for the human body.

Since fruit production is seasonal, to be consumed throughout the year, without altering the nutritional and organoleptic qualities of the fruits, they are subject to preservation processes.

Dehydration is one of the most effective methods of long-term preservation of fruits. By dehydration, fruits reduce their weight about 8-10 times, their volume 3-4 times, and along with the reduction in volume, it focuses its nutritional and organoleptic qualities, and can then be restored to the initial qualities, by rehydration, if the situation requires.

2. Technological flow used

The technological flow used for the presented research is discontinuous. It represents the ordered sequence of operations performed to process the product, in order to obtain the end-product.

1. Reception includes controlling the quantity and quality of fruits. The quality of fruits, as well as apples, is assessed based on indicators established by various regulatory standards, internal standards, specifications, establishing quality classes: Extra, I, II.
2. Removal of impurities is done by washing it. Through this process, the number of microorganisms on the fruits should be reduced at least six times, and the last wash water must be free of mold and yeast. Detergent substances or HCl (1.5%) are added to the wash water in order to remove traces of pesticides. The washing temperature is about 40°C.
3. Sorting is a operation in which bad apples are separated: damaged, altered , impaired shape, etc.
4. The calibration is an operation used in order to separate the product on groups, based on size classes. For the drying process to be used for medium to large apple , with high uniformity.
5. Cleaning means the separation and removal of the non-edible or difficult to digest (seminal house, stem, flower scraps) parts of vegetables. The operation can be performed mechanically, or for small quantities, by hand.
6. The division has a great importance for technological operations that are to follow, because the thermal treatment velocity is proportional to the product's surface (which increases by division) and inversely proportional to the product's thickness (which decreases by division). Depending on the required degree of fineness used for fruit and vegetable division:

cutting sliced, diced, noodle form, scraped, and crushed.

7. Drying is the technological process in which the moisture content is reduced to the desired value. It takes place in two stages: first the initial moisture content of 84 % of the apples is reduced to a value of 20 %, and in the second, the moisture is reduced from 20% to 8%. In the research we have used a dryer room.

8. Dried apple packing is carried out in packaging material that must allow the viewing of the products and have a commercially attractive appearance, must keep out the foreign odors, must be strong enough, must be able to close slightly, and must be inexpensive. These conditions are met by: polyethylene film, polyvinyl chloride, polypropylene, and other materials.

The drying used for this research is an universal dryer, with multistage shuttles for vegetables and fruits (Fig.2.1). The unit operates on discharge. When the humidity of the drying agent (hot air) exceeds the amount determined in the drying unit, the pre-charge unit starts, and introduces fresh air under pressure. Because of the overpressure created in the room, the air filled with moisture extracted from the product is discharged outside, through the frame with dampers. The fresh air introduced is taken by the unit that prepares and circulates warm air, it is brought to operating temperature, and discharged trough the shuttles with produce.

Fig.1 Universal dryer for vegetables and fruits

The essential parameters of drying (temperature, humidity, cycle duration on phases) can be programmed and controlled automatically. When the moisture sensor signals the controller of exceeding the limit of moisture prescribed, it commands the fan that introduces pre-heated fresh air into the drying room, and subsequently, the flaps open to discharge moisture-filled air extracted from the product.

When the humidity drops below the prescribed limits, the probe stops the fan that introduces fresh

air, and simultaneously, without overpressure in the room, the exhaust valves close.

The advantages of this method of drying:

- increases the uniformity of drying;
- reduces energy consumption;
- decreases the drying time of a batch;
- automatic control of the drying system.

Technical characteristics of the universal dryer for vegetables and fruits are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

No.	Feature	Value	Unit
1	Product's surface of alignment	38	m ²
2	Installed power	1,5	kW
3	Power consumption	0,9	kW
4	Installed thermal power	100	kJ
5	Average thermal power consumption	35	kJ
6	Duration of the Drying Cycle	6	h
7	Energy cost per kg product	0,12	kW/kg
8	Useful volume drying room	1,22	m ³ /șarjă
9	Dimensions (LxWxH)	2,8x1,2x2	m

3. Experimental research

Phenomena that occur during the process of dehydration:

- External diffusion - evaporation of water from the surface of the product to the outside;
- Internal diffusion - migration of water from the inner layer to the outside, as a result of water evaporation from the surface and the tendency to equalize the moisture in the product;
- Thermo-diffusion of water - the movement of vapors and water from the heated layer to the layers with lower temperature.

Diffusion phenomena are phenomena of capillary nature, therefore we will avoid damaging capillaries through an improper shredding of our products (eg pasty products dry harder than solids due to clogging capillaries).

In most drying methods (especially the convection method) removing moisture from the inside of the product is the result of internal diffusion carrying water out, where, due to the external diffusion process, its evaporation takes place. If the external diffusion is greater than the internal diffusion, the water existing at the product's surface is rapidly eliminated, and as a result there forms a crust which will prevent the drying process.

Because the thermo-diffusion's direction is opposite to the internal diffusion's direction, actions must be taken to reduce the thermo-diffusion's effect. The easiest way to do this is by scalding products that determine a high internal temperature so that the internal-external temperature gradient is reduced.

The raw material used is of the Idared apple variety. The fruit size is large (170 -200 g), and has the collection period after 1st October. Optimum storage period: October to March. In Romania, it was approved in 1979.

Tree of medium vigor, with branched port, blooms early but phased, very productive and fairly constant. It is quite sensitive to scab, powdery mildew and bacterial burns. The fruit is medium-large and large, slightly flattened spherical shape, yellowish green, covered with red on half of the surface.

The flesh is yellowish white, crisp, hoppy, good quality. It is considered the best variety for storage, without having any loss at storage. Consumption reaches full maturity after 3-4 months of storage and retains that status until the summer months.

The chemical composition of the product, used in measurement, is shown in Table 2.

To determine the individual mass, 20 Idared apple were individually weighed. Weighing results are shown in Table 3.

Table 2

Idared apples	100 g/product	200 g/product	300 g/product
Calories	47	94	141
Proteins	0,4	0,8	1,2
Lipids	0,1	0,2	0,3
Carbohydrates	11,8	23,6	35,4
Fibres	1,8	3,6	5,4

Table 3

No.	The individual mass of apples [g]	The medium mass of apples [g]
1	166,60	160,73
2	142,96	
3	164,18	
4	183,21	
5	160,73	
6	134,95	
7	130,93	
8	143,62	
9	181,01	
10	178,29	
11	172,16	
12	162,53	
13	180,97	
14	155,83	
15	174,36	
16	155,03	
17	186,96	
18	121,59	
19	150,42	
20	168,22	

To determine the initial values of apples moisture, a moisture analyzer was used. There have been two types of measurements

of humidity, from the peel and from the apple pulp. The following measurements were obtained the results shown in Table 4.

Table 4

Initial moisture content (%)	
Apple peel (%)	Apple pulp (%)
78,83	81,87
76,20	80,21
79,30	82,01
77,40	81,40
Initial medium umidity of apple peel 77,93 %	Initial medium umidity of apple pulp 81,37%

- The weight of the samples before placing in the dryer (fresh):

Four samples were made by using two different cutting modes:

- a) Apples cut into slices (fresh);
Sample1 S1= 501,80 g;
Sample 2 S2= 501, 30 g;
Sample 3 S3= 501,70 g;
Sample4 S4= 503,82 g (Fig.1).

- b) Radial sliced apples (fresh);
Sample 1 S1= 502,86 g;

- Sample 2 S2= 500,20 g;
Sample 3 S3= 500,69 g;
Sample 4 S4= 503,72 g. (Fig.2).

- Sample weight after removal from dryer (dry basis):

- a) Apples cut into slices (dry);
Sample 1 S1= 86,86 g;
Sample 2 S2= 82,13 g;
Sample 3 S3= 84,40 g;
Sample 4 S4= 84,80 g. (Fig.3).

b) Radial sliced apples (dry);
 Sample 1 S1= 240,45 g;
 Sample 2 S2= 234,75 g;

Sample 3 S3= 249,16 g;
 Sample 4 S4= 239,56 g. (Fig.4).

Fig.1 Apples cut into slices (fresh)

Fig.2 Radial sliced apples (fresh)

Fig.3 Apples cut into slices (dry)

Fig.4 Radial sliced apples (dry)

Fig.5 Drying parameters

Fig.6 Final product

For the food quality assurance an important link is conservation, which helps extend the product's shelf life. Among the various methods and principles of conservation, good results can be obtained by drying, which consists in removing part of the water from the content of a

food product, thus creating an unsuitable environment for the activities of microorganisms.

The fruit drying operation results in:

- Product stability over time, without the need for complex installations or special packaging;

- Achieve a volume reduction for products, resulting in smaller storage spaces and lower transport costs and sales.

It is considered that for this, it is sufficient to reduce the moisture content to 8 ... 10 % for vegetables and 18-24% for fruits. The moisture's different level of reduction in the fruit is due to the fact that a certain amount of water is blocked, being linked to sugars.

If the air temperature is higher, then the drying rate will be higher. This is due to the fact that, as the temperature is higher, the vapor carrying capacity of the air is increased.

The evaporation rate depends also on the speed with which the air transfers heat to the product that is being dried, the transmission is directly proportional to the difference between the air temperature (dry thermometer temperature) and the temperature of the product surface (wet thermometer temperature).

The product's dimensions affect the rate of drying because the ones with a smaller volume, shredded or chopped, have a larger area of evaporation, and as a result, dry quicker.

With drying, especially if the conditions are not optimal, transformations of sugars, nitrogenous substances, aroma, vitamins and color, will appear.

Dried fruits are very hygroscopic, as a result, they easily absorb moisture from the air. Therefore, the relative humidity in storage should be as low as possible (60-65 % for fruit and up to 75% for some vegetables, given that the fruits are more hygroscopic than vegetables). The storage temperature should not exceed 15⁰C, the recommended temperature being 0 - 10⁰C.

5. References

1. Burtea, O., Fugel, S., *Conservation in the household of vegetables and fruit by drying*, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest, 1985;
2. Danilevici, C., *Fruit and vegetable processing technology in the canning industry*, Wallachia University Press, Targoviste 2006;
3. Ioancea, L., Kathreim, I., *Conditioning and better use of plant materials for food, technology and equipment*, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest, 1988;
4. Tane, N., *Machinery, and equipment for vegetable and fruit processing*, University "Transilvania" of Brasov, Brasov, 2002;
5. Tane, N. and od., *Food vegetable Engineering*, University "Transilvania" of Brasov, Brasov, 2012.

USING OF GRANULOMETRIC DISTRIBUTION FUNCTIONS IN ESTIMATING FLOWS OF GRIST SORTED IN A PLANSIFTER COMPARTMENT

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Abstract: *In milling plants grinding and sorting operations are complementary and repetitive. After each grinding of wheat seeds or intermediate products of grist, at a grinding machine, follows a sorting on class size of grist mixture resulted at grinding in a plansifter compartment. Knowledge of the flow that feeds each technological passage is essential for technologists in the regulation of functional parameters of machines used in the process flow. Both grist that feeds a plansifter compartment, and fractions sorted here, follows a certain distribution on class size, which can be determined by testing the experimental results obtained at particle size analysis with known distribution mathematical laws. In paper is presented a model to use size distribution functions for determining the theoretical flow of undersize particle, respectively of oversize particles, of grist fractions sorted on sieves in plansifter compartment of Break 1 at a wheat milling plant with capacity of 100 t/24 h.*

Keywords: *plansifter compartment, undersize particle flow, oversize particle flow, Rosin-Rammler function, Schuhman function.*

1. Introduction

In milling industry, knowledge of sifting operation is a necessity because it is still unknown in the field, [1]. Plansifters are the main sifting equipments used in milling plants. These are correlated to the technological flow rather by intuition and experience of miller than on theoretical grounds, so that the majority of plansifters are used at minimum efficiency, [2].

Although sifting is a common operation and considered simple, in fact it is governed by a number of factors that may influence its efficiency. Many of relatively recent papers address the factors that influence the effectiveness, [3,4,5], but also kinetic of sifting, [6]. Most of these papers, addressing the sifting process, are based on empirical analysis, [3].

Mathematical modeling of sifting process with a high accuracy is one of the prerogatives of researchers in the field. A large number of articles in the scientific literature, in the field, attack the problem of mathematical modeling. Thus, in paper [7], Sultanbawa et. al. studies the kinetic aspects of sifting and develops a new methodology based on a mass balance to predict the separation performance. Approach followed by Andrzejcyak and Wodzinski, [8], has both an

analytical description but also empirical of sifting process of a particles mixture. The model is based on the assumption that the sifting process consists of two steps: passing of undersize particles through the general material layer, up to contact with the sieve, and separation of particles through the screen apertures.

At the same time, correct estimation of undersize and oversize particle flows of grist fractions sorted within plansifter compartments from milling plants can help the technologists at proper adjustment of the equipments on the technological flow of those plants (respectively grinding machines and plansifters).

In our paper we present how to use the granulometric distribution functions in estimating flows of undersize and oversize grist particles sorted within a plansifter compartment

2. Material and method

Theoretical flows of undersize and oversize particles can be estimated using the granulometric distribution functions from scientific literature. Though, should be noted that, experimentally, values of these flows differ from theoretical ones, because within the sifting process a number of variables are involved which

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modifies separation efficiency, variables such as flow and stratification of material on the sieve, grist composition etc.

Fig. 1. Interior scheme of analyzed plansifter compartment

Further, is presented an algorithm for estimating of oversize and undersize particles flows of frame packages within plansifter compartment, algorithm that is based on granulometric distribution functions Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman. To apply the algorithm was necessary to perform granulometric analysis for sorted fractions in analyzed compartment to determine, through nonlinear regression on computer, of coefficients b and n . Thus, determinations were made at plansifter compartment of Break 1 of a milling plant of 100 t/24h, of which interior scheme is shown in fig. 1.

Grist fraction that feeds analyzed plansifter compartment is sorted, inside it, in five fractions with different particle size distribution and composition. Break 1 compartment consists of five frame packets, undersize particle flow is denoted with q_y , and oversize particle flow is denoted with q_y , where y is number of packet. Thus, Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman relations, characterizing oversize and undersize fractions are:

Undersize particle fractions

Rosin-Rammler

$$T_I = 100 \cdot \left(1 - e^{-b_I \cdot x_I^{n_I}} \right)$$

$$T_{II} = 100 \cdot \left(1 - e^{-b_{II} \cdot x_{II}^{n_{II}}} \right)$$

$$T_{III-IV} = 100 \cdot \left(1 - e^{-b_{III-IV} \cdot x_{III-IV}^{n_{III-IV}}} \right)$$

$$T_V = 100 \cdot \left(1 - e^{-b_V \cdot x_V^{n_V}} \right)$$

Schuhman

$$T_I = 100 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{x_I}{b_I} \right)^{n_I} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$T_{II} = 100 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{x_{II}}{b_{II}} \right)^{n_{II}} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$T_{III-IV} = 100 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{x_{III-IV}}{b_{III-IV}} \right)^{n_{III-IV}} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$T_{III-IV} = 100 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{x_{III-IV}}{b_{III-IV}} \right)^{n_{III-IV}} \right] \quad (4)$$

Oversize particle fractions

Rosin-Rammler

$$R_I = R_1 = 100 \cdot e^{-b_I \cdot x_I^{n_I}}$$

$$R_{II} = R_2 = 100 \cdot e^{-b_{II} \cdot x_{II}^{n_{II}}}$$

$$R_{III-IV} = 100 \cdot e^{-b_{III-IV} \cdot x_{III-IV}^{n_{III-IV}}}$$

$$R_V = R_3 = 100 \cdot e^{-b_V \cdot x_V^{n_V}}$$

Schuhman

$$R_I = R_1 = 100 \cdot \left(\frac{x_I}{b_I} \right)^{n_I} \quad (5)$$

$$R_{II} = R_2 = 100 \cdot \left(\frac{x_{II}}{b_{II}} \right)^{n_{II}} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{III-IV} = 100 \cdot \left(\frac{x_{III-IV}}{b_{III-IV}} \right)^{n_{III-IV}} \quad (7)$$

$$R_V = R_3 = 100 \cdot \left(\frac{x_V}{b_V} \right)^{n_V} \quad (8)$$

where b_i and n_i – coefficients determined by nonlinear regression on the computer, x_i – aperture size of frame fabric from package i .

From the analysis of fig. 1, is observed that frame packages III and IV works in series, oversize and undersize fractions of these two packages being evacuated together. For ease of calculation algorithm, at the two packages was calculated a single undersize particle flow and a single oversize particle flow.

Knowing the distribution by size of oversize and undersize fractions, for Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman laws, their flows can be estimated, for analyzed plansifter compartment (Break 1), by the following relations:

Frame package	Undersize particle flow	Oversize particle flow	
Package I	$q_1 = \frac{T_I}{100} \cdot q_0$	$q_1^* = \frac{R_I}{100} \cdot q_0$	(9)
Package II	$q_2 = \frac{T_{II}}{100} \cdot q_1 = \frac{T_I \cdot T_{II}}{(100)^2} \cdot q_0$	$q_2^* = \frac{R_{II}}{100} \cdot q_1 = \frac{T_I \cdot R_{II}}{(100)^2} \cdot q_0$	(10)
Package III-IV	$q_{3-4} = \frac{T_{III-IV}}{100} \cdot q_2 = \frac{T_{III-IV} \cdot T_I \cdot T_{II}}{(100)^3} \cdot q_0$	$q_{3-4}^* = \frac{R_{III-IV}}{100} \cdot q_2 = \frac{T_I \cdot T_{II} \cdot R_{III-IV}}{(100)^3} \cdot q_0$	(11)
Package V	$q_5 = \frac{T_V}{100} \cdot q_{3-4}^* = \frac{T_I \cdot T_{II} \cdot T_V \cdot R_{III-IV}}{(100)^4} \cdot q_0$	$q_5^* = \frac{R_V}{100} \cdot q_{3-4}^* = \frac{T_I \cdot T_{II} \cdot R_{III-IV} \cdot R_V}{(100)^4} \cdot q_0$	(12)

3. Numerical application

For analyzed plansifter compartment were determined the experimental flows by sampling of grist from compartment input (Q) and from those five fractions sorted within compartment

(three oversize fractions and two undersize fractions) in a time of 10 seconds. Experimental flow was used to show the differences between real flows and theoretical flows determined with the algorithm proposed in this paper. Thus, experimental data are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Flows at input (Q) and five outputs (R1, R2, R3, C1, C2) of plansifter compartment

Grist fraction	Q (q ₀)	R1 (q ₁ [*])	R2 (q ₂ [*])	R3 (q ₅ [*])	C1 (q ₃₋₄)	C2 (q ₅)
Grist flow, [g/s]	729.46 (100%)	224.26 (30,74%)	193.9 (26,58%)	118.64 (16,26%)	68.17 (9,35%)	124.49 (17,07%)

After sampling and determining the flow of fractions, was performed the granulometric analysis of the six grist fractions, with a sieve

shaker Anallysette 3 Spartan, at a amplitude of 2 mm, for 3 minutes. The analysis results and the sieve used are shown in table 2.

Table 2. Weight values p (%) of grist on sieve of classifier and weight values R (%) for grist products collected at input and the five outputs of Break 1 plansifter compartment

m (mm)	Q (C1 Entrance)		R1 (C1 Break 2)		R2 (C1 DIV1')		C1 (C1 F)		R3 (C1 DIV1'')		C2 (C1 M2)	
	p(%)	T(%)	p(%)	T(%)	p(%)	T(%)	p(%)	T(%)	p(%)	T(%)	p(%)	T(%)
0	0.000	53.30	0.000	3.10	0.000	2.50	0.000	0.50	0.000	6.10	0.000	11.00
1	0.710	10.80	0.710	6.40	0.180	8.90	2.50	0.045	15.00	0.50	0.125	11.80
2	1.000	14.50	1.000	35.00	0.250	12.90	11.40	0.063	25.80	15.50	0.180	15.60
3	1.400	5.90	1.400	19.30	0.400	26.80	24.30	0.090	29.30	41.30	0.250	22.80
4	2.000	9.80	2.000	28.40	0.630	38.60	51.10	0.125	23.90	70.60	0.315	33.20
5	2.800	5.70	2.800	7.80	0.710	10.30	89.70	0.160	5.50	94.50	0.400	10.50
Mean diameter	d _{1E} =0.98 mm		d _{1Break2} =1.76 mm		d _{1DIV1'} =0.55 mm		d _{1F} = 0.10 mm		d _{1DIV1''} =0.29 mm		d _{1M2} = 0.17 mm	

Using experimental data from granulometric analysis was performed a nonlinear regression analysis on the computer, in program Microcal Origin v. 7.0, in order to determine the

coefficients b and n of the Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman relations, for grist sorted at the five frame packages of analyzed plansifter compartment. Granulometric distribution curves

obtained are shown in fig. 2, and the values of the coefficient R^2 , are shown in table3. coefficients b and n, as well as of the correlation

Fig. 2. Granulometric distribution curves given by Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman equations in correlations with experimental data for grist fractions from analyzed plansifter compartment in breakage phase at a milling plant of 100 t/24h
 (— Rosin-Rammler; — Schuhman)

Table 3. Values of b and n coefficients for those two relations and of correlation coefficient R^2

Distribution law	Coefficients	Q	R1	R2	C1	R3	C2
Rosin-Rammler	b	0.404	2.178	0.118	0.001	0.020	0.009
	n	-1.429	-2.640	-2.733	-2.849	-2.750	-2.331
	R^2	0.996	0.986	0.902	0.984	0.948	0.983
Schuhman	b	3.090	2.872	0.766	0.161	0.421	0.268
	n	0.389	1.516	2.464	1.747	2.071	1.610
	R^2	0.993	0.949	0.966	0.973	0.999	0.987

Now, knowing the values of the coefficients b and n for the two distribution laws, the algorithm can be applied to determine theoretical undersize and oversize particle flows. For package I was used, in calculus, values obtained for the fraction R1, for package II values of R2, for packages III and IV values of C1, and for package V values of C2. After applying the relations (1-12) were

obtained values shown in table 4, for theoretical undersize and oversize particle flows, calculated according to Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman relations. In fig. 3 are presented comparative variations of these flows together with variations of real flow, experimentally determined, at plansifter compartment of Break 1, analyzed.

Table 4. Comparative data for undersize and oversize particle flows obtained by applying the relations (1-12), as compared with the real flow, at Break 1 plansifter compartment

Undersize particle flow											
q ₁ RR	q ₁ Sch	q ₁ real	q ₂ RR	q ₂ Sch	q ₂ real	q ₃₋₄ RR	q ₃₋₄ Sch	q ₃₋₄ real	q ₅ RR	q ₅ Sch	q ₅ real
473.30	504.97	505.20	145.50	155.12	311.30	29.02	18.04	68.17	45.90	64.35	124.49
Oversize particle flow											
q [*] ₁ RR	q [*] ₁ Sch	q [*] ₁ real	q [*] ₂ RR	q [*] ₂ Sch	q [*] ₂ real	q [*] ₃₋₄ RR	q [*] ₃₋₄ Sch	q [*] ₃₋₄ real	q [*] ₅ RR	q [*] ₅ Sch	q [*] ₅ real
256.16	224.48	224.26	327.80	349.85	193.90	116.48	137.08	243.13	70.58	72.73	118.64

RR – Rosin-Rammler; Sch – Schuhman; real – experimentally obtained flow.

Fig. 3. Variation of undersize and oversize particles, theoretical and real, flows for fractions sorted in analyzed plansifter compartment

From fig. 2 and table 3 it can be seen that both distribution law used in regression analysis correlates very well the experimental data, being obtained correlation coefficients $R^2 \geq 0.902$. Though, it can be seen that Schuhman distribution law correlate better the experimental data. Coefficient b of the two distribution laws indicates the degree of unevenness of analyzed grist fractions. It can be seen that for undersize fractions C1 and C2 values of b are close to zero, which means that the fractions are uniform in particle size and physical composition, instead for oversize fractions, especially for first refusal of compartment, values of b are great showing unevenness of these fractions. Thus, it can be said that efficiency of sifting is reduced, because some of the undersize particles, which would have to pass, normally, through fabric apertures,

remain blocked in refusal fractions of frame packages and are discharges along with them.

Also due to sifting inefficiency arise differences from table 4 and fig. 3, between oversize and undersize particles flows obtained from Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman relations and oversize and undersize particles flows experimentally determined.

Another reason, for these differences, it may be the wrong choice of fabrics and, therefore, is recommended a judicious choice of their, but also kinematic regime imposed to plansifter, revolution speed of actuating mechanism and motion amplitude influencing the efficiency of the sifting process.

Analyzing variation charts from fig. 3 can be said that, using the algorithm for determining the oversize and undersize particles flows based on the Schuhman distribution law, were obtained

values closer to reality, than that which is based on the Rosin-Rammler law. It stresses thus, the importance of finding the granulometric distribution law that best represents the experimental data for grist fractions sorted plansifters.

4. Conclusions

In paper was presented how to use the laws of particle size distribution in determination of oversize and undersize particles flows of sifting frame packages within the plansifter compartments.

It was experimentally determined, firstly, the real flow to have a basis for comparison. To grist fractions, collected when determining flow, have been firstly made size analysis. With experimental data from particle size analysis, by nonlinear regression on the computer, was determined values of the coefficients b and n from distribution functions Rosin-Rammler and Schuhman. Thus, could be estimated the oversize and undersize particles flows for a plansifter compartment.

At plansifter compartment of Break 1, of a milling plant of 100 t/24 h, analyzed in paper, Schuhman distribution law presented values closest to the real values of flow, differences appear due to percentages of undersize particles blocked in refusal fractions of frame packages, to unevenness of grist fractions, to kinematic regime of plansifter and, possible, due to inappropriate choice of plansifter frame fabrics.

These relationships may be useful in the work of efficient use sifting systems with sieves, in the design of these, in the activity of making appropriate adjustments etc..

References

1. Sosland N.: *Limited gains in sifter technology contrast with overall mill strides*. In: World Grain, 9, p.: 30-35, 1987;
2. Posner, E.S., Hibbs, A.N.: *Sieving*. In: Wheat Flour Milling, AACC International: St. Paul, MN, p.:155-186, 1997 b;
3. Jansen M., Glastonbury J.: *The size separation of particles by screening*. In: Powder Technology 1, p.: 334-343, 1967;
4. Li J., Webb C., Pandiella S., Campbell G.: *Discrete particle motion on sieves – a numerical study using the DEM simulation*. In: Powder Technology, 133, p.:190 – 202, 2003;
5. Standish, N., Bharadwaj, A., Hariri-Akbari, G.: *A study of the effect of operating variables on the efficiency of a vibrating screen*. In: Powder Technol. 48, 161–172, 1986;
6. Kaye B., Robb N.: *An algorithm for deducing an effective sieve residue from the rate of powder passage through a sieve*. In: Powder Technology, 24, p.: 125-128, 1979;
7. Sultanbawa F.M., Owens W.G., Pandiella S.S.: *A new approach to the prediction of particle separation by sieving in flour milling*. In: Transactions of IchemE, 79 (Part C), p. 201-218, 2001;
8. Andrzejczak P., Wodzinski P.: *Model of screening in the layer*. In: Powder Handling Proc., 6(3), p.: 264-272, 1994.

INVESTIGATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE PROCESS AND THE MEDIUM PROPERTIES CONDITIONS ON THE KINETICS OF GREEN BUCKWHEAT FLAKES SWELLING PROCESS

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Abstract: The chemical composition of green buckwheat flakes, swelling of the flakes peculiarities at different process conditions are studied in the article.

Key words: green buckwheat flakes, swelling process, limiting degree and swelling rate constant, hydrate water.

1. Introduction

Green buckwheat flakes (GBF) are rich in proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, macro- and micro-nutrients and are an important source of raw materials, increasing the nutritional and biological value of food.

GBF protein content varies between 13-15%. The protein fraction is represented by 18.2% albumin, 43.3% globulin, 0.8% prolamine, 22.7% glutelin and 5.0% others biologically active components. Albumins are readily soluble in water and salt solutions. Therefore, their swelling especially at increased temperatures is the first stage of dissolution (unlimited swelling). Globulins are insoluble in water but soluble in aqueous solutions of neutral salts.

GBF basic amino acids composition (g/100g protein) is given in Table 1:

Table 1

Amino acid	GBF
lysine	5,1
methionine	1,9
cystine	2,2
threonine	3,5
valine	4,7
isoleucine	3,5
leucine	6,1
phenylalanine	4,2
histidine	2,2
tryptophan	1,6

Green buckwheat contains many flavonoids known for their effectiveness in reducing cholesterol levels and preventing high blood pressure. Composition of flavonoids of green buckwheat flakes is determined as follows: rutin, quercetin, orientin, vitexin, izovitexin, izoorientin.

Special attention is also given to a unique composition of carbohydrates of GBF due to their content of hiroinozitol. It was proved that this vegetable matter is able to reduce blood glucose and to activate insulin. Total dietary fiber content in green buckwheat seed is 5-11%. The main components of dietary fiber are cellulose, non-starch polysaccharides represented by glucuronic acid, mannose, arabinose, galactose, glucose, and lignans. Green buckwheat occupies the 3^d place among many crops according to the number of lignans generated. These vegetable components act as hormones, like phytoestrogens. In its turn fiber is divided into soluble and insoluble. В X3Г преобладает раств Sor и мая клет лuble fiber prevails in GBF. [1, 2, 3].

Besides functional properties GBF, due to the content of hydrophilic macromolecular compounds, in particular proteins, starch and fiber, have important technological properties such as water binding capacity and swelling that helps to improve the structural and mechanical properties of semi-finished products the food systems developed and finished products consumer properties. All this creates conditions for GBF use as an additive in the production of many foods [3].

The process of swelling depends on the nature of high-molecular compounds (HMC), temperature, composition and pH of the liquid being absorbed and can flow as both bounded and unbounded. The process nature has an impact on quality indicators of semi-finished and finished products. It is therefore important to know the peculiarities of GBF swelling at different process conditions [4]. The purpose of the work was to study the process of swelling of green buckwheat

flakes at different pH values of the medium, to determine the proportion of free and bound water in the swollen GBF.

Green buckwheat flakes are a multi-component system where the ability to swell belongs to proteins, starch and cellulose mainly.

As the working solutions we used:

- the distilled water (pH measured 5,86);
- model solutions with different pH, prepared from solutions of HCl and NaOH (pH was controlled). Investigation of the kinetics of green buckwheat flakes swelling was carried out in a special device by the method described in [5], at a temperature of 20⁰ C. The amount of water hydrated in GBF was obtained by measuring of swelling heat by the method proposed by A.V. Dumanskiy and E.F. Nekryach [7].

Mixing of the first portions of water to polar groups of the HMC (the first stage of swelling called hydration) occurs as a weak exothermic reaction, the thermal effect of which is the higher the more emphasized hydrophilic properties of the substance are; additional portions of water are sorbed without any appreciable energy release.

Mass of water $m_{h.w.}$ being bound by a unit of mass of HMC can be determined if the transition energy of mass water unit from the free to the bound state (according to A.V. Dumanskiy and E.F. Nekryach for most of HMC it is 334.4 J / g) and the specific heat of swelling ΔH are known:

$$m_{h.w.} = \frac{\Delta \dot{I}}{334,4}. \quad (1)$$

The heat of swelling was determined in the calorimeter, linked with a personal computer and allowing to record the temperature change during the process with accuracy $\pm 0,001$ °C by the method described in [6].

A quantitative characteristic of swelling is the swelling degree i - index which indicates the relative increase in the mass of HMC during the

$$\text{swelling: } i = \frac{\dot{\sigma} - m_0}{m_0} = \frac{m_1}{m_0} \quad (2)$$

where m_0 , m – mass of the dry and swollen substance; m_1 – mass of liquid absorbed.

The kinetic curves obtained (Figure 1) indicate the limited nature of the GBF main components swelling in all test solutions: the degree of swelling i reaches the limit under the given conditions of the process value i_{\max} and does not change fur-

ther. In the alkaline pH range partial dissolution of certain components took place that was proved by clouding of the working solution. But the general nature of the process was not affected greatly.

Fig. 1. Kinetic curves of green buckwheat flakes swelling in model solutions with different pH index at 20 °C.

The kinetics of limited swelling takes place by the first order reaction mechanism [4]:

$$\frac{di}{d\tau} = k(i_{\max} - i), \quad (3)$$

where $di/d\tau$ – the rate of swelling (the change of the swelling degree per unit time); k – swelling rate constant; i , i_{\max} – current (during the time τ) and limit degree of swelling.

Solution of the equation (1) for the rate constant has the following form:

$$k = \frac{1}{\tau} \ln \frac{i_{\max}}{i_{\max} - i}. \quad (4)$$

In this paper we determined the limiting degree and the rate constant of GBF swelling in solutions with various pH index (Fig. 1).

Acidity of the medium affects mainly the swelling of polyampholytes, which are the proteins that make up most of the swelling components of GBF. Depending on the medium pH the protein macromolecules adopt various conformations. The minimum degree of protein swelling corresponds to its isoelectric point (IEP) at which the equality of the positive and negative charges in the macromolecule takes place. It curls up into a ball or a globule, and this hinders the penetration of solvent molecules into the HMC matrix.

According to the data [3], albumins and globulins have individual IEP albumin - 8.0; globulin - 5.5. Studies showed that the minimum values of the limiting degree of swelling are observed at pH equal to 5.86, close to the globulin IEP. Relatively low values of the limiting degree of swelling are also observed at a pH of 8.23 and 9.84, close to the albumin IEP. Comparison of the values of the rate constant showed (Figure 2) that the maximum rate of swelling was observed at pH 3.98, and it was slightly lower at a pH of 5.86 and 8.23. In this paper, the integral specific heats ΔH of the swelling GBF fraction were measured and the mass of water $m_{h.w}$ adsorbed by high molecular substances in the hydration stage is calculated, its share $x_{h.w}$ in the total mass of liquid absorbed was determined (Table 2).

Fig. 2. GBF swelling rate constant in model solutions with various pH index at 20 °C

Table 2

Medium p H	2,18	3,11	3,98	5,86	6,86	8,23	9,84	10,72
$-\Delta H, J/g$	20,5	22,7	20,7	19,3	19,0	20,7	22,3	24,5
$m_{h.w.s}$ gH ₂ O/gBMC	0,061	0,068	0,062	0,058	0,057	0,062	0,067	0,073
$X_{h.w.s}$ %	3,0	3,0	3,8	3,7	3,7	3,5	3,2	3,0

Hydrate water firmly held by the substance and has special properties: low freezing point, high enthalpy of vaporization, high viscosity, low solubility of substances in it. Its high content provides better keeping ability of the product and its consumer properties. The dependence of $m_{h.w.}$ on the pH medium is virtually identical to similar relationship for i_{max} . In the total mass of absorbed water the hydration water accounts from 3.0 to 3.8%. The studies carried out suggest the following conclusions: in the investigated pH range GBF swelling degree is maximum at pH of 10.72, its lowest values are observed at pH 3.98 and 9.84, the equilibrium time is 8-10 minutes, at a pH of 3.98 the mass of hydrated water containing in HMC unit mass, as well as limiting swelling degree is maximum; In the total mass of absorbed liquid the share of hydrated water accounts from 3.0 to 3.8%.

References

1. Kretovich, V. L. Plants biochemistry [Text] / V. L. Kretovich. - M.: Vyssh. sh k 1980. – 445 pages.

2. Smirnov V.S., Rukosuev A.N. Commodity of grain - M: Publishing house of technical and economic literature on the workpieces questions, 2001. - 280 pages.

3. Ivanova, M. F. Merchandising assessment of flour proteins and wheat germ leykozine use in the manufacture of pastry products and sauces for catering [Text]: abstract of thesis of Cand.Tech.Sc / M. F. Ivanova. - Moscow, 2011.

4. Voyutsky, V.V. Colloid chemistry course [Text] / VV Voyutsky. - M.: "Chemistry", 1975.

5. Laboratory workshop on colloid chemistry [Text] / T.S. Kornienko, S.I.Garshina, T.V. Mastjukova and others. - Voronezh, VSTA, 2001.5. Pinchuk, L.G. Biochemistry: Textbook. / L.G. Pinchuk, E.P. Zinkevich, S.B. Gridina; Kemerovo Technological Institute of food industry. - Kemerovo, 2011. – 364 p.

6. Laboratory workshop in physical chemistry [Text] / N.M. Podgornova, T.S. Kornienko, S.I. Garshina and others - Voronezh, VSTA, 2005.

RESEARCH OF QUALITY INDICES OF DRINKING COW MILK

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Abstract: *Proper nutrition is important for the health of the population. Among the products used, especially for young people is cow's milk. This article makes a study of the quality of liquid cow's milk based on different samples of Bulgarian and foreign producers.*

Key word: *research, liquid cow's milk, quality*

1. Introduction

Food is one of the most important determinants of health. Proper nutrition ensures normal growth and development of children and helps to prevent disease, prolong life, improve efficiency and create conditions for adequate adaptation to the environment. Among the dietary factors that are of particular importance to health, the most important role is in full and regular all the necessary receipts of the human body micronutrients.

Milk - is a biological fluid generated by mammary glands of mammals during lactation, physiologically designed to supply young. For a man - a complete product, significantly different from other foods as qualitative and quantitative set of macro - and micronutrients, which are particularly useful for the health of people of all ages. The most popular type of cow's milk provided because the volume of production has a leading position.

Drinking cow's milk, according to regulatory documents - is milk, which is made from raw milk from cows, past normalization temperature processing, packaging, before or after treatment, chilled to set modes and is intended for direct human consumption.

2. Problem statement

Quality of drinking cow's milk was studied in the following groups of indicators - informative

- trade name of the food product;
- components of the food product (except alcoholic beverages);
- amount of certain constituents or groups of constituents of the food product;
- net weight or volume for packaged;

labeling, organoleptic characteristics, physical and chemical indicators.

For the study were selected 7 samples of drinking cow's milk with different fat content of domestic and foreign manufacturers. For convenience and objectivity of research quality of the milk samples were encoded as follows:

- №1 – TM Vereya;
- №2 – TM Meegle;
- №3 – TM Kaufland Classic;
- №4 – TM Cheh;
- №5 – TM Fibela;
- №6 – TM Laciate;
- №7 – TM Olympus Oly Milk.

All samples of drinking cow's milk were packed together in a combination packaging - Tetra. Packaging integrity of all samples was not damaged or broken.

The study was carried out visually marking content-analytic method. Results of the study content labeling are shown in Table 1.

Labeling requirements for food products produced in Bulgaria and Poland are in the Rules of labeling of food products in the European Union. Labelling of packaged food products must be in a clearly visible place on the primary packaging or attached to the respective food product label. Provided on the labeling information must be easily understandable and visible, legible and indelible. Labeling of food products must contain the following information:

- minimum shelf life of the food product, or if the goods are perishable, the deadline date;
- special storage conditions or use of the food product, if necessary to comply with such conditions to ensure the proper use;

- name and address registered in the European Community the manufacturer, packer or importer;
 - information about the origin of the food product, if such lack of information the consumer may be a misconception of the true place of origin of the food product
 - if necessary, detailed instructions for use;
 - energy value and nutritional value
- According to the rules on labeling of food products in the European Union, the trade name of the food product to include an indication or name, which is complemented by information about the physical condition or specific treatment of the food product.

3. Research methodology

Analyzing the data in Table 1, it can be concluded discrepancy labeling samples № 2, № 4, and № 5 on the requirements for trade name product. In the name of the samples shows the type of the specific heat treatment of milk. Also sample number 4 did not meet the requirements of normative documents as directed by the percentage of the product of protein, fat, carbohydrate and energy value per 100g. All other samples for labeling requirements are complained with the requirements of the Rules of labeling of food products in the European Union. Table 1 does not present information included on the labeling of all of the samples of the final expiration date, information about the origin of the food product, the name and address registered in the European Community the manufacturer, packer or importer. Determination of the organoleptic characteristics of quality of drinking cow's milk was conducted by an expert immediately after opening the packaging of each sample. Determination results of organoleptic quality indicators of drinking cow's milk are given in Table 2.

From Table 2, it follows that the appearance and texture of the samples corresponded to regulatory requirements, i.e. was homogeneous without sludge flakes of protein and fat lumps. Consistency is more dense each sample with increasing fat content. In addition, the number of sample 3 was observed in occurrence of gas bubbles on the walls of the tasting vessel that may be associated with impaired heat treatment technology of drinking cow's milk or transport and storage of the product in the trade network.

At number 5 samples revealed the presence of the cream on the foil packaging. Since the fat content of the sample is 3.0 %, then perhaps it is the result of improper transport of the finished product. Organoleptic characteristics of taste and smell test samples number 4 and number 6 did not meet regulatory requirements due to the presence of outsiders, not peculiar to fresh milk tastes and smells - of feed and water is very pronounced in a sample of milk with not very low in fat 2.0 %. Other samples meet the requirements of normative documents on organoleptic characteristics of taste and smell. It is worth noting that in the samples № 3, № 5 number 7 clean milk smell and taste , with a sweetish aftertaste were more pronounced than in the samples № 1, № 2. Most pleasant taste and smell have been observed in the sample number 5. Organoleptic color the entire test samples meet the requirements of regulatory documents, except sample number 1 (the color was yellowish milk that is not peculiar to drinking milk with low fat content). For samples of drinking cow's milk № 3, № 5, № 6 was marked by a uniform shade of creamy, due overlooking heat treatment - short-term or UHT ultra-high temperature (UHT). From the above it follows that the compliance requirements of regulatory documents on all organoleptic characteristics showed samples number 2, 5, 7. Currently in food industries, including the breast, the most widely used modern physical and physico - chemical methods of analysis: electrochemical, spectroscopic, chromatographic, rheology, etc. Study of physico- chemical quality of drinking cow's milk using rapid methods of instrumental analysis allows you to quickly and accurately determine the most interesting indicators of quality. For example, by measuring ultrasonic analyzer quality of milk "Ecomilk" (type 98 - QAM Milkana 2A). Analyzer is used for rapid determination of quality milk, its products and control of technological parameters of infant formula in measuring laboratories of the food industry, in scientific research, with the acceptance and processing of milk. Analyzer is used to measure the mass fraction of fat, protein, lactose, density (reduced to 20 °C), titrated acidity, skimmed milk (SM), the freezing point, the mass fraction of water added to the sample, which is explored in a special mode for different milk animals (cows, sheep and buffalo) test at a temperature of milk in the range 5-30 °C.

Table 1 - Results of the study content labeling of the samples of drinking cow's milk

No. Crt.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
TM	Vereya	Meggle	Lapte	Cheh	Fibera	Laciate	oly
Price, lev	1,79	1,95	1,39	1,79	1,95	1,95	2,09
Product name	Pasteurized cow's milk with 0.1% fat	Fresh milk	Standardized cow milk with 1.5% fat, homogenized, UHT	Cow milk "Cheh"	Cow milk	Cow's milk UHT 3,2%	Fat whole milk, 3.7% fat homogenised, UHT
Country	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Poland	Bulgaria
Milk fat,%	0,1	1	1,5	2	3	3,2	3,7
Protein g/100 ml	3	3,2	3,2	-	3,1	3,2	3,2
Carbohydrates g/100 ml	4,1	4,7	4,7	-	4,2	4,7	4,7
Fats, g/100 ml	0,1	1	1,5	-	3	3,2	3,7
Energy value, ccal/100 ml	29	40,6	45	-	56,2	60	62
Package volume l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Type of heat treatment of milk	-	Homogenization, UHT	Homogenization, UHT	UHT	UHT	UHT	UHT
Add. information	Count of saturated fats 0.065 g/100 ml	Calcium mg/100 ml - 120 ml nanog/100 Vitamin B12 - 0.4			count of saturated fat 1.95 g/100 ml		Calcium mg/100 ml - 100 count of saturated fat 2.04 g/100 ml
Storage mode	Keep at a temperature of 4 to 6 C After opening consume within 2 - 6 days.	Keep at a temperature of 2 to 6 C After opening consume within 2 - 3 days.	Store at room temperature. After opening the package to keep at a temperature of 2 to 4 C and consume within 3 - 4 days	Keep at a temperature of 4 to 24 C, open the packaging to keep at a temperature of 4 to 6 ° C - 4 days.	Save up to 25 C. After opening keep refrigerated.	Keep at temperatures up to 25 ° C, to avoid frost and direct sunlight. After opening keep at a temperature of 2 to 8 C and consume within 3-4 days.	Save up to 25 C. After opening keep in the refrigerator for 48 hours.

Table 2 - The results of the organoleptic characteristics of the quality of drinking cow's milk

	Appearance and consistency	Taste and smell	Color
Requirements of regulatory documents	Homogeneous liquid without sediment, cereal protein and fat lumps	Clean, no outsiders, not peculiar to fresh milk tastes and odors. For pasteurized milk and UHT - with a hint of pasteurization for UHT milk and ghee - pronounced flavor pasteurization	White, uniform throughout the mass to warm milk - from light cream to dark cream-colored, for sterilized milk - with a light cream color, for low-fat milk - with a slightly bluish tint to warm milk may be slightly brownish tint
№1	Homogeneous without sludge, cereal protein and fat lumps	Clean, smell poorly defined, watery, sweet taste	White, uniform throughout the mass with a yellowish tinge
№2	Homogeneous without sludge, cereal protein and fat lumps	Clean, pleasant milky taste, smell poorly defined	White, uniform throughout the mass
№3	Uniform, no sediment, cereal protein and lumps of fat on the walls of the vessel, gas bubbles are present	Clean, weakly expressed pleasant milky flavor with a slightly sweet flavor, expressed milk smell	White, uniform throughout the mass with a cream shade
№4	Homogeneous without sludge, cereal protein and fat lumps	Expressed particular unpleasant watery taste, smell ulterior	White, uniform throughout the mass
№5	Homogeneous without sludge, cereal protein and fat lumps, on the foil packaging in contact with the product, the availability of cream	Clean, pleasant expressed milk smell and taste with a sweet aftertaste	White, uniform throughout the mass with a cream shade
№6	Homogeneous without sludge, cereal protein and fat lumps	Expressed unpleasant smell food and fresh milk, sweet aftertaste	White, uniform throughout the mass with a cream shade
№7	Homogeneous without sludge, cereal protein and fat lumps	Net expressed pleasant odor and specific dairy milk flavor	White, uniform throughout the mass

Test samples of drinking cow's milk is exposed to certain levels of titratable acidity (pH) and electrical potential, with a pH meter (model 004TA RNT). Measurements were made through software RNISOM v1.5.

Measurements were carried out on ultrasonic milk analyzer conducted three times for samples of each sample to obtain results with a small range. Measurements at a pH meter were produced by software with given parameters measurement every 5 seconds for 5 minutes for each of the test samples, including the control (distilled water).

Results of the experimental data obtained as mean values of physico - chemical quality of drinking milk cow are shown in Table 3.

Analysis of physico-chemical parameters listed in Table 3 showed the following. The fat content in the samples was in the range from 0%

to 3.64 %, which depended on the positioning of the assortment of products manufacturer.

The protein content in the samples № 2, 3, 6 is in the acceptable range of regulatory documents . Several reduced protein content, which is different from the standard value for the shares hundredths found in samples № 1, 5, 7, that does not affect the overall level of compliance of the test cow milk drinking regulations. Although attracts attention and requires additional practical research of raw materials for the production of these products. Perhaps reduced protein content in the final product can be determined due to the level of quality of raw milk. The sample number 4 showed the lowest protein content of 2.47 %, which is lowering from the norm by 23%, indicating that unscrupulous manufacturers.

Table 3 - Results of experimental data of physico-chemical quality of drinking cow's milk

Sample number	Average standard value	№1	№2	№3	№4	№5	№6	№7
Fat,%	Depends on the kind of assortment of milk	0	1,22	1,46	2,03	2,83	3,24	3,64
Protein,%	3-3,2	2,99	3,32	3,12	2,47	2,92	3,07	2,93
Lactose%	4,7	4,42	4,89	4,58	3,59	4,24	4,45	4,25
SNF%	8-9	8	8,86	8,3	6,53	7,73	8,12	7,75
Density, g/cm3	1,027	1,0294	1,0318	1,0294	1,0218	1,0258	1,027	1,0252
Added water content,%	Depends on the normalization on process step	6,2	0	1,63	24,03	8,58	3,9	8,05
Cryoscopic point, C	-0,520	-0,521	-0,588	-0,547	-0,423	-0,508	-0,534	-0,511
Acidity pH	6,68	7,46	7,50	7,51	7,58	7,54	7,56	7,49
Electric potential, mV		-27,78	-29,85	-30,17	-34,04	-31,65	-32,76	-29,46

Lactose content in the samples was less № 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 normative values, the smallest deviation in the smaller side showed a pattern number 6. In the above samples, reduced lactose content can be the result of adding a quantity of water in step machining operation –

normalization. The biggest addition of water was observed in samples number 4 (24, 03%), № 5 and № 7 (about 8.6 % and 8.05 %), respectively, the least amount of lactose was found in these samples. Dependence in lactose content of added water is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 - Dependence of the lactose content of the added water content in the samples of drinking cow's milk

Determination of skimmed milk (SM) in the samples showed № 1, 2, 3, 6 regulatory compliance intervals for this indicator. Samples № 5, 7 revealed a downward deflection, but it is around 2.5%, so it can be justified by the addition of water at a stage of

normalization in the production of milk. Lowest SM content showed a pattern number 4 (6.53%), which again explains the introduction of 24% added water. SM dependence on the content of water added is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 - Dependence of SM from the added water content in the samples of drinking cow's milk

The data on the density value of cow's milk showed that the samples № 1, 2, 3, 6 figure corresponds to the normative value and exceeds it by a higher SOMO and a lower content of added water than samples № 4, 5, 7. For samples № 5, 7 densities lower than the standard value of 0.2%. And the sample number 4 is the lowest density, which is 1.0218 g/cm³, which shows the deviation from the norm of 0.5%. Impact on the value of the density also has a fat content of the

milk of cows drinking. Figure 3 shows the relationship between the above parameters. Cryoscopic point value depends on the content in the product water added and the SNF. Figure 4 shows the relationship between the above parameters. Cryoscopic highest point will be observed for the sample number 4, the lowest - in the sample number 2 (added water - 0%).

Fig. 3 - Surface physico-chemical parameters of the samples of drinking cow's milk (density, SOMO, fat content)

Fig. 4 - Surface depending on physico-chemical parameters of the samples of drinking cow's milk (cryoscopic point, the content of water added SOMO)

Cryoscopic point value depends on the content in the product water added and the SNF . fig. 4 shows the relationship between the above parameters. Cryoscopic highest point will be observed for the sample number 4, the lowest - in the sample no. 2 (added water - 0%). Environment of drinking cow's milk should be slightly acidic and be 6.68 . All of the samples of environment and slightly alkaline pH value exceeds the standard value of at least 11.7% (sample number 1) , maximum - 15% (sample number 4). The obtained results of measurements of the electric potential and the acidity are depicted in the

diagrams in fig. 5. The relationship between the physico- chemical parameters is insensitive. The experimental data on the percentage of protein, fat, carbohydrate and energy values were compared with the corresponding values specified on the label. Comparison results are shown in fig. 6. Comparison of experimental data and labeling of sample no. 4 has not been made due to non-compliance with the requirements of Regulation manufacturer labeling of food products in the EU and the lack of information on the product packaging.

Data on the labeling of the samples number 1 and number 2 is slightly underestimated and samples № 3, № 5, № 6, № 7 - somewhat understated, but are within rounding decimals values of the data. The

weighty error cause cannot harm to consumers, but there is the potential negative impact of these products on the preferences of consumers who strictly follow the balance of calories consumed.

Fig. 5 - Graphs and acidity measurements of the electric potential of milk samples

Foregoing to the following conclusions: research data quality indicators of drinking cow's milk producers in Bulgaria and Poland indicate either a full or partial non-compliance with regulatory requirements for manufacturers labeling organoleptic and physico- chemical parameters. Noted that, even if the sample complied with all regulatory requirements for labeling, then at least one of the organoleptic or physico- chemical parameters it observes deviation. For example, sample number 5 met all the requirements for labeling and organoleptic, a number of physico-chemical parameters and density of milk showed a decrease of 0.2%. The same sample had the highest rates of quality compared with samples of similar products from other manufacturers. The lowest quality characteristics found in the sample number 4 - there was a frank non-compliance labeling and low consumer product.

Focusing on the most common discrepancies quality of drinking cow's milk should be mentioned: incomplete name of the product, any failure to mention its special heat treatment, the presence of extraneous odors and flavors, not provided for manufacturing technology increased water content.

Based on the fact that the main priority of any country is the preservation of public health and nutrition is one of the most important determinants of human health, it follows from the foregoing that the failure to comply with regulatory requirements for manufacturers of quality of drinking cow's milk - one of the most popular among the Bulgarian population may lead to a decrease in the level of consumers obtain essential nutrients, and as a consequence - to variations in human health and the negative demographic consequences.

Fig. 6 - Comparison of the experimental data on the percentage of protein, fat, carbohydrate and energy value of the information labeling of the samples

References

- [1] . Vilkova S.A. Examination of consumer goods: Textbook. - Moscow: Publishing and Trading Corporation "Darya and K °», 2007. - 252.
- [2] . Grigorenko O.M. Evolution of food conception theory [E-resource] / Grigorenko O.M. - Mode of access <www.nbuu.gov.ua/portal/Soc_Gum/Vdnuet/tehn/2011_1/Grigor.pdf>.
- [3]. Gutikov V.V. Environmental and food safety: lecture, Donetsk -2005, 41
- [4]. DSTU 2661: 2010 Cows Milk. General technical minds, Kiev, Derzhspozhivstandart
- [5]. Commodity of food products: Manual/T. P. Lapina, Kovalevych T.I., Kemerovo Technological Institute of Food Industry. - Kemerovo, 2006. - 109 p.

DRYING OF PLANT MATERIALS IN A VIBRO-FLUIDIZED BED WITH INFRARED HEATING

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Abstract: *The article presents results of experimental studies on the drying of sunflower seeds and fruit pits in a vibro-fluidized bed with infrared heating. We analyzed the influence of the heat flux density on drying kinetics of the products.*

Keywords: *drying, infrared heating, sunflower seeds, fruit pits, drying and drying rate curves.*

1. Statement of the problem and its relationship with the most important scientific and practical tasks

Traditionally, the Ukraine and Russia drying of various kinds of bulk plant materials, including fruit pits and sunflower seeds, carried by the convective process in drum, tunnel, mining, recycling dryer, the main advantage of which is a greater productivity. However, these dryers is quite energy intensive, cumbersome and do not provide uniform heat treatment of the products as it does not take into account specificity of many products such as drying objects. For sunflower seeds and fruit pits this specificity is heterogeneous structure, as they have a shell (for sunflower seed husk), fruit shells (film) and the seed (kernel). Different chemical composition of these components causes varying degrees of cohesion moisture to be removed by drying. For example, husk, which contains large amounts of polysaccharides, can be regarded as a capillary-porous body and kernel which contains a large amount of protein - colloidal. Note also that some varieties of sunflower seed as fruit pits has the shell which is not tight to the kernel, that is, between the shell and the kernel there is an air cavity. Thus, these products include components that differ sharply on thermodynamic properties.

When selecting the method of drying the products should also be considered that their storage stability depends essentially on the integrity of the structure. A damage sunflower seed, which performs the function of mechanical protection of the core from the action of microorganisms, reduces their stability during storage. Thus specificity of sunflower seeds as a drying object makes it impractical to use the surface heat supply, which, due to the relatively

high moisture inertia seeds, creates the conditions for cracking its husk.

More promising for the drying of such products look volumetric methods of heat supply, of which, in recent years the most widely used infrared and microwave. They can provide uniform heating of the particles of the product or a more intensive heating of the core. Furthermore, there is no need to use air as a heat agent, which significantly reduces the energy consumption for the drying process.

The aim of this work is to study the drying of sunflower seeds and fruit pits in a vibro-fluidized bed with infrared heating.

2. The main material

Studies were carried out on the experimental setup, which schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 1. Infrared radiation generators are tubular electric 2 in the form of eight ("dark" emitters). They are equipped with a reflector 1, which directs the heat rays falling upward on a cylindrical steel pan 4 with the product 6. Block emitters mounted on a rack 8 and can vertically move and be fixed at different distances relative to the pan 4. The magnitude of radiation was varied by varying the autotransformer 7 and the distance between the emitters block and the pan 4. Vibro-fluidized layer of the product is created using the eccentric vibrator 5, which transmits circular vibrations to the pan 4. Vibrations parameters are changed by the autotransformer 7.

The Fig. 2 shows the curves of drying and drying rate of sunflower seed varieties "Titanic" with an initial moisture content of 19.4%, depending on the heat flux of infrared radiation. Experiments carried out when the specific load on the horizontal surface of the pan 4 kg/m².

Analysis of the curves shows that the drying process takes almost two periods - the constant and falling drying rate. Period of constant drying rate in the classical representation [1] on the curves is absent because the corresponding thermograms not visible characteristic gently sloping plot.

The first critical moisture content, which separates the two drying period, varies depending on the magnitude of the heat flux density from 11.6% (1570 W/m^2) to 13.6% (660 W/m^2). Tendency of first critical moisture content change indicates its decrease with increasing rigidity of the thermal action of the product.

Fig. 1 – Schematic diagram of the experimental setup

Fig. 2 - Curves of drying and drying rate of sunflower seeds at different values of the infrared radiation heat flux: 1, 1' - 1570 W/m^2 ; 2, 2' - 1310 W/m^2 ; 3, 3' - 980 W/m^2 ; 4, 4' - 660 W/m^2

The drying to a moisture content of 6%, which ensures long-term storage of seeds, varies from 24 minutes (1570 W/m²) and 69 min (660 W/m²). It should be noted essentially nonlinear dependence of the drying of heat flux. Thus, when the heat flux density decreases to 1570 W/m² to 980 W/m² (curves 1-3 in fig. 2) the duration of the drying to a moisture content of 6% is changed from 24 min to 34 min and reduction of the heat capacity, making the above non-linear dependence.

For curve-fitting the drying rate in the period falling speed we used the equation [1]:

$$du/d\tau = \chi' N(u - u_e)^n, \quad (1)$$

where $du/d\tau$ – drying rate, u – current moisture content, u_e – equilibrium moisture content, N – drying rate in constant period, χ' – relative drying coefficient, n – coefficient, which describes product properties.

From equation (1) by integrating the formula for the calculation of the drying to final moisture content of u_f :

$$\tau = \frac{(u_c - u_e)^{1-n} - (u_f - u_e)^{1-n}}{\chi' N(1-n)} + \frac{u_0 - u_c}{N}, \quad (2)$$

where u_c – critical moisture content, which separates the two drying period, u_0 – initial moisture content. Result of the approximation is shown of Table 1.

Table 1. Date of drying rate curves approximation

Heat flux density, W/m ²	1570	1370	980	660
χ'	3,99	8,68	6,85	0,52
n	0,55	0,57	0,51	0,49
Correlation coefficient	0,999	0,999	0,998	0,995

Table 2. Kinetic data of fruit pits drying, depending on the heat flux density of infrared heating

Data	Heat flux density 1480 W/m ²	890 W/m ²	570 W/m ²
Apricot pits			
Initial moisture content, %	32,2	29,8	28,7
Drying rate in constant period, %/minutes	0,64	0,46	0,26
Critical moisture content, which separates the two drying period, %	17,6	24,7	25,6
Equilibrium moisture content, %	4,4	5,2	9,2
Drying to equilibrium moisture content, minutes	84	134	182
Sweet cherry pits			

decreases to 980 W/m² 660 W/m² (curve 4 in Fig. 2) - with a 34 min to 69 min.

This, in our view, confirms that the drying rate in the infrared heat supply depends not only on the heat flux density, but also on the spectrum of emitters. Obviously, as the temperature decreases the emitters surface main irradiation wavelength is shifted toward its worst absorption product, which together with the

In Fig. 3 shows the curves of drying and drying rate of apricot pits varieties "Early Marusicha" and sweet cherry and cherry pits harvest in 2013. Experiments carried out at specific loads on the horizontal surface of the pan 0.69 kg/m².

Their analysis shows that the drying process in all cases is occurring in almost two periods - the constant and decreasing speed, and tendency increase in the duration of the first period and the first critical moisture content decrease with increasing heat flux density, as in the experiments with sunflower seeds drying.

The form of the drying rate curves in the second period indicates the presence of capillary and colloidal moisture both in the shell and kernel. Several inflection points on the curves of speed drying sweet cherry and cherry pits indicate that these types of moisture are removed from the shell and the kernel simultaneously (probably originally from the shell, then from the kernel).

Data from the drying kinetics are given in Table. 2. Their analysis shows that, despite the considerable difference in size apricot pits compared with sweet cherry and cherry pits, drying period is mainly determined by the initial moisture content of the product, as the drying rate in the first period at the same rate of heat flow values differ slightly.

Initial moisture content, %	27,3	25,4	25,5
Drying rate in constant period, %/minutes	0,75	0,53	0,25
Critical moisture content, which separates the two drying period, %	15,7	17,8	22
Equilibrium moisture content, %	2,0	2,4	6,6
Drying to equilibrium moisture content, minutes	76	114	198
Cherry pits			
Initial moisture content, %	19,4	21,4	20,4
Drying rate in constant period, %/minutes	0,61	0,49	0,26
Critical moisture content, which separates the two drying period, %	10,8	15,3	17,3
Equilibrium moisture content, %	2,1	3	6
Drying to equilibrium moisture content, minutes	60	94	150

a

b

Fig. 4 - Curves of drying and drying rate of apricot (a), sweet cherry (b) and cherry (c) pits at different values of the infrared radiation heat flux: 1, 1' - 1480 W/m²; 2, 2' - 890 W/m²; 3, 3' - 570 W/m²

Conclusions

The experimental results confirmed the promise of sunflower seeds and fruit pits drying in a vibro-fluidized bed with infrared heating, as for all values of the heat flux density managed to provide sufficiently low final moisture content, there was no shell cracking and no uneven areas of processing of the product particles. Factor which limits the heat flux of infrared heating is

permissible heating temperature during drying of pits, which affects the quality of the most valuable kernel component- oil.

References

1. Lykov A.V. Theory of drying: Textbook. Textbook for students of technical universities. – M.: Energy, 1968. – 472 p.

CAVITATION TREATMENT OF GRAPE RAKIA

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Abstract: *In the present work we observe a method for improving the organoleptic and physic-chemical properties of grape rakia. We use cavitation for treatment of grape rakia, aiming to decrease any unwanted impurities. There is also a silver plate in the zone of hydrodynamic cavitation, which gives away silver ions during cavitation. These silver ions serve as catalyst. 24V constant current is given to the plate for more intensive ions radiating. The cavitation number, at which the experiments have been performed, is constant. After eight minute cavitation treatment of the grape rakia we can see change of the complex alcohols and decrease of methanol, ethyl-acetate and acetaldehyde. This leads to better taste of the rakia.*

Keywords: *cavitation treatment, water-alcohol mixtures.*

1. Introduction

The distillates for high alcohol content drinks, the rectified spirit and the ready for drink high alcohol content drinks contain fatty and aromatic alcohols, which influence the taste and aroma of the distillates, spirit and drinks. The main representatives of the monovalent fatty alcohols are: ethyl, methyl, insatiable isoamyl, isoamyl and n-butyl. The aromatic alcohols are presented by phenylethyl, benzyl, tyrosol and tryptophol [1, 2, 3, 4]. The grape rakis are high alcohol content drinks, which are obtained by distillation of fermented grape pulp, grape juice or secondary alcohol containing products from wine production. The modern grape rakia process apply partial rectification of the rakia distillates, which increases their alcohol content, the concentration of typical for the grape rakia aroma substances and removing of the difficult to ferment unwanted final impurities. The main staged of the rakia production are distillation, rectification and depuration [4, 6, 7]. In the industrial production the water-alcohol mixtures are processed in adsorption columns with active charcoal in static or dynamic regime. In vodka production the method of hydrodynamic cavitation in silver ion and active charcoal zone is also applied [4, 6, 7]. In this work we present a method, in which the grape rakia is subject to cavitation processing, in order to decrease the difficult to evaporate components: aldehydes, esters, complex alcohols and fatty acids, which give unpleasant odor and non-typical for the

grape rakia taste and opalescence. The method is applicable only when the produced rakia does not correspond to the requirements and standards for admissible harmful substance according to Bulgaria State Standard. Before starting the processing we add to the rakia active charcoal, which absorbs different harmful substances and the separated silver ions in the cavitation zone serve as catalyst [1, 2, 3, 4].

2. Materials and methods

We use 35 liters grape rakia with alcohol content 68 volume %. We add 100 gr. active charcoal. This mixture is put in the tank of the cavitation installation and is being cavitation processed for eight minutes. During that time in the zone of the hydrodynamic cavitation there are silver ions. The observations are executed at constant cavitation number. For performing the test we use a cavitation installation, which has been developed in University of Food Technologies – Plovdiv. The installation has the following technical parameters: Cosed circulation system made of stainless steel $\Phi=56 \times 4$. A tank with maximal volume 35 liters. The transition of the rakia is done by centrifugal pump with the following characteristics:

Installed power	N	kW	5.5
Flow	Q	m ³ /s	19.10 ⁻³
Head pressure	H	N/m ²	0.5x10 ⁶
Rotation frequency of the pump shaft	n	min ⁻¹	2900

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The cavitation installation design allows the regulation of the cavitation process intensity. This can be achieved by alteration of the pressure and velocity in the system, as well as by alteration of the geometrical parameters of the cavitation installation [1, 3, 5].

There is a silver plate in the cavitation zone, which is constantly powered so that it gives away silver ion more intensively. We use a close type scheme for experiment, which has been previously used by us to prove the efficiency of the cavitation on fluids. It contains the following units: cavitation installation, centrifugal pump, tank, pipeline, measuring units and regulating valves (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Drawing of the experimental stand
 1 – collective tank; 2 – pipe system; 3 – flange; 4 – cavitating unit; 5 – differential pressure meter; 6 – blende (flow meter); 7 – regulating valve; 8 – inlet valve; 9 – discharge valve; 10 – centrifugal pump; 11 – vacuum meter; 12 – sample valve.

The aim of the experiments with the cavitation stand is to confirm the hypothesis that the hydrodynamic cavitation can be used for changing the quantity of aldehydes, esters, fatty acids and complex alcohols in the content of the grape rakia. After research we found no data of experiments regarding the topic of cavitation process of grape rakia [1, 2, 5]. Method for working with the stand:

1. The tank 1 is filled with 35 liters grape rakia and 100 gr. active charcoal.

2. The centrifugal pump 10 is started when valve 8 is closed.

3. After getting into working regime we slowly open valve 8.

4. We use closed circulation system, in which the mixture passes through the zone of hydrodynamic cavitation with multiplicity, which

depends on the flow Q . In this zone we have the separation of silver ions.

5. We report from the pressure meter the values of the pressure difference before and after the flow meter (blende) 6 and form the standard characteristic of the blende and the flow in the system.

6. The program for recording the current is started in the computer.

7. During a defined time interval we take samples through Valve 12 and each sample is 15 ml. processed rakia. We also take a zero sample – unprocessed rakia.

We perform analysis of the samples (gas-chromatographic method).

The shape of the cavitation installation is designed in such a way, so that it is possible to have maximal circulation zone, as well as achieving intensive cavitation.

Fig. 2. Drawing of a cavitating unit and the instruments
 1 – cavitation unit, 2 – silver plate; 3 – rectifier; 4 – registration unit (digital multiset), 5 – computer; 6 – flanges.

For intensification of the absorption process in the cavitation unit we put a silver plate, which gives away silver ions (Ag^+). The location of the silver plate is chosen in such a way, so that it has to be in the zone of the cut jet impact, where we expect the strongest cavitation erosion. Thus we can guarantee the availability of silver ions in the liquid. To intensify the process of ionization we put constant 24V current to the silver plate (Fig. 2) [3, 4, 5]. We measure the pressure and flow in all executed experiments. We also measure the time for cavitation treatment and perform gas-chromatographic analysis of the rakia samples. The cavitation processed rakia is filtered so that the active charcoal is removed and we add distilled water to achieve alcohol grade of

minimal 40 volume %. (according to the standard).

3. Result and discussion

We have graphically presented the results for the influence of the cavitation treatment on the impurities content in the grape raki. Two series of tests have been performed and the results are put together in the following two graphics:

Fig.3 Influence of the time for the cavitation treatment on the methanol

Fig.4 Influence of the time for the cavitation treatment on the acetaldehyde

Fig.5 Influence of the time for the cavitation treatment on the ethyl acetate

Fig.6 Graphic for the percentage content of some complex alcohols at two tests

The raki. must meet the following requirements according to the standard:

Table 1

Ethyl alcohol	Vol.%	40,0±0,3
Methyl alcohol	g/dm ³ not more than	2
Furfural	mg/dm ³ not more than	4
Acids (like acetic)	mg/dm ³ not more than	800
Esters (like ethyl acetate)	mg/dm ³	600-4800
Complex alcohols	mg/dm ³ not more than	2000
Aldehydes (like acetaldehyde)	mg/dm ³ not more than	600
Total SO ₂	mg/dm ³ not more than	200
Free SO ₂	mg/dm ³ not more than	20

The specific characteristics of the grape rakis are mainly defined not by the common quantities of the main rude volatile impurities – which contain in the rakis, but by the concentrations of the separate representatives of each group. The grape rakis must meet defined organoleptic properties, which define the taste, the odor, the color and the clearness of the rakis.

The cavitation treatment causes quantity changes of acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate, methanol, complex alcohols. In the cavitation treated samples the quantity of acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate and methanol decreases compared to the quantity in the control sample (not cavitation treated). The most significant parameter decrease appears in the fourth minute of cavitation, Fig. 3, 4 and 5. This statement can be explained by assuming the possibility at long time cavitation

treatment (over 4 minutes) to have oxidation processes to part of the fatty aldehydes to the corresponding alcohols.

The decrease of acetaldehydes and ethyl acetate compared to their quantity in the control (not cavitation treated) samples depends on the duration of the cavitation treatment.

The most significant decrease of the acetaldehydes and ethyl acetate we achieve at the variants of 6 minutes duration of the treatment. The quantity changes for the shown complex alcohols vary depending on the time for treatment, as the tendency is to be increased up to the fourth minute and after that it drops till the eighth minute of treatment.

As a whole, the tendency for dropping of the quantity of the observed parameters: methanol, ethyl acetate, acetaldehyde and complex alcohols is explained by the passing of the solutions, mixed with active charcoal through a zone of hydrodynamic cavitation.

The air in the micro-pores of the active charcoal serves for forming cavitation caverns (bubbles). The formed at closing of the caverns local effects – acoustic waves, hits and heating at the presence of silver ions catalyst oxidize the impurities of the spirit.

The cavitation provides maximal penetration of the water-alcohol mixture in the micro-pores of the adsorbent (active charcoal).

The added with the mixture silver ions catalyze the oxidation processes on the surface of the active charcoal.

The treatment effect is defined by the speed of interaction between the spirit and the active charcoal and depends on the duration of the treatment and the cavitation process characteristics.

For characterizing the stage of purification of water-alcohol mixtures a gas-chromatographic analysis has been used.

4. Conclusions

1. The cavitation treatment of water-alcohol mixtures and rakia significantly decreases the

volatile mixtures content – complex alcohols, acetaldehydes, ethyl acetate and methanol.

2. With the cavitation treatment duration we decrease the quantity of the acetaldehydes, ethyl acetate, methanol and complex alcohols.

3. The optimal decrease of complex alcohols is achieved in the interval 4-6 minutes of cavitation treatment.

4. The added silver ions have good effect as catalyst of the process of rakia purification.

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References

1. Angelov M. and others, *Hydrodynamic Treatment of high alcohol solutions*, Scientific conference of Hydroaerodynamics, Technical University “Lenin”, Sofia, 1985.(in Bulgarian)
2. Angelov M., Marinov M. and others, *Hydrodynamic cavitation application in the vodka production*. Food Technology, issue 6, Sofia, 1987. (in Bulgarian)
3. Angelov M., *Cavitation application for liquid treatment*. Habilitation work “Professor”, Plovdiv 2009. (in Bulgarian)
4. Marinov M., *High alcohol drinks and spirit processing*. Academic issue of University of Food Technology – Plovdiv, 2005. (in Bulgarian)
5. Stoeva D. Cavitation treatment of liquids, Dissertation, 2006. (in Bulgarian)
6. Buglass A.J., at all , *Applications of natural ingredients in alcoholic drinks*. A volume in Woodhead Publishing Series in Food Science, Technology and Nutrition, 2012, Pages 358–416.
7. Lachenmeiera D. W., Haupta S., Schulzb K., *Defining maximum levels of higher alcohols in alcoholic beverages and surrogate alcohol products*. Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology, Volume 50, Issue 3, April 2008, Pages 313–321.

OBSERVATION OF THE AERO-DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CORRUGATED WALL TUBE

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Abstract: *The corrugation of the smooth steel tubes increases the heating surface per length unit. The advantages compared to smooth pipe bodies are the lower relative mass at same thermal power and the smaller volume. The interesting subject is the observation and the analysis of the aero-dynamic parameters in a corrugated tube. The aerodynamic parameters studied in this work are: the distribution of the velocities in length of the fluid flow, the formation of circulation zones, their dimensions and position in the tube. There are many graphical relations, derived at the post-processing of the solutions, which clearly show the effect of the corrugated wall at two different thresholds. Defining the location and the dimensions of the circulation zones we can optimize the geometric parameters of a corrugated tube, so that we achieve better heat transfer.*

Keywords: *circulation zone, corrugated tube, CFD, boundary layer conference, editing.*

1. Introduction

The corrugated tubes are used for intensification of the heat transfer of different heat-exchanging units. For the proper studying of the heat transfer processes in such tubes, we should achieve also the aerodynamic parameters of the fluid inside the corrugated tube. In the present work we observe the following aerodynamic parameters: velocity and pressure distribution of the fluid in the tube pipe, the achieved circulation zones. These are the zones with zero velocity at the place of the returning of the velocity vector.

These very zones are of interest for hydrodynamic point of view, because they define the intensity of the heat distribution inside the flow [10, 11, 13, 14,].

We can achieve increased heat flows by increasing the velocity of the heat carrier or by corrugating the surfaces.

There are two methods for intensification of the heat transfer: increasing the heat flow independently by the expensed and increasing the heat flow at set power of the heat carrier [1, 2, 3, 4].

The increase of the fluid velocity leads to increasing the heat flow, but it also leads to increasing the pressure losses ($\Delta P = P_1 - P_2$) and thus the effect from corrugation is decreased.

The contaminations, deposits - their formation depends on the aerodynamic factors -

whirl zones - with low velocities, cutting of the flow.

The study helps for developing means of prevention and forecasting of the possible deposits areas.

The heat transfer intensity can be affected by alteration of the geometric dimensions of the channel, alteration of the heat carrier velocity and the shape of the heat transferring surface, which defines the temperature field.

In case of flowing within a solid wall there is a boundary layer formed. It is the main thermal resistor.

The thicker the boundary layer is, the weaker the heat transfer becomes.

The decrease of the boundary layers thickness and the increase of the transferring coefficients for moment and heat is the essence of the heat transfer intensification.

The most favorable hydrodynamic regime regarding the heat transfer is the transitional and turbulent regime in the boundary layer. In natural conditions the turbulent regime can be reached at high velocities, as the pressure losses (P_{loss}) are higher and the pumps power is high. We can avoid this by artificial turbulence of the flow in the boundary layer or by destroying the boundary layer near the wall.

This makes necessary the application of artificial methods for heat transfer intensification [7, 8, 9, 12].

The heat transfer intensification methods are divided in two groups: passive and active.

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Passive methods are the ones that do not need direct use of outer energy source. Active are those, who use outer source.

The most frequently used passive method is intensification through surface baffles, such as rough surfaces and equally distributed roughness [5, 6]. The configuration of the baffles is chosen in such a way, so that it destroys the viscosity sub-layer and increases the turbulence near the wall. The aim of the present research is to trace the boundary layer alteration near to a specially corrugated wall with baffles. The baffles have variable step towards the flow direction at same height.

2. Materials and methods

The model researches are carried out at four different Reynolds numbers (Re). We have used the equation for fluid movement for turbulent regime and we have added two equations for kinetic energy – and kinetic energy dissipation . The mesh contains 16500 cells, 33350 faces and 16851 knots, as there has been done a preliminary research for independence of the solution from the mesh thickness [3, 4, 9, 11]. The movement equations are described as follows:

At high Reynolds number κ -turbulent model is expressed by the following equations:

$$U_i \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(v + \frac{v_t}{\sigma_v} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_i} \right] + C_{\varepsilon 1} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} v_t \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} - C_{\varepsilon 2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} \quad (1)$$

$$v_t = C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (2)$$

$$U_i \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i} = v_t \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(v + \frac{v_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i} \right] - \bar{\varepsilon} - 2v \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{k}}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$U_i \frac{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(v + \frac{v_t}{\sigma_v} \right) \frac{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}}{\partial x_i} \right] + C_{\varepsilon 1} \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}}{k} v_t \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} - C_{\varepsilon 2} \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}^2}{k} + 2v v_t \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_k} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\bar{\varepsilon} = \varepsilon - 2v \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{k}}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$U_i \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(v + \frac{v_t}{\sigma_v} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_i} \right] + C_{\varepsilon 1} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} v_t \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{c_\mu \eta^3 (1 - \eta/\eta_0) \varepsilon^2}{1 + \beta \eta^3} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} - C_{\varepsilon 2} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} \quad (6)$$

The constants are:

$$C_{\varepsilon 1} = 1,44; \quad C_{\varepsilon 2} = \frac{1,92}{(1 + 0,9 A_1^{1/2} A_2)} = 1,92 \quad (7)$$

3. Results

We observe model air flow (developed, turbulent) with temperature at the inlet of the tube 353K (80oC) through corrugated tube with inside diameter $d=0,08\text{m}$ and length $0,2\text{m}$. The wall of the tube is heated to 453K (180oC). The aerodynamic of the fluid flow has been modulated at two different degrees of corrugation

of the tube – X1 and X2 – equation (8) and at four different Reynolds numbers – equation (9).

The graphical relations are described for section in the center of the geometric body and for outgoing section.

$$X_1 = \frac{h_1}{D} = \frac{0,002}{0,08} = 0,025$$

$$X_2 = \frac{h_2}{D} = \frac{0,004}{0,08} = 0,05 \quad (8)$$

$$Re_1 = \frac{V_1 \cdot D}{v_{e-x}} = \frac{0,75 \cdot 0,08}{1,7894 \cdot 10^{-5}} = 3353,1$$

$$Re_2 = \frac{V_2 \cdot D}{v_{e-x}} = \frac{1,0,08}{1,7894 \cdot 10^{-5}} = 4470,8$$

$$Re_3 = \frac{V_3 \cdot D}{v_{e-x}} = \frac{2,0,08}{1,7894 \cdot 10^{-5}} = 8941,5$$

$$Re_4 = \frac{V_4 \cdot D}{v_{e-x}} = \frac{2,8,0,08}{1,7894 \cdot 10^{-5}} = 0,125 \cdot 10^5 \quad (9)$$

Fig. 1 Geometric model of observed area from the corrugated tube with threshold height $h_1=2$ mm.

The steps between the two thresholds are different. For the first scheme (Fig 1) the height is $h_1=2$ mm and for the second one $h_2=4$ mm. The dimensionless ration of the threshold height and the distance between the two thresholds have been calculated by equation (10).

$$Y_1 = \frac{P_1}{h_1} = \frac{0,045}{0,002} = 22,5 ;$$

$$Y_2 = \frac{P_2}{h_1} = \frac{0,085}{0,002} = 42,5 \quad (10)$$

The distance between two thresholds (the step P) is different.

$$Y_3 = \frac{P_1}{h_2} = \frac{0,045}{0,004} = 11,25$$

$$Y_4 = \frac{P_2}{h_2} = \frac{0,085}{0,004} = 21,25 \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2 Velocity gradient in cross section in the center for $Re_1=3353,1$ at height of the threshold $X_1=0,025$ and $X_2=0,05$

We can see that at the high threshold X_2 there is a removal in the maximal velocity in the flow direction.

At X_1 the maximal velocity is reached at Y-coordinate lower than $[-0,6]$, while at X_2 maximum velocity appears at the coordinates near to $[-0,5]$. This means that there is a removal of the circulation zone towards the flow direction

The mixing (stirring) of the fluid flow at the higher threshold is stronger – X_2 . The curve for X_1 is neared to the wall.

Fig. 3 Distribution of the dynamic pressure in cross section in the center for $Re_1=3353,1$ at height of the threshold $X_1=0,025$ and $X_2=0,05$

We can see the same removal of the maximal of the dynamic pressure value in cross section of the flow.

Fig. 4 Distribution of the dynamic pressure at the outlet at $Re_1=3353,1$ at two different heights of thresholds $X_1=0,025$ and $X_2=0,05$

Fig. 5 Distribution of the turbulent kinetic energy in cross section in the center of the pipe at two different heights of the threshold $X_1=0,025$ and $X_2=0,05$ and same value of the $Re_1=3353,1$.

Key indicator for the intensification of the heat transfer processes is the change of the turbulent kinetic energy near the flow surface, as well the dissipation of the turbulent kinetic energy.

We can see on Fig. 6 the change of the turbulent kinetic energy when the relative height of the threshold. We can see that at the higher threshold the turbulent kinetic energy has 2,25 higher value.

This proves the main statement, that the higher threshold leads to turbulized flow. Therefore at higher threshold we have bigger circulation zone and therefore the fluid flow is more turbulized.

Fig. 6 Turbulent Dissipation Rate (Epsilon) in cross section in the center of the tube at two different heights of the threshold $X_1=0,025$ and $X_2=0,05$ and $Re_1=3353,1$.

Fig.7 Distribution of the velocity in the middle section for all Re numbers and height of the threshold $X_1=0,025$.

The change in the character of flowing near the wall reflects in the distribution of the velocity towards the flow direction and cross the flow.

Fig. 8 Distribution of the turbulent kinetic energy in cross section in the central section of the tube at different initial value – Re number – Re_1 to Re_4 and $X_1=0,025$.

Fig. 9 Distribution of the turbulent kinetic energy in cross direction at the outlet of the tube at different initial value of the Re number - Re_1 to Re_4 and $X_1=0,025$.

The change in the peak of the TKE at cross direction of the flow testifies for the better mixing of the fluid flow (turbulizing) at the higher values of the Re number. If the Re number is increased, then the area of the circulation zone decreases.

Fig. 10 Visualization of the circulation zone behind the threshold at $X_1=0,025$. Formation of the circulation zone and inverting of the velocity vector behind the second threshold.

Fig. 11 Graphical determination of the circulation zone – tracing the place of inverting the vector direction for different cross sections – line 12, line 13, line 14

Fig.12 Location of lines 12, 13 and 14, which describe the circulation zone

Lines 12, 13 and 14 are specific places for velocity vector inversion and formation of the circulation zone. In the place of velocity vector conversion is also the line with zero velocity, which presents the outer loop of the circulation zone.

Fig. 13 Loop of the zero velocity – circulation zone at $X_1=0,025$ and $Re_1=3353,1$

Before first and second threshold there is also a slight turbulence and flow cutting (it is determined by the presence of hydraulic resistances) but before the third threshold there is no such circulation zone.

Fig. 14 Loop of the zero velocity – circulation zone at $X_2=0,05$ and $Re_4=0,125 \times 10^5$

Each subsequent circulation zone is bigger than the previous. At $X_2=0,05$ (threshold height 0,04mm) before the corrugation there is a bigger circulation zone, which is determined by the higher local resistance.

The observation of the location and the size of the circulation zone give us the possibility to optimize the shape and the geometrical parameters of the corrugation. After modulation and analysis of the circulation zone we can estimate the best solution for maximum effective heat transfer, which is the final goal of the numerical modulation. The forecasting of the

hydrodynamic parameters inside the flow through a corrugate tube is possible only by the methods of CFD modulation. The analysis and the visualization of the flow in such tubes have great importance, because they have wide application in the heat system and many more. Each observation has been done after check of the calculation mesh for adequacy and after proving the independence of the solutions by the mesh thickness. For this reason we need high calculation capacities and time.

Fig. 15 Lines of constant velocity $X_1=0,025$ and $Re_1=3353,1$

In the program for modulation of the flow through corrugated tube we have calculated and drawn lines with constant velocity. The visualization of the equal velocity curve is of great interest, because it is the one that determines the size of the circulation zone. After comparison of the two loops with zero velocity (Fig. 16 and Fig. 17) we can conclude that at the higher threshold the circulation zones are bigger.

Fig.16 Lines of constant velocity – after the second threshold at $X_1=0,025$ and $Re_1=3353,1$

Fig. 17 Constant velocity line – after the second threshold at $X_2=0,05$ and $Re_1=3353,1$

Fig. 18 Constant velocity lines – after the second threshold at $X_1=0,025$ and $Re_4=0,125 \times 10^5$

Fig. 19 Constant velocity lines. $X_1=0,025$ and $Re_4=0,125 \times 10^5$

By increasing the Re number the circulation zone decreases, which proves that the stillness zones are decreased (Fig. 13 and Fig. 14; Fig. 15 and Fig. 19).

The same relation is confirmed also by the dissipation distribution – ϵ (Fig.8 and Fig. 9)

We also observe alteration of the turbulent viscosity by increasing the Re number (Fig. 7, Fig. 8, Fig. 9)

The strongest aspect of increasing the turbulent pulsations near the wall is observed through the turbulent number of Re (Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12).

The change in the character of the flow near the wall reflects in the distribution of the velocity in direction of the flow and perpendicular to the flow. On Fig. 13, 14 and 15 we can see the velocity profiles (for distribution of the velocity at the X axis) for specific sections at three different Re numbers.

By comparison the shape of the velocity profiles we can see the influence of the corrugation on the redistribution of the velocity in direction Y. At the highest values of Re number (Re_3) we have the highest value of the velocity in perpendicular direction to the flow.

4. Conclusions

On the base of the result, we can make the following conclusions:

1. The uneven step of the baffles leads to better picture of the wall flowing.
2. By increasing the Re we reduce the size of the non-flowing zone after the baffles.
3. The redistribution of the velocity under influence of the baffles is higher expressed in the flow direction.

4. The turbulent parameters are highly dependent by the baffles and the Re number. This relation can be used for finding the optimal values of the Re number, considering the conditions of heat transfer.

References

1. Bergles, A. E. *ExHFT for fourth generation heat transfer technology*, Exp. Thermal Fluid Sci., Vol. 26, Nos. 2-4, pp. 335-344, (2002).
2. Catchpole, J.P., Drew, B.C.E., *Evaluation of some shaped tubes for steam condensers*, Steam Turbine Condenser, Report of a Meeting at NEL, Glasgow, UK, pp. 68-75, (1974).
3. Manglik, R.M., Bergels, A. E, *Enhanced Heat transfer in the New Millenium: A Review of the 2001 Literature*, Thermal Fluids and Thermal Processing Laboratory, Laboratory report № TFTPL-EB01, University of Cincinnati, OH, (2002).
4. V. Zimparov, *Enhancement of heat transfer by a combination of three-start spirally corrugated tubes with a twisted tape*, International Journal of heat and Mass Transfer 44 (2001) 551-574.
5. V. Zimparov, *Enhancement of heat transfer by a combination of a single - start spirally corrugated tubes with a twisted tape*, Experimental thermal and Fluid Science 25 (2002) 535-546.
6. V. Zimparov, *Prediction of friction factors and heat transfer coefficients for turbulent flow in corrugated tubes combined with twisted tape inserts*. Part 1: friction factors, International Journal of heat and Mass Transfer 47 (2004) 589-599.
7. V. Zimparov, *Prediction of friction factors and heat transfer coefficients for turbulent flow in corrugated tubes combined with twisted tape inserts*. Part 2: heat transfer coefficients, International Journal of heat and Mass Transfer 47 (2004) 385-393.
8. V. Zimparov, N. Vulchanov, L. Delov, *Heat transfer and friction characteristics of spirally corrugated tubes for power plant condensers - 1*. Experimental investigation and performance evaluation, International Journal of heat and Mass Transfer, Vol. 34, №9, pp. 2187-2197,1991.
9. O. Agra, H. Demir, *Numerical investigation of heat transfer and pressure drop in enhanced tubes*, International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer 38 (2011) 1384-1391.
10. Kostov P., K. Atanasov, N. Krastev, D. Angelova." *Universal velocity profiles of whirled injected jet*" Scientific Works Volume LX "Food Science, Technics and Technologies - 2013" - 18-19 October 2013, Plovdiv. (in bulgarian)
11. Petar KOSTOV, Neven KRASTEVA, Diana ANGELOVA, "*Observation of injected radial jet at isotherm conditions*", International conference "Machine Sciences 2012" - Sliven. (in bulgarian)
12. Kostov P., N. Krastev, D. Angelova. "*Aerodynamic observation of injected whirled jet*" Reports for the XVIII international scientific conference EMF 2013, I, 40-45; http://ecad.tu-sofia.bg/e-publ/search/files/1058_TE%20i%20QE_THT_2013.pdf(in bulgarian)
13. Kostov P., N. Krastev, D. Angelova "*Some observations of the aerodynamic of injected whirl jet*" Heat Engineering 5, year 4, book 2 (ISSN 1314-2550), pages.73-76; http://ecad.tu-sofia.bg/e-publ/search/files/1057_Sliven_2013.pdf(in bulgarian)
14. Angelov M., Raynov P., *Model studies of the hydrodynamics of flow in corrugated tubes*, Journal of food and packaging Science Technique and Technologies, ISSN 1314-7420, Vol 2, 2013.

EFFECT OF SOME TECHNOLOGICAL TREATMENTS OF COLD PRESSED WALNUT OIL (*JUGLANS REGIA* L.) ON ITS ANTIOXIDANT PROFILE AND QUALITY CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: *In this work technological treatment experiment was set up to determine the effectiveness of applied processing on quality and antioxidant properties of cold pressed walnut oil. The influence of the treatments was assessed by measuring the primary and secondary oxidation products in oil samples immediately after treatment. Primary oxidation products of walnut oil samples were evaluated by measuring peroxide value and conjugated dienes content. Secondary oxidation products of walnut oil samples were evaluated by measuring p-anisidine value and 2-thiobarbituric acid value. Antioxidant profile of walnut oil was analyzed by reaction kinetics and reducing power of the oil samples towards DPPH stable free radical. These data should help to describe oxidation mechanism of walnut oil and to recommend optimal conditions for walnut oil stabilization. However it is necessary to note that these data are not enough to make a final conclusion about the behavior of walnut oil after applied treatments.*

Keywords: *walnut oil, processing technology, DPPH assay, primary and secondary oxidation products.*

1. Introduction

Walnut is a crop of a high economic interest for the food industry. Walnut kernels have a lipid content of 65% of which 73% consists of polyunsaturated fatty acids, although values do vary between cultivars. Walnut kernels are consumed fresh or toasted, alone or in other edible products. Among the by-products of the walnut industry the oil has not yet obtained popularity, although it has been demonstrated that its consumption has a lot of nutritional benefits. The consumption of walnut oils from different geographic origins has been reported extensively. Their major constituents are tryglicerides, in which monounsaturated (oleic acid mainly) and polyunsaturated fatty acids (linoleic and α – linolenic acids) are present in high amounts. The presence of other bioactive minor components, such as tocopherols and phytosterols, has been also documented. Walnut oil is appreciated as specialty oil also because of its characteristic flavor, aroma and health benefits [8].

A major goal in walnut production is to find an appropriate method to stabilize lipids from walnut kernels. The oxidative stabilization of walnut oil is imperative to determine the

feasibility of bringing it into commercial production. However, the addition of this type of oil in processed food is not usual due to its low stability. To avoid this stability problem, researcher Calvoa et al. (2012) investigated the possibility to introduce walnut oil to the processed food as its microencapsulated form. As result of this research work, walnut oil was protected while food processing and released after consumption by the digestive process. Tsamouris et al. (2002) extracted and analized total lipids of walnut oil by high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC)/FID and GC-MS. Unsaturated fatty acids were found as high as 85%, while the percentage of the saturated fatty acids was found 15%. On the base of this data, researchers decided to prepare liposomes, which were characterized as new formulations. As authors declare, these formulations may have future applications for encapsulation.

In view of the fact, that walnut oil is to be effectively used in the food industry and human nutrition, it is extremely important to elaborate technology of walnut oil stabilization. This trial was set up to determine the effective method of technological treatment on quality of walnut oil. The effectiveness of the applied treatments was

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assessed by measuring the physicochemical properties and antioxidant potential of walnut oil.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample preparation and extraction procedure

Walnut fruits (*Juglans regia* L.) were obtained from agency Moldsilva, which is the central public administration body on state policy in

forestry and hunting in the Republic of Moldova (<http://www.moldsilva.gov.md/>). At full maturity, fruits were hand-picked directly from the trees. After harvest fruits were transported to the laboratory. Before oil extraction, the walnuts were manually cracked and shelled. Then, kernels were chopped in a KEM 36 mill. Walnut oil extraction was carried out essentially following the procedure presented in figure 1

Fig. 1. *Extraction procedure of walnut oil*

In particular, walnut oil expression was carried out at 20 ± 2 °C using an electrical press (Model PCU-125). The oil obtained was subjected to different technological treatments as centrifugation, dehydration, heat processing and their combination. Walnut oil without applied technological treatments was used as reference sample.

2.2. Chemicals

2-thiobarbituric acid (4,6-dihydroxy-2-mercaptopyrimidine) and p-anisidine were obtained from Alfa Aesar. 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) as free radical form (90% purity) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Ethanol (99.9%), methanol (99.8%), chloroform, 1-butanol, glacial acetic acid, potassium hydroxide, phenolphthalein, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and starch were supplied by Eco-Chimie (Chisinau, Moldova). All the chemicals used were of HPLC or analytical grade. Distilled water was used throughout.

2.3. Acid Value

Acid value was determined by potassium hydroxide titration as described in AOCS Official Method Cd 3d-63 (AOCS, 1999). The method was based on the number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide necessary to neutralize the

free acids in 1 gram of oil sample. Results were expressed as milligram of potassium hydroxide per gram of walnut oil sample [1].

2.4. Peroxide Value

Oxidation rate was studied by determination of the peroxide value (PV). This was determined according to AOCS Official Method Cd 8-53 (AOCS, 2003). Peroxide value was expressed as millimoles peroxide per kilogram of walnut oil [2].

2.5. Conjugated trienes

The experiment was carried out according to the AOCS Official method Ti la 64 (AOCS, 1993) with minor modifications. Approximately 0.02 g of walnut oil was placed into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The sample was dissolved in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane, brought to volume and mixed thoroughly. Absorbance of the dissolved walnut oil was measured in UV/Vis spectrophotometer HACH-LANGE DR-5000 (Germany) at 270 nm using quartz cuvette 10×10 mm. The CT values were calculated using the following equations:

$$C_{CT} = A_{270} / (\square \times 1) \text{ and } CT_{\text{value}} = [C_{CT} \times (2.5 \times 10^4)] / W$$

where C_{CT} is the CT concentration in mmol/ml (i.e., the molar concentration), A_{270} is the absorbance of the oil solutions at 270 nm, ϵ is the molar absorptivity (i.e., the extinction coefficient) of linoleic acid hydroperoxide ($2.525 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$), l is the path length of the cuvette in cm (1 cm), 2.5×10^4 is a factor that encompasses the volume of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (25 ml) used to dissolve the oil sample as well as a unit conversion (1000 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mmol}$) so that the content of CTs can be expressed in μmol , and W is the weight of the walnut oil in gram. Results were expressed in micromole conjugated trienes per gram of walnut oil [3].

2.6. p-Anisidine Value

The p-anisidine value of walnut oil samples was measured following the methodology described in AOCS Official Method Cd 18-90 (AOCS, 1997). This value was determined by the amount of aldehydes (principally 2-alkenals and 2,4-dienals) in walnut oil samples after reaction in an acetic acid solution of the aldehydic compounds in the walnut oil and the p-anisidine mixture. Absorbance of the samples was measured in UV/Vis spectrophotometer HACH-LANGE DR-5000 (Germany) at 350 nm using quartz cuvette 10×10 mm [4].

2.7. 2-Thiobarbituric acid Value

The 2-thiobarbituric acid was determined according to the AOCS Official Method Cd 19-90 (AOCS, 2009). The method is based on the spectrophotometric quantitation of the pink complex formed after reaction of one molecule of malondialdehyde (MDA), product of oxidation, with two molecules of 2-thiobarbituric acid added to the walnut sample [5].

2.8. TOTOX Value

The total oxidation (TOTOX) value of walnut oil samples was calculated by equation:

$$\text{TOTOX Value} = 2 \cdot \text{PV} + \text{p-AV}$$

2.9. DPPH assay

The radical scavenging activity of walnut oil samples as well as the kinetics of inhibition of free radicals were studied in terms of radical scavenging ability using the stable DPPH[•]

method [9]. Briefly, 0.1 ml of the sample was added to 3.9 ml of 60 μM solution of DPPH[•] in methanol. The reaction was carried in dark and the absorbance was recorded at 515 nm to determine the concentration of remaining DPPH[•]. Methanol as instead of DPPH[•] solution was used as blank solution. The values of $[\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_t$ at each reaction time were calculated according to the standard curve. Concentration range of DPPH was of 0.38-38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ ($A_{515 \text{ nm}} = 0.0293 [\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_t - 0.0072$), where the concentration $[\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_t$ is expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$). The coefficient of linear correlation of the above relation is $R = 0.9999$. The radical scavenging activity was calculated using the equation:

$$\text{RSA} = 100\% \cdot ([\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_0 - [\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_{30}) / [\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_0$$

where $[\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_0$ is the concentration of the DPPH[•] solution (without sample) at $t=0$ min and $[\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_{30}$ is the remained DPPH[•] concentration at $t=30$ min. Lower $[\text{DPPH}^{\bullet}]_t$ in the reaction mixture indicates higher free radical scavenging activity.

2.10. Statistical analysis

Variance analysis of the results was carried out by least square method with application of coefficient Student and Microsoft Office Excel program version 2007. Differences were considered statistically significant if probability was greater than 95% ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). All assays were performed by triplicate at room temperature 20 ± 1 °C. Experimental results are expressed as average \pm SD (standard deviation).

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 illustrates the physicochemical properties of oils treated by different technological methods. The acid value of fresh walnut oil sample (reference sample) was 0.39 mg KOH/g walnut oil. Acid value of dehydrated and thermally treated oil sample was 0.46 mg KOH/g walnut oil, for dehydrated sample was 0.63 mg KOH/g walnut oil and for thermally treated sample was 0.29 mg KOH/g walnut oil. The lowest acid value was in the thermally treated oil. Differences are attributed to the applied methods of technological treatments of the walnut oil.

Table 1. Quality characteristics of cold pressed walnut oil samples (\pm SD*)

№	Quality characteristics	Samples of the walnut oil			
		Reference sample	Dehydrated and thermally treated sample	Dehydrated sample	Thermally treated sample
1.	Acid value, [mg KOH/g oil]	0.39 \pm 0.01	0.46 \pm 0.01	0.63 \pm 0.05	0.29 \pm 0.03
2.	Peroxide value, [mmol/kg oil]	2.49 \pm 0.18	3.33 \pm 0.01	1.66 \pm 0.01	5.73 \pm 0.13
3.	Conjugated trienes, [μ mol/g oil]	3.65 \pm 0.56	5.69 \pm 0.15	10.24 \pm 0.23	6.08 \pm 0.17
4.	p-Anisidine value, [c. u.]	6.10 \pm 0.57	3.26 \pm 0.18	5.96 \pm 0.27	0.88 \pm 0.17
5.	2-Thiobarbituric acid value, [mg/kg oil]	0.07 \pm 0.01	0.11 \pm 0.01	0.11 \pm 0.04	0.10 \pm 0.02
6.	TOTOX value, [c. u.]	11.08 \pm 0.93	9.91 \pm 0.89	9.27 \pm 0.26	12.34 \pm 0.53

*Average concentration of three measurements \pm standard deviation.

Changes in peroxide value were also registered. The peroxide value of reference walnut oil sample was low enough (2.49 mmol/kg walnut oil). All technological treatment conditions significantly affected peroxide value of walnut oil samples. After heat treatment walnut oil sample had higher peroxide value 3.33 mmol/kg walnut oil in accordance with reference sample. But the peroxide value of the oil sample subjected only to dehydration was very low 1.66 mmol/kg walnut oil. The observation is that thermally treatment leads to a rapid lipid oxidation of walnut oil.

As with acid value and peroxide value, technological treatment significantly affected conjugated trienes content. Reference sample of walnut oil had the lowest conjugated trienes content – 3.65 μ mol/g walnut oil.

The health benefits of walnut oil are attributed to its chemical composition. Walnut oil contains approximately 7% saturated, 20% monounsaturated and 73% polyunsaturated fatty acids [16]. These high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids make walnut oil prone to oxidation and may mean that oil has a limited shelf-life, i.e. nutritional and organoleptic changes due to losses of essential fatty acids and formation of volatile compounds from subsequent degradation of hydroperoxides.

Oxidation is a radical chain reaction. After an induction period, it may run very fast under certain circumstances. A chemical attack on the alkyl group is followed by a chain reaction, resulting in a hydroperoxide group (-OOH) in the

chain. The chain reaction is started by *peroxy*-, *alkoxy*- and *alkyl*-radicals:

The fatty acid **RH**, by giving a hydrogen atom, is converted to the alkyl radical of the type **R[•]**. Further, the radical **R[•]** activated by interaction with a molecule of oxygen brings to the formation of peroxy-radicals (**ROO[•]**):

where **R₁[•]** - alkyl-radical;

ROO[•] – peroxy-radical;

ROOH – hydroperoxide radical.

Due to the lower energy of 30-40 kcal, the reaction of oxygen-oxygen debonding **ROOH** radical, some of hydroperoxides turns into alkyl-radicals (**RO[•]**) and hydroxyl (**HO[•]**):

Immediately after the decomposition of hydroperoxides, alkyl-radical (**RO[•]**) is involved in reactions with native fatty acids (**R₁H**) forming a new alkyl-radical (**R₁[•]**):

The chain reaction ends by combination of two radicals. It is well known, that this negative reactions can be stopped by the application of some technological treatments.

Changes in secondary oxidation products accumulation were expressed by p-anisidine and 2-thiobarbituric acid values. To compare the

influence of technological treatment conditions on the oxidation process of walnut oil samples were calculated TOTOX value. Comparison of data leads to the conclusion that as the dehydration treatment was applied to walnut oil physicochemical properties were significant better (figure 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of applied technological treatments on the amount of primary and secondary oxidation products accumulation in walnut oil samples

The knowledge of the kinetics of atom transfer is important because free radicals in the organism are short-lived species, what implies that the impact of a substance as an antioxidant depends on its fast reactivity towards free

radicals. A kinetic assay following the changes in the absorbance of DPPH• reagent was applied to evaluate the level of antiradical activities of the walnut oil samples in the current study (figure 3).

Fig. 3. Reaction kinetics of DPPH with walnut oil samples

It is well known that the absorbance decreases as a result of a colour change from purple to yellow when the DPPH radical is scavenged by antioxidants through donation of hydrogen to form the stable DPPH-H molecule. A more rapid decrease of the absorbance means more potent antiradical activity, expressed in terms of hydrogen donating ability of the compounds. The DPPH scavenging capacity of biologically active compounds is mostly related to their phenol hydroxyl groups.

The dehydrated walnut oil sample had the highest efficiency to scavenge DPPH[•] radicals. However, no significant difference was found in the inhibiting behavior of the thermally treated oil sample. The reference sample had the lowest efficiency to scavenge DPPH[•] radicals. The antioxidant potential of walnut oil samples was expressed as radical scavenging activity (RSC) and was influenced by the applied technological treatment (figure 4).

Fig. 4. Radical scavenging activity DPPH[•] of walnut oil samples

In general, this parameter was in the range of 24.11 – 54.73 %. The highest antioxidant function (minor amounts of DPPH[•]) was found in dehydrated walnut oil and sample treated in combination of dehydration and thermal processing. Antioxidant potential of walnut oil may be attributed to the phenolic compounds and tocopherols present in the oil samples [7].

4. Conclusions

The results of this research showed the influence of dehydration, thermal treatment and their combination on the quality properties (primary and secondary oxidation products) and antioxidant potential cold pressed walnut oil. It was demonstrated that walnut oil possess high quality after dehydration treatment and quality deteriorates after combined dehydration and heat treatment. It is important to underline, that obtained results of this study are intermediate and could help to describe the scheme of walnut oil oxidation

process and also to elaborate improved technology for walnut oil stabilization.

5. Acknowledgements

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6. References

- [1] AOCS, 1999. Official Methods and Recommended Practicles of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Cd 3d-63*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
- [2] AOCS, 2003. Official Methods and Recommended Practicles of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Cd 8-53*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
- [3] AOCS, 1993. Official Methods and Recommended Practicles of the American Oil

- Chemists' Society. *Method Ti la 64*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
- [4] AOCS, 1997. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Cd 18-90*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
- [5] AOCS, 2009. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Cd 19-90*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
- [6] Calvoa P., Lozanoa M., Espinosa-Mansillab A., González-Gómez D. In-vitro evaluation of the availability of α -3 and α -6 fatty acids and tocopherols from microencapsulated walnut oil. *Food Research International*, Volume 48, Issue 1, August 2012, Pages 316–321.
- [7] Gharibzahedi S.M.T., Mousavi S.M., Hamed M., Rezaei K., Khodaiyan F. Evaluation of physicochemical properties and antioxidant activities of Persian walnut oil obtained by several extraction methods. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 45 (2013) 133 - 140.
- [8] Martínez M.L., Penci M.C., Ixtaina V., Ribotta P.D., Maestri D. Effect of natural and synthetic antioxidants on the oxidative stability of walnut oil under different storage conditions. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 51 (2013) 44 – 50.
- [9] Popovici C., Saykova I., Tylkowski B. 2009. Evaluation de l'activité antioxydant des composés phénoliques par la réactivité avec le radical libre DPPH. *Revue électronique internationale pour la science et la technologie*, no 4, pp. 26-39, <http://www.revue-genie-industriel.info>
- [10] Tsamouris, G., Hatziantoniou, S., Demetzos C., (2002). Lipid analysis of greek walnut oil (*Juglans regia* L.). *Z. Naturforsch*, 57c, 51-56.

OVERVIEW OF NATIONAL MOLDAVIAN REGULATIONS ON FOOD LABELING

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Iulia IATCO**

Abstract: *This review of the global regulatory environment around food labeling, including nutrition labeling and health claims aims to provide an overview of existing national regulations and a description of past and future regulatory developments. It compiles, categorizes, and tabulates national regulations. It also reviews regulations on the quantitative declaration of ingredients (information which indicates to consumers the proportion of healthful and less healthful components of the food product).*

Keywords: *food labeling, national regulations, nutrition and health claims.*

1. Food labeling

Consumers gather information about the foods they purchase from a wide variety of sources. Family knowledge, education, the media and advertising all convey messages about different food characteristics; information may also be found on the food product label. From a health standpoint, the information on those labels about the nutritional content and health benefits of food is particularly important. Two types of such information appearing on food products are “nutrition labels” and “health claims”.

By providing information to consumers, nutrition labels and health claims on foods have the potential to contribute to the achievement of public health objectives. Labeling provides consumers with information about the nutritional properties of a food and health claims (statements connecting a food, food component or a nutrient to a state of desired health) provide information to consumers about the nutritional and health advantages of particular foods or nutrients. Health claims are also a marketing technique used by food companies.

In the Republic of Moldova food labeling is carried out in conformity with national regulations in the food industry. According to the national regulation No. 996/2003 “Norms on food labeling and labeling of household chemicals” food labeling means labeling or labeling of identification elements on foods or its

packing, which accompanies foods represented for realization.

According to another national regulation namely the Parliament Law of the Republic of Moldova nr. 78 as of 18.03.2004 “On foodstuffs”, *labeling* (marking) is any words, trademarks, registered trademarks, signs, elements drawn or written, stamped, embossed or printed on, or attached to a container with foodstuffs and positioned on any packaging, accompanying document, notice, label, band or flange, which is accompanying or is referring to such foodstuff.

The label must be placed so as not to separate from a packing and information contained on it can not be erased. Information on food labels must be placed in a visible place so that consumers could read and understand it during normal conditions of use and purchase. It is prohibited to extend food’s shelf life, including by label’s substitution or repacking. It is not allowed to use such inscriptions whereby foods are assigned or consumer is suggested prophylactic or healing properties for some human diseases during labeling. There are some exception cases when these properties have been proved or confirmed by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Moldova and also which mislead consumers about food properties by indication other properties, origin, identity, features, composition, suitability, method of production

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and manufacturer. The distribution of wrong labeling foods by any means is prohibited.

2. General regulations

Food labeling mustn't mislead consumers and must provide them with necessary, sufficient, reliable and easily amenable comparison

information. It would allow to choose a product that corresponds to consumers' claims and their financial possibilities and also to receive the information about possible risks to which consumers may be exposed. General national regulations on food labeling in the Republic of Moldova are given in table 1.

Table 1. General national regulations on food labeling

№	Number and title of regulation	Short review of regulation
1.	Regulation No. 996/2003. <i>Norms on food labeling and labeling of household chemicals.</i>	Norms on food labeling are mandatory sanitary and technical regulations and apply to all foods available on the market of the Republic of Moldova. These norms regulate the way of food labeling on the market for the final consumer and catering enterprises. The requirements of these rules also apply to certain aspects of food products' presentation and advertising.
2.	Regulation No. 78/2004. <i>The law on food products.</i>	This law establishes a regulatory framework in the field of foods' production, processing and distribution. It also regulates basic trade's conditions of these foods, including its security with the purpose of human's health protection, protection of consumer interests concerning foods, ensuring conscientious practices in the food trade. This law applies to all foods intended for placement on the domestic market.
3.	Regulation No. 196/2011. <i>Sanitary regulation on nutritional content and health claims on foods</i>	This regulation establishes the rules concerning nutrition labeling and health claims on foods with the purpose of ensuring the effective functioning of the domestic market and a high level of consumer protection.
4.	Regulation No. 01-04/2004. <i>Sanitary norms on nutrition labeling, food labeling for special dietary use, food labeling genetically modified or food labeling that has been obtained from genetically modified organisms.</i>	These rules regulate requirements and methods of nutrition labeling on foods; genetically modified foods; foods for special dietary use; mineral waters; food additives; foods enriched with missing nutrients.
5.	Regulation No. 538/2009. <i>Sanitary regulation on food additives.</i>	This regulation establishes the standards for food additives used in foods with the purpose of ensuring a high level of public's health protection and a high level of consumer protection.
6.	Regulation No. 105/2003. <i>The law on consumer rights protection.</i>	This law establishes a regulatory framework for people's state protection who acts as consumers.

3. Food label requirements

According to the resolution of the Government of the Republic of Moldova No. 996/2003 labeling provides customers with necessary, sufficient, easily verifiable and comparable information. It allows him to choose the food product that corresponds to his

requirements from the standpoint of his needs and financial capabilities, as well as learn the possible risks to which he may be exposed by purchasing foods. Mandatory food label requirements are given in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Mandatory food label requirements in accordance with national food legislation

All marks made during labeling, should be clear, legible, indelible and easily understandable and placed in a visible place for consumers during normal conditions of use and purchase. Marks on the label mustn't be covered or separated by other instructions, inscriptions or drawings.

The information contained on the label mustn't mislead the consumer. Labeling and the methods by which it is carried out, mustn't assign foods with such properties as prevention, healing or curing diseases or make reference to such properties. This prohibition does not apply to natural mineral waters, as well as any foods for special dietary use, permitted for this purpose by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Moldova.

Some foods require additional mandatory labeling. Such products include: milk, concentrated or powdered milk, fermented milk products, cheese, butter, margarine, meat and meat products, fish and fish products, eggs and egg products, vegetables and fruits, natural fruit and vegetable juices, cool drinks, canned fruits, chocolate and chocolate products, coffee, salt, spices, wine, alcohol products, vinegar, sugar.

Food labeling that has been treated with ionizing radiation is carried out with an indication on the label "Treated with ionizing radiation". Food labeling that has been obtained from genetically modified organisms is carried out with an indication on the label "Genetically modified food" or "The product obtained from genetically modified organisms". Food labels for special dietary use and food additives must

contain additional relevant information about their properties and characteristics. Food labels for special dietary use for babies and small children mustn't contain any information which would prevent or would not be favorable for breastfeeding. Food additives' labels mustn't be used for assign them prophylactic and healing properties and also it is not allowed to make any reference to such properties.

4. Nutrition and Health claims

The use of indications about nutritional content and health claims on foods is carried out in conformity with national regulation No. 196/2011 " Sanitary regulation on nutritional content and health claims on foods " and regulation No. 01-04/2004 "Sanitary norms on nutrition labeling, food labeling for special dietary use, food labeling genetically modified or food labeling that has been obtained from genetically modified organisms".

Nutrition labeling on foods is voluntary but it may be required in case of a food product appears on the label during its presentation or advertising to the declaration about nutritional content.

It is allowed to indicate the declarations about the nutritional content which relate to the energy value; nutritional substances such as proteins, carbohydrates, fats, fiber, sodium; vitamins and mineral salts, when they are present in significant amounts (more than 15 % of recommended daily allowance-RDA). Recommended daily allowance (RDA) for vitamins and minerals are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Recommended daily allowance (RDA) for vitamins and minerals

No	Nutrient	Unit	RDA	No	Nutrient	Unit	RDA
1	<i>Vitamin A</i>	µg	800	10	<i>Biotin</i>	mg	0.15
2	<i>Vitamin D</i>	µg	5	11	<i>Vitamin PP</i>	mg	18
3	<i>Vitamin E</i>	mg	10	12	<i>Vitamin C</i>	mg	60
4	<i>Vitamin B₁</i>	mg	1.4	13	<i>Calcium</i>	mg	800
5	<i>Vitamin B₂</i>	mg	1.6	14	<i>Phosphorus</i>	mg	800
6	<i>Vitamin B₆</i>	mg	2	15	<i>Magnesium</i>	mg	300
7	<i>Vitamin B₁₂</i>	µg	1	16	<i>Zink</i>	mg	15
8	<i>Folic acid</i>	µg	200	17	<i>Iron</i>	mg	14
9	<i>Pantothenic acid</i>	mg	6	18	<i>Iodine</i>	µg	150

All information about nutritional content is grouped into one or two groups during labeling.

The first group includes the energy value, amount of proteins, fats and carbohydrates. The second

group includes the energy value, amount of proteins, carbohydrates, sugars, fats, saturated fatty acids, dietary fibers and sodium. Nutrition labeling may also include amounts of one or more of the following substances: starch, polyols, monounsaturated fatty acids, polyunsaturated fatty acids, cholesterol and any of vitamin or mineral elements contained in significant amounts in foods.

Along with nutritional content there may be indicated some health claims which mean any indication whereby declares, supposes or from which follows the fact of a relationship category of food, food product or one of its components with health. Conditions for indications of health claims are given in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Conditions for indications of health claims

It is allowed to indicate health claims which describe or refer to influence of a nutrient or other substance on the growth, development and organism's functions, as well as psychological and behavioral functions.

5. Conclusions

Food labeling can be an effective means of helping consumers to make healthful food choices, although existing evidence concerning the effect of health claims on diet and public health is insufficient. Regulations can play a crucial role in enhancing the potential for nutrition labeling and health claims to promote

health. This review shows that regulations have many the same approaches to select from when constructing a regulatory framework. To maximise the potential of nutrition labels and health claims to improve public health, regulations should be developed with long-term dietary improvements across populations as their underlying goal.

The effectiveness of nutrition labeling and health claims in improving national dietary patterns relies largely on a motivated and educated public to make healthful choices. This approach has limitations. If there is to be significant change, action on nutrition labels and health claims need to be part of an integrated

approach that tackles the increasing rates of diet-related non-communicable diseases at a population level, as well as targeting individuals.

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7. References

- [1] Hotărîre de Guvern. (2003). *Norme privind etichetarea produselor alimentare și norme privind etichetarea produselor chimice de menaj*. HG nr. 996 din 20.08.2003. Monitorul Oficial al RM, 2003, nr. 189-190, art. 1046. Modificat HG 296 din 26.04.11, Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova 74-77/06.05.11, art. 343, HG 1208 din 27.10.08, Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova 198-200/07.11.08 art. 1226; în vigoare: 07.11.09, <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=305926>
- [2] Lege de Parlament. (2004). *Privind produsele alimentare*. LP nr. 78 din 18.03.2004. Monitorul Oficial al RM, 2004, nr. 83-83, art. 431. Modificat LP nr. 318 din 27.12.12, Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova 49-55/08.03.13 art. 152, LP nr. 93 din 26.04.12, MO149-154/20.07.12 art. 482; în vigoare: 20.09.12. <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=313238>
- [3] Hotărîre de Guvern. (2011). *Regulamentul sanitar privind mențiunile nutriționale și de sănătate înscrise pe produsele alimentare*. HG nr. 196 din 25.03.2011. Monitorul Oficial al RM, 2011, nr. 46-52, art. 229; în vigoare: 01.07.2011. <http://lex.justice.md/viewdoc.php?action=view&view=doc&id=337965&lang=1>
- [4] Hotărîre Ministerul Sănătății. (2004). *Norme sanitare privind etichetarea nutrițională, etichetarea produselor alimentare cu destinație dietetică specială, etichetarea produselor genetic modificate sau provenite din organisme genetic modificate*. HMS nr. 01_04 din 31.05.2004. Monitorul Oficial al RM, 2004, nr. 138, art. 281; în vigoare: 13.08.2004. <http://lex.justice.md/viewdoc.php?action=view&view=doc&id=306412&lang=1>
- [5] Hotărîre de Guvern. (2009). *Regulamentul sanitar privind suplimentele alimentare*. HG nr. 538 din 02.09.2009. Monitorul Oficial al RM, 2009, nr. 138-139, art. 603. <http://lex.justice.md/viewdoc.php?action=view&view=doc&id=332200&lang=1>
- [6] Lege de Parlament. (2003). *Privind protecția consumatorilor*. LP nr. 105 din 13.03.2003. Monitorul Oficial al RM, 2003, nr. 126-131, art. 507; în vigoare: 28.10.2003. http://lex.justice.md/document_rom.php?id=546986A0:88685EC5
- [7] Cristina Popovici, Nina Mija, Adriana Birca, Iulia Iatco. *Compliance with labeling legislation of the republic of moldova in the field of confectionery products*. Acta Universitatis Cibiniensis. Series E: Food Technology. Volume 17, Issue 2, December 2013, p. 61–67.

FOOD LABELS – AN OPPORTUNITY FOR INFORMED CHOICE OF FOOD

M. PETROVA*, I. KOSTOVA, N. IVANOVA, I. IVANOVA, S. DAMYANOVA

Abstract: A survey of consumers' interest in the information from food labels in Bulgaria is done. It has been found that the labels have a decisive role in the selection of food products which puts increasing demands on their appearance and the information given in them.

Key words: food labels, a survey, food products, consumers.

Introduction

In recent years, more and more people appreciate food as a source of valuable and useful health substances. People realize the role of food for maintaining good health [3, 4, 6]. Consumers get the first information on food label.

Do Bulgarian consumers have habits of informed choice when they buy food and drinks? Does this count that beautiful, colorful and effective label sells goods in spite of the information on it. In order to achieve better realization of food products on the market, producers put awards, medals, badges and trademarks on the labels which can distract attention from the method of preparation, ingredients, additives, expiration date and the producer of the offered product [5-10].

The labeling is based on the Labeling Directive from 2000. By the end of 2014 is expected to be replaced by the Regulation for providing food information to consumers FIC (Food Information for Consumers) [1, 2].

The purpose of this study is to track consumers' interest in the information from food labels in Bulgaria and how it affects food selection. This study is a part of work team from the Ruse University- Branch Razgrad, project NUTRILAB (NUTritional LABELing Study in Black Sea Region Countries), Project number: 318946 - FP7-PEOPLE - 2012 – IRSES.

Materials and methods

298 Bulgarian consumers were surveyed in 2013 including 70,42% women and 29,58% men. The survey was filled out electronically and on paper. Educational and social status of the participants are given in Table 1.

Table 1 *Social and educational status of the participants in percentages*

Social status	
Worker	15,92%
Employee	15,51%
Contractor; Businessman	4,08%
University student	56,73%
Pensioner	2,04%
Unemployed	3,27%
Other	2,45%
Educational status	
Secondary education	75,12%
University education	22,54%
Primary education	2,35%

For creating electronic surveys, proceeding the collected data and displaying results is used MS Excel program which has a rich set of build- in statistical and mathematical functions.

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Results and discussions

from food labels, 51% have partial trust and 15% do not trust.

It is evident from Figure 1 that only 9% of respondents trust completely the information

Fig. 1 Do you trust the information on food labels

Fig. 2 Do you find the information on food labels difficult

Fig. 3 Education and understanding

66% from the survey participants have some difficulties with information, 49% of them sometimes have any difficulties. 34 % from respondents do not have any difficulties (fig 2).

About 78% of respondents educational status does not matter to understand the information on labels (fig. 3).

When reading food labels respondents have the greatest difficulties with small print (92%); using

many numbers and symbols with illegible information (73%) (fig. 4).
uncomprehensible meaning (90 %) or pale and

Fig. 4 Difficulties have you ever met when reading food labels

From the results in Figure 5 it is seen to what extent information on food labels is understandable for consumers. 30% of respondents think that the most unclear information is about the additives in the product which are marked with the letter E and a number that specifies the type of additive. The symbols, the abbreviations and components of the product are also unclear to the general consumer.

How the specific data on labels provide clear information to consumers about the composition of foodstuffs, it can be seen from the results in Figure 6.

From the eight shown names of components it turned out that not all are well-known to the respondents. They recognize especially the components which enter into the composition of commonly consumed foods such as lecithin,

Fig. 5 Which information is unclear when reading labels

fructose syrup, hydrogenated fats, sodium glutamate, etc.

Sometimes consumers ignore all information given on food labels for various reasons: they just hurry and do not have enough time, they are not a habit, think that reading labels is a waste of time, consumers are confident of what they buy and

think that it is not necessary to read labels, etc. The results relating to the degree of awareness of consumers are presented in Figure 7. It can be seen that more than half of the respondents read selectively the information on labels. More than a third read all product information on labels.

Fig. 6 Which names of food labels are known

Fig. 7 Do you read everything on food labels

One of the most discussed issues related to labeling of foods and drinks is about compulsory information that should be available to consumers. To the point what should be the compulsory information on food labels the respondents placed first the need for information about dangerous components which carry a

health risk and also information about availability of genetically modified objects (fig.8).

Is it true that a good label is an important factor in selecting food? Figure 9 shows that half of respondents make their choice of food according to the label.

Fig. 8 What information should be on food labels according you

Fig. 9 Does the labels influence on your choice

Producers looking for attractive ways to attract attention to their products they often overburden labels with attractive and effective pictures, graphical objects and facts which do not give a correct notion and even distort the information. Is it necessary to change food labels?

The results from Figure 10 show that the labels should be improved according a third of the respondents, 28,08% think that labels should be simplified and 16,44% of the respondents prefer a new vision.

In this context, the following issues about specifying the preferred changes in labels that support and make convenient shopping.

According to the Table 2 preferred changes in labels are directed to protecting consumers and information about the specific use of products. The other suggestions concern using special symbols and illustrations and colors to make easier the visual way of informing consumers.

Fig. 10 *Is it necessary to change food labels*

Table 2 *Suggested changes to the labels*

Index	% of respondents
Using different colors	17,07%
Special symbols and illustrations	20,43%
Instructions for whom the products are dangerous	33,54%
Indicating for whom the products are intended	25,00%
Without any changes	3,96%

Fig.11 *Does food influence on your health*

The extent to which food affects the health of consumers, it can be seen in Figure 11.

According 47% of respondents food influences greatly on human health and only 7% disagree.

In this connection it is important to study and analyze the process of shopping, what motivates

consumers to buy a certain type of food and not to buy other. Therefore the next issue concerns the way of selecting food.

According to the results from Figure 12 the most important factor when shopping is the information on labels of food and drinks.

Therefore, the labels have a decisive role in selecting food products which puts increasing requirements to their appearance and the information in them.

Fig. 12 How do you select food in the shops

Conclusion

The survey done among Bulgarian consumers in 2013 shows that labels should provide clear, understandable and complete product information.

Desire for quality and healthy lifestyle requires improving awareness and culture of shopping.

References

1. COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 231/2012 of 9 March 2012
2. COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 380/2012 of 3 May 2012
3. Grunert, K., Wills, J., Fernández-Celemiín, L.: Nutrition knowledge, and use and understanding of nutrition information on food labels among consumers in the UK, *Appetite*, 55, 2010, p. 177–189.
4. Hieke, S., Taylor, C. R.: A Critical Review of the Literature on Nutrition Labeling,” *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 46, (1), 2012, p. 120–56.
5. Mdrjorie, R. F., Rachel Connors, M. S.: Point-of-Purchase Nutrition Information Influences Food-Purchasing Behaviors of CollegeStudents: A Pilot Study, *Journal of the AMERICAN DIETETIC ASSOCIATION*, 111, (5), 2011, p. 42-46.
6. Newman, C. L., Howlett, E., Burton, S.: Shopper Response to Front - of - Package Nutrition Labeling Programs: Potential Consume rand Retail Store Benefits, *Journal of Retailing*, 90, (1), 2014, p. 13–26.
7. Olavarrieta, S., Hidalgo, P., Manzur, E., Farías, P.: Determinants of in-store price knowledge for packaged products: An empirical study in a Chilean hypermarket, *Journal of Business Research*, 65, 2012, p. 1759–1766.
8. Sacks, G., Rayner, M., Swinburn, B.: Impact of front-of-pack ‘traffic light’ nutrition labelling on consumer food purchases in the UK, *Health Promotion International*, 4, 2009, p. 344–352.
9. Vyth, E. L., Steenhuis, I. H. M., Mallant, S. F., Mol, Z. I.: A front-of-pack nutrition logo: a quantitative and qualitative process evaluation in the Netherlands, *Journal of Health Communication*, 14, 2009, p. 631–645.
10. Wills, J. M., Grunert, K. G., Fernández Celemín, L., Storcksdieck genannt Bonsmann, S.: European consumers and nutrition labelling, *Food Engineering and Ingredients Magazine*, 34 (3), 2009, p. 11–13.

RESEARCH OF PROCESS OF OUTPUT OF FOAMED MIXTURES MADE OF RAW FISH

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Abstract: *The article provides the results of dependencies of duration of the process of foaming and drying of raw fish on temperatures, pressure of the process and density of initial raw material stuffing were determined, as well as experimental relations of the temperature on the lateral surface of a floating feed granule for trout during glazing process and the speed of the movement of granules in the glazing agent were stated. Rational parameters of the process of foaming, drying and glazing in processing of raw fish into foamed mixtures have been proposed.*

Key words: *fish raw materials, foaming and drying, glazing, experimental research, rational parameters.*

Fish and fish products play an important role in the human diet. Fish flesh is marked by high nutritive value. The need of population in food protein is satisfied on the account of fish and fish products for 20-30% [1]. Nowadays the average consumption of fish products in Ukraine does not exceed 12 kg per capita annually with the physiologically substantiated annual norm of consumption of fish products as 20.1 kg per 1 resident [2]. The current situation may be improved on the account of expansion of the range of the output of fish products by food enterprises, development of new useful food stuffs made of aquatic organisms having demand within the population.

Apart from food goals, about 28 million tons of fish are used annually for feeding purposes including feeds for fish farming [3]. In order to provide intensive growth of aquaculture it is necessary to apply correctly balanced feeds. It makes possible to increase the efficiency of aquatic farms significantly. One of the basic problems in output of floating feeds for fish farming is difficulty in balancing of these feeds in respect of essential components [4].

The solution of the stated above problems is possible when processing raw fish material into foamed mixtures, and the quality of the obtained products (including the content of vitamins) may be increased on the account of reduction in temperature during thermal processing down to 55°C.

At present the foamed fish products are produced by means of extrusion, intensive thermal processing at temperature more than 120°C taking place [5]. This method was adopted as a basis for research, reduction of thermal processing temperature having been provided on account of operational pressure.

A new method of processing required designing of apparatuses for processes and undertaking experimental research in order to determine rational parameters of the process.

Proceeding from the stated above, the aim of the paper has been determined: development and research of the process of output of foamed mixtures made of raw fish materials at temperature not more than 55°C and estimation of the rational parameters for this process.

In order to achieve the aim outlined, the following tasks have been solved: analytical overview concerning the problem of research, development of the pilot equipment, planning of the experiment, analysis of disperse composition of the foamed products, estimation of the rational parameters of the process, preparation and obtaining legal documents for the proposed equipment and technique. As final products of raw fish processing into foamed mixture the following products are reviewed:

- Food product – Snack «Khrustik rybnyi (Fish crunch)» - minced meat of round goby as an initial raw fish.

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– Feed product – floating feed for rainbow trout fingerlings. The recipe of the feed was calculated by means of the option «Finding solution» of the software Microsoft Office Excel 2010. Data about food value of the raw fish and its chemical composition were used [6, 7]. Table 1 gives results concerning composition of the feed mixture; Table 2 provides data about

the requirements for chemical composition of feeds and how to apply these requirements for selected recipes.

In order to carry out the preliminary studies the laboratory installation was used (Patent of Ukraine for useful model №55632), the photo and principal scheme of which are given at Figure 1.

Table 1 – Estimated data about composition of feed mixtures for trout

Component	Content, %
Black Sea sprat	68.0
Soya oilseed meal	2.0
Canola oilseed meal	2.0
Sodium chloride	1.5
Limestone flour	2.0

Table 2 – Requirements for granulated feeds for trout and parameters for finished feed

Parameters	Requirements, %	Factual content, %
Protein	40.00-50.00	41.38
Fats	5.00-13.00	12.45
Fibre	2.00-5.00	3.95
Mineral salts	10.00-15.00	10.30
Humidity	Up to 15.00	12.0

Fig. 1 – The photo and principal scheme of the laboratory installation
 1 – operational chamber; 2 – water bath; 3 – auxiliary chamber;
 4 – vacuum pump; 5 – vacuum gauge; 6 – temperature sensor

The principle of the installation operation is as follows: vacuum was created by means of the vacuum pump 4 via the three-way cock in the auxiliary chamber 3. The specimens of products under research were placed in the operational chamber 1. By means of the water bath 2 the operational chamber was heated. After achieving the desired temperature, the operational chamber

was connected with the auxiliary one; a sharp decrease in pressure took place – a liquid in the specimens under review boiled.

In the course of the preliminary experimental research the positive results were obtained, this making possible to propose a principally new method of raw fish processing into foamed mix-

tures at temperature 55°C (Patent of Ukraine for useful model №65473).

The quality of foaming for products obtained was checked by organoleptic properties for

snacks and by visual estimation of the time taken by feed granules to be found on the water surface (Table 3).

Table 3 – Results of research in duration of occurrence of foamed fish raw materials on water surface

Parameter	Granules obtained by		
	Drying at atmospheric pressure, min.	Drying at pressure 10 kPa, min.	Foaming and drying at pressure 10 kPa, min.
Swelling of granules	5.5	38.5	128.0
Loss of shape by granules	7.0	42.5	131.0
Suspended state of granules in water	12.0	60.0	168.5
Complete destruction of granules	15.5	69.0	182.0

The different time of granules occurrence on the water surface is explained by the availability of pores formed during foaming. This is proved while comparing cross-sections of these granules. The cross-sections were studied by means of a digital microscope (Bresser LCD Micro) with 4-fold magnification (Figure 2). On photos of cross-sections of granules for drying at the at-

mospheric pressure (Figure 2a), drying of granules under vacuum (Figure 2b), foaming and drying of granules under vacuum (Figure 2c) it is seen that the foamed product has much more pores filled with air, i.e. obviously we can see the difference of the foamed product from the dried one. The material had similar structure.

Fig. 2 – Cross-section of granules obtained by various ways of production

The further research required modernization of the apparatuses for the process. Modernization of the laboratory installation made possible to increase efficiency of the research, join in one operational chamber the processes of foaming and drying as well as to control loss of liquid without withdrawal of the product out of the installation.

The photo and the principal scheme of the modernized installation (Patent of Ukraine for

useful model №76438) are given on Figure 3. The scheme consists of the operational chamber 1, water bath 2, auxiliary chamber 3, vacuum pump 4, thermoscales 5, sensor of which 6 is placed on the control panel. Besides, the control panel incorporates switch 7, control lamp 8, thermostatic regulator 9, and the screen with readings of temperature in the operational chamber 10. As well the installation consists of connecting, stopping and measuring devices.

Fig. 3 – Photo and principal scheme of the pilot installation for foaming raw fish materials
 1 – operational chamber; 2 – water bath; 3 – auxiliary chamber;
 4 – vacuum pump; 5 – thermoscales; 6 – screen of thermoscales; 7 – switch; 8 – control lamp;
 9 – thermostatic regulator; 10 – screen for readings of temperature in the operational chamber

In order to estimate the effect of modes on the processes of foaming and drying the statistical method of the experiment planning was applied, as well as full factorial experiment of 2^3 type was undertaken. The input parameters were considered to be the following ones: temperature (t , °C) and pressure (P , kPa) in the operational chamber and the density of stuffing of the initial raw material into the perforated moulds (ρ ,

kg/m^3). The output parameter was adopted to be the duration of the process (τ , min.), which affected the efficiency and energy consumption.

In order to preserve thermally labile vitamins and to provide the required foaming and firmness of the product on the basis of the preliminary experimental research the intervals in variability of the input parameters [8] were estimated the results of which are given in Table 4.

Table 4 – Variable parameters of the process of foaming and drying of raw fish

Factors	The basic level	Unit of variability	The upper level	The lower level
P, kPa	12.5	2.5	15.0	10.0
t, °C	50.0	5.0	55.0	45.0
ρ , kg/m ³ (snacks)	1160.0	60.0	1220.0	1100.0
ρ , kg/m ³ (feedstuff)	1155.0	105.0	1260.0	1050.0

Results of the full factorial experiment were verified for trustworthiness applying coefficients by Student, Fisher and Cochren.

The dependence of the foaming and drying process duration on the temperature and pressure in the operational chamber, as well as on density of stuffing of the initial raw material was estimated:

- for snacks made of round goby minced meat:
 $\tau = 1.564 \cdot P - 2.068 \cdot t + 0.2135 \cdot \rho - 12.520$ (1)

- for floating feeds for trout:

$$\tau = 24.140 + 1.472 \cdot P - 1.550 \cdot t + 0.102 \cdot \rho$$
 (2)

In order to calculate the minimum values for equations (1) and (2) with specified limits for variable factors the methods of convex optimization (simplex methods) were applied using the function «Finding solutions» of the table editor Microsoft Office Excel 2010. The values to be found for variable parameters were given in Table 5.

Table 5 – Results for determination of rational parameters for the foaming and drying processes

Type of the product	P, kPa	t, °C	ρ, kg/m ³
Snacks	10	55	1100
Feeds	10	55	1050

One of the stages in the process of output of floating feed for trout according to the proposed technological scheme [9] is glazing. The studies of this stage were aimed at estimation of the rational parameters for the glazing process.

In order to reduce power consumption and to increase the efficiency the scheme of glazing under which granules with temperature 50° moved in the glazing agent (gelatin solution) with temperature 18-20°C was adopted. Non-stationary heat exchange took place: a granule chilled, the glazing agent adjacent to it got warm. At reaching the temperature 32°C (temperature of melting/crystallization of food gelatin P11) a granule covered with a layer of the glazing agent on the account of adhesive properties. A granule was

taken away from the gelatin solution into the ambient environment where the further chilling of the granule with gelatin crystallizing took place.

In order to determine the effect of the modes on the glazing process the statistical method of the experiment planning was applied and the full factorial experiment of 32 type was carried out. The variable factors were adopted be speeds of moving granules in the glazing agent (V, m/sec) and duration of the glazing process (τ, sec.). The output parameter was adopted to be temperature on the lateral side of a granule of floating feed for trout (t, °C). Basing on the data of the preliminary studies [10], variable parameters of the glazing process were estimated, they being given in Table 6.

Table 6 – The variable parameters for the process of glazing the raw fish material

Factors	The basic level	Unit of variability	The upper level	The lower level
V, m/sec	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.01
τ, sec.	30.00	20.00	50.00	10.00

The results of full factorial experiment were verified for trustworthiness by applying coefficients by Student, Fisher and Cochren. The dependence of the temperature on the lateral side of granule under the process on the speed of granule movement and duration of the process:

$$t=52.89+0.006\cdot\tau^2-141\cdot V-0.67\cdot\tau \quad (3)$$

The process of glazing should take place until chilling of the lateral surface of a granule down to the temperature of melting/crystallizing of the glazing agent (t=32°C).

In order to calculate the minimum value τ for equation (3) and t=32°C, under which the maximum efficiency and minimum power consumption are provided, with specified limits of the variable factor V methods of convex optimization (simplex methods) were applied using the function «Finding solutions» of the table editor Microsoft Office Excel 2010. The value to be found for the speed of movement was equal to V = 0.05 m/sec. Thus, the duration of the glazing process at the speed of granules movement V = 0,05 m/sec and chilling of the lateral surface of the granule down to temperature 32°C made up 27.4 sec. As a result of studies there has been

developed a new method for processing of raw fish into foamed mixtures at the temperature of thermal processing 55°C. In order to implement this provision there has been designed the installation integrating the operational and auxiliary chambers, vacuum pump, water bath, thermoscales, stopping and controlling devices. The examination of the product obtained by various ways with 4fold magnification under the microscope revealed that the foamed product had much more pores filled with air as compared with dried product. In the experimental way rational parameters for the processes of foaming and drying were determined which provided the maximum efficiency with minimum power consumption. These parameters were equal to: for snacks – pressure in the operational chamber P=10 kPa, temperature in the operational chamber t=55°C, the density for stuffing snacks ρ=1100 kg/m³; for floating feeds – pressure in the operational chamber P=10 kPa, temperature in the operational chamber t=55°C, density of stuffing for granules ρ=1050 kg/m³. Glazing as a stage of the process of output should be carried out Г л а з и р о ф а н и е 27.4 seconds with the speed of movement for granules through the glazing agent 0.05 m/sec.

The further research will be aimed at development of the design of the apparatus of continuous action for the processes of foaming and

drying raw fish and designing the workshop for processing raw fish into foamed mixtures in order to implement at the fish processing enterprises.

References

1. Grinjevskii M.V. Intensifikatsiya vyrobnytstva produkttsii akvakultury i vnutrishnih vodoimakh Ukrainy [text] / M.V.Grinjevskii. – K. : Svit, 2000. – 192 s.; Intensification of the output of aquaculture products in the inner water basins in Ukraine
2. Rybnaia otrasli Ukrainy: sostoianie i perspektivy. [elektronnyi resurs] / Vseucrainskiy Business-To-Business internet rynek produktov pitania. – <http://edab2b.com/opinions/rybnaya-otrasl-ukrainy/> - 31.01.2013 r.; Fisheries of Ukraine: state and prospects [electronic resource] All-Ukrainian Business-To-Business internet-market of foodstuffs
3. Dovbish O.E. Zarubejnyi opyt morskoi akvakultury i ee prioritetye zadachi v Ukraine [text] / O.E.Dovbysh, E.P. Gubanov, V.N. // Rybne gosudarstvo Ukrainy. – 2010. - №2(67) – s.2-9; Foreign experience in development of marine aquaculture and its priority tasks in Ukraine // Fisheries of Ukraine, – 2010. - №2(67) – s.2-9
4. Sukmanov V.O. Obgruntovanny neobhidnosti pererobki biologichno-aktivnykh dobavok ta ii vikorystannia u iakosti plavaiuchih kormov dlia rybnitstva [text] / V.O.Sukmanov O.A.Iashonkov // Obladnannya ta tehnologii harchovyh vyrobnytstv- 2011, Vyp 26, s. 474-479, Substantiation of the necessity of processing of raw fish materials adding thermally labile biologically active supplements and its usage as a floating feed for fish farming Equipment and technologies for food production, - Issue 26, pp.474-479
5. Osovskii D.I. Nekotorye problem proizvodstva plavaiushchego rybnogo korma s biologicheskoy aktivnymy dobavkamy. [text] / D.I. Osovskii, A.A.Iashonkov // Rybnoe hoziaystvo Ukrainy. – Kerch, KGMTU, 2009.- №1 (60). – C.33-34; Some problems in output of floating feeds for fish (with biologically active supplements) // Fisheries of Ukraine – Kerch: KGMTU
6. Klassifikatsia kormov, vidy, himicheskii sostav, pitatelnosti/ Selskohoziaistvennyi i fermerskii business [elektronnyi resurs] – <http://www.landwirt.ru/2009-12-12-16-06-35/229-2009-03-10-17-45-10> - 09.03.2011 r.; Classification of feeds, types, chemical composition, nutritive value / Agricultural and farming business [electronic resource]
7. Panin I.G. Povyshenie effektivnosti proizvodstva jivotnovodcheskoy produkttsii s ispolzovaniem program optimizatsii retseptov kombikormov // I.G.Panin, V.V.Grechishnikov / Vettorg Portal [elektronnyi resurs] – <http://www.vettorg.net/magazines/3/2004/94/577/> - 09.03.2011 r.; Increase in efficiency of production of farming products applying the programs for optimization of feed recipes
8. Sukmanov V.A. K voprosu eksperimentalnih issledovaniy vspenivaemosti rybnogo syria [text] / V.A. Sukmanov, A.A.Iashonkov // Rybnoe hoziaystvo Ukrainy. – Kerch, KGMTU, 2011. – № 6 (77). – C. 40-43.; To the problem of experimental studies of foaming of raw fish.
9. Sukmanov V.O.. Perobka rybnoy syroviny na spinney sumishi ta eksperimentalne obladnannya dlia doslidjennia tsiogo protsessu / V.O.Sukmanov, O.A.Iashonkov// Obladnannya ta tehnologii harchovyh vyrobnytstv. – 2011. – Vyp. 27. – C. 168-173; Processing of raw fish into foamed mixtures and experimental equipment to investigate this process.
10. Sukmanov V.O. Modeliuvannya nestatsionarnogo teploobmenu pri glazuruvanni granul spinenyh sumishei / V.O.Sukmanov, O.A.Iashonkov // Obladnannya ta tehnologii harchovyh vyrobnytstv.- 2011.- t. 2, vyp. 29, s. 157-164. Modeling of non-stationary heat exchange at glazing of granules of foamed mixtures.

METAL LEVELS IN WINE BETWEEN TOXICITY AND BENEFICIAL EFFECTS ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Motto: "Wine is sunlight, held together by water." (Galileo Galilei)

Abstract: *This paper presents a mini review of the existing literature data concerning sources of metals in wine, role of metals in wine quality and their concentration in wine, analytical methods used for their quantitative determination and their impact on human health. The main focus is set on manganese, iron, copper, zinc, lead, cadmium and chromium since these elements affect most often wine quality and human health.*

Keywords: *metals, wine quality, health.*

I. Introduction

Wine occupies an important place in many cultures and it is often associated with religious purposes. Nowadays, wine is a beverage commonly consumed worldwide being an important source of minerals for humans. Owing to their beneficial influence on human health, wines were investigated intensively over last decade. Consumed in small amounts may present health benefits that has been highlighted in many scientific papers [1, 2]. For example, there are studies which emphasizes that polyphenols (resveratrol) found in red wines present significant antioxidant protection [3]. Other studies present the health-protective properties of wines attributed to their capacity to eliminate free radicals [4].

Wines contain some metallic species that are essential to human body and consumption of wine in moderate quantities may cover the physiological needs. On the other hand, the presence of some metals such as lead, cadmium, nickel, chromium may create toxicological issues [5].

Composition of wine varies depending on soil characteristics (metals and nutritive species contents, physical properties), phytosanitary treatments (Bordeaux mixture, zinc thiocarbamates), oenological practices or fraudulent addition of forbidden chemicals. Nevertheless, there are some components present in all cases: water, alcohol, organic acids, sugars, polyphenols, anthocianins, volatile acids,

vitamins [6]. Wines contain different metallic ions, some of them being involved in winemaking processes. Potassium concentrations in wines are between 0.5-2 g/L, red wines being richer than white ones [7]. Also, potassium it is added as metabisulphite or carbonate during wine making processes [6]. Sodium is encountered in small concentrations that range between 10 up to 40 mg/L [7], but it also may be added illicitly as chloride [6]. Wine contains magnesium in higher concentrations (60-150 mg/L) than calcium. In red wines, calcium levels are slightly lower than those found in white wines [7]. Even if the metals concentration is a very small percentage of wine composition, it plays an important role in wine making process and wine quality. The analytical assessment of metals in wines it is used often to characterize the wines by their authenticity, geographic origin [8], to certify its quality concerning the maximum allowable limits according to different regulations and to detect falsifications of wines. Mineral profiles of wines are unique to a geographical location and could be used as chemical descriptors to discriminate the geographical origin due to the direct relationship with soil characteristics [9].

In contrast with those mentioned above, there are concerns regarding exposure to some metals known as "heavy metals" found in wines and if concentrations are significant, the beneficial effects are outweighed by adverse effects. In the light of these considerations, a brief review regarding heavy metals contents in wines

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worldwide and the possible effects on human health is appropriate.

II. Sources of metals in wines

The presence of metals in wine is correlated with some factors such as grape variety, soil, climate, culture technology, winemaking processes (figure 1).

Fig. 1. Sources of metals in wines (endogenous sources - solid line, exogenous sources - dotted) (after Pohl, 2007) [10]

Application of phytosanitary treatments and fertilizers may increase Cu, Cd, Mn and Pb levels in wines. Moreover, wines produced from vineyards located in industrial areas present high content of lead [11].

Copper and zinc are assimilated from soil, from phytosanitary treatments or from equipments used in winemaking processes. Vineyard topsoil in the Bento Goncalves region from Brazil was strongly polluted by copper. Copper soil accumulation depends on soil type, its total concentration varied between 211 and 1504 mg/kg in Ferrosol (FR) vineyard soil, between 1508 and 3215 mg/kg in Podzol (PZ) vineyard soil and copper concentration was lower compared to PZ and FR in the Arenosol (AR) vineyard soil, varying from 36 to 689 mg/kg (fraction <63 mm). Copper distribution in soil profile relate that in vineyard soils on volcanic rocks, copper concentration drastically decreased within the first 10 cm [12].

It has been found that grape must contain approximately 5 mg/L copper [7], most of it coming from fungicidal treatments with Bordeaux mixture against Downy Mildew. Dithiocarbamate fungicides may represent an important source of zinc in wine. Other zinc source is winemaking equipment (pumps, hose connections, taps) [7].

Literature studies reveal two fractions of iron: "physiological iron" (2-6 mg/L) that comes from grapes and "technological iron" (up to 60 mg/L) that comes from the dust deposited on grapes, from machines, transportation equipments [7, 13].

Chromium is encountered in wine in small concentrations, probably due to interaction with metallic containers. Some studies indicate that chromium content increase significantly with the age of wine, probably as a result of contamination with chromium oxides used for pigmentation of the bottles [14]. Also, species grown on chromium contaminated soil contain higher levels of chromium [15].

III. Role and importance of metals for wine quality and effects on human health

Metal toxicity and bioavailability depends of chemical form and of concentration. In wines, metals are present as free ions or complexed with organic species that are encountered in wine (organic acids, polyphenols, saccharides).

Metals are important for efficient alcoholic fermentation of wine and affect their properties such as stability, flavor, freshness, aroma, colour, clarity and taste [10].

Zinc is less toxic than other metals (cadmium, lead) and presents an important role in the nutrition and health of plants, animals and man. Zinc is a component of a variety of enzymes (dehydrogenases, peptidases, proteinases and phosphohydrolases) [16]. Excessive intake of zinc can have long term effects whereas the deficiency syndrome manifests itself by retardation of growth, anorexia, lesions of skin and affects the function of reproductive organs [17].

There are studies that pointed out that zinc causes the persistence of the sour taste, meanwhile iron changes the wine flavor [18].

Copper is an essential micronutrient for normal plant metabolism, playing an important role in a large number of metalloenzymes, photosynthesis-related plastocyanin and membrane structure but it has been reported to be among the toxic heavy metals [19, 20]. Copper is essential in humans for bone formation, elastin synthesis, energy metabolism, nerve transmission, normal hair growth, pigmentation of the skin and red blood production [21]. Excessive intake of copper may cause hemolysis, hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic effects. Continuous ingestion of copper from

food induces chronic copper poisoning in man [17].

High copper content can cause spoilage leading to pinking of red wine and haze formation [22]. Cu, Fe and Mn are involved in oxido-reductive reactions resulting from wine browning, case, turbidity or astringency [23]. The phenomena named "browning" that affects especially white wines is based on a process of continuous oxidation, a loss of aromatic freshness and the appearance of precipitates in bottled wines [24]. To minimize these effects, it is recommended to maintain copper levels below 0.3-0.5 mg/L [24,25].

Manganese is an essential trace element and both deficiency and excess of manganese have detrimental health effects and are associated with disease states. Excessive intake of manganese (inhalation, ingestion), may result in central nervous system pathology. Health effects caused by lower levels of manganese exposure are not well defined, due to more subtle signs, this aspect requiring further investigation [26].

Iron is involved in a wide variety of metabolic processes as oxygen transport, DNA synthesis and electron transport. Disorders correlated with iron metabolism are among the most encountered diseases in humans meanwhile, iron toxicity is nearly always due to accidental ingestion of iron supplements mainly by children [27]. Polyphenols present in different food products, including wine, exhibit inhibitor effect on iron absorption [28].

Manganese and iron play an important role in chemical processes that involve acetaldehyde, one of the main parameters in wine quality control. At low levels, acetaldehyde can contribute to fruity aromas of a wine. Manganese favors its formation meanwhile, iron catalyzes acetaldehyde reaction with phenols [23].

Iron is important because when it is present in excessive quantity, it may cause cloudiness and colour change. When wine is aerated occurs oxidation Fe(II) to Fe(III) which is responsible for the appearance of blue casse (precipitation of colouring matter) or white casse (cloudiness in white wines) [29].

Lead as a well-known toxic heavy metal that accumulates in human's body through food chain and endangers mankind's health [30]. It is estimated that from 70% intake of lead from food and drinks, the wine is the alcoholic beverage that shows the highest level of lead [13]. As far as it is known till today, lead has no essential function for plants, animals and microorganisms

and it inhibits the thiolic groups of some enzymatic systems, especially those that potentiate haemoglobin synthesis [31]. Chronic effects of lead on heme synthesis have been reported, with inhibition and reduction of various enzymes in blood and urine [32, 33]. Chronic intoxications can arise through the regular consumption of foodstuffs that are only slightly contaminated with lead.

Literature studies report many cases of lead poisoning with homemade wine left for fermentation in a glazed earthenware vat [34].

Cadmium is one of the most well-known environmental intoxicants and causes serious damage in kidneys, lungs, bones and also anaemia and sometime hypertension [35]. Also, the balance of other minerals such as P and Ca in the body is also disturbed by high intake of Cd [36].

IV. Metals content in various types of wine and legislative regulations

The levels of metals with biological importance and toxic ones will be compared with the limits set by the Organization Internationale de la Vigne et du Vin (OIV) (table 1 - metal content in white wines and table 2 - metal content in red wines). The Romanian regulations [37] are similar with those imposed by OIV, excepting the maximum admitted level for lead which is 200µg/L.

According to Gayon [7], all wines contain small quantities of **manganese** (1-3 mg/L) due to vineyard soil or winemaking techniques. The manganese content in wines could reach accidentally the value 10 mg/L, this being a consequence of fungicide contamination (Maneb, for example) or to fraudulent treatments with potassium permanganate (to intensify the colour of red wines or to desulfitation of white wines) [51]. Research studies indicated that white wines accumulate lower manganese than red or rosé wines, mainly due to winemaking techniques [7]. To highlight the statement above, study carried out by Scaeteanu et al. on Romanian wines [52] revealed that the average manganese content ranges between 0.856-0.963 mg/L for Tamaioasa Romaneasca (white), 0.788-0.947 mg/L for Sauvignon Blanc (white), 0.621-0.738 mg/L for Riesling Italian (white), 0.488-0.595 mg/L for Feteasca Alba (white), 1.261-1.340 mg/L for Busuioaca de Bohotin (rose) and 1.231-1.354 mg/L for Feteasca Neagra (red).

Other studies indicate that manganese content in wines (France) ranges from 0.435 to 7.836 mg/L

in red samples and from 0.844 to 1.805 mg/L in rosé ones [53]. Ferreira et al. [54] found that the content of manganese in some wines varied from 0.78 to 2.89 mg/L.

The Organisation International de la Vigne et du Vin (OIV) fixed an uppermost level for some metals in wine, but there is no legislative limitation for manganese level.

Wine contains naturally up to 25 mg/L of **iron** [29], 2-6 mg/L being present due to the iron content of grapes [7, 13]. Iron casse may appear in the case of wines with higher iron content than 5-10 mg/L.

At low concentration, **copper** is involved in oxidative transformations that occurs in red wine ageing, promotes oxidation of iron and casse, specific mainly to white wines, that are not very well protected from redox processes, as red ones [7].

At the concentrations around 1 mg/L causes turbidity. To minimize the incidence of these unwanted transformations, it is recommended to maintain copper level below 0.3-0.5 mg/L [25]. At high doses it is toxic, which it justifies the legal limit of 1 mg/L [7]. The copper content is correlated with wine quality.

Researches carried out on wines from Romania [55] indicated that copper content is higher in white wines (0.255-0.538 mg/L) than red ones (0.122-0.214 mg/L). The average value retrieved for copper in two major wine producing areas from Southeast Romania ('Valea Calugareasca' and 'Murfatlar'), and also wine from the region of Moldova (Eastern Romania) was 0.602 mg/L in white wines towards 0.347 mg/L in red wines [43]. Literature studies indicated that red wines undergo higher must aeration during the winemaking process and their higher oxygen content may increase copper oxidation and copper salt precipitation. This causes, usually a higher copper content in white wines as reported by Ostapczuk et al [56]. The same difference between copper content in white and red wines was reported by Provenzano et al. [57].

Literature survey regarding **zinc** content in wines revealed that in most cases (table 1 and 2) found contents were below limit set by OIV (5 mg/L), excepting study carried out by Galani-Nikolakaki et al. [58] when zinc ranged from 0.06 mg/L up to 5.5 mg/L. Zinc content of wines increases if during vinification processes are used zinc containers and when zinc containing pesticides are used.

Lead is a toxic metal and wine contamination with it is a problem dating back to ancient times. Because of unwanted physiological effects on human beings (nervous central disturbances, biosynthesis of haemoglobin), the threshold limit value in wines set by OIV have been lowered progressively from 600 µg/L [7] in 1953 to 150 µg/L in 2013 [59]. Wine does not contain excessive levels of lead (60 µg/L) and most of the researches present lead levels lower than maximum admitted level (150 µg/L). In some cases, it was recorded concentrations that are higher than this threshold [39]. Increased lead levels may be associated with environmental pollution or winemaking processes. Anyway, within last years it have been noticed a clearly visible decrease of lead content in wines.

Analyzing the literature data concerning **cadmium** levels in wines it is observed that follows a wide variation: from undetectable levels up to values higher than maximum threshold (10µg/L). Cvetkovic et al. [42] analyzed cadmium content in white and red wines from different regions of Macedonia and observed that cadmium levels are higher in red (0.28-0.90µg/L) than in white ones (0.10-0.65µg/L).

The investigations of **chromium** content in wines are associated with its toxic potential. It is known that in human body, chromium it is involved in glucose metabolism and excessive amounts of chromium may produce serious health disturbances.

Cabrera-Vique et.al [14] determined levels of chromium in French wines and the results indicated that white wines contain 6.60-43.90 µg/L, red wines contain 6.60-90.00 µg/L, meanwhile in champagne were found concentrations that ranges between 10.50-36.00 µg/L. Also, the same research team stated that on the basis of the analysis of chromium contents for different vintage wines from the same vineyard and winery, chromium levels increase with the age of wine, probably due to contamination by stainless steel or glass bottles that contain chromium oxides.

Contrariwise, Cvetkovic et al. [15] observed for Macedonian wines that white wines contain higher levels of chromium (8.90-37.80µg/L) than red ones (9.90-19.30 µg/L) due to contamination that appear during wine production and storage.

Table 1

Country	Metal contents in white wines							Ref.
	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	
	mg/L				($\mu\text{g/L}$)			
Cehia	0.310-1.600	2.30-3.50	0.130-0.180	0.290-0.540	22.00-48.00	-	18.00-32.00	[38]
Ethiopia	1.04-1.88	1.42-2.33	0.500-0.610	1.820-2.400	140-310	<LOD	<LOD	[39]
France	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.60-43.90	[40]
Italy	-	-	0.500-0.100	0.200-3.700	16.9-198	1.30-15.30	-	[41]
Macedonia	-	-	-	-	-	-	8.90-37.80	[15]
	-	-	-	-	-	0.12-0.79	-	[42]
Romania	0.233-2.454	-	0.082-2.594	0.178-1.442	19.20-235.90	-	60.96-1725.80	[43]
Spania	0.410-3.180	0.290-2.600	0.004-0.186	0.057-0.405	-	-	6.00-36.00	[44]
	0.160-1.970	1.23-8.13	0.030-1.370	0.130-1.560	-	-	-	[45]
Turkey	0.069-0.139	0.310-1.270	0.139-0.232	0.377-0.397	<LOD	<LOD	7.23-65.66	[46]
MAL (OIV)	-	-	1.00	5.00	150.00	10.00	-	

(MAL - maximum admitted level)

Table 2

Country	Metal contents in red wines							Ref.
	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	
	mg/L				($\mu\text{g/L}$)			
Argentina	0.820-1.300	0.800-2.80	0.100-0.290	0.300-1.30	-	-	-	[47]
Brazil	0.800-2.900	1.10-6.34	<LOD-0.250	0.150-1.64	-	-	-	[48]
Cehia	0.520-1.400	1.80-4.60	0.045-0.260	0.470-1.000	11-26	-	19-32	[38]
Ethiopia	1.460-1.560	1.49-3.16	0.550-1.500	2.14-2.40	160-250	-	<LOD-190	[39]
France	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.60-90.00	[40]
Italy	-	-	0.116-0.267	-	-	-	-	[49]
	1.04-1.63	2.60-3.92	-	0.560-0.720	33.05-46.19	0.250-0.380	14.67-19.68	[50]
Macedonia	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.90-19.30	[15]
	-	-	-	-	-	0.21-0.97	-	[42]
Morocco	0.934-1.342	-	0.077-0.127	0.563-0.771	-	-	79.90-111	[4]
Romania	0.280-3.077	-	0.026-1.216	0.057-1.004	17.01-57.65	-	109.58-982.81	[43]
Turkey	0.120-1.901	0.590-5.79	0.044-0.525	0.807-0.953	<LOD-25.92	<LOD-11.50	7.75-137.80	[45]
MAL (OIV)	-	-	1.00	5.00	150.00	10.00	-	

(MAL - maximum admitted level)

V. Analytical methods for metal analysis in wine

Wine analysis presents a great importance because chemical species present into its composition influence stability, organoleptic properties and some of them present hazardous potential for consumers. Moreover, wine analysis is recommended when considering possible fraud involving branded products.

Selection of appropriate method for metal analysis is made accordingly to the metal concentration, number of metallic species present in the sample and matrix effects (interferences). International Organization of Vine and Wine considers and recommend that for routine analytical control of metals in wine is suitable

atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). Major metals (manganese, iron, copper, zinc) are atomized satisfactory by air/acetylene flame when method is flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS). In some cases, FAAS is capable to detect ultra trace elements after a preconcentration stage. Furthermore, preconcentration and separation methods are needed when the concentrations of metallic ions in wines are too low to be determined directly [60].

Sample decomposition before analysis is required in many cases. Wet digestion using nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide or microwave mineralization with nitric acid to oxidize the organic matrix is usually performed to decompose wine samples [24].

In the case of FAAS, it has been observed that matrix effects are mitigated probably due to the

flame robustness and when dealing with matrix effects due to refractory compounds, this inconvenient is removed by optimizing gas flows [61].

Because of their capacity to determine concentrations much below their maximum threshold, for trace and ultratrace metals are usually approached electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ETAAS) [14, 15, 42, 62, 63], hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry (HGAAS) [62, 63], inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) [63, 64], inductively coupled plasma - mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) [9, 65, 66], total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (TXRF) [67], square-wave anodic-stripping voltammetry (SWASV) [68]. ICP-MS and ICP-AES are analytical techniques mostly reported in literature for multielement analysis that are characterized by high sensitivity.

Parameters that may influence the elimination of matrix effects in the case of ETAAS are furnace characteristics, temperature program and selection of modifier [61]. During the direct analysis of complex matrixes, the non-specific background absorption from interfering species occurs often and may produce erroneous results. To minimize this aspect it is recommended the application of a continuum deuterium source or Zeeman effect as background correction [24].

In last decade was introduced commercially high-resolution continuum source atomic absorption spectrometry (HR-CS AAS), a new alternative technique for determination of trace and ultratrace metals in wine samples. Continuum source is a xenon short-arc lamp that provides the opportunity to determine almost known elements, other advantages being represented by the possibility to use the principal and secondary lines and to extend the linear working range [69]. Taking into consideration the importance of metals winemaking processes but also their relevant implication for human health, it is worth noticing the scientific papers that has been focused on development of suitable analytical methods for the assessment of these species.

VI. Conclusions

As a conclusion of this brief overview, metals influence many aspects of wine production and it therefore absolutely necessary to understand the role of metals in winemaking processes to ensure and improve wine quality.

Considering vinification processes, metals determine wine quality and have a great effect on human health and well-being. Knowledge of the metal content of wine is crucial for not only winemakers but also consumers. Certainly, because of the nutritional value of metals in wine, analysis of the total contents of major, minor and trace metals is of a particular interest with respect to quality and safety of wine.

References

1. Tomera, J.F.: *Current knowledge of the health benefits and disadvantages of wine consumption*. In: Trends in Food Science&Technology, vol. 10, 1999, p.129-138.
2. Arranz, S., Chiva-Blanch, G., Valderas Martinez, P., Medina-Remon, A., Lamuela-Raventos, R.M., Estruch, R.: *Wine, beer, alcohol and polyphenols on cardiovascular disease and cancer*. In: Nutrients, vol. 4, 2012, p. 759-781.
3. Siemann, E.H., Creasy, L.L.: *Concentration of the phytoalexin resveratrol in wine*. In: Am.J.Enol.Vitic., vol. 43(1), 1992, p. 49-52.
4. Tenore, G.C., Troisi, J., Di Fiore, R., Manfra, M., Novellino, E.: *Nutraceutical value and toxicological profile of selected red wines from Morocco*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 129, 2011, p. 792-798.
5. Marais, A.D.: *Do heavy metals counter the potential health benefits of wine? In: Journal of Endocrinology, Metabolism and Diabetes of South Africa*, vol. 14(2), 2009, p. 77-79.
6. Volpe, M.G., La Cara, F., Volpe, F., De Mattia, A., Serino, V., Petitto, F., Zavalloni, C., Limone, F., Pellecchia, R., De Prisco, P.P., Di Stasio, M.: *Heavy metal uptake in the oenological food chain*. In: Food Chemistry, vol.117, 2009, p. 553-560.
7. Ribéreau-Gayon, P., Glories, Y., Maujean, A., Durbridieu, A.: *Handbook of enology*, vol.2. The chemistry of wine, stabilization and treatments. John Wiley and Sons, 2006, p. 102-104.
8. Alvarez, M., Moreno, I.M., Jos, A., Camean, A.M., Gonzalez, A.G.: *Differentiation of two andalusian DO "fino" wines according to their metal content from ICP_OES by using supervised pattern recognition methods*. In: Microchemical Journal, vol. 8, 2007, p.72-76.
9. Martin, A.E., Watling, R.J., Lee, G.S.: *The multi-element determination and regional discrimination of Australian wines*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 133, 2012, p.1081-1089.
10. Pohl, P.: *What do metals tell us about wine?.* In: Trends in Analytical Chemistry, vol. 26(9), 2007, p.941-949.
11. Kaufmann, A.: *Lead in wine*. In: Food Addit.Contam., vol.15, 1998, p.437-445.

12. Mirlean, N., Roisenberg, A., Chies, J.: *Metal contamination of vineyard soils in wet subtropics (southern Brazil)*. In: Environmental Pollution, vol. 149, 2007, p. 10-17
13. Artimon, M., Tanase, I.Gh., Vasile, G.: *The validation of the method for iron determination in roumanian wines using flame atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: Revue Roumaine de Chimie, vol. 54(3), 2009, p.247-254.
14. Cabrera-Vique, C., Tessedre, P.L., Cabanis, M.T., Cabanis, J.C.: *Determination and levels of chromium in French wines and grapes by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: J.Agr. Food Chem., vol.45, 1997, p. 1808-1811.
15. Cvetkovic, J., Arpadjan, S., Karadjova, I., Stafilov, T.: *Determination of chromium in Macedonian wine by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: BAÜ Fen Bil.Enst.Dergisi, vol. 4.2, 2002, p. 80-84.
16. Anke, M., Röhrig, B., Schäfer, U., Müller, R., Latzel, F.: *Zinc in the food chain: biological importance*. In: Acta Medica Lituanica, 12(4), 2005, p.50-58.
17. Hashmi, D.R., Ismail, S., Shaikh, G.H.: *Assessment of the level of trace metals in commonly edible vegetables locally available in the markets of Karachi city*. In: Pakistan Journal of Botany, vol. 39(3), 2007, p. 747-751.
18. Esparza, I., Salinas, I., Caballero, I., Santamaria, C., Calco, I., Garcia-Mina, J.M., Fernandez, J.M.: *Evolution of metal and polyphenol content over a 1-year period of vinification: sample fractionation and correlation between metals and anthocyanins*. In: Analytica Acta, vol. 524, 2004, p.215-224.
19. Wong, M.H, Bradshaw A.D.: *A comparison of the toxicity of heavy metals, using root elongation of ryegrass*. In: New Phytol., 91, 1982, p. 255-261.
20. Xiong, Z.T., Wang H.: *Copper toxicity and bioaccumulation in Chinese cabbage (Brassica pekinensis Rupr.)*. In: Environ. Toxicol., 20, 2005, p.188-194.
21. Johnson, M.A.: Copper. In: R. Macrae, R. K. Robinson, M. J. Sadler(Ed). Ency. Fd. Sci.Fd. Tech. Nutri. Academic Press.London, 1997.
22. Clark, A.C., Scollary, G.R.: *Determination of total copper in white wine by stripping potentiometry utilising medium exchange*. In: Analytica Chimica Acta, vol. 413, 2000, p.25-32.
23. Cacho, J., Castells, J.E., Esteban, A., Laguna, B., Sagrista N.: *Iron, copper, manganese influence on wine oxidation*. In: Journal of Enology and Viticulture, 46, 1995, p.380-384.
24. Artimon, M., Dumitrescu, V., Tanase, I.Gh., Pele, M., Nedelcu, R.: *The optimization of the methods for Cu, Zn and Pb content determination in Romanian wines by AAS after dry or microwave mineralization*. In: Romanian Biotechnological Letters, vol. 14(2), 2009, p.4319-4325.
25. Pyrzynska, K: *Analytical methods for the determination of trace metals in wine*. In: Critical reviews in analytical chemistry, vol. 34, 2004, p. 69-83.
26. Rollin, H.B.: Manganese: *Environmental pollution and health effects*. In: Encyclopedia of Environmental Health, 617-629.
27. Gurzau, E.S., Neagu, C., Gurzau, A.E.: *Essential metals - case study on iron*. In: Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety, vol. 56, 2003, p. 190-200.
28. Hurell R.F., Reddy M., Cook J.D.: *Inhibition of non-haem iron absorption in man by polyphenolic-containing beverages*. In: British Journal of Nutrition, vol.81, 1999, p. 289-295.
29. Ferreira, S.L.C., Ferreira, H.S., de Jesus, R.M., Santos, J.V.S., Brandao, G.C., Souza, A.S.: *Development of method for the speciation of inorganic iron in wine samples*. In: Analytica Chimica Acta, vol. 602, 2007, p.89-93.
30. Liu, J.G., Li, K.Q., Xu, J.K., Zhang, Z.J., Ma, T.B., Lu, X.L., Yang, J.H., Zhu, Q.S.: *Lead toxicity, uptake, and translocation in different rice cultivars*. In: Plant Sci. 165, 2003, p.793-802.
31. Grecu, I., Neamtu, M., Enescu, L.: *Implicatii biologice si medicale ale chimiei anorganice*, Ed. Junimea, Iasi, 1982.
32. Tsuchiya K.: *Handbook on the Toxicology of Metals*, ed. L. Friberg, G. F. Nordberg and V. B. Vouk, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1986, vol. II.
33. Ewers, U., Schlipkoter, H. W.: *Metals and Their Compounds in the Environment*, ed. E. Merian, VCH, Weinheim, 1991, p. 971
34. Loi, F., Battista, G., Malentacchi, G.M., Paradiso, C., Pompella, A., Rubegni, M., Federico, A: *Familial lead poisoning from contaminated wine*. In: The Italian Journal of Neurological Sciences, vol.3, 1981, p. 283-290.
35. Afshar, M., Ghazei, S, Saad, E.: *Determination of cadmium in Amol and Thailand rice*, 4th International Iranian Congress on Poisoning, Theran, Iran, 2000, <http://www.irandoc.ac.ir>.
36. IFDC, 1996, The basics of zinc in crop production. Technical Bulletin T-43, International Fertilizer Development Centre, Muscle Shoals, Alabama, USA, p.19.
37. Hotărâre nr. 1.134 din 10 octombrie 2002 pentru aprobarea Normelor metodologice de aplicare a Legii viei și vinului în sistemul organizării comune a pieței vitivinicole nr. 244/2002
38. Sperkova, J., Suchanek, M.: *Multivariate classification of wines from different Bohemian regions (Czech Republic)*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 93, 2005, p. 659-663.
39. Woldemariam, D.M., Chanravanshi, B.S.: *Concentration levels of essential and non-essential elements in selected Ethiopian wines*. In: Bull.Chem.Soc.Ethiop., vol. 25(2), 2011, p. 169-180.

40. Cabrera-Vique, C., Teissedre, P.-L., Cabanis, M.-T., Cabanis J.-C.: *Determination and levels of chromium in French wine and grapes by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: J.Agric.Food Chem., vol. 45, 1997, p. 1808-1811.
41. Provenzano, M.R., El Bilali, H., Simeone, V., Baser, N., Mondelli, D., Cesari, G.: *Copper contents in grapes and wines from a Mediterranean organic vineyard*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 122, 2010, p. 1338-1343.
42. Cvetkovic, J., Arpadjan, S., Karadjova, I., Stafilov, T.: *Determination of cadmium in wine by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: Acta Pharm., vol. 56, 2006, p. 69-77.
43. Geana, I., Iordache, A., Ionete, R., Marinescu, A., Ranca, A., Culea, M.: *Geographical origin identification of Romanian wines by ICP-MS elemental analysis*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 138, 2013, p. 1125-1134.
44. Jurado, J.M., Alcazar, A., Palacios-Morillo, A., De Pablos, F.: *Classification of Spanish DO white wines according to their elemental profile by means of support vector machines*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 135, 2012, p. 898-903.
45. Alvarez, M., Moreno, I.M., Pichardo, S., Camean, A.M., Gonzalez, A.G.: *Mineral profile of "fino" wines using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry methods*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 135, 2012, p. 309-313.
46. Alkis, I.M., Öz, S., Atakol, A., Yilmaz, N., Anli, R.E., Atakol, O.: *Investigation of heavy metal concentration in some Turkish wines*. In: Journal of Food Composition and Analysis, vol. 33, 2014, p. 105-110.
47. Saavedra, J., Fuentealba, C., Yanez, L., Bravo, M., Quiroz, W., Lukacsy, G., Carot, J.M.: *Chemometric approaches for the zoning of Pinot Noir wines from the Casablanca valley, Chile*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 127, 2011, p. 1842-1847.
48. Dos Santos, C.E.I., Da Silva, L.R.M., Buofleur, L.A., Debastiani, R., Alberici Stefenon, C., Amaral, L., Yoneama, M.L., Diaz, J.F.: *Elemental characterization of Cabernet Sauvignon wines using Particle-Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE)*. In: Food Chemistry, vol.121, 2010, p. 244-150.
49. Galgano, F., Favati, F., Caruso, M., Scarpa, T., Palma, A.: *Analysis of trace elements in southern Italian wines and their classification according to provenance*. In: Food Science and Technology, vol. 41, 2008, p. 1808-1815.
50. Dugo, G., La Pera, L., Pellicano, T.M., Di Bella, G., D'Imperio, M.: *Determination of some inorganic anions and heavy metals in D.O.C. Golden and Amber Marsala wines: statistical study of the influence of ageing period, colour and sugar content*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 91, 2005, p. 355-363.
51. Artimon, M.: *Studii privind influența cantității unor macro- și microelemente asupra calității vinurilor*. Teza de doctorat. Universitatea din Bucuresti, 2008.
52. Scăteanu, G., Călin, C., Ilie, L., Pele, M., Pântea, O.: *Manganese content in wine samples from Tohani-Dealul Mare*. In: Journal of EcoAgriTourism- Bulletin of Agri-Ecology, Agri-Food, Bioengineering and Agriturism, vol.8, no.1(24), 2012, p. 227-231.
53. Cabrera-Vique, C., Teissedre, P.L., Cabanis, M.T., Cabanis, J.C.: *Manganese determination in grapes and wines from different regions of France*. In: Am.J.Enol.Vitic., vol. 51(2), 2000, p.103-107.
54. Ferreira, S.L., Souza, A.S., Brandao, G.C., Ferreira, H.S., dos Santos, W.N., Pimentel, M.F., Vale, M.G.: *Direct determination of iron and manganese in wine using the reference element technique and fast sequential multi-element flame atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: Talanta, vol. 74(4), 2008, p.699-702.
55. Călin, C., Scăteanu, G., Pele, M., Ilie, L., Pântea, O., Bomboș, D.: *Assessment of copper content in wines from Tohani-Dealul Mare by flame atomic absorption spectrometry*. In: Revista de Chimie, vol. 63(10), 2012, p.1062-.....
56. Ostapczuk, P., Eschnauer, H.R., Scollary, G.R.: *Determination of cadmium, lead and copper in wine by potentiometric stripping analysis*. In: Fresenius Journal of Analytical Chemistry, vol. 358, 1997, p. 723-727.
57. Provenzano, M.R., Bilali, H.El, Simeone, V., Baser, N., Mondelli, D., Cesari, G.: *Copper contents in grapes and wines from a Mediterranean organic vineyard*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 122, 2010, p. 1338-1343.
58. Galani-Nikolakaki, S., Kallithrakas-Kontos, N., Katsanos, A.A.: *Trace element analysis of Cretan wines and wine products*. In: The Science of the Total Environment, vol.285, 2002, p. 155-163.
59. Compendium of International Methods of Wine and Must Analysis, volume 2, 2013.
60. Cvetkovic, J., Arpadjan, S., Karadjova, I., Stafilov, T.: *Determination of thallium in wine by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry after extraction preconcentration*. In: Spectrochimica Acta, part B, vol. 57, 2002, p. 1101-1106.
61. Grindlay, G., Mora, J., Gras, L., De Loos-Vollebregt, M.T.C.: *Atomic spectrometry methods for wine analysis: a critical evaluation and discussion of recent applications*. In: Analytica Chimica Acta, vol. 691, 2011, p. 18-32.
62. Santos, S., Lapa, N., Alves, A., Morais, J., Mendes, B.: *Analytical methods and validation*

- for determining trace elements in red wines. In: Journal of Environmental Science and Health, part B, vol. 48, 2013, p. 364-375.
63. Jos, A., Moreno, A. G., Gonzalez, A. G., Repetto, G., Camean, A. M.: *Differentiation of sparkling wines according to their mineral content*. In: Talanta 63(2), 2004, p. 377-382.
64. Martin, A.E., John, R., Lee, G.S.: The multi-element determination and regional discrimination of Australian wines. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 133, 2012, p. 1081-1089.
65. Cozzolino, D., Kwiatkowski, M.J., Damberg, R.G., Cynkar, W.U., Janik, L.J., Skouroumounis, G., Gishen, M.: *Analysis of elements in wine using near infrared spectroscopy and partial least squares regression*. In: Talanta, vol. 74, 2008, p. 711-716.
66. Rodrigues, S.M., Otero, M., Alves, A.A., Coimbra, J., Coimbra, M.A., Pereira, E., Duarte, A.C.: *Elemental analysis for categorization of wines and authentication of their certified brand of origin*. In: Journal of Food Composition and Analysis, vol. 24, 2011, p. 548-562.
67. Pessanha, S., Carvahlo, M.L., Becker, M., Von Bohlen, A.: *Quantitative determination on heavy metals in different stages of wine production by Total Reflection X-ray Fluorescence and Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence: comparison on two vineyards*. In: Spectrochimica Acta Part B, vol. 65, 2010, p. 504-507.
68. Illuminati, S., Annibaldi, A., Truzzi, C., Finale, C., Scarponi, G.: *Square-wave anodic-stripping voltammetric determination of Cd, Pb and Cu in wine: set-up and optimization of sample pre-treatment and instrumental analysis*. In: Electrochimica Acta, vol.104, 2013, p. 148-161.
69. Welz, B., Sperling, M.: *Atomic Absorption Spectrometry* (third ed.), Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 1999.

PERSPECTIVE ON HUMAN EXPOSURE TO PESTICIDES AND THEIR METABOLITES IN DIFFERENT MEDIA

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Abstract: *Pesticides use has indubitably increased the agricultural production but beside beneficial effects, persistent residues present tremendous harmful impact on environment and on human health. Lately, it has been observed that exposure to pesticides is increasingly linked with serious diseases. In this context, pesticide safety, regulation of pesticide use, integrated pest management and suitable application technologies represent the strategies that assure a minimisation of human exposure and of environmental pollution. In the light of these considerations, is appropriate to present a brief review regarding pesticides and the effects on human health.*

Keywords: *agriculture, pesticide, pollution, pesticide residue, health.*

I. Introduction

It is widely known that agricultural activities produce a diverse range of harmful on environmental quality and the main danger is correlated with the contaminants as a result of agricultural practices. Notwithstanding, responsible utilization of fertilizers and pesticides guarantees the presence on the market of food products, fruits and vegetables of high quality at low prices accessible to consumers.

The term "*pesticide*" refers to chemicals that are used to kill or to control pests and covers a wide range of compounds that include insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, rodenticides, molluscicides, nematocides, plants growth regulators and many other categories. Some pesticides are very toxic, non-biodegradable and are characterized by long persistence in the environment for a long time.

Literature studies indicate that world pesticide amount used was approximately 2.4 million tonnes in both 2006 and 2007, the herbicides having the highest percent from total use, followed by other pesticides [1]. Widely used pesticides for agricultural market sector were herbicides [2].

According to a study developed by Aktar et al. [3] concerning the consumption pattern of pesticides worldwide, the most used are insecticides (44%), followed by herbicides (30%), fungicides (21%) and others (5%). Pesticide use to date has increased 50 fold since 1950 and currently there are thousands of

synthetic pesticide products made up of more than 1000 different chemicals and combinations thereof [4].

Pesticides are widely used throughout the world due to their benefits concerning high product quality and yield, but there are many concerns and disadvantages correlated with environmental pollution and human health. Of the side effects of pesticides and their residues we mention a few:

- affect drinking water quality;
- some pesticides contain bromide compounds which when are volatilized convert into stratospheric ozone depleting gases;
- contaminate food for human consumption;
- cause adverse health effects: cancer, genetic disturbances, irreversible deterioration of immune system.

Because pesticides are designed to be effective against pests they must be toxic or poisonous. Therefore, persons who handle or use pesticides must understand the potential danger and health effects of the products they use and must respect recommended safety measures.

The interaction between pesticides and human body is mediated by skin contact by handling pesticide products, inhalation by breathing of dust or spray and by ingestion together with contaminated food and/or water. Workers are at a great risk to develop health problems since they show higher cumulative exposures that regular population and accordingly, potential associations are more easily to be observed [1].

In recognition of pesticide abuse and of environmental and public health impacts, the

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European countries have adopted a variety of measures that include the following (FAO/ECE 1991) [5]:

- reduction in use of pesticides (by up to 50% in some countries);
- bans on certain active ingredients;
- training and licensing of individuals that apply pesticides;
- limitations on aerial spraying;
- environmental tax on pesticides;
- promote the use of mechanical and biological alternatives of pesticides.

Along with the wide use of pesticides worldwide, the concerns regarding their impact on human health are growing rapidly and according to literature data [6], there is a correlation between pesticide exposure and elevated rate of chronic diseases (cancer, neurodegenerative disorders like Parkinson, Alzheimer, birth defects, reproductive disorders).

II. Brief historical perspective

The concept of pesticides is not new, pesticide use being an old practice. Homer referred to the use of sulphur to fumigate homes; in ancient times the Chinese were using arsenic to control garden pests and in 1930s are used for the first time some organo-mercuric compounds that were more efficient than CuSO_4 in seeds treatment. A little later, during 1940-1950, compounds as Paris green, lead arsenate, calcium arsenate, selenium compounds, mercury, copper sulphate, and nicotine were used frequently. The introduction of organophosphate pesticides in the 1960s, carbamates in 1970s, pyrethroids in 1980s and herbicides and fungicides during 1970s-1980s contributed greatly to pest control and increase of agricultural yield [3]. Researches concerning synthesis of safe pesticides conducted during 1970-1980 period to the greatest selling broad spectrum herbicide, glyphosate, used to kill weeds [7]. Beside of these beneficial effects, there are studies that indicate its potential to produce human breast cancer [8].

In view of potential toxic and persistent nature of some pesticides, there is the pressing need for their control and monitoring in the environment.

III. Pesticide toxicity

The toxicity of plant protection products is characterized by lethal dose (LD). The lethal dose is quantity of plant protection product that

causes death. Usually presents through DL_{50} , that is the amount of preparation which has causes 50% mortality in animals to which it was applied. The lethal dose is expressed in mg/kg.

Another indicator of toxicity is the lethal concentration (CL_{50}), which represents the dose rate of product from air, water and soil which produces a mortality of 50%.

According to Directive 91/414/CEE [9], pesticides are divided into four groups depending on the DL_{50} :

1. highly toxic products, with LD_{50} in the 50 mg/kg body weight;
2. highly toxic products, with LD_{50} between 50-200 mg/kg;
3. moderately toxic products, with LD_{50} between 200-1000 mg/kg;
4. products with a low toxicity, with LD_{50} between 1000 mg/kg body weight.

The toxicity of pesticides can be acute or chronic. Acute intoxication occurs soon after introduction into the body of a quantity of toxic. Chronic intoxication occurs after continuous accumulation of toxic body and when it reaches a sufficient concentration it causes cell toxicity.

Pesticides have been classified using many criteria, one of them being their persistence in soil. So far, there are *very stable pesticides* (persist more than 18 months - organochlorides and metal containing pesticides), *stable* (persist up to 18 months - triazines), *moderately stable* (persist up to 12 months - benzoic acid derivatives), *unstable* (stable up to 6 months - fenoxiacetic pesticides) and pesticides that decompose quickly (up to 3 months - carbamic compounds).

Keeping in view the potential toxicity, persistent character and cumulative behavior of pesticides, it has been established the maximum residue limits (MRLs) for pesticide residue according to potential daily intake which should not be exceeded in food products [10].

IV. The main chemical classes of pesticides and their effects on human body

From chemical point of view, pesticides fall into four classes: organochlorines, organophosphates, carbamates and pyrethroids.

IV.1. Organochlorines (chlorinated hydrocarbons)

a) General aspects

Organochlorines were commonly used in the past, but many have been removed from the

market due to their health and environmental effects and their persistence. These compounds can break down very slowly and can remain in the environment for long periods of time, are relatively insoluble, persist in soils and aquatic sediments and can bioconcentrate in the tissues of vertebrates from their food, due to their lipophilicity.

b) Toxicity

The common characteristics of organochlorines are affinity for fat and high stability. It penetrates the human body through the skin, digestive and respiratory tracts. In particular, the adipose tissue accumulates in the liver, brain, muscle, kidney and heart. The action of toxic in acute poisoning is manifested by a strong initial excitation and then paralyzing the central nervous system. In the subacute poisoning appears distorted hearing, impaired coordination of motion, muscle atrophy, damage to the liver and kidney, dementia [11].

Exposure to organochlorine compounds has been linked to an increased incidence of breast cancer, although not all data have been consistent [7]. Other studies sustain the idea according to which organochlorine compounds present increased risk to favorize prostate cancer [12,13].

The toxicities of the chlorinated cyclodiene insecticides (aldrin, dieldrin, endrin, chlordane, endosulfan, isodrin) are relatively high and similar to each other. Intoxications include symptoms as headaches, dizziness, nausea, vomiting and convulsions. It has been proven that dieldrin, chlordane and heptachlor cause liver cancer in test animals [14].

c) DDT – first synthetic organochlorine

DDT (1,1,1 - trichloro-2,2-bis(p-chlorophenyl)ethane) (figure 1) was discovered in Switzerland in 1939, was very effective and was used extensively to control human disease vectors and agricultural pests [15].

During World War II, DDT was excessively used to control disease carrier insects as malaria, dengue fever and typhus and after this period was used on agricultural crops [16].

Paul Muller was awarded in 1948 with Nobel Prize in medicine for discovering the insect-killing properties of DDT. During 1950-1980s it was the most used insecticide in agriculture, the used quantity being 0.5-35 kg/ha and more than 40.000 tonnes used each year worldwide.

Since early 1970s, the usage of many organochlorine has been progressively restricted to specific applications and has subsequently been phased in many countries [17].

Lately, in 1968 it was banned in Hungary and then in Norway and Sweden in 1970s. In 1972, DDT use it is restricted in agriculture by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. In Romania, DDT use was forbidden starting with 1985. Nowadays, only a few organochlorines are still used, essentially DDT in tropical countries to control malaria vectors through indoor residual spraying [18].

Routes of DDT loss and degradation include runoff, volatilization, photolysis and aerobic and anaerobic biodegradation.

DDT is toxic to birds and bees and affects nervous system at human beings. The toxicity for humans is increased due to its' high solubility in lipids. Intoxications caused by DDT follow a specific pattern: early signs (tremor, ataxia, dizziness, nausea) and progress gradually to convulsions. Usually, all signs and symptoms are reversible and complete recovery occur. There are no specific antidote and in the case of accidental or deliberate ingestion or skin contact, the subjects must be kept under surveillance [17]. DDT degradation provide other two toxic compounds: DDE and DDD (figure 2) that are also highly persistent and have similar chemical and physical properties. In the food chain it is accumulated mainly the form DDE [16]. In humans DDD and DDE half-lives are 6 and up to 10 years, respectively. Seaweeds have been shown to act as bioremediation agents and can reduce the toxicity of soil contaminated by DDT by up to 80% within six weeks.

Fig. 1. DDT chemical structure

Fig. 2. Degradation products of DDT

d) Organochlorines in various products

Among environmental contaminants, organochlorine pesticides represent the most important group of dangerous organic contaminants and their occurrence has been intensively documented, as it is presented below. There are researches that investigate the DDT content in human milk because it reflects very suggestively the accumulation of organochlorines. Because of their highly lipophilic nature, organochlorine pesticides and their residues can easily concentrate in milk leading to bioconcentration. Comparing data regarding DDT content in milk from 19 countries revealed that Chinese population present high levels of DDT because in the past, China was a major producer and consumer of DDT [16]. Similar study developed in 2003 on human milk from Mexico [19], indicated persistently high levels of DDT. This situation appeared because in 1992 it was used 1000 tonnes of DDT even if its use has been restricted since 1990.

Organochlorine pesticides residues have been identified in cheese, yogurt and milk collected

from Ghana, but the recorded concentrations were lower than those recorded for fresh milk from Uganda, Nigeria, India, Kenya, Ethiopia. These results are not unexpected since all these countries use more chlorinated pesticides than Ghana does [20].

Other similar study carried out in Jordan [21] evidenced the presence of organochlorine pesticides residues in 233 dairy products samples (milk, butter, cheese, yogurt). It were analyzed the residual contents of aldrin, DDT and its metabolites, dieldrin, endosulfan isomers, endrin, hexachlorocyclohexane isomers, heptachlor and the results indicated that 9% (21/233), 8.5% (20/233), 6% (14/233) and 2.1% (5/233) of samples were contaminated with b-HCH, pp'-DDE, α -HCH and γ -HCH, respectively. Also, the order for the contamination in the dairy products was cheese>yogurt>butter>milk.

Whereas many of the banned pesticides are no longer in use in the developed world, there are many developing countries that are still using such type of pesticides. For example, farmers in Ghana used for several decades pesticides not

only for agricultural purposes but also in the public health sector to control disease vector control. As consequence, there has been expected an over accumulation of pesticides in food products, moreover it has been reported several cases of pesticide poisoning. A survey developed on 320 locally produced fresh fruits (pawpaw, tomato) and imported apples were purchased from markets within Accra in order to quantify the pesticide residues. Analysis indicated that heptachlor, heptachlor oxide, endrin aldehyde and endrin ketone exceeded the reference dose for children, suggesting an important potential for systemic toxicity in children [22].

A similar study was developed on 240 samples of vegetables collected from Greater Accra region of Ghana [23]. The results indicated the presence of residue pesticides in 71.9% of all analysed vegetables. Lindane was found in carrot, cabbage and tomato exceeded the maximum residue limit (MRL). Also, heptachlor exceeded the MRL in tomato samples. The most frequently found and abundant pesticides were the metabolites of DDT.

Organochlorine pesticides were identified in honey collected from Italy (industrialized area and non-industrialized area) [24]. The majority of honey samples (94%) were contaminated and the presence of DDT, DDD and DDE were evidenced even if their concentrations were lower than maximum residue level. Anyway, the highest concentrations were recorded with higher frequencies in honey samples produced in industrialized area, reflecting in this way the specific pollution of a given environment.

IV.2. Organic phosphates (organophosphates)

a) General aspects

Jean Louis Lassaigne and Philip Clermout synthesized the first organophosphate in the 19th century. Meanwhile, Gerhard Schrader was responsible with their initial development as insecticides and chemical warfare as nerve gases [25].

Many organophosphates are used as insecticides and apart from agriculture it can be used for household and other building pests. Other application of organophosphates is to control eoparasites in domestic animals or to kill head lice in humans [26].

From chemical point of view, organophosphates are compounds that derived from phosphoric, phosphonic and phosphinic acids (figure 3).

Fig. 3. Structural formula for phosphoric, phosphonic and phosphinic acids.

b) Toxicity

Organophosphates are characterized by high toxicity to humans and do not remain in the environment for long. They act as acetylcholinesterase inhibitors which prevent the breakdown of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine, increasing both its concentration and duration of action in the body [27].

There are studies indicate the correlation between organophosphates and a large number of diseases of the nervous and immune system of mammals. They are linked with mad cow disease, Gulf War syndrome, Parkinson's disease and multiple sclerosis and possess proven mutagenic and teratogenic effects [28].

Poisoning is very dangerous, is characterized by a pronounced strain of speech, loss of ability to coordinate movements, inhibition of reflexes and coma. The antidote for organophosphates poisoning is atropine (*Atropa belladonna*) [14]. Organophosphate intoxications are encountered especially in poorer countries where lax controls and poor protective measures had main contribution to this aspect. In Zimbabwe it was reported an epidemic organophosphate poisonings and three fourths of the adult poisonings were suicidal attempts meanwhile poisoning encountered in children were accidental [14].

Many studies have investigated the neurodevelopment effects of prenatal and early childhood exposures to organophosphate pesticides among children [27, 29].

Cognitive deficiencies (related to memory) were found at children 7 years old, behavioural deficiencies (related to attention) seen mainly in toddlers, and motor deficiencies (abnormal reflexes) seen mainly in neonates [27].

It has been found that tetraethyl pyrophosphate (TEPP) and parathion had high mammalian toxicities [30].

c) Organophosphates in various products

Bempah et al. [31] conducted a study to investigate the organophosphates residues in fruits and vegetables from markets from Ghana. The analytical results indicated that diazinon and malathion were the least predominant pesticides

with residues of 0.007 mg/kg and 0.006 mg/kg in pineapple samples, meanwhile the most dominant pesticide was chlorpyrifos (0.055 mg/kg in pineapple). It followed dimethoate with minimum value of 0.004 mg/kg in water melon and maximum value of 0.010 mg/kg in mango. The results were below in comparison with maximum residue level set by European Council Directive [10] for these pesticides (0.02 mg/kg). The same team of researchers [31] investigated the organophosphate pesticide residues in vegetables and it was found that diazinon residues is the most predominant, followed by chlorpyrifos, malathion, dimethoate and at least was pirimifos-methyl. Maximum value for diazinon was recorded in the case of cabbage (0.016 mg/kg) and the minimum value was found in the case of lettuce (0.004 mg/kg). Chlorpyrifos achieved maximum value of 0.055 mg/kg in onion and the minimum in the case of tomato (0.007 mg/kg). The highest malathion concentration was in tomato (0.038 mg/kg) and minimum was found in lettuce (0.003 mg/kg). For dimethoate and pirimifos-methyl the maximum levels were detected in lettuce and tomato as 0.021 mg/kg and 0.017 mg/kg. In all cases, recorded values were below maximum residue levels.

A similar study concerning organophosphate pesticides in fruits was conducted by Anwar et al. [32]. The study indicated the presence of dimethoate, chlorpyrifos, methyl parathion in apples, banana, grapes, pear, guava and pear, but found concentrations were undetectable or below maximum residue level.

IV.3. Carbamates

a) General aspects

Carbamates are derivatives of carbamic, tiocarbamic and ditiocarbamic acids.

carbamic acid tiocarbamic acid ditiocarbamic acid

Fig. 4. Structural formula of carbamic, tiocarbamic and ditiocarbamic acids

Dithiocarbamates are a group of organosulphur compounds characterized by broad-spectrum of activity against various plant pathogens [33]. It can be categorized into thiourams (Thiram, Methiram, Disulfiram),

dimethyldithiocarbamates (Ferbam, Ziram), unsaturates alkylthiocarbamates (Mancozeb, Maneb, Nabam, Zineb) [34]. They are used to prevent fungal plant diseases mainly in ornamental flowers coniferous plants and vegetables [34].

b) Toxicity

Carbamates are less toxic to humans, but some there are some concerns regarding potential effects of some carbamates on immune and central nervous system. A beneficial aspect regarding this category is that they rarely bioaccumulate or cause major environmental impacts.

Dithiocarbamate fungicides are very attractive for agricultural purposes due to their effectiveness and relatively low toxicity to animals [14]. The main concern is related to their environmental breakdown products, in particular ethylenethiourea and propylenethiourea that can cause tumors in thyroid, neuropathological effects and are suspected to be carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic [14, 35, 36].

c) Carbamate and dithiocarbamate residues in various products

Caldas et al. [37] analyzed food samples (papaya, banana, apple, strawberry, orange, potato, tomato, rice and dry beans) collected from local market (Brazil) with the aim to analyze dithiocarbamate content. It was found detectable levels of pesticide (≥ 0.10 mg/kg CS₂) in 60.8% samples, the highest contents (up to 3.8 mg/kg CS₂) being encountered in the case of strawberry, papaya and banana but there is no hazardous potential for human health.

Other study conducted in Spain [38] concerning dithiocarbamate content in different types of fruits (apples, grapes, strawberries) indicated the presence of ethylenebis(dithiocarbamates) and propylenebis(dithiocarbamates) and in 6% from samples, their contents exceeded maximum residue limits.

IV.4. Pyrethroids

a) General aspects

Pyrethroids were developed as a synthetic version of the naturally occurring pesticide pyrethrin, which is found in chrysanthemums (these species have the best insecticide properties) and are often applied against household pests. On the basis of symptoms of poisoning in mammals and insects, pyrethroids can be classified into two main groups [39] as it is presented in table 1.

Table 1

Pyrethroid classification		
Types	Type I	Type II
Structural characteristics	do not contain cyano group fenvalerate	
	Examples	permethrin allethrin tetramethrin d-phenothrin
Poisoning signs	tremor hyperexcitation ataxia convulsions paralysis (T syndrome)	hypersalivation hyperexcitation ataxia convulsions paralysis (CS syndrome)
Antidote	there is no specific antidote available	

b) Toxicity

These types of compounds are not easily taken up by the roots of plants because they bind to the soil. Because of this, pyrethroids usually do not get into groundwater and do not contaminate drinking water supplies.

Pyrethroids are less toxic to mammals, fish and bees but some synthetic pyrethroids are toxic to the nervous system [39]. The synthetic pyrethroids possess remarkable knock-down insecticidal properties and have retained some of the chemical properties that made the pyrethrins virtually non toxic to mammals [40].

The number of pyrethrin poisoning incidents in children is increasing and due to their widespread use, children have been subjects of exposure to several pyrethroid pesticides [41].

Concerning their effects on human health, there is no evidence that cause birth defects in humans and do not cause cancer in people.

c) Pyrethroid residues in various products

A survey on "market basket" developed by Bempah et al. [31] had the aim to evaluate pyrethroid residues in fruits and vegetables. The results indicated that among various pyrethroid pesticides, permethrin, cyfluthrin and cypermethrin were the most predominant, followed by fenvalerate and deltamethrin. Maximum level of permethrin (0.041 mg/kg) was found in the case of pineapple and the minimum (0.006 mg/kg) was found in pear. Cyfluthrin was

found as highest value of 0.035 mg/kg in watermelon (exceed the maximum residue level of 0.02 mg/kg) and the lowest (0.004 mg/kg) was encountered in pear. Cypermethrin was found as maxim value in papaya samples (0.035 mg/kg), meanwhile the minimum concentration was found in mango samples (0.008 mg/kg).

In the case of vegetables, maximum values of 0.049 mg/kg and 0.016 mg/kg were found for permethrin and cyfluthrin.

A study developed by Anwar et al [32] indicated the presence of cypermethrin in different types of fruits (apples, banana, grapes, pear, guava and pear) and in the case of apple was found a concentration (0.94 mg/kg) that exceeds maximum residue level (0.7 mg/kg).

V. Methods for pesticide and pesticide residues quantification

Various methods have been developed for the analysis of pesticides and their potential degradation products in environmental samples and in foodstuff. The analytical methods for the determination of pesticides depend on of the matrix complexity origin and of the chemical classes. In products of biological origin were mostly analyzed four main groups of pesticides, namely organochlorine pesticides, organophosphorus pesticides, carbamates and pyrethroids.

The *extraction methods* are an important aspect of the pesticides analysis and depend of sample origins. The procedure consists in selected organic solvent if the extraction technique is

direct solid-liquid extraction (SLE) or liquid-liquid extraction (LLE). Solvent mixtures was used in the case of pesticide multi-compounds and have to be able to extract pesticides and pesticide residues with a wide range of polarities from the same matrix and the extraction requires different solvent systems according to compounds polarity. The EU recommended a recovery rates between 70 and 120%. For organochlorine pesticides the classic extraction method especially on animal matrix is Soxhlet [42].

In the last decade was reported for solid sample in pesticides extraction two more new methods pesticide supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) and accelerated solvent extraction (ASE). Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) has also been tested for both organochlorine pesticides (OCP) and organophosphorus pesticides (OPP) extractions. Matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD) has been applied to the extraction of both OCP and OPP residues and combines sample homogenisation, disruption, extraction, fractionation, and cleanup within a single process [43]. In separation and determination of the pesticides, *gas chromatography* (GC) is the most used method and *liquid chromatography* (LC) is also used for measuring levels of some pesticide and residues of pesticides in foods. Analytical methods for quality control and bioanalysis of pesticides and metabolites in biological matrices were elaborated. Multi-residue methods including GC-mass spectroscopy (MS) have been developed for the routine analysis of pesticides from different classes, including OCPs, OPPs, pyrethroid pesticides (PYRs), triazines (TRZs), and their degradation products, in composite foods. The dithiocarbamate (DTC) fungicide residues in foodstuffs were determinate by photometric carbon-disulfide (CS₂) methods after acid digestion of DTC or by GC or LC combined with MS. DTCs rapidly degrade and will decompose into carbon disulfide (CS₂) and the respective amine under acid digestion. The DTC-residue analysis consist in collecting evolving CS₂ and a direct consequence is that maximum residue limits (MRLs) are specified as mg CS₂/kg food [33, 44]. GC is combined with different kinds of detection methods, mainly depending on the class of pesticides to be quantified. Electron capture detection (ECD) has usually been employed for OCPs and PYR analyses. structures in aqueous and solid environmental samples as well as in foods of vegetable origin.

Electrolytic conductivity detection (ELCD) after GC separation has also been proposed for the detection of several pesticide residues including OCPs, PYRs, TRZs, and carbamates. A number of different selective detectors can be coupled with GC for analyzing OCPs, including halogen specific detector (XSD) or Hall detector and atomic emission detector (AED) [45].

Both flame photometric detection (FPD) with phosphorus filter and nitrogen-phosphorus detection (NPD) have been used for OPP detection.

In tree leaves organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) were determined by GC and electron capture detection (GC-ECD) after a microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) followed by solid-phase extraction (SPE) clean-up. Analytical recoveries obtained were ca. 100% for all the studied pesticides with this method.

MS method has been described as an important tool for the structural elucidation and quantification of metabolites and transformation products of pesticides in foodstuffs. The use of MS/MS may overcome the problems arising from chromatographic interference that occurred with GC-ECD and consequently provide better sensitivity for the determination of OCPs [42, 46]. Gas chromatography coupled to high-resolution time-of flight mass spectrometry (GC-HR-TOF-MS) is a new analytical technique with high sensitivity and accurate-mass measurements. GC-TOF-MS it is one of the most promising techniques to investigate the presence of organic compounds in different fields [47]. Carbamate pesticides including DTCs were successfully separated and quantified using micellar electrokinetic chromatography (MEKC) and ion-exchange chromatography (IEC) follows by UV detection.

Liquid chromatography (LC) has been used for the analysis for which GC conditions were not suitable, mainly carbamates and their metabolites and degradation products. LC has also been combined with conventional detectors such as fluorescence or UV detectors for identifying and quantifying pesticide residues. LC has been coupled with different kinds of MS detectors, including single quadrupole, ion trap, tandem-MS, and time-of-flight-mass spectroscopy (TOF-MS) in order to determine pesticide residue levels and/or to elucidate their

More selective techniques for the analysis of DTCs include various HPLC approaches. Reversed phase chromatography (RP-HPLC) and

ion-pair chromatography (IPC) followed by UV detection for the analysis of Thiram Dibam, Ferbam, Metam-sodium, Ziram, Mancozeb, Zineb, and Propineb or with chemiluminescence detection for the separation of Mancozeb and Propineb. The compounds were analyzed in plants, soil and foods. Fortification experiments of Ziram, Zineb and Propineb in diverse crops at 0.2, 1.0, and 3.0 ppm (w/w) resulted in recoveries of 93–120% and for Thiram in the presence of Ziram in the same concentration range resulted in lower values of 78.5–91.2% [48].

RP-HPLC interfaced to MS via atmospheric pressure chemical ionisation (APCI) and electrospray ionisation (ESI) was applied to the analysis of Thiram, Disulfiram, Dazomet (3,5 dimethyl-1,3,5-thiadiazinane-2-thione), ethylenethiourea (ETU), and propylenethiourea (PTU) in fruits and vegetables. Thiram and degradation of DTCs as ETU and PTU in fruits and vegetable was analyzed in normal phase liquid chromatography (NP-HPLC) and UV detection. HPLC methods for the determination of pesticide residues in juice and wine could employ UV absorption, UV diode array, fluorescence (FL) and chemiluminescence (CL) detection [48, 49]. New methods to detect carbamates and phenylurea pesticide residues in fruit juices was developed using solid-phase microextraction (SPME) coupled with liquid chromatography–single quadrupole mass spectrometry (LC/MS) and liquid chromatography–quadrupole ion trap mass spectrometry (LC/QIT-MS) [50].

The simultaneous determination of two herbicides (glyphosate GLYP and glufosinate GLUF) and their metabolites aminomethylphosphonic acid and methylphosphinicopropionic acid) was quantification by applying *capillary electrophoresis* (CE) combined with mass spectrometry (MS) and dimethyl-, diethyl-, butyl, octyl-, and pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (PDTC) coupled with diode-array detection (DAD) [51]. The analysis of DTCs was developed by a *biosensor* based on aldehyde dehydrogenase inhibition, a biosensor is an analytical device which converts a biological response into an electrical signal. The limit of detection (LOD) for Maneb was found in the lower ppb level.

Chromatographic determination of heavy metals using diverse DTCs as chelating agent is an indirect method of pesticide analysis. The method was applied to soil and water samples.

Immunoassay (IA) provides rapid, sensitive and cost effective analysis for a variety of pesticide residues but only one compound at a time can be determined. An enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used to directly determine carbaryl, metolcarb and residual imidacloprid in fruit juices [49].

VI. Conclusions

Pesticides have largely benefited the human life through enhancement of agricultural products but in turn have influenced human health. The potential health impact of using the aforementioned huge amounts has merit increasing concerns in the public opinion.

To minimize the problems related to health and environment due to pesticide application, it is recommendable to encourage the transformation from chemical based farming practices to environmental friendly alternatives. Also, it is proper to organize special training programmes for farmers, operators and consumers and to monitor permanently the use of pesticides and their residues in food products according to actual legislation.

References

1. Parron, T., Requena, M., Hernandez, A.F., Alarcon, R.: *Environmental exposure to pesticides and cancer risk in multiple human organ system*. In: Toxicology Letters, 2013, DOI:10.1016/j.toxlet.2013.11.009, in press.
2. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Pesticide Market Estimates: 2006-2007. Office of Pesticide Programs, Washington DC. 2011. Available from: http://www.epa.gov/opp00001/pestsales/07pestsales/table_of_contents2007.htm.
3. Aktar, M.W., Sengupta, D., Chowdhury, A.: *Impact of pesticides use in agriculture: their benefits and hazards*. In: Interdisciplinary Toxicology, 2009, vol. 2(1), 2009, p. 1-12.
4. Miller, G.T.: *Living in the environment*, 12th Ed. Belmont, Wadsworth/Thomson Learning, 2002.
5. FAO/ECE. 1991. Legislation and Measures for the Solving of Environmental Problems Resulting from Agricultural Practices.
6. Mostafalou, S., Abdollahi, M.: *Pesticides and human chronic diseases: evidences, mechanisms and perspectives*. In: Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology, vol. 268, 2013, p.157-177.
7. George, J., Shukla, Y.: *Pesticides and cancer: insights into toxicoproteomic-based findings*. In:

- Journal of Proteomics, vol. 74, 2011, p. 2713-2722.
8. Thongprakaisang, S., Thiantanawat, A., Rangkadilok, N., Suriyo, T., Satayavivad, J.: *Glyphosate induces human breast cancer cells growth via estrogen receptors*. In: Food and Chemical Toxicology, vol. 59, 2013, p. 129-136.
 9. Council Directive 91/414/CEE of July 1991 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market.
 10. Commission Regulation (EC) 149/2008 setting maximum residue levels for products.
 11. Zaganas, I., Kapetanaki, S., Mastorodemos, V., Kanavouras, K., Colosio, C., Wilks, M.F., Tsatsakis, A.M.: *Linking pesticide exposure and dementia: What is the evidence?* In: Toxicology, vol. 307, 2013, p. 3-11.
 12. Cockburn M., Mills P., Zhang X., Zadnick J., Goldberg D., Ritz B.: In: *Prostate cancer and ambient pesticide exposure in agriculturally intensive areas in California*. In: American Journal Epidemiology, vol. 173, 2011, p. 1280-1288.
 13. Koutros S., Beane Freeman L.E., Berndt S.I., Andreotti G., Lubin J.H., Sandler D.P., Hoppin J.A., Yu K., Li Q., Burdette L.A., Yuenger J., Yeager M., Alavanja M.C.: *Pesticide use modifies the association between genetic variants on chromosome 8q24 and prostate cancer*. In: Cancer Research, vol. 70, 2010, p. 9224-9233.
 14. Manahan, S.E.: *Toxicological chemistry and biochemistry*, third edition, Lewis Publishers, 2003.
 15. Mitra, A., Chatterjee, C., Mandal, F.B.: *Synthetic chemical pesticides and their effects on birds*. In: Research Journal of Environmental Toxicology, vol. 5, 2011, p. 1-16.
 16. Wong, M.H., Leung, A.O.W., Chan, J.K.Y., Choi, M.P.K.: *A review on the usage of POP pesticides in China, with emphasis on DDT loadings in human milk*. In: Chemosphere, vol. 60, 2005, p. 740-752.
 17. Tordoir, W.F., Van Sittert, N.J.: *Organochlorines*. In: Toxicology, vol. 91, 1994, p. 51-57.
 18. Tren, R.: *DDT and malaria prevention*. In: Environmental Health Perspectives, vol. 118(1), 2010, A14-A15.
 19. Jaga, K., Dharmani, C.: *Global surveillance of DDT and DDE levels in human tissues*. In: International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health, vol. 16, 2003, p. 7-20.
 20. Darko, G., Acquah, S.O.: *Levels of organochlorine pesticides residues in dairy products in Kumasi, Ghana*. In: Chemosphere, vol. 71, 2008, p. 294-298.
 21. Salem, N.M., Ahmad, R., Estaitieh, H.: *Organochlorine pesticide residues in dairy products in Jordan*. In: Chemosphere, vol. 77, 2009, p. 673-678.
 22. Bempah, C.K., Donkor, A., Yeboah, P.O., Dubey, B., Osei-Fosu, P.: *A preliminary assessment of consumer's exposure to organochlorine pesticides in fruits and vegetables and the potential health risk in Accra Metropolis, Ghana*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 128, 2011, p. 1058-1065.
 23. Bempah, C.K., Buah-Kwofie, A., Enimil, E., Blewu, B., Agyei-Martey, G.: *Residues of organochlorine pesticides in vegetables marketer in Greater Accra Region of Ghana*. Food Control, vol. 25, 2012, p. 537-542.
 24. Panseri, S., Catalano, A., Giorgi, A., Arioli, F., Procopio, A., Britti, D., Chiesa, L.M.: *Occurrence of pesticide residues in Italian honey from different areas in relation to its potential contamination sources*. In: Food Control, vol. 38, 2014, p. 150-156.
 25. Terry Jr., A.V.: *Functional consequences of repeated organophosphate exposure: potential non-cholinergic mechanisms*. In: Pharmacology & Therapeutics, vol. 134, 2012, p. 355-365.
 26. Kavvalakis, M.P., Tsatsakis, A.M.: *The atlas of dialkylphosphonates; assessment of cumulative human organophosphorus pesticides' exposure*. In: Forensic Science International, vol. 218, 2012, p. 111-122.
 27. Munoz-Quezada, M.T., Lucero, B.A., Barr, D.B., Steenland, K., Levy, K., Ryan, P.B., Iglesias, V., Alvarado, S., Concha, C., Rojas, E., Vega, C.: *Neurodevelopmental effects in children associated with exposure to organophosphate pesticides: a systematic review*. In: NeuroToxicology, vol. 39, 2013, p. 158-168.
 28. Mota, L.C., Hernandez, J.P., Baldwin, W.S.: *Constitutive Androgen Receptor-Null Mice Are Sensitive to the Toxic Effects of Parathion: Association with Reduced Cytochrome P450-Mediated Parathion Metabolism*. In: Drug Metabolism and Disposition, 2010, vol. 38, p. 1582-1588.
 29. Alavanja M., Hoppin J, Kamel F: *Health effects of chronic pesticide exposure: cancer and neurotoxicity*. In: Annual Review of Public Health, 2004, vol. 25, p. 155-197.
 30. Freed, V.H., Haque, R., Schmedding, R., Kohnert, R.: *Physicochemical properties of some organophosphates in relation to their chronic*

- toxicity. In: Environmental Health Perspectives, vol. 13, 1976, p. 77-81.
31. Bempah, C.K., Asomaning, J., Boateng, J.: *Market basket survey for some pesticides residues in fruits and vegetables from Ghana*. In: Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology and Food Sciences, vol. 2(3), 2012, p. 850-871.
32. Anwar, T., Ahmad, I., Tahir, S.: *Determination of pesticide residues in fruits of Nawabsaha District, Sindh, Pakistan*. In: Pakistan Journal of Botany, vol. 43(2), 2011, p. 1133-1139.
33. Crnogorac, G., Schwack W.: *Residue analysis of dithiocarbamate fungicides*. In: Trends in Analytical Chemistry, 28(1), 2009, p. 40-50.
34. Liesivouri, J., Savolainen, K.: *Dithiocarbamates*. In: Toxicology, vol. 91, 1994, p. 37-42.
35. Vettorazzi, G., Almeida, W.F., Burin, G.J., Jaeger, R.B., Puga, F.R., Rahde, A.F., Reyes, F.G., Chvartsman, S.: *International safety assessment of pesticides: dithiocarbamate pesticides, ETU and PTU-a review and update*. In: Teratogenesis, Carcinogenesis and Mutagenesis, vol. 15, 1995, p. 313-317.
36. Kazos, E.A., Stalikas, C.D., Nanos, C.G., Konidari, C.N.: *Determination of dithiocarbamate fungicide propineb and its main metabolite propylenethiourea in airborne samples*. In: Chemosphere, vol. 68(11), 2007, p. 2104-2110.
37. Caldas, E.D., Miranda, M.C.C., Conceicao, M.H., De Souza, L.C.K.R: *Dithiocarbamate residues in Brazilian food and the potential risk for consumers*. In: Food and Chemical Toxicology, vol. 42, 2004, p. 1877-1883.
38. Lopez-Fernandez, O., Rial-Otero, R., Gonzalez-Barreiro, C., Simal-Gandara, J.: *Surveillance of fungicidal dithiocarbamate residues in fruits and vegetables*. Food Chemistry, vol. 134, 2012, p. 366-374.
39. He, F.: *Synthetic pyrethroids*. In: Toxicology, vol. 91, 1994, p. 43-49.
40. Jett, D.A.: *Neurotoxic pesticides and neurologic effects*. In: Neurologic Clinics, vol. 29, 2011, p. 667-677.
41. Morgan M.K., Sheldon L.S., Croghan C.W., Jones A.P., Chuang J., Wilson N.: *An observational study of 127 preschool children at their homes and daycare centers in Ohio: environmental pathways to cis- and trans-permethrin exposure*. In: Environmental Research, vol. 104(2), 2007, p. 266-274.
42. Le Doux, M.: *Analytical methods applied to the determination of pesticide residues in foods of animal origin. A review of the past two decades*. In: Journal of Chromatography A, vol. 1218, 2011, p. 1021-1036.
43. Pareja, L., Fernández-Alba, A.R., Cesio, V., Heinzen, H.: *Analytical methods for pesticide residues in rice*. In: Trends in Analytical Chemistry, vol. 30(2), 2011, p. 270-291.
44. Rao, L. J., Verma, N.: *Spectrophotometric determination of zinc bis-ethylenedithiocarbamate (zineb)*. In: Talanta, 36(10), 1989, p. 1041-1043.
45. Chung, S., Chen, B.: *Determination of organochlorine pesticide residues in fatty foods: A critical review on the analytical methods and their testing capabilities*. In: Journal of Chromatography A, vol. 1218, 2011, p. 5555-5567.
46. Barriada-Pereira, M., González-Castro, M.J., Muniategui-Lorenzo, S., López-Mahía, P., Prada-Rodriguez, D., Fernández-Fernández, E.: *Determination of 21 organochlorine pesticides in tree leaves using solid-phase extraction clean-up cartridges*. In: Journal of Chromatography A, vol. 1061, 2004, p. 133-139.
47. Hernández, F., Portolés, T., Pitarch, E., López, F.: *Gas chromatography coupled to high-resolution time-of-flight mass spectrometry to analyze trace-level organic compounds in the environment, food safety and toxicology*. In: Trends in Analytical Chemistry, vol. 30(2), 2011, p. 388-400.
48. Szolar, O.H.J.: *Environmental and pharmaceutical analysis of dithiocarbamates*. In: Analytica Chimica Acta, vol. 582, 2007, p. 191-200.
49. Jin, B., Xie, L., Guo, Y., Pang, G.: *Multi-residue detection of pesticides in juice and fruit wine: A review of extraction and detection methods*. In: Food Research International, vol. 46, 2012, p. 399-409.
50. Sagratini, G., Manes, J., Giardiná, D., Damiani, P., Picó, Y.: *Analysis of carbamate and phenylurea pesticide residues in fruit juices by solid-phase microextraction and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry*. Journal of Chromatography A, vol. 1147, 2007, p. 135-143.
51. Goodwin, L., Startin, J., Keely, B., Goodall, D.: *Analysis of glyphosate and glufosinate by capillary electrophoresis- mass spectrometry utilising a sheathless microelectrospray interface*. In: Journal of Chromatography A, vol. 1004, 2003, p. 107-119.

DO YOUNG PEOPLE UNDERSTAND THE INFORMATION ON FOOD LABELING?

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Abstract: *This article presents instruments for researching the understanding of information on food labels from young people. It is developed an inquiry, which contains 14 questions, separated conditionally in three groups. Through them we search the answers of the following questions: a) Do the young people use the information on the labels? b) Do they know the basic nutrients, which are marked on food labels? c) Do they understand the information on food labels?*

The first results show that the developed inquiry is hopeful instrument for researching the knowledge of young people about the information on food labels. This gives us grounds to continue the researches, which refer to obtaining reliable and objective results.

Keywords: *understanding, food labeling.*

1. Introduction

In the recent years there is an increase in scientific knowledge of the relation between nutrition and health. With regard to the actuality of wholesome food's problem The World's Health Organization took preventive measures, which should help people by the selection of food products. One of the precautions is to place necessary information about food products and soft drinks through appropriate labeling and indication of the energy and nutrient content.

In this order it is included the adoption of enactments in European Union, which refer the labeling of food products and soft drinks. They collate all regulations about labeling, which give the consumer the possibility to take informed and conscious choice, consistent with their view of rational and healthy eating.

One of the enactments is Regulation № 1169/2011, which gives information about food products to the consumers, was adopted from the European Commission to raise awareness of consumers by their selection of food products. This Regulation leads in obligatory information about the nutrient content, on purpose to help consumers by selection of food products, consistent with their personal preferences or requirements about the regimen of diet.

Mandatory nutrition information includes:

- energy;
- fats - of which saturates;

- carbohydrates - of which sugars;
- protein;
- sodium.

Where appropriate in close proximity to the nutrition declaration, a statement indicating that the salt content is exclusively due to the presence of naturally contained in food sodium.

The nutritive value may be supplemented with an indication of the quantities of one or more of the following substances:

- monounsaturated fatty acids;
- polyunsaturated fatty acids;
- polyols;
- starch;
- fiber;
- vitamins or minerals

The motivation of young people to be interested in the information on the food product's labels, to read it and understand it is of the day and in relation with the necessity of health feeding. There have been a researches, connected with this whether the consumers read the food labels, what kind of difficulties do they meet and what kind of information do they keep abreast of [1].

For the future life of young people, the middle school should enable them to live and act adequately in the contemporary, with information entrusted society, to handle the dynamic everyday life problems [1, 2]. The understanding of the information on the food product's labels depends on the preliminary knowledge and

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attempts of young people. This means, that they must be prepared for the type of information on the labels, what does it mean, how to make use of it and practically to make their realized choice.

The preparation of these skills by the young people can be possible, if the teachers are prepared for achieving of these aims. Furthermore, we regard that this has a decisive meaning, because the use of various didactic means, methods and strategies can help this process.

In this connection, we set aims to develop an instrument for researching the understanding of the information on labels by young people.

2. Instruments for researching the understanding of the information on labels by young people

Consumer's knowledge about the information given on food labels, cause:

1. Knowledge for the existence of information.
2. Knowledge for basic products (nutrients).
3. Understanding the information.

For researching the knowledge of young people to read and understand the information on food and drink labels, it is developed inquiry, which is anonym and does not contain identifiable information. The selection of instruments for the research is connected with the following privileges: 1) The inquiry used from us gives the possibility for implementing research in short time, with no need of previous preparation of the respondents. 2) It gives the opportunity to analyze the examinees problem through the relation between knowledge of young people for the labeling of food products and middle school education.

The inquiry is shown Application 1. The questions in it can conditionally be separated in three groups.

First group questions – they relate to the knowledge for existence of information on food labels. They give the opportunity to receive information about the habits of young people to

The material is developed in relation with a project NUTRILAB (NUTRitional LABELing study in black sea region countries).

read information on food labels, the decisive factor by the purchase

The *second group refers* to the knowledge for basic food products (nutrients). In this group the questions refer to the basic nutrients, which are necessary for the person to ensure his energy, constructing and regulative necessities and which are mark off on food labels. The nutrients are separated in six groups – proteins, fats, carbohydrates, mineral substances, vitamins, water.

The *third group refers* to the correct understanding of the information on labels. The question in this group causes the respondents to apply scientific knowledge in current situations.

3. Conclusion

The inquiry is developed and tested in small group of people in real conditions and after qualitative and quantitative analysis there are placed in necessary corrections, thus it is formed the final version.

The first results show that the developed inquiry is hopeful instrument for researching the knowledge of young people about the information on food labels. This gives us grounds to continue the researches, which refer to obtaining reliable and objective results.

References

1. Delvina Gorton. Nutrition labelling -Update of scientific evidence on consumer use and understanding of nutrition labels and claims. New Zealand, 2007.
2. Millar R., J. Osborne. Beyond 2000: Science education for the future. The report of a seminar series funded by the Nuffield Foundation, 1998.
3. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development: The Definition and Selection of Key Competencies. OECD, Executive summary, (2005).

Application 1

Survey: *Understanding the information on food labeling*

1	In your opinion, have an impact on human food you eat?	Definitely, yes	
		Not always	
		I'm not sure	
		Definitely, no	
2	When you buy food you always read what is written on the label?	Yes	
		Not always	
		No	
3	Are you having difficulties in reading food labels?	Yes , always	
		sometimes	
		No, never	
4	What difficulties most often you meet when reading labels food?	the text size	
		bar code symbols	
		E-th	
		the amount of information	
5.	Which of the following factors influenced the purchase of food?	Information about nutrients	
		The price of the product	
		с р о к њ т н а г о д н о с т н а п р о д у к т а	
		Fat content	
		Salt content	
		Carbohydrate content	
6	What does the "energy 626 6 kG/150 kcal" for 100g product?	Energy content	
		Heat quantity	
		Caloricity	
		I don't know	
7	Do you use low calorie products?	Yes, always	
		Sometimes	
		No, never	
8	Product that is marked "energy value" 179 kJ / 40 kcal per 100 g is:	Low-calorie	
		High-calorie	
		I don't know	
9	Do you read what is the noted fat content on food labels?	Yes , always	
		sometimes	
		No, never	

10	For a food to be indicated on the label that contains fat with a high content of saturated fatty acids, it must be:	Animal product – like meat and milk products	
		Vegetable and plant oil	
		I'm not sure	
11	For a food to be indicated on the label that contains fat with a high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids, it must be:	Plant origin	
		Animal origin;	
		I'm not sure	
12	For food to not content cholesterol on the label should be noted that it contains:	Plant oil	
		Animal fat	
		None	
13.	If the label of food product is noted that contains protein in an amount of greater or equal to 10g per 100g of it is:	High-protein	
		Low-protein	
		I don't know	
14	Meaning " carbohydrates" on food labels means only the contents of plain sugar.	Definitely, yes	
		I'm not sure'	
		Definitely , no	

RESEARCH ON OPTIMISING THE PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY OF ICE WINE AT THE TÂRNAVE VINEYARD, JIDVEI WINE CENTRE

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Abstract: *The production of ice wine at the Târnavă vineyard, Jidvei wine centre has been an experiment for us, and the first step was to overripe a hectare of vines of the Traminer grape variety in 2011, which was pursued to determine the optimal time for grape harvest, and its wine production under the best conditions throughout the whole technological process, in order to obtain a semi-flavoured high quality ice wine. We note it without surprise that the wine producer has developed a true art throughout history in choosing the perfect location for growing different varieties of vines. This has been accomplished by combining the perfect soil and climatic conditions with an optimal effect on certain grape varieties. "Ice Wine" (ice wine in English or Eiswein in German) is a special potion that is particularly expensive, it is produced with great care and only in certain circumstances, and it is a dessert wine varietal that originates from Germany for over 200 years ago. The grapes used to produce these true works in the art of wine making (Traminer) are usually left on the vine – sometimes till the end of December or even January – in order to achieve high levels of sugar concentration before freezing from the low temperature of that time of year. Traminer is a grape variety of a noble vine with medium-sized clusters of about 60-80 g that has pearly pink, tiny and round berries, which taste of rose petal jelly. Traminer wine is a very personal, ample, smooth wine, and particularly with a specific cachet that suggests a "freshly mown hay". It is considered to be an aromatic wine that suggests the aroma of rose, and it is greatly appreciated on the international market.*

Keywords: *Traminer, ice wine, maturation, grape processing, technology, flavour*

1. Introduction

The reason for approaching this topic is the high favourability for producing quality wines at the Târnavă vineyard proven by scientific data, and the meritorious results obtained at international competitions.

To obtain semisweet white ice wines, the grapes are picked when overripe, and those vine varieties are used that accumulate large amounts of carbohydrates when mature (over 200g/l). Quality white wines with sugar content (semidry, semisweet and sweet) are produced in strictly limited viticultural areas where the highly favourable pedoclimatic conditions for vines are capitalised through certain grape varieties with a high biological potential for sugar accumulation in the grape berries (Aldea Aurelia, Ana Ileana Popa, 2006). Wines with natural residual sugar are products of high class as they are particularly appreciated even by consumers of the most refined tastes and demands.

The technology of producing semisweet wines is based on the same technological schemes that are used to produce quality dry white wines with

some specific technological peculiarities determined by: determining the optimal time for grape harvest; processing over-mature grapes; processing musts rich in sugars; cessation of alcoholic fermentation to preserve the sugars in the wine.

2. Materials and methods

Determining the optimal time for grape harvest

The Traminer grape variety for ice wines is harvested when over-mature, and the harvest of this grape variety must be done in 2-3 days after several days of frost, after reaching temperatures below -7 °C and a sugar content of >300 g/l in the grapes, which is required for the type of wine to be made, and to facilitate obtaining a high aromatic potential. Harvesting was carried out manually when the grapes were covered by a thin layer of ice, and the grapes that become pink in colour when mature are harvested particularly in early morning or in the evening when the temperatures are negative.

Processing over-mature grapes

Over-mature grapes are very rich in oxidase enzymes (polyphenol oxidase, laccase). As a result, the antioxidant protection of grapes and grape mashes must be performed with high doses of SO₂:60-80 mg/kg in healthy grapes.

The qualitative and quantitative reception consists of:

- checking the state of health and the grape variety of each shipment received.
- checking the sugar content, and determining the total acidity of the must when filling each must container of the same grape variety.

Unloading grapes

The unloading of the grapes received into the wine press is carried out immediately. To avoid oxidation, the protection of grapes is carried out by sulphitation with sulphur dioxide (Cotea V, 1985): 60-80 mg/kg of grapes in the case of healthy grapes, and 120-150 mg/kg of grapes in the case of grapes attacked by rot. Sulphitation is done with an aqueous solution of sulphur dioxide in a concentration of 5-6%.

Crushing grapes – is the operation of breaking the skin of grape berries in order to facilitate the flow of the must (Pomohaci, N., V. Stoian, M. Gheorghiuță, V. Cotea, I. Nămoșanu, 2005). The work is executed with the help of crushers.

Separating the free-run must

The free-run must is the fraction of the highest quality that is free flowing by gravity, and due to the high proportion of raisined berries this operation is rather cumbersome.

In such situations, the best must flows slowly, thus more is obtained by pressing instead of free flowing (Tita Ovidiu, 2001).

Enzymatic treatment of the grape mash

It improves the performance of certain technological operations and processes, the extraction and settling of the must, the clarification, extraction and stabilisation of the colour, the extraction and release of varietal aromas with pectolytic enzymes, such as Ultrazim Premium, which is a pectolytic preparation with a polygalacturonase activity essential for hydrolysing pectins, and it is administered directly in the wine press in doses

of 1-5 g/100 kg; The operation of maceration lasts for 12 hours at a temperature of 10-12 °C, and 2 g/hl of Zimaskin is used for the extraction of aromas.

The methods used to clarify the must are:

Clarification of the must with the help of enzymes, by cold and decanting

Alcoholic fermentation

The fermentation of the must was carried out in vats kept at a constant temperature.

The alcoholic fermentation is performed with selected yeasts; Oenoferm® PinoType is *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast strain 99/3, and it is an excellent yeast that promotes and emphasises the typical modern profile of the grape variety in doses of 20-30 g/hl; for the rapid onset of fermentation the leaven is poured into the fermentation vats at the surface of the must, which is characterised by a slow fermentation and a high power to produce alcohol.

Stopping alcoholic fermentation

The technological processes to stop the alcoholic fermentation are the following:

Racking the wine off the yeast lees during the alcoholic fermentation while sheltered from air to impoverish the yeast in it by cooling it to 5-6 °C (heat shock), followed by a sulphitation of 150 mg/l SO₂ and a bentonite addition of 100-150 g/hl.

Maturation – is the technological stage where the wine develops its quality characteristics and gains a lasting clarity, colour, stability, and it receives a new qualitative characteristic, the “maturing bouquet”, in vats at 9-14 °C, (Cotea V. et al., 1988)

3. Results and discussions

Table 1. Grape sugar content and total acidity of the Traminer to obtain ice wine in year 2011

GRAPE VARIETY	COMPLETE MATURITY		HARVEST 29 - 30.11.2011	
	Sugar g/L	Acidity g/L H ₂ SO ₄	Sugar g/L	Acidity g/L H ₂ SO ₄
Traminer	175	6.3	302	3.03

To facilitate the separation of the must and pressing the grape pomace the following was used: The use of pectolytic enzymes, such as Ultrazim Premium in doses of 1-5g/hL of grape mash.

Table 2. Evolution of grape maturation of the Traminer grape variety at the Jidvei wine centre (2011)

Traminer			
Date	Sugars g/l	Total acidity g/l	Weight of 100 berries g/l
25-Aug	117	8.0	164
31-Aug	127	7.2	172
5-Sep	139	6.7	180
9-Sep	153	6.3	187
14-Sep	168	5.9	191
19-Sep	178	5.4	194
26-Sep	200	5.1	197
1-Oct	214	4.8	196
5-Oct	221	4.6	195
10-Oct	238	4.4	186
15-Oct	260	4.1	160
20-Oct	274	3.7	153
27-Oct	292	3.18	130
5-Nov	294	3.10	117
16-Nov	298	3.03	100
29-Nov	298	3.02	100

In table 2. the maturation process of the Traminer grape variety in 2011 can be seen, which was performed by taking samples of the grapes at the onset of ripening from 25 August to harvest on 29 November when the grapes accumulated 298 g/l sugar with an acidity of 3.02 g/l tartaric acid while the weight of 100 berries dropped to 100 g.

Table 3. Physico-chemical properties of the wine yeast after it is racked off the yeast

Traminer 2011	
Alcohol content by volume %	14.9
Total acidity g/l H ₂ SO ₄	5.45
Volatile acidity g/l CH ₃ -COOH	0.38
Sugar g/l	40.3
Free SO ₂ mg/l	46
Total SO ₂ mg/l	252

Table 4. Organoleptic properties

Organoleptic properties	Traminer semisweet white wine
Appearance	clear
Colour	amber
Aroma	characteristic
Taste	pleasant

The stabilisation operation causes a reduction in the total acidity, a slight increase in acetaldehyde, a darkening in colour and an improvement in the organoleptic properties.

The free sulphur dioxide content of 46 mg/l provided a good antioxidant and biological

protection for the wine during the stabilisation operation.

Wine bottling – bottles are filled at the optimal time determined by the technological age and the organoleptic development of the wine. This point is reached after a period of maturation in the vats.

Table 5. The physico-chemical analysis of the product after bottling are the following:

Physico-chemical properties of the wine after bottling

TRAMINER - WINE 2011	
Alcohol content by volume	14.8
Total acidity g/l H ₂ SO ₄	5.39
Volatile acidity g/l CH ₃ -COOH	0.35
Sugar g/l	40.3
Free SO ₂ mg/l	14
Total SO ₂ mg/l	252
Extract g/l	23.3

Identification of terpene compounds

Among the many factors that contribute to the typicality and quality of a wine, the most important organoleptic property is its aroma (I. Buia, 2001), see Table 6.

The aroma of the wine is composed of hundreds of volatile compounds of different

chemical origin and nature (SANCHEZ - PALOMO et al., 2007).

The volatile compounds derived from grapes vary by grape variety, but also by the cultural and climatic factors. Both the free compounds and the glycolytic forms of the varietal compounds are accumulated in the grapes during maturation (BAYOVONE,1993)

Table 6. Identification of terpene compounds

Sample	Identified compound	Concentration (µg/l)
Traminer 2011	Ethyl butyrate	9874.2
	2-Methyl-1-butanol + 3-Methyl-1-butanol	4447.8
	1-Hexanol	ID
	Ethyl octanoate	10625
	2-Phenylethanol	44.1
	Linalool	35661
	Terpineol	15442
	Ethyl acetate	100024
	Isoamyl acetate	25558
	Heptanoic acid	36647
	Dodecanoic acid	36668.2

Of all the compounds identified, phenylethanol, ethyl octanoate and isoamyl acetate are the most potent aromatisers. The compound responsible for the nuances of coriander and orange blossom is linalool, and for the nuances of lilac is α -terpineol.

Final description of the product

The wine bottled immediately after conditioning presents a harmony between the components, a favourable report regarding the free and total sulphur dioxide content. Also, the

wine presents organoleptic properties specific to the grape variety, from which it descends (Arina Oana Antocea 2005).

The young wine is of yellow-greenish colour, it has a slightly pronounced fragrance, a floral aroma that gives it a personality, a taste full of flavour and elegance, subtle and persistent, it is a balanced wine with a high alcoholic strength (14.8% ABV), the acidity gives it a touch of liveliness, it is savory wine, sweet, liqueury and it has a wildflower honey aroma.

4. Conclusions

- During over-maturation the concentration of sugars reaches high values in the Traminer grape variety (302 g/l sugar).
- The decrease in acidity occurs gradually, faster in the first 2-3 weeks after ripening, and somewhat slower later.
- The quality of a wine largely depends also on the acidic content of the grapes.
- The weight of berries had an average growth rate, and it decreased towards harvest (Ecaterina Popa, 1967).
- Seeding the must with the selected yeasts is a technological measure required for the smooth conduct of alcoholic fermentation, and to ensure the quality of the wines.
- The fermentation process depends on a number of factors: the temperature, the degree of clarity of the must, the sugar content of the must, the nature of the yeast strains, the volume of the must, and the degree of sulphitation (Tița Ovidiu, 2004).
- To stop the fermentation the following is done: racking the wine off the lees while cooling it to 5-6 °C, followed by a sulphitation of 150 mg/l SO₂ and bentonite addition.
- Wines are stored until stabilisation and bottling. The maturation period is 6-12 months, and it takes place in vats; the wine storage temperature is 9-14 °C.
- The complex conditioning of the wine ensures its good stability.
- Bottling the new product is done when the wine it begins to gain the characteristic of an old wine but not in all of its qualities by evolving in the vat.
- Bottling with a 6-12 months maturation in vats and then in bottles preserves the best the characters and personality of the grape variety through the smoothness of the lightly aromatic taste of a particular specialty.
- By comparing the quantitative and qualitative indicators of the finished product with those of the raw material provides the possibility of a strict control over the production process.
- The physico-chemical analysis and the sensory analysis of the wines showed that in grape processing the must obtained at once goes under sulphitation until the concentration level reaches minimum 15 to 25 mg/l of free SO₂, the racking process after the termination of the alcoholic fermentation, followed by a maturation, lead to obtaining the right products and of outstanding sensory attributes (Țârdea C., 2007).
- We have obtained a new series product of a high cost, with new organoleptic properties in an original packaging.

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5. Reference

1. Aldea Aurelia, Ana Ileana Popa, 2006 – Oferte tehnologice de realizare a vinurilor albe cu denumire de origine controlată din

soiuri semiaromate, în Podgoria Târnavă [Technological choices in making white wines of protected designation of origin of semi-flavoured grape varieties at the Târnavă vineyard], Annals ICVV, Volume XVIII, 235.

2. Arina Oana Antocea, 2005 – Condiționarea, ambalarea și etichetarea vinurilor [Conditioning, packaging and labelling wines], Bucharest, Romania: Editura Ceres
3. Bayonove, C., 1993 – Les composés terpéniques. In: Les acquisitions récentes en cromatographie du vin. Applications á l'analyse sensorielle des vins, 99 - 119, Paris, France: Lavoisier
4. Buia I., 2001 – Contribuții la studiul compușilor de aromă din vinurile albe de Târnave. [Contributions to the study of aroma compounds of the Târnave white wines], PhD thesis, Cluj-Napoca, Romania: Babeș-Bolyai University
5. Cotea V., 1985 – Tratat de oenologie, vol. I. [Treaty on Oenology], Bucharest, Romania: Editura Ceres
6. Cotea V. et al., 1988 – Tratat de oenologie, vol. II. [Treaty on Oenology], Bucharest, Romania: Editura Ceres
7. Cotea V. D., Constantin C. Grigorescu, N. Barbu, 2000 – Podgoriile și Vinurile României [The vineyards and wines of Romania], Bucharest, Romania: Editura Academiei Române.
8. Popa Ecaterina, 1967 – Stabilirea momentului optim de recoltare a strugurilor în podgoria Târnave [Determining the optimal time for grape harvest at the Târnave vineyard], Buletin Tehnic
9. Pomohaci N., V. Stoian, M. Gheorghită, V. Cotea, I. Nămolosu, 2005 – Prelucrarea strugurilor și producerea vinurilor [Grape processing and wine production], Bucharest, Romania: Editura Ceres
10. Sanchez Palomo, E., M. C. Diaz-Maroto, M. A. Gonzales Vinas, A. Soriano Perez, M. S. Perez-Coello, 2007 – Aroma profile of wines from Albillo and Muscat grape varieties at different stages of ripening, Food control 18, 398-403.
11. Țârdea C., 2007 – Chimia și analiza vinului [The chemistry and analysis of wine], Iași, Romania: Editura "Ion Ionescu de la Brad"
12. Țârdea C., Sârbu Gh., Țârdea Angela, 2010 – Tratat de vinificație [Treaty on winemaking], Iași, Romania: Editura "Ion Ionescu de la Brad"
13. Țița Ovidiu, 2001 – Tehnologia, Utilajul și Controlul calitatii produselor în ind. Vinului [The technology, equipment and quality control of the products in wine industry], Sibiu, Romania: Editura Universității Lucian Blaga
14. Țița Ovidiu, 2004 – Tehnologiile de obținere a vinurilor [Winemaking technologies], Sibiu, Romania: Editura Universității Lucian Blaga.

THE PHENOLIC CONTENT OF RED WINES FROM TÂRNAVE VINEYARD, IN 2010-2011-2012

C. MĂRGINEAN, C. TANA, O. TIȚA, A. TIȚA

Abstract: Red wines have a structure more complex than white wines because of phenolic compounds, which gives them a ruby-red color, softness, astringent taste, extractivity (corpulence), physico-chemical stability and long storage. Phenolic compounds can be found in both the white wines and red wines, their concentration in the red be at least four times higher than in white wine (Muntean V., 2013). The amount of phenolic compounds depends by the variety, annual climatic condition, soil and agrotechnical factors. Phenolic compounds participate at the color formation, taste and aroma of red wines. In the vinification process of grape we extract only a small part of phenol compounds (30-50%), which depending on the degree of maturity of the grapes and the must during the process of soaking the marcs (Vinson, 1995). The study was conducted over the three years (2010-2011-2012), on four types of red wine (Pinot Noir, Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and Sirah), obtained in Târnavă vineyard. This wine region is part of the Transylvania Plateau, located in the catchment area of the two rivers, Târnavă Mică and Târnavă Mare, being the largest vineyard from North of Transylvania and the Carpathian ecosystem. Holds an area of over 2300 hectares of vines, producing white and red grape. It should be noted that Sirah wine has been studied only in 2011 and 2012, because in 2010 there were wines made from this grape variety, the area is very low in that year.

Keywords: Pinot Noir, Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot, Sirah, red wine, phenolic compounds.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wine is a complex physicochemical, balanced drink that changes in an ongoing and regular basis. To certify the quality of a wine using a complex of different items such as specification of the place of origin, variety, agricultural technique and maximum yield per hectare, its technology and adherence to limits of composition and harmony relationships between components. Outlining criteria for quality wine relate to organoleptic the grapes from which are taken with relative yields in the composition of musts and wines, during the pulp processing and during the maceration. During the maceration, in addition to coloring, marcs again yields wine and other substances, such as those tannins, aromatic, nitrogen, pectin and minerals. Their presence in certain proportions make red wines to be different by white wines, not only in terms of color, but also in terms of astringent flavor and extract (Mărginean C., 2012). Phenolic compounds also come from the wood (oak) used to maturation and aging of wine (Popa., 2008). The color of wine is influenced by many factors such as variety, vintage

characteristics and compositional concern, physico-chemical and biological stability, naturalness and integrity, origin and authenticity, presentation and submission of consumer sale (Stoian V., 2006). Equally important are the gusto-olfactory qualities of the wine, its physico-chemical analyzes and other complex analysis (the content of polyphenols). The color of the wine is an important indicator of quality. It characterizes the variety, type, composition and age of wine (Tița O., 2001). Phenolic compounds found in the seeds and peel year, soil conditions, the degree of maturation of the grapes, their health, the size of production, vinification technology, age, storage conditions, etc.. Grape maturation is influenced by climatic conditions, so that the quality of raw materials for wine varies from year to year (Țârdea Constantin, 2000). The ripening of the grapes varieties studied is achieved in a period of 35-55 days from the entry into firstfruits until full maturity. Colors may be more intense or paler. The color of wine is determined by the nature of the phenolic (anthocyanins, tannins, flavones). Among the phenolic compounds in red wines there are: gallic

acid, catechin, syringic acid, vanillic acid, epicatechin, p-coumaric acid, rutin and quercetin.

Gallic acid is free in nature and is in the form of derivatives of the tannins. It is a solid substance, smooth appearance, it is highly soluble in cold water but dissolved at hot. It is soluble in alcohol and it has astringent tastes. Gallic acid has antifungal and antiviral properties, cytotoxic activity on tumor cells, without affecting healthy ones and is used to treat diabetes.

Catechins are a class of organic compounds, which exist in the tannins composition. It is a substance capable of polyphenolic antioxidant properties. Reduce the risk of four common diseases: stroke, myocardial disease, cancer and diabetes. Catechin tannins in acid and hot environment turns anthocyanins (cyanidin), hence the name assigned proanthocyanidins from the grape tannins. As catechins, they are colorless, but differs from them in that transformation enhances anthocyanin color of young red wines. Proanthocyanidins are responsible for the astringency of the wines (Arnold et al., 1980), play an important role in browning reactions and oxidation (Cheyner et al., 1991) and red wine color stability (Singleton et al., 1992). Where there is a condensation of catechins and proanthocyanidins advanced, the resulting compounds are called flobafene. They are colored red brown, bitter taste and bitterness that appears likely to wines made from grapes processed in continuous media, which crushes too solid parts of the grape, is due precisely to these substances (Cotea, 1985).

Syringic acid is a color component that is not present in the white wine.

Vanillic acid is a derivate used as a flavoring agent. Acid is a protective antioxidant and anticancer effect against chronic and degenerative diseases, among which obesity, diabetes, hypertension, atherosclerosis, and joints and nervous system disorders.

Epicatechin is an antioxidant that may reduce the risk of developing serious illnesses such as heart or heart failure.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The analyzes which we make on the four types of red wines were made using a high performance liquid chromatograph HPLC SURVEYOR PLUS, equipped with a PDA detector, Thermo Plus Detector and column chromatography-Accuare

P-coumaric acid presents antimicrobial action and anti-inflammatory detoxification.

Rutin is a flavonoid that helps block potentially harmful enzymes involved in blood clotting. It is a powerful antioxidant with many benefits on the human body. Main features are: strengthening the cardiovascular system, helps blood circulation and increase the flexibility of blood vessels. Significantly, affect the capillaries under the skin and decreases their fragility, accelerates healing of various injuries such as muscle sprains, crushing, pressure sores, scars, bumps and other similar problems.

Resveratrol accumulates in grain husks during training in response to the fungus *Botrytis cinerea* attack and drops abruptly at the entrance grapes ripen, the maximum accumulation is after 1-5 weeks of flowering vines. By maceration - fermentation process, resveratrol passes from skins of the grapes into wine. Geographical area and variety are influencing resveratrol content from the wine. Red wine is promoted since ancient times as a good medicine for the body in general and the cardiovascular system in particular. Resveratrol is a powerful antioxidant from wine, which is believed to be responsible for the beneficial effects of red wine. It is an ingredient of many herbal products for treatment of blood disorders, heart or liver. Today, resveratrol is considered by scholars promoted a strong antioxidant, anticancer and a phytoestrogen. Resveratrol is a miraculous ingredient in red wine, it can extend life, has anti-aging powers and the ability to fight cancer, heart disease and obesity. It also lowers cholesterol, blood sugar level, blood thinners, prevents colds and improve brain capacity (memory).

Quercetin is a flavonoid very studied, with anticancer and antioxidant properties. It has anti-inflammatory powerful, protects the lens and controls diabetes.

FFP. However, there is a data acquisition and processing software. The device is non-destructive for the sample, running with low noise and is stable in a long time of operation, and the answer is independent of the mobile phase composition, flow rate and temperature. Wine sample must be filtered, then fed into the machine, which renders

the results in few seconds. Expression results are in mg/l.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following table is about the analysis of the four types of red wines obtained at

Târnave vineyard, during the three years (2010-2011-2012).

Table 1. The content of phenolic compounds (mg/l) for red wines in the 2010-2011-2012

	Gallic acid	Catechin	Siringic acid	Vanilic acid	Epicatechin	p-cumaric acid	Rutin	Resveratrol	Quercitin
Pinot noir 2010	6.440	2.516	0.253	<0.1	1.569	<0.1	0.289	<0.1	0.151
Pinot noir 2011	6.652	2.407	<0.1	<0.1	1.748	<0.1	0.298	<0.1	0.238
Pinot noir 2012	<0.1	0.342	0.126	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	1.804	<0.1	7,263
Cab.Sv. 2010	3.728	6.849	<0.1	<0.1	0.560	<0.1	1.516	<0.1	0.59
Cab.Sv. 2011	4.855	11.772	1.840	<0.1	8.398	<0.1	0.69	<0.1	0.643
Cab.Sv. 2012	1.531	5.496	0.164	<0.1	4.655	<0.1	0.367	<0.1	0.693
Merlot 2010	6.485	0.768	0.660	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.277	<0.1	0.122
Merlot 2011	6.112	1.003	0.531	<0.1	0.693	<0.1	0.391	<0.1	0.176
Merlot 2012	6,524	0,999	0,688	<0,1	0,701	<0,1	0,402	<0,1	0,142
Sirah 2011	<0,1	0,27	<0,1	<0,1	0,743	<0,1	0,201	<0,1	0,154
Sirah 2012	<0,1	0,29	<0,1	<0,1	0,749	<0,1	0,211	<0,1	0,160

4. CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the amount of phenolic compounds we can say that red grape varieties studied recovered quite well the climatic conditions of vineyard Târnave, in particular temperature and insolation, thus obtaining red wines rich in phenolic compounds, which provides a characteristic color wines. Also, the analysis of these types of red wines studied are in normal limits.

Wines made from grapes harvested at the highest phenolic maturity has a big content of phenolic compounds and are the most popular in terms of sensory quality was considered wine (Rădulescu A., 2011). The quality of red wines is given by their composition, which depends not

only on the quality of the raw material, but also on de vinification type.

The study is valuable for fundamental research, the data obtained can be benchmarks for new experiments or to establish efficient processing conditions in the wine industry to achieve quality finished products in accordance with modern quality standards. Interpretation of results in terms of technology indicated that the Târnave vineyard can produce quality red wines, that are typical of the variety show typicity balanced taste, because the harmony of chemical composition parameters. The wine industry in our country, the main task is to define the most rational technologies for producing high quality wines in large blends, homogeneous and stable physical, chemical and

microbiological, able to satisfy increasingly consumer demands.

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REFERENCES

1. Muntean Vasile, Industrial Microbiology, Cluj University Press, Cluj-Napoca, 2013
2. Cotea V.D., Treaty of winemaking, Vol. I: Winemaking and wine biochemistry, Ceres, Bucharest, 1985
3. Mărginean C., Tana C., Tița O., Maturation of red grapes (Cabernet Sauvignon and Pinot noir) from Târnavă vineyard in 2010 and 2011, The Agri-Food Sciences, Processes and Technologies Conference, Sibiu, 2012
4. Popa Aurel, The secret of good wine, Alma Publishing House, Craiova, 2008
5. Rădulescu Axenia, Research on optimization technology of red wines from Drăgășani vineyard, PhD Thesis, "Lucian Blaga" University, Sibiu, 2011
6. Stoian Viorel , The great book of tasting wines, Artprint Publishing House, Bucharest, 2006
7. Tița Ovidiu, Manual of quality analysis and control technology in the wine industry, "Lucian Blaga" University, Sibiu, 2001
8. Țârdea C., Sârbu Gh., Țârdea Angela , The wine Treaty, "Ion Ionescu de la Brad" Publishing, Iași, 2000

COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF QUALITY OF MILK AND VEGETABLE MINCE WITH BUTTERMILK CONCENTRATE

T. Yudina * I. Nazarenko **

Abstract: *Quality of milk and vegetable minces with buttermilk concentrate is evaluated by organoleptic, physicochemical, microbiologic, and structural-mechanical properties and their nutrition value taking into account their importance at using them. The result verifies high quality of minces in comparison with mince of low-fat acid curd cheese mince.*

Keywords: *comprehensive quality indicator, nutrition value, structural-mechanical properties, microbiologic properties.*

Health of the population depends on nutrition. This fact is proved by numerous researches and practical experience. According to WHO, health depends by 50% on life style, the most important part of which is nutrition.

Unfortunately, modern level of nutrition is unsatisfactory both qualitative, and quantitative relation. The reason for this is lack of native proteins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamins, macro- and micro-nutrients, and dietary fibres [1]. Lack of nutrients leads to reduction in immunity towards diseases and unfavourable environmental factors.

One of the ways to provide an optimal balance of nutritives is combining of different types of raw materials with certain functional and technological properties. Thus, combination of milk and vegetable raw materials gives the possibility to get food with high content of animal protein, rich in bioactive compounds. As well, it gives the chance to use raw materials rationally [2].

We developed milk and vegetable mince production technology. The designed technology proposes to use milk and protein concentrate with buttermilk as the main component. Also, mince recipes should include mashed carrot, pumpkin and zucchini, egg mixture, wheat flour, and sugar.

Evaluation of the designed milk and vegetable minces is of current interest as one of the main tasks of modern society is providing quality food raw material and food products, including culinary goods. Evaluation of quality should be made on the basis of different properties of various types which characterise the product, namely - nutrition value, structural-

mechanical, organoleptic, physicochemical, and microbiologic properties.

Today, the most popular method of quality determination is combination of properties which influence its ability to satisfy established and forecast requirements [3]. The issues of quality evaluation of food are the topics of research for native and foreign scientists: Dorokhovich, A.M., Korolkova, E.P., Matiukhina, Z.P., Nesterenko, A.A., Ratushnyi, A.S., Topolnik, V.G., J.R. Brunner, H. Mulder, P. Walstra and others.

As the quality of the designed minces is characterised by a number of parameters, the purpose of the work was determining a comprehensive quality indicator using theoretical background of qualimetry [4].

The paper [4] offers the algorithm of determining of comprehensive quality indicator of culinary goods which consists of several stages.

First, there was developed a hierarchical structure of comprehensive properties which are required for proper evaluation of milk and vegetable minces quality, and which concern stages of production and storage. During production, quality of the goods is determined by nutrition value, structural-mechanical, organoleptic, physicochemical, and microbiologic properties. During storage, the quality of minces is determined by structural-mechanical, organoleptic, and microbiologic properties.

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Nutritional value is characterised by proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. Structural-mechanical properties are represented by border shift stress and viscosity. Organoleptic properties are represented by outer appearance, colour, smell, taste, and texture. Physicochemical properties include titrated and active acidity. Microbiologic properties include quantitative characteristic of yeast, mold, coliform bacteria, and pathogenic microorganisms. Properties that were included into the above mentioned groups were measured and used as singular indicators of quality. Evaluation of singular quality indicators of the designed minces (studied sample No.1 - milk and carrot mince, No. 2 - milk and pumpkin mince, No. 3 - milk and zucchini mince, No. 4 (reference [5]) – mince of low-fat acid curd cheese mince) were carried using Harrington desirability function:

$$K_i = \exp[-\exp(-Y_i)], \quad (1)$$

Where Y_i - coded identification of adjustable scale.

Coded and respective absolute values of properties indices are located on X-axis, and relative values are located on Y-axis. Harrington scale implies 5 intervals in, total interval of the

scale is from 1 to 0: 1.00...0.80 - very good (perfect); 0.80...0.63 - good; 0.63...0.37 - satisfactory; 0.37...0.20 - bad; 0.20...0.00 - very bad. Harrington desirability function has the following useful and important properties: monotone, continuity, smoothness, adequacy, effectiveness and statistical sensitivity. On the following stage, we determined possible interval for change of each of simple quality indicators in terms of allowable values of indicators $P_{ij}^{allowable}$, which are minimum according to the requirements of documentary standards, desired reference value P_{ij}^{ref} - the best values among similar objects in the world practice, and faulty indicator value P_{ij}^{faulty} . Note that if the values are lower than faulty, it is impossible to turn production into condition allowed under documentary standard.

To calculate $P_{allowable}$, we considered the values given in the documentary standard – DSTU 4554:2006 “Acid curd cheese” and values of the known sample – “Milk and protein products of buttermilk” TOR U 40-01566330.094-2000, “Milk and protein minces” TOR U 15.5-01566330-161-2004. Specific values of reference, allowable and faulty indicators are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Critical limits of mince quality indicators

Indicator	Units of measurement	Reference indicator	Allowable indicator value	Faulty indicator value
Nutrition value				
Protein content	%	25	14	10
Fats content	%	0	6	8
Carbohydrates content	%	20	11	8
Vitamins content	%	0,025	0,010	0,005
Minerals content	%	1,5	0,6	0,3
Structural-mechanical properties				
Shift stress	Pa	700	1900	2300
Effective viscosity	Pa*s	21	6	3
Organoleptic properties				
Outer appearance	grade	50	30	20
Colour	grade	50	30	20
Smell	grade	50	30	20
Taste	grade	50	30	20
Texture	grade	50	30	20
Physicochemical properties				
Titrated acidity	°T	60	180	220
Active acidity	%	4,8	4,0	3,7
Microbiologic properties				
Yeast	CFU/G	$0,5 \times 10^2$	10^2	5×10^2
Microscopic fungi	CFU/G	$0,5 \times 10^2$	5×10^2	10^2

Values of Table 1 were considered during evaluation of the designed goods. Evaluation of the reference (P_{ij}^{ref}), allowable ($P_{ij}^{allowable}$) and

faulty P_{ij}^{faulty} indicator values under adjustable Harrington scale will be equal to 1.00 ($Y_{ij}^{ref}=+3$); 0.37 ($Y_{ij}^{allowable}=0.0$); 0.20 ($Y_{ij}^{faulty}=-0.5$)

respectively. Indicator values between 1.00 and 0.37 were chosen in terms of providing steadiness of the scale as well as practical and logical reasoning.

Absolute quality indicators nodal values scale if designed in terms of data from Table 1 and is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Nodal values scale of mince quality indicators

Indicator	Units of measurement	Evaluation, Ki					
		1,00	0,80	0,63	0,37	0,20	0,00
		Coded identification Y					
		3,00	1,50	0,85	0,00	-0,50	-3,00
Nutrition value							
Protein content	%	25	21	18	14	10	5
Fats content	%	0	2	4	6	8	10
Carbohydrates content	%	20	17	14	11	8	5
Vitamins content	%	0,025	0,020	0,015	0,010	0,005	0
Minerals content	%	1,5	1,2	0,9	0,6	0,3	0
Structural-mechanical properties							
Shift stress	Pa	700	1100	1500	1900	2300	2700
Effective viscosity	Pa*s	21	16	11	6	3	0
Organoleptic properties							
Outer appearance	grade	50	45	40	30	20	10
Colour	grade	50	45	40	30	20	10
Smell	grade	50	45	40	30	20	10
Taste	grade	50	45	40	30	20	10
Texture	grade	50	45	40	30	20	10
Physicochemical properties							
Titrated acidity	°T	60	100	140	180	220	260
Active acidity	%	4,8	4,6	4,3	4,0	3,7	3,5
Microbiologic properties							
Yeast	CFU/G	0,5×10	1×10	0,5×10 ²	10 ²	5×10 ²	10 ³
Microscopic fungi	CFU/G	0,5×10	2×10	3×10	5×10	10 ²	10 ³

Relative values of singular quality indicators K_{ij} were determined using chart method using curves (Figure 1) and in terms of absolute quality indicators nodal values (Table 2).

The received results of quality evaluation calculation K_i of certain properties of calculations are shown in Table 3.

Average-weighted arithmetic value was used to calculate a comprehensive evaluation of quality indicators of j-group:

$$K_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} K_{ij} \cdot m_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

Where K_{ij} - is evaluation of a singular indicator;

m_{ij} - ratio of indicator's weight;

n - quantity of indicators considered in j-

Where m_{ijcp} - is arithmetic average of expert evaluations of quality i -value of j-group.

group.

Weight ratios were determined using expert method:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_{ij} = 1, \quad (3)$$

Where m_{ij} - weight ratio of i -value of j-group ($m_i > 0$);

n - number of production quality indicators.

Weight ratio m_{ij} was calculated as follows:

$$m_{ij} = \frac{m_{ijcp}}{\sum_{i=1}^n m_{ijcp}}, \quad (4)$$

Table 3. Mince quality indicator

Indicator	Units of measurement	Absolute values, P_i				Relative value, K_i			
		Studied sample			Reference sample No. 4	Studied sample			Reference sample No. 4
		№1	№2	№3		№1	№2	№3	
Manufacturing									
Protein content	%	14,06	13,99	15,79	17,2	0,37	0,37	0,49	0,58
Fats content	%	1,82	1,81	1,80	1,00	0,82	0,82	0,82	0,9
Carbohydrates content	%	17,23	18,49	7,62	11,1	0,82	0,90	0,18	0,38
Vitamins content	%	0,015	0,023	0,015	0,002	0,64	0,93	0,64	0,09
Minerals content	%	0,830	0,825	1,400	0,486	0,57	0,57	0,93	0,31
Shift stress	Pa	744,1	947,0	801,05	1153	0,98	0,88	0,95	0,78
Effective viscosity	Pa*s	15,68	11,3	16,98	9,1	0,79	0,64	0,84	0,53
Outer appearance	grade	49	49	49	47	0,96	0,96	0,96	0,88
Colour	grade	49	50	50	44	0,96	1,00	1,00	0,77
Smell	grade	48	49	49	46	0,92	0,96	0,96	0,84
Taste	grade	48	49	50	46	0,92	0,96	1,00	0,84
Texture	grade	49	49	49	45	0,96	0,96	0,96	0,8
Titrated acidity	°T	65	72	69	67	0,98	0,94	0,95	0,97
Active acidity	%	4,68	4,50	4,61	4,74	0,88	0,75	0,81	0,94
Yeast	CFU/G	6	8	8	8	0,96	0,88	0,88	0,88
Microscopic fungi	CFU/G	7	5	7	7	0,97	1,00	0,97	0,97
Storage									
Outer appearance	grade	47	48	48	45	0,88	0,92	0,92	0,80
Colour	grade	49	49	49	44	0,96	0,96	0,96	0,77
Smell	grade	45	45	43	43	0,80	0,80	0,73	0,74
Taste	grade	45	46	44	44	0,80	0,84	0,77	0,77
Texture	grade	49	47	48	45	0,96	0,88	0,92	0,80
Shift stress	Pa	720	866,0	759,4	1110	0,99	0,92	0,97	0,80
Effective viscosity	Pa*s	12,02	9,7	16,04	19,63	0,67	0,56	0,80	0,95
Yeast	CFU/G	36	32	31	36	0,79	0,81	0,82	0,79
Microscopic fungi	CFU/G	29	28	34	30	0,70	0,71	0,64	0,69

Average value $m_{ijc p}$ was calculated as follows:

$$m_{ijcp} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{z=1}^N m_{ijz}, (z=1, 2, 3 \dots N) \quad (5)$$

Where N – is quantity of experts;
 m_{ijz} – is evaluation of quality i -value of j -group given by z -expert ($z = 1, 2, 3 \dots N$).

The results of weight ratio calculations are shown in Table 4.

Weight ratios of values properties' groups were chosen according to practical and logical reasoning on importance of this or that values for the studied products. At the production stage, they constitute: nutrition value - 0.25, structural-mechanical properties - 0.35, organoleptic properties - 0.15, physicochemical properties - 0.1, microbiological properties 0.15.

At the storage stage, they constitute: organoleptic

properties - 0.25, structural-mechanical properties - 0.35, microbiological properties - 0.40. Weight ratio for the production stage constitutes 0.6, for storage stage - 0.4.

In order to receive a comprehensive quality evaluation at the stage of production and storage, the following model was applied:

$$K_{e m} = (x_1 \wedge x_2) \sum_{j=1}^n M_j \cdot K_j, \quad (6)$$

Where $K_{e m}$ – is a comprehensive production quality evaluation at the stage of shelf life;

$x_1 \square x_2$ – is veto function made by quality indicators having alternative nature - coliforms and pathogenic microorganisms (when meeting the requirements x_1 and x_2 are equal 1, alternatively it equals 0);

M_j – is weight ration of indicators' j -group;

K_j – is group evaluation of indicators.

Table 4 Weight indicators (as of the data from the expert group)

Expert	Weight ratio											
	Manufacturing											
	Nutrition value					Structural-mechanical properties		Organoleptic properties				
	Protein content	Fats content	Carbohydrates content	Vitamins content	Minerals content	Shift stress	Effective viscosity	Outer appearance	Colour	Smell	Taste	Texture
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1	5	3	4	5	5	5	5	4	3	4	4	5
2	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	5
3	5	3	3	5	4	5	3	3	4	5	3	4
4	5	3	4	4	4	5	4	4	3	4	4	5
5	5	3	3	4	5	5	4	4	5	5	3	5
6	5	4	4	5	4	5	3	3	4	5	3	5
7	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	4
m_{ijc}	5,00	3,43	3,57	4,43	4,29	4,86	3,86	3,71	3,86	4,71	3,57	4,71
m_{ji}	0,241	0,166	0,172	0,214	0,207	0,557	0,443	0,181	0,188	0,229	0,174	0,228

Continued Table 4

Expert	Weight ratio												
	Manufacturing				Storage								
	Structural-mechanical properties		Microbiologic properties		Organoleptic properties					Structural-mechanical properties		Microbiologic properties	
	Titrated acidity	Active acidity	Yeast	Microscopic fungi	Outer appearance	Colour	Smell	Taste	Texture	Shift stress	Effective viscosity	Yeast	Microscopic fungi
1	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
1	4	4	4	5	4	3	4	4	5	5	5	4	5
2	5	4	5	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	4
3	4	3	5	5	3	4	5	3	4	5	5	5	4
4	5	4	5	4	4	3	4	4	5	5	4	5	4
5	5	4	5	4	5	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	4
6	4	5	4	5	3	4	5	3	5	5	4	4	5
7	5	4	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	5
m_{ijc}	4,57	4,00	4,71	4,57	3,86	3,71	4,71	3,57	4,71	5,00	4,43	4,71	4,43
m_{ji}	0,533	0,467	0,508	0,492	0,188	0,181	0,229	0,174	0,228	0,530	0,470	0,516	0,484

Weight ratios of values properties' groups were chosen according to practical and logical reasoning on importance of this or that values for the studied products.

At the production stage, they constitute: nutrition value - 0.25, structural- mechanical properties - 0.35, organoleptic properties - 0.15, physicochemical properties – 0.1,

microbiological properties 0.15.

At the storage stage, they constitute: organoleptic

properties - 0.25, structural-mechanical properties - 0.35, microbiological properties - 0.40.

Weight ratio for the production stage constitutes 0.6, for storage stage - 0.4.

In order to receive a comprehensive quality evaluation at the stage of production and storage, the following model was applied:

$$K_{e\ m} = (x_1 \wedge x_2) \sum_{j=1}^n M_j \cdot K_j, \quad (6)$$

Where $K_{e\ m}$ – is a comprehensive production quality evaluation at the stage of shelf life;

$x_1 \square x_2$ – is veto function made by quality indicators having alternative nature - coliforms

and pathogenic microorganisms (when meeting the requirements x_1 and x_2 are equal 1, alternatively it equals 0);

M_j – is weight ration of indicators' j-group;
 K_j – is group evaluation of indicators.

The received data of the comprehensive quality evaluation of milk and vegetable minces and control are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Mince quality evaluation

Samples	Groups										General
	Production stage						Storage stage				
	Nutrition value	structural-mechanical properties	Organoleptic properties	Physicochemical properties	Microbiologic properties	Comprehensive quality	Organoleptic properties	structural-mechanical properties	Microbiologic properties	Comprehensive quality	
Reference	0,438	0,669	0,825	0,956	0,924	0,702	0,776	0,870	0,742	0,79	0,739
Milk and carrot mince	0,621	0,896	0,944	0,933	0,965	0,849	0,881	0,840	0,746	0,81	0,834
Milk and pumpkin	0,697	0,774	0,968	0,851	0,939	0,816	0,877	0,751	0,762	0,78	0,804
Milk and zucchini	0,614	0,901	0,974	0,885	0,924	0,842	0,858	0,890	0,733	0,81	0,833

The analysis of the received data shows that the comprehensive quality indicator of milk and vegetable minces is higher than the results of the reference sample: milk and carrot mince – by 12.86%, milk and pumpkin mince – by 8.83%, milk and zucchini mince – by 12.71%.

High comprehensive qualitative indicator of milk and vegetable mince in comparison with the reference sample is determined by the evaluation of its quality both at the stage of production and storage.

For example, at the stage of production, the comprehensive evaluation of milk and carrot mince constitutes 0.849; milk and pumpkin mince - 0.816; milk and zucchini mince - 0.842. All these values are higher than those of the reference samples by 10.94%, 16.24% and 19.94% respectively.

High evaluation of milk and vegetable mince at the stage of production can be explained by the fact that minces have higher absolute values of indicators of the following groups: “nutrition value”, “structural and mechanical properties”, “organoleptic properties”, and “microbiologic properties”.

For example, milk and vegetable mince contain more nutritives which characterise “nutritional value” group than the reference sample; that is why the evaluation of this milk

and vegetable mince properties is higher than the evaluation of reference sample. It should be noted that the values of “structural and mechanical properties” group has better indicators for milk and vegetable minces, that is why their evaluation is higher than the evaluation of the reference sample.

According to Table 5, high quality evaluation at the stage of storage is characteristic for “organoleptic properties” and “microbiologic properties” groups, which also influences the comprehensive evaluation of mince quality.

Thus, comprehensive quality indicator of the designed milk and vegetable mince lies within the interval of “perfect quality”.

At the same time, the reference sample lies in the interval of “good quality”.

The determined comprehensive indicator verifies high quality of milk and vegetable minces and practicability of their use for manufacturing culinary products.

The perspective of the following researches in this direction is determining of economic effectiveness of using milk and vegetable minces in culinary production.

References

1. Romanovskaia, I. V. Development and research of technology of acid curd cheese and vegetable products with wheat germ flakes: Dissertation ... Candidate of Sciences: May 18, 2004, Kemerovo, 2005, 155 pgs.
2. Lipatov, N. N. Cumulative quality of milk industry technological processes and quantitative criteria of its evaluation / Lipatov, N. N., Sazhinov, S. Yu., Bashkirov, O. I. // Storage and processing of agricultural raw materials. – 2001. - No. 4. – S. 33-34.
3. Quality of products. Evaluation of quality. Terms and determining [Text]: DSTU 2925-94. – [as of January 01, 1996]. - Kyiv : State Committee of standardisation, metrology and certification of Ukraine, 1994. – 34 pgs. – (National standard of Ukraine).
4. Topolnik, V. G. Qualimetry in catering industry: monograph/ Topolnik, V. G., Ratushnyi, A. S.; Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after M. I. Tugan-Baranovsky Donetsk, 2008. – 243 pgs.
5. Recipe book of ethnic dishes and culinary products: for public catering enterprises of all proprietary types // Shalyminov, O. V., Diatchenko, T. P., Kravchenko, L. O., et. al. - Kyiv: A. S. K. Press, 2003. – 848 pgs

A STUDY IN BEER PASTEURIZATION WITH THE HELP OF MICROWAVES

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Abstract: *The use of the micro-wave-processing in order to pasteurize, sterilize, condition etc. food products is one of the most frequently studied a-thermal processes. Yet, its use is still considered quite controversial in many countries, especially in Europe. On the one hand, the insufficient development of microwave processing in an industrial context, and the sparse technological information available, on the other, account for this situation. It is not generally known that there is no real evidence of a link between the consumption of microwave processed food products and the incidence of different types of cancer or foetal malformations. Microwave processed food products do not become radioactive because of the pasteurization or sterilization amounts used in the food - processing industry.*

Keywords: *pasteurization, microwaves, electromagnetic radiation.*

1. General Considerations

Beer pasteurization within an electro-magnetic field is not brought about by the thermal effect or by the direct influence of the microwaves, on account of the fact that they are not endowed with a sufficient amount of energy, the micro-wave energy quantum with frequency of 2450 MHz being only $12.10/6$ Ev. Moreover, the beer pressure obtained by the pump of the micro-wave processing plant within the reactor's module must stay between 12-14 bar, otherwise carbon dioxide would not preserve its state of dissolution in the beer, and the thermal process of pasteurization would fail. Thus, within the micro - wave resonance chamber, atmospheric pressure is maintained. Beer pasteurization with the help of micro - waves, beer being a dielectric material, takes place as a consequence of the polarization effect of electro-magnetic radiation, an effect which can appear due to the structure of polar water molecules (beer consists of approximately 92 per cent water). The mechanism of dipolar polarization or the mechanism of orientation, manifesting itself in the frequency interval of micro - waves, is based on the rotation of the permanent dipoles within the electric field they are applied to. The heating of beer is brought about by absorbing of the microwave energy, by rotating the water molecules but also of the carbohydrates and proteins in beer, this energy being afterwards

transformed into heat. Thus, the warming up is instantaneous, fast and very effective, approximately 90 per cent of energy being saved.

The electric component of the micro-waves is the one that yields energy to the polar molecules so that they get aligned and then it loses that energy due to the thermal agitation of the molecules, this energy being equivalent to a rise of temperature. The complexity of the physical properties of food products and of the mechanism of interaction between the electro-magnetic field and food products turns the attempt to understand / clarify the process of heating within the microwave field into a real challenge for deep study if the implementation of this method in the industrial production context is targeted.

2. The principles of heat processing within the micro-wave field.

Heating with the help of micro-waves is a form of volume heating, thus it does not depend on the thermal conductivity of the food product, but it does depend on the depth of micro - wave penetration, therefore in the size of the food product in question. In the case of this type of heating, heat is transferred from the inside to the outside, as opposed to conventional heating, where heat is transferred the reverse way, as can be observed in figure 1.

Fig.1. Symbolic representation of conventional thermal transfer and with microwaves

The absorption of micro – waves by food- products manifests itself by the transformation of their electric energy by means of ionic conduction and dipole rotation.

This process is to be put down to the existence in the structure of food products, of beer, in our case, of free and bonded electric charges, apt to move under the influence of the electric field of the micro-waves. The free charges in beer consist of the ions of the mineral salts in beer, and the bonded ones, of the water molecules. It is the free charges that bring about the phenomenon of ionic conduction. Under the influence of the electric component of the micro – wave field, they move around and collide with the neutral, less mobile particles. Depending on the number and frequency of the encounter impacts, the micro – wave energy turns into weak and disorderly kinetic energies, which, added up, make up thermal energy, which partially remains stored in the product, depending

on the mass/weight thermal capacity, while the rest is spread in the surrounding area. Ionic conduction is only sparsely present in beer, on account of the fact that the number of ions is low, as they come only from the mineral salts present in water and very few from malt.

The bonded charges in beer are the water, carbohydrate and fat dipoles, which are all neutral. Under the influence of the electro-magnetic waves, these dipoles effect vibratory and spinning movements, thus generating an additional internal electric current.

The process by which food products absorb the micro – wave energy is called dielectric heating. The mechanism of dielectric heating is based on the fact that the water molecule is a dipole, i.e., it has a positive pole, represented by the hydrogen atoms, and a negative pole, represented by the oxygen atom (the bond between the atoms is polar covalent) (fig.2.).

Fig.2.The structure of the water molecule and its dipole moment

When the dipole is introduced into the microwave field, which rapidly changes its sense, the dipole

continuously attempts to get aligned to the electric field, thus changing its sense too.

This phenomenon is called rotation or polarization of the dipole. The dipole's change of sense comes about with a certain delay, as the molecules have to overcome the water's inertia and inter-molecular forces. The electric component of the microwave field yields energy to the water molecule, so that the latter can get aligned, then it loses energy on account of thermal agitation. This energy equates to a rise of temperature. Due to the microwaves' rapid change of sense, there emerge successive rotations of the dipoles that generate frictional heat at molecule level. When the applied field is

removed, the dipole molecules return to their initial equilibrium state. The energy transfer mechanism will be effective only if the time elapsed between two sense-changes is so short that the dipoles can hardly return to their initial state.

In the extremely short time interval when the electric field changes its sense, the water's dipoles are orientated in a disorderly way (as compared to their initial state), then they tend to get again aligned to the electric field, which brings about a certain degree of polarization.

Fig.3. The mechanism by which the microwaves' energy is transmitted to the water's dipoles.

The exchange of energy accumulated during the displacement and returned to the field while regaining the equilibrium state, accounts for the wave's propagation as an elastic phenomenon. This phenomenon does not exist in perfect dielectric bodies. The higher the frequency of the microwaves, the more intensely the dipoles will vibrate, which leads to a higher accumulation of heat. If frequency is too high, the dipoles will not move sufficiently between two field polarity inversions and the energy transfer will be low. If frequency is too low, the ratio of the dipoles' vibration will be reduced, and the energy transfer will be also low. The number of water molecules bonded by hydrogen bonds (very weak bonds) is very small at high temperatures, thus the dipoles' inertia is low. Yet, due to the fact that the microwaves' frequency is constant in time and lower than the optimal frequency to bring about effective energy transfer, it can be inferred that the more temperature rises, the lower the efficiency will be. The two phenomena, the dipole's rotation and ionic conduction, take place simultaneously.

The water percentage in beer is extremely high and that is the reason why it can be said that the interaction between beer and microwaves is essentially to be traced back to dipoles, whose vibration and rotation movements by and by transmit the energy of the electric component to the nearby dipoles, thus bringing about the heating up of beer. Considering the facts above, it can be inferred that the thermal treatment of food products with the help of microwaves is volume heating.

This phenomenon can be explained by the energy transfer mechanism as follows: the microwaves penetrating the food dielectric produce heat by dipole rotation and ionic conduction, which heat is then spread on the product's surface. For the above reason, the temperature on the dielectric's surface is will always be higher than that at the core. Therefore, the microwave treatment is also called cold pasteurization of food products. The heating process also depends on the microwaves' penetration depth, thus at a frequency of 915 MHz, microwaves penetrate 30 cm deep into the food – product, and at a frequency of 2450 MHz, 10 cm.

3. The effect of microwaves on beer

Regarding the possible effects of microwaves on beer, there have allegations about micro – waves taking deteriorative effects on beer, the same as on any other food product. Considering the relation for a photon's energy $E = h f$, it can be remarked that energy is in inverse ratio to wave length. Food – products absorb a large number of energy quanta. Opinions have been voiced that the

microwaves' intensity would induce modifications in the food – product, an allegation which is not supported by scientific evidence. Fact is that the energy quantum of microwaves with a frequency of 2450 MHz is so low, i.e., $1,2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (Ev) that it is not capable of breaking the bonds between the particles making up food – products.

Table 1. Energies ensuring the stability of chemical bonds

<i>Chemical bond</i>	<i>The bond's energy, in eV</i>
<i>H-OH, water with a polar covalent bond</i>	5,2
<i>H-CH₃, methane, with a non-polar covalent bond</i>	4,5
H-NH- CH₃, amino-acid (basic component of protein), with a non-polar covalent bond	4,0

On studying the values in the above table, it can be remarked that microwaves do not possess sufficient energy to affect or break and the bonds listed in table 1. For the waves to break the bonds simultaneously 105 energy quanta per second should be absorbed.

Calculation has proved that 5,2 $\cdot 10^{26}$ energy quanta/sec, distributed on 3 $\cdot 10^{24}$ molecules of $\frac{1}{2}$ kg of product, are absorbed in a time period of 1/170 s. For the same chemical bond to be affected, two energy quanta should be absorbed by the same atomic group, before the latter has reached thermal equilibrium, the time necessary for this process to take place being 10/6 s. To conclude, it is impossible for the microwave energy quanta to be transformed into heat, before the same molecule has absorbed another amount of energy quanta.

Therefore, microwaves do not possess sufficient energy to break the chemical bonds in the component molecules of the food product. In

addition, microwaves are not capable to stimulate certain chemical reactions by way of the free radicals (toxic components, accounting for the degeneration and aging processes).

Possible traces of O₃ detected during the running of microwave plants, appear to be the consequence of electric discharges or of soft X radiation passing over from the magnetron into the resonance chamber, where the product is placed. By no means is it the effect of the microwaves' interactions with the food – product.

4. Beer pasteurization with the help of the FlowSINTH plant

For the smooth run of our research in the field of beer pasteurization in the microwave field, with the help of the continuous flow plant FlowSINTH Milestone, it was considered necessary to draw up a program/schedule containing the stages to follow during the experiment.

Fig.4. Schedule for micro – wave pasteurization

The optimal variant for beer pasteurization in the microwave field is when the power – value is 800W (fig.4). This option can be explained by the fact that it ensures the best correlation between the piston pump discharge, the reactor’s volume and the dissipation of the heat inside the reactor of the FlowSINTH micro – wave – oven, produced by the power issued by the micro – wave generators.

This correlation ensures the lowest power consumption for the optimal pasteurization effect, i.e., for the organoleptic properties (color, taste, capacity for foam/froth formation) of the processed liquid product, namely, Ciucas beer to be preserved.

At power values of 700 W and 600 W, it can be remarked that power consumption rises, the more the magnetron power is reduced. This effect can be explained by the fact that by maintaining a

constant discharge, while the power issued decreases, the magnetrons have, in order to ensure the pasteurization temperature, to issue electro – magnetic waves at shorter intervals of time, which leads to power consumption increasing.

Therefore, in this case there is no correlation between the liquid discharge through the reactor, the reactor’s volume and the power issued by the magnetrons.

The final conclusion of this research in beer pasteurization in the micro – wave field is that working at a certain beer discharge, correlated with the reactor’s volume and the power issued by the magnetrons into the resonance chambers, the power consumption during the processing and, implicitly, the “consumption” of thermal energy will be low, while the organoleptic properties of the product are preserved (fig.5).

Fig.5. Experimental graphic at microwave pasteurization

5. Conclusions

The study of pasteurization of liquid foods with the help of micro – waves was made only under laboratory or pilot circumstances, and was not extended to an industrial production context, on account of the sparseness of information in the field, even if it could be proved that, by this application, energy can be saved, while the beer's organoleptic properties are preserved. Thermally treated beer with the help of micro – waves has a five times longer keeping time than classically pasteurized beer. Moreover, the microwave pasteurization plant can be completely automated, whereas it is possible to improve the classical pasteurization plant to obtain substantial cuts in power consumption but that comes with the price of greater complexity of the plant itself and of the

interdependence between the different material and power flows.

References

1. Banu C., ș.a., *Tratat de industrie alimentară, Probleme generale*, Editura ASAB, București, 2008.
2. Banu Constantin – *Progrese tehnice, tehnologice și științifice în industria alimentară*, vol. I, Editura Tehnică, București, 1992;
<http://www.chemlin.net/chemistry/photochemistry.html>
<http://ro.scribd.com/doc/60024539/Procesarea-cu-Microunde>
3. Giese, J., 1992 – *Advances in Microwave Food Processing*, Food Technology., nr 9, pg. 118-121
D. M. P. Mingos, D. R. Baghurst “*Applications of Microwave Dielectric Heating*

HPLC STUDIES ON OPTIMUM TECHNOLOGICAL CONDITIONS TO OBTAIN GARLIC POWDER, RICH IN ALLICIN, FROM GARLIC BULBS FOR PHYTOTHERAPIC PRODUCTS

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Abstract: This paper studies the optimum technological condition to obtain garlic powder with a high content in alliin for phytotherapeutic uses. The garlic bulbs were processed in different conditions both in laboratory and in production, with specialized equipment and all the samples were analyzed by HPLC. The conclusion of this study is that the fine grinding should be avoided, before the drying process, because it leads to favorable conditions for allinase enzyme to transform alliin into alliin, which is very unstable.

Keywords: garlic, alliin, phytotherapy.

1. Introduction

Originating from China, the garlic is a very well-known plant which has been used as spice and as medicine for thousands of years. Because of its high adaptability, garlic is now grown all over the world. Its many medicinal properties¹ (antibiotic, antiviral, antimycotic, antihypertensive, regulator of “bad” cholesterol (LDL), antitumor, antiplatelet, sustainer of the immune system, etc.) are attributed to the sulfur compounds. From these compounds numerous tests have shown that alliin has the highest medicinal activity. Alliin is a sulfoxide which is synthesized enzymatically from alliin by allinase enzyme, according to reaction 1².

2. Experimental research

The HPLC system used for alliin analysis is a Hitachi Elite LaChrom, equipped with an L-2130 pump, a thermo-controlled L-2200 Autosampler, L-2300 Column oven and a DAD UV-Vis L-2455 detector. The column used for alliin separation is C₁₈ silica Lichrospher® 100 RP-18 column (250×4mm i.d., 5μm particle size). The HPLC method can be found in European Pharmacopoeia, ALLII SATIVI BULBI PULVIS Monograph³ and is briefly the following: 0.8 mL/min flow of isocratic mobile phase -

Alliin and the enzyme allinase are situated in the garlic bulbs in different compartments and when the bulb is sliced, crushed or heated at a temperature higher than 65°C they come into contact and alliin is produced. The main problem with alliin is that it is very unstable and it transforms into other compounds (ajoenes, diallyl disulfide, diallyl trisulfide, etc.) which are volatile and/or have lower medicinal activity.

Knowing that alliin has the highest medicinal potency it is necessary to determine the optimum technological conditions of transforming fresh garlic bulbs into garlic powder to assure high alliin content and therefore high efficiency of phytotherapeutic products.

methanol: 1% formic acid, 60:40 (v/v), Butyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (BHB) as internal standard, 254 nm UV detection and 10 μL injection.

The garlic sample used for this analysis is dried powder.

Methanol HPLC grade was purchased from Merck, formic acid 99-100% was purchased from VWR and butyl-parahydroxybenzoate (BHB) 99% was purchased from Fluka. The water for formic acid solution came from a Millipore Ultrapure Water system. To obtain relevant results from our experiments only one type of

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garlic from a single source (from Botosani County) was used.

At the beginning of the experiment the fresh garlic bulb was processed in laboratory as follows: the garlic cloves were peeled, sliced (every clove in 4 or 5 pieces), dried in a stove (hot air oven) at 50°C until the weight of the cloves was 60-65% smaller and then they were grinded to a fine powder. The obtained garlic powder was analyzed by HPLC.

The next step was to use specialized industrial equipment to obtain dried garlic cloves for analysis (the grinding process to fine powder was made exclusively in laboratory). For this purpose we used 2 methods of processing garlic:

- 1) with a machine which transforms fresh garlic cloves into a paste (similar to a meat grinder machine);
- 2) with a plant cutting machine (with adjustable speed of blade and conveyer belt) which was adjusted to cut (chop) the garlic cloves into big pieces. The drying of the samples was made in an industrial hot air dryer, which blows air heated at 40°C. For comparison reasons we dried a part of

the garlic cloves obtained from the plant cutting machine in our laboratory stove at 50°C.

3. Results and discussions

Because alliin is very unstable (high reactivity) the use of alliin standard is not a good idea (very high price, must be kept at -80°C). That is why the European Pharmacopoeia uses butyl-parahydroxybenzoate (BHB) as internal standard, which does not interfere with garlic's native compounds.

As it was mentioned before only one type of garlic was used for this study which came from Botosani County. After it was processed in laboratory (described in Experimental part) and according to the European Pharmacopoeia method, the obtained garlic powder was analyzed. Figure 1 shows the chromatogram of this analysis. As it can be seen the alliin peak is well separated from the others and the use of BHB as internal standard is justified. The obtained quantity of alliin was 0.869 g/100 g dried garlic powder.

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of the fresh garlic bulbs processed entirely in laboratory.

Using an industrial grinder machine a paste of garlic cloves was obtained and after drying it in an industrial hot air dryer (40°C) it was analyzed. The obtained chromatogram, figure 2, is showing an important decrease of alliin's peak (all of the samples were analyzed in the same way and the chromatograms are presented on the same absorption scale which mean that they can be compared) the calculated quantity being 0.429 g

alliin/100 g dried garlic powder. It appears that 50% of alliin was lost in this fine grinding process (in another study in which we used the same method of processing we obtained alliin values with 50-80% smaller than those of the garlic processed entirely in laboratory).

Another part of this experiment was to process the garlic cloves as little as possible and therefore to cut the garlic cloves into bigger pieces by

passing them through a plant cutting machine. It is true that the drying process (industrial hot air dryer at 40°C) was longer but the result can be observed in figure 3.

The quantity of allicin was 0.725 g/100 g dried garlic powder only 16% lower than the fresh garlic. As it was mentioned before a small part of the garlic cloves passed through the plant

cutting machine were dried in a laboratory stove at 50°C. After analysis we found a quantity of 0.720 g allicin/100 g dried garlic powder, just a little bit smaller than of those dried in the industrial dryer.

The obtained results are summarized in figure 4.

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of garlic cloves transformed into a paste.

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of garlic cloves passed through the plant cutting machine.

Fig. 4. The content of allicin in the studied samples.

4. Conclusions

Knowing that allicin has the highest medicinal activity, to obtain a maximum efficiency of garlic containing supplements it is necessary to have high levels of allicin. The present experiment has showed that the first phase of the fresh garlic's transformation into dried powder process is of

great importance because in this stage occurs the highest loss of allicin (by fine grinding the garlic more allicin comes into contact with alinase and allicin is formed and therefore lost). Even though cutting the garlic cloves into bigger pieces has the disadvantage that it increases the drying period, the fact that it can ensure high quantities of allicin has a bigger importance.

References

1. World Health Organization – *Monographs on selected medicinal plants*, Vol. 1, Geneva, 1999.
2. Peter Josling – “*Allicin – The hearth of garlic*”, HCR Publishing, Chicago, Illinois, 2005.
3. European Pharmacopoeia – Herbal drugs and herbal drug preparations - *Allii sativi bulbi pulvis* Monograph, Ed. 7.0, 2010.

EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES OF A TOURISM SOFTWARE (FRONT OFFICE SYSTEM) AT THE UNIVERSITY OF DEBRECEN

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Abstract: *The aim of this paper is on the one hand to present one of the most important professional subjects (Professional Informatics) of the tourism-catering course (the most popular training from the time of its start) at the University of Debrecen Faculty of Applied Economics and Rural Development. On the other hand we would like to present the Hostware Front Office system, which is the basic of the subject and contribute to the education of proper experts suitable for the labour market expectations.*

Keywords: *Hostware, front office system, reservation, education, tourism-catering.*

1. Introduction

Tourism-catering education started in 2009 at the University of Debrecen Faculty of Applied Economics and Rural Development. It was one of the most popular training at the time of its start, which was proved by the fact that in the year 2009 344 students, while in 2010 298 students applied for this education at the first place. After five years it is the third most popular education regarding all of the applications, while highlighting the first-place-applications it is the second most popular education at the faculty in 2014 (bachelor, full-time education, with state scholarship).

Besides providing professional knowledge the highlighted task of this popular education operated within the Department of Tourism and Catering Management is the preparation for specialization, in which students may get to know the differentiated essence of health tourism, touristic destination management and hotel specialization. During the three-year-education students acquire knowledge being suitable in practice as well besides theoretical knowledge. Among these the subject called Professional Informatics is one of the seminars providing the most concrete professional knowledge, where students may get to know the hotel front office system, which is used in majority of the hotels and is one of the market leader systems in Hungary. The aim of the education in the third year is that students should learn and know the practical knowledge on a high level built on theoretical basis and after the professional probation they could successfully find jobs in the labour market.

During the semester the students learn to use the demo version of the Front Office system of Hostware Ltd used for educational purposes. When educating the program by the help of situational tasks our aim is that students could use the software in a wider spectrum. They learn how to use the program from the aspects of the administrator, reception, housekeeping and the manager.

2. Hostware Front Office System

The Hostware is a Hungarian developed hotel software family, which consists of different modules. According to the own characteristics of the given unit (hotel, restaurant, bath etc.) it decides whether which module is necessary for the operation. The compatibility of the modules makes the fact possible that the appropriate solution should be available for both smaller city hotels and greater complexes as well. In case of hotels, the Hostware is a framework, the given unit fills up with data necessary for the operation, by which a hotel may be totally individualized.

The systems developed by the company were planned for Windows operating system, thus utilizing the arising advantages. For example reports (different statements and lists) created during the different workflows may be directly exported to a Microsoft Excel table and a pdf-file as well. Moreover, it is compatible with the Microsoft Outlook Express e-mail program, which makes the fact possible that the correspondence between the guest and the hotel from the request till the confirmation may be brought out with one click.

The basis of the system is the robust SQL database engine, which greatly enhance the data

security and the stability of the system, in this way data cannot be viewed with the help of simple utility programs; furthermore, it avoids data corruptions even in case of on-going failures or when the electricity is ceased.

Hostware Ltd has the best references among the hotel software suppliers in Hungary. At the moment, 406 hotels are using this hotel front office system. This is due to the fact that, on one hand, the majority of the hotels opening in our country implement the products, and, on the other hand, many hotels using the systems of other suppliers are switching to Hostware software.

Front office system of Hostware Ltd. plays market leader role in Hungary among commercial accommodations which are using hotel software and have more than 14 rooms.

In the last seven years the hotel software sales distribution has not changed significantly among the three suppliers of the Hungarian market (Opera, Flexys, Hostware), although the number of investments showed a strong increase in 2008 due to the EU tender funds, and decreased significantly in 2009 owing to the global crisis. During all these times, the vast majority of the hotels have chosen the Hostware program.

First figure shows the hotel software sales distribution among the three most important suppliers from 2009 to 2013 (red – Hostware, blue – Opera, green – Flexys), while the second figure shows percentage of hotels according to applied hotel software [1,2].

Fig. 1. Number of hotels using hotel software in Hungary [2]

Fig. 2. Percentage of hotels according to applied hotel software [2]

3. Possibilities and requirements of the education of the software

Prominently important element of the practice-orientated education is that students of University of Debrecen Faculty of Applied Economics and Rural Development become acquainted with the use of Hostware Front Office system.

Within the confines of professional informatics subject (2 hours lectures and 2 hour-practice weekly) students acquire the front office system during the last term; by the time they have had adequate knowledge of hotel management, which is crucial important expectation in the course of software usage.

We have used demo version of Front Office system (WinFro), which is suitable for the educational purposes. Demo version of the software assures possibility for students to acquire the system in real circumstances without the violence of the personality rights (fictitious database) and there doesn't need any report prepared for responsible authority [5].

The appropriate educational person, who knows the smallest parts of the software and has adequate practical knowledge, plays an important role in the learning process [3]. During seminars it is very important to deal with students patiently, because of the different levels of informatics knowledge of students.

We assure separate work possibility (one student – one computer) for every student in order to obtain the appropriate practical knowledge.

During seminars the usage of separated computer and the independent trainings are vital important, because future specialists have to apply their knowledge in real situations after university.

At the University of Debrecen practical courses of the front office system are sufficient to acquire the basic knowledge of the software, however, students do not gain enough practical knowledge without extra individual practice.

On behalf of education of quality specialist, there is opportunity for students to practice in the computer room, so anybody can improve own knowledge independently after weekly obligatory seminars. It is especially important in the case of students, whose have difficulties in the usage of the software because they do not possess the basic informatics skills.

Therefore the initiation of the practical opportunities is significant, because this program can be used only in two computer rooms, where the lectures also go on. Twenty students per seminar are appropriate; hereby we can deal with the emerging individual problems of the students. Nevertheless, projector connected to the computer is a great solution during the seminars; therefore the usage of the software can be shown in detail for the students, who can follow step by step the usage of the software.

Our important task is to achieve that students be aware of that the software are only demo version at the university, but in a hotel they have to take responsibility of their work among real circumstances. If students know the software and modules as precisely as possible, their work can be more simply in hotels.

In 2012 the education of the system started in the case of graduating students in two computer rooms with 42 computers.

Nowadays the education of the third year goes on. The number of the first year was 170 persons, the number of second year was 130 persons and the number of current year is 120. On the basis of the examination of preliminary application data, the number of year may be calculated 120 persons.

During a seminar in a computer room there are 20-21 persons in order to assure students of their individual work on computer.

Students can become acquainted with the next subjects at the lectures during the 14 or 15 weeks of the seminar:

- Basic knowledge of database: most important definitions related to the topic, integrated hotel software.
- Surface and structure of Hostware Front Office System, employees and their privileges in the programme, system settings.

- Tasks of individual and group reservation, use of room plan, management of guest data, searching of reservations, rooms and guests).
- Tasks in connection with arriving guests.
- Tasks during the residence.
- Cashier module (charges, hiding, discount, billing, cancellations).
- Tasks in connection with leaving guests.
- Housekeeping, reports, lists.

Students can become acquainted with the next subjects and tasks at the practices during the use of the software:

- Surface and structure of Hostware Front Office System, creation and settings of employees and their privileges.
- Tasks of individual and group reservation (creating and deleting reservation, searching among the guests, confirmation, room reservation and classification, guest data, housekeeping information, registration card, pre-charges, notes, interface, wake up calls, data of debit cards, cash deposit, tools reservation).
- Overview of tasks in the room plan (quick reservation, check-in, moving).
- Cashier module (charges, pre-charges, shifted charges, hiding, discount, cancellations, check-out and billing).
- Cashier closure, quick balance, night closure, closure lists.
- Housekeeping, reports, lists.

Generally, hotels do not utilize all function provided by the software, except those which are needed for in their daily operation. Therefore we have compiled the curriculum of the semester based on practical experiences so that the most important parts of the curriculum receive more emphasis.

During the semester students have four tests (two practical tests on computer and two theoretical written tests). On the one hand, the two theoretical tests contain of 30 questions which are mainly based on the use of the software and on the other hand, the two practical tests (on computer) include several situational tasks. Next example shows one task from the practical test:

The air conditioner system of the room 23 has broken down and it's indicated by guest. Receptionist moves guest to another room and then informs the maintenance department of the problem. Receptionist has to change the room status to out of order for two days – where the air conditioner system has broken down – while the

maintenance team repairs the machine. Carry out the necessary tasks!

Generally speaking, we can be satisfied with the efficiency of tests, only 10-20 per cent of the students fail during the semester. There are two major reasons for failures: lack of preparedness and do not write the tests. In the first table (Table 1) we can see that the results of practical tests are better than the results of theoretical tests which derive from characteristics of test (three years average). Theoretical part of tests counts lower emphasis in the final exam mark.

Table 1

Multiple-choice tests %	Practical tests %	Mark
5-10	25-35	5
20-30	20-30	4
30-40	15-25	3
20-30	10-20	2
10-20	10-20	1

In contrast with full time training, students in correspondence training do not have opportunity to get acquainted with the program so detailed. Correspondence students have several difficulties related to the subject, on the one hand, there are huge amount of information about the program during the lessons and on the other hand, they have got less time for practice. At this training we make an effort to explain the most important tasks of a receptionist (create reservation, check-in, billing, check-out) for students.

After three years, students have one compulsory practical term (after professional informatics) at an optional company. Generally, students, who chosen hotel specialization, spend this practical term at a Hungarian hotel, where they can apply the gained knowledge and try themselves in real situations.

Trainees obtain different responsibilities per hotels. Different hotels give different assignments their trainees, for example: there are hotels where trainees are only observers, and there are hotels where trainees do the whole works of the front office system [5].

4. Meeting of education and profession

A Hungarian research collected the most important deficiencies relating to the trainees on the basis of hotel experts being involved in their education. The negative factors are listed below, which are strongly connected to the software

training as well as to the tourism and catering education [3,4].

- There are a great number of trainees with lack of self-reliance who are afraid of staying alone at the reception, at the same time it may occur that a trainee is too confident, which is not too good as well, because of the lack of sufficient professional experiences he or she might make mistakes.
- The computer skill of the trainees often contains only the use of the Internet and they are not aware of handling basic programs such as Word or Excel.
- When billing they do not know the different paying forms, and have difficulties in studying the cashier modules.
- The language skill of the trainees still reflects many problems. Though most of them have language exams, they use the language improperly in prominent situations [4].

To eliminate these deficiencies, a great attention is paid in our university to educate proper experts suitable for the labour market expectations, which means that our aim is to provide a marketable degree for the students, by which companies may get experts who can be utilized immediately; in this way they do not have to spend time and money for training the employees with a degree later in harmony with their requirement.

The education is realized by the cooperation of practical experts in order that our tourism-catering education should meet the labour market expectations and the university should educate marketable labourforce and not just simply educated experts having great lexical knowledge. Without the need for completeness the following practical experts take part in the education:

- hotel director
- sales manager
- catering specialist
- regional marketing director of Hungarian Tourism Ltd

A major part of the students coming from the tourism-catering education have professional language exams, which itself does not absolutely ensure the proper communication, but it is an advantage by all means in the probation semester and later when finding a job.

Among the basic subjects studying the basic informatics gains relevance, by which students become able to handle basic programs such as for example Word or Excel. The education focuses

on educating both of the programs, as the would-be experts have to be aware of the fundamental knowledge.

The use of the function of the software is different in the hotels thus the biggest emphasis is concentrated on two major fields, such as creating the reservation (check-in) as well as billing (check-out).

During the semester the students may make more than 30 bills when practicing; they can get to know with different paying forms, which is illustrated with the next example from the second paper of the semester: *Mr. and Mrs. take a journey. They pay by holiday check, while the remaining part is covered by a credit card. Carry out the necessary tasks!*

In this example they have to disintegrate the bill first, and then they have to use the paying forms of holiday check and credit card.

Students of a higher leveled performance than the average coming from the education may find jobs without the deficiencies typical to trainees; furthermore, they can continue their education in the MSc course.

In the next part the most relevant interfaces are introduced in the Hostware Front Office system.

5. Most important parts of the software

The demo program of 7.11.1.214 version is available for the university, which though changed during the years in appearance, the most important processes, menu points and functions remained the same. After logging-in, the system stands up, where there are the following menu points: Reception, Cashier, Housekeeping, Reports, Night audit, Basic data, Service (Fig.3.)

During the semester the students use the program with an admin level access in order that they can reach every function of the system;

however, in real life users are not entitled to have a full access. The certain main and sub menu points are available depending on the access privileges [1,2].

In the program the reservation is the most important field for the marketing and the reception (Fig. 4.), where everything may be realized, from informing the inquiring guest, through fixing and confirming the concrete reservation (individual and group) and till checking-in the guests.

The user staying the reservation window may represent several tables reflecting reservation and turn-over projections (for instance: forecast of the reserved rooms window, category of room window), which may help in informing the inquiring people.

The former inquiry resulting in the form of booking is fixed in the reservation as well, than a confirmation is sent to the customer even by e-mail. Recording the special requirements regarding booking and transiting the modifications happen in the reservation.

The reservation service provides a great help in the administration relating to the check-in of the guests [1,2,6].

The information in connection with room reservation may be classified into three major groups, which are determinant when using the program. Data which may not be linked directly to the booked room are in the reservation head (orange border), while data being in a strong connection with the room and of not price-information typed are in the room reservations (blue border).

The third part is room prices, where the booked rooms may be priced differently for the period of residence (black border) [1,2].

Fig. 3. Hostware Front Office system after log in

Fig.4. Reservation window

At the room reservations (Fig. 5.) it is possible to register the data of the guest.

These data should be filled in independent from the hotel accounting. If a regular guest, a frequenter arrives at the hotel and his or her data were registered in the table of frequenters, we can put these data in it here, thus making the process more rapidly.

If a guest arrives who is not a frequenter, we have the possibility to put his or her data from here to the table of frequenters with only one click [1,2].

The room plan is the most spectacular part of the Front Office system, a window being used most often by the receptionists, which make the room reservation of the hotel easily overviewed.

Beside the good transparency, it provides several operations relating to reservation such as reservation record (quick reservation), check-in, making bills.

In the room plan a so-called quick reservation and quick check-out may be carried out, which may accelerate the processes.

The window may be freely sized, where we can adjust that whether room reservations of 2, 3 or 5 weeks should be seen at the same time.

Room reservations with different colors cover different status dependent on the fact whether it is an individual or a group reservation and whether the guests are arriving (blue), residing (green) or leaving guests (red).

Black color covers out of order status in the room plan [1,2,5].

Fig.5. Room plan window

In the window of cashier module (Fig. 6.), financial operations relating to the reservation may be realized. Here we can see the actual balance of a given reservation, a room or a guest, its recorded services and bills. It is here where charges, pre-charges and room price pre-charges can be posted, discounts may be given, charge items of other guests or reservation can be taken over and cashier modules may be realized. Service account may be created here as well as for check-out. When entering, we have to log-in the cash register, where checking the privilege is extremely important as it is a financial activity. In the cash register there are shifts, which replace

each other, according to a given time. After logging-in, we arrive at a guest-searching window. If we want to make prompt billing to a guest without a room, we can step out from this (service billing) [1,2,7].

On the basis of the room rate code and pre-charge registration fixed in the reservation the night closure or the room price pre-charge automatically charges the required services. If the guest asks for and uses an extra service, the receptionist charges it on the guest's account by hand with the functions of charge or pre-charge. Beside this, systems measuring the consumption of the guest may also charge the guest's account.

Számaműveletek

Név: Fa Péter Felhőt: 3 Érkezés: 2011.03.18
 Megrendelő: Fa Péter Gyerek: 1 Utazás: 2011.03.22 Fizetés:
 Megjegyzés: nyugós vendég, lopja a sajtot

Szobaigénylő: Fa Nándor Érkezés: 2011.03.18 Árkkód: 3=4AI
 Megjegyzés: Utazás: 2011.03.22 Szobaár: 23 000 HUF

R-No: 18964 L
 Főszámla
 Szoba: * 114 L
 Vendég: * Szobaszá F
 Fólia: * Mind

EGYENLEGEK

TELJES: 111 920
 Főszámla: 0
Szobaszámla: 106 640
 Vendégszámla: 0
 TELJES - előleg: 111 920

Tételek		Számlák	Átterhelések	Kiegészítések	Számolatlan tételek			Kiszámlázott tételek	Sztorizott és jóváírók				
Dátum / Bizonylat	Szoba	Kód	Szolgáltatás	Üzem.	T	F	Menny.	Összeg	Valuta	Engedmény [Ft]	Összeg [Ft]	Fel.	S.
2011.03.18.	114	30	Ágynemű használat		K		1	1 000,00	HUF	0	1 000	100	N
2011.03.18.	114	1	Gyerekágy		K		1	5 000,00	HUF	0	5 000	100	N
2011.03.18.	114	885	Szállásdíj		E		1	23 000,00	HUF	0	23 000	100	N
2011.03.18.	114	22	Idegenforgalmi adó		E		1	410,00	HUF	0	410	100	N
2011.03.19.	114	885	Szállásdíj		E		1	23 000,00	HUF	0	23 000	100	N
2011.03.19.	114	22	Idegenforgalmi adó		E		1	410,00	HUF	0	410	100	N
2011.03.19.	114	440	Bowling		A		1	3 500,00	HUF	0	3 500	100	N
2011.03.20.	114	885	Szállásdíj		E		1	23 000,00	HUF	0	23 000	100	N
2011.03.20.	114	22	Idegenforgalmi adó		E		1	410,00	HUF	0	410	100	N
2011.03.20.	114	440	Bowling		A		1	3 500,00	HUF	0	3 500	100	N
2011.03.21.	114	885	Szállásdíj		E		1	23 000,00	HUF	0	23 000	100	N
2011.03.21.	114	22	Idegenforgalmi adó		E		1	410,00	HUF	0	410	100	N

Terhelés Előterhelés Szobaár előterhelés Egyéni árkkód előterhelés Mennyiség módosítás Tétel bontás Bujtások Átterhelés Terhelés sztorizálás Szolgáltatás sztorizálás Engedmény Faliák

PRO430 | 2011.03.22 | HOSHOS | Felhasználó: DEMO

Fig.6. Cashier module window

The night closure (Fig. 7.) is an automatic process, which consists of several smaller services, for example carrying out the maintaining processes of the databases, rate code charge of the guest in the hotel and updating certain parts of the program. During the night closure the following tasks are carried out by the program [1,2,6]:

- Cashiers check
- Arrivals and departures check
- Database backup

- Automatic room charge and extra charge posting
- Change room status to dirty

If any deficiency or mistake occurs during the night closure, the closure will not run till the end, and the program will make a so-called error-list. On the basis of the list the necessary actions are carried out and then the night closure has to be run again [1,2,7].

Fig.6. Night closure window

6. Summary

Professional Informatics is one of the seminars providing the most concrete professional knowledge during the tourism-catering education, where students may get to know the hotel front office system, which is used in majority of the hotels and is one of the market leader systems in Hungary. Demo version of the software, which is suitable for the educational purposes, assures possibility for students to acquire the system in real circumstances. Great attention is paid in our university to educate proper experts suitable for the labour market expectations. Our primary aim is to provide a marketable degree for the students (with the help of Professional Informatics), by which companies may get experts who can be utilized immediately. Our education is realized by the cooperation of practical experts in order that our tourism-catering education should meet the labour market expectations and the university should educate marketable labourforce.

References

- HostWare winFRO v7.9 Felhasználói kézikönyv: Az integráltság harmóniája. 2009, pp. 355.
- Internet1: Official website of Hostware Ltd, www.hostware.hu
- Internet2: Baross Gábor Program – Észak-Magyarországi Régió „Innovációs kompetencia- és szolgáltatásfejlesztés”: *Oktatási innováció a szálloda-menedzser képzés területén.* 2009, Downloaded: 12-04-2014.; <http://szallodamenedzsmen.ektf.hu/down/1.pdf>
- Internet3: Baross Gábor Program – Észak-Magyarországi Régió „Innovációs kompetencia- és szolgáltatásfejlesztés”: *Oktatási innováció a szálloda-menedzser képzés területén.* 2009, Downloaded: 12-04-2014.; <http://szallodamenedzsmen.ektf.hu/down/2.pdf>
- Internet4: Baross Gábor Program – Észak-Magyarországi Régió „Innovációs kompetencia- és szolgáltatásfejlesztés”: *Oktatási innováció a szálloda-menedzser képzés területén.* 2009, Downloaded: 12-04-2014.; <http://szallodamenedzsmen.ektf.hu/down/3.pdf>
- James A. Bardi: *Hotel Front Office Management.* John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2007, New Jersey, USA, pp. 482.
- Denney G. Rutherford, Michael J. O’Fallon: *Hotel management and operations.*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2007, New Jersey, USA, pp. 498.

CONCEPTION OF AN INTEGRATED SYSTEM FOR AGRI-TOURISM AT SECUSIGIU (ARAD COUNTY)

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Abstract: *Sustainable development of rural areas represents a major goal for the European Union. To achieve this, in this paper are highlighted some conceptual issues of interference between the real needs and interests of the beneficiaries of agro-tourism services from urban areas, and in same time from the rural area. It presented a package of measures needed for compatibility between the two entities: the townspeople-villagers, as suppliers-beneficiaries, after the known principles of agro-tourism and by the rules of family farms and those unwritten traditional Romanian households.*

Keywords: *integrated system, family farm, rural, urban, area.*

1. Introduction

In studying the possibilities of rural development, the Agri-tourism can be considered a style of vacation with capitalization of the hospitality which can be offered by family farms. In this can include the opportunity to assist with farming tasks during some visiting. The Agri-tourism is often practiced in wine growing regions, as in Italy, France and Spain. In USA, Agri-tourism is wide-spread and includes any farm open to the public at least part of the year. Tourists can pick fruits and vegetables, ride horses, taste honey, learn about wine, shop in gift shops and farm stands for local and regional produce or hand-crafted gifts, and much more. Each farm generally offers a unique and memorable experience suitable for the entire family. Also, the Agri-tourism is being developed as a valuable component of a business model to support many agricultural entities when the farm products they produce are no longer economically competitive otherwise. [5]

2. Methods

In order to establish the conceptual directions of the project were initially identified some basic needs of food and leisure conditions of urban families in relation to bidding the opportunities in rural areas. It was designed a questionnaire comprised 10 questions. Of these, three questions were related to the characterization of the person

surveyed (social conditions, age and school education). Other questions focused on rural expectations, the purveyance possibilities agri-food, rest and relaxation conditions, involvement in household activities, involvement in initiation and development of business in partnership, playground for children, conducting sports and hiking, parties, request other services and proposals for increasing the attractiveness of rural areas for individuals and / or families in urban areas.

Were launched in urban areas a total of 300 questionnaires: 150 in Timisoara and Arad 150. These were taken into consideration only these who experienced a serious interest towards harnessing the countryside, just a number of 236 questionnaires. These were supplemented by representatives of the families surveyed, which could be characterized as in Table 1.

The difference of 64 questionnaires was: 48 questionnaires indicating express disinterest to use the rural area and 16 were rejected due to partial completion and contradictory responses, required initial research showing indifference and a lack of trust reinvigorate rural perspective. These questionnaires disregarded, came in roughly equal categories of families consulted, without the possibility of concluding significant in this respect.

The number of questionnaires was applied to a representative sample sufficient for the desired accuracy of this research.

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Table 1.

<i>Social conditions (monthly income/family member, [lei]</i>	<i>No.</i>	<i>Average age [Years]</i>	<i>No.</i>	<i>Medium-level training school</i>	<i>No.</i>
Under 500	59	Under 25	42	Without a specific school training	26
501 – 800	106	26-35	94	Mostly high school graduates	98
801 – 1000	37	36-50	56	Mostly university graduates	88
Over 1000	34	Over 50	46	High degree of intellectual	24
TOTAL	236		236		236

After the studying of valid questionnaires, were resulted follows needs and proposals:

- The desire to re-find of "country house", most families don't have property or relatives in rural areas relatively close to the city of permanent residence;
- The need for regular supply of food products, fresh and obtained environmental conditions, even direct involvement in the maintenance part of the culture harvesting and livestock and poultry
- Spending a few days in a rustic environment, especially in times of celebrations;
- Educational purposes, children and young people, for practical knowledge, skills, with elements characteristic of rural life;
- Willingness for a variety of issues in a geographical unit.

For to give more application of this research, it have identified characteristics of the place offered for experimentation research results , the farm commune Secusigiu (Arad), composed of 2 houses, 2 stables for animals, 560 sq yard , a garden with different cultures, covering 1,600 square meters and a plot of 2 ha farm, located in the agricultural perimeter of the village, at a distance of about 1 km from the house.

The family -owner , is composed of 4 people, and have two horses, a tractor and some other equipment for preparing fodder and soil and crop maintenance. Also they have a car.

The family members are accustomed to rural activities and they want to stay and grow in this environment.

Fig. 1. - Secusigiu (Arad county).

3. Results and discussion

For designing of integrated system for agritourism, adapted at this research conditions it were considered the following aspects:

- a. One honest form of the agritourism, could be like a "creative agriculture" where it can "increase the 'happiness index' of urban dwellers." This creative agriculture development includes simple homes, fields, small village like gathering places and orchards. It is run by people who were formerly rural farmers. Urban dwellers can come and help work in the fields, stay in the simple homes and be reminded of their former rural lifestyle. Agridisneyland, China style. The purpose is clear and the result, according to reports, is satisfactory to both farmers and visitors. [10]
- b. The concept of family farming covers various elements. From a sociological perspective, family farming is associated with family values, such as solidarity, continuity and commitment; in economic terms, family farming is identified with specific entrepreneurial skills, business ownership and management, choice and risk behaviour, resilience and individual achievement. Family farming is often more than a professional occupation because it reflects a lifestyle based on beliefs and traditions about living and work. [6]
- c. In general, the consumers are looking for local, fresh, organically or naturally grown products;"
- d. Kyle McEnroe, wrote about integrated system in rural space: „*Modern agriculture practices in the United States have been accompanied with social, environmental and economic issues. Recent agriculture trends show a declining number of small independent farmers and decreasing farm incomes. In 2007, the average Dutchess County, New York farmer's annual loss was approximately*

twenty thousand dollars. This thesis found that synergy was created within a system that uses agri-tourism as a vehicle for public education of an integrated farm system. Much of that synergy comes in the form of value-added production. Value-added production in the form of agri-tourism provides economic diversification opportunities to farmers that can help buffer the fluctuating commodities market. Agri-tourism can also be used as an educational tool and create better connection for the consumers with their food system. Integrated farm systems also have the ability to increase food production while advancing agricultural sustainability production practices. Combining agri-tourism, integrated farm systems and agriculture education creates a needed value-added to farm production.” [10]

- e. The Agri-tourism may be the fastest growing rural tourism niche. The majority of the EU's 12 million farms is family farms, passed down from one generation to another, and contributes to the socio-economic and environmental sustainability of rural areas. [10]

To solve the problem must be identified general and peculiar characteristics of the rural area designated for application.

The characteristics of this area, in which the household where it will apply this research are similar for majority of different regions of Romania. But, about commune Secusigiu can show that has a rich history and charming geography, standing in the north-west Plain Vinga, with an area of 17202 ha. In the commune there are four villages, with Secusigiu - village commune residence, situated at a distance located at 31 km from Arad and 52 km from Timișoara.

Fig. 2. – Nature reserve: "Prundul Mare"

The tourism potential of the village is one exception, with nearby of the Natural Park "Lunca Mureșului", nature reserve "Prundul Mare", a church built in 1529, a monastery of the Serbian Bezdin, a lake with white lilies near the monastery, a church assembly Roman Catholic patron "St. Peter and Paul" (1774) and the statue of St. Peter. The economy is based on agriculture, especially wheat, corn, sunflower, barley, sugar beet, tomato culture, watermelon green and yellow. Secondary economic sector is the textile industry, a section of knitwear which offers jobs for women in general. [8].

An integrated system for production presumes the existence of a first base for the beginning, which became the start point for developing in cycles. The main piece of this system is the simplification of financial activity, some economical barriers that can be found usually, in commercial activities, industrial part, in general, in whole business. The stages in conception and planning integrated for a production system are: analyses of available personal resources; choose the real business; establish the main objectives for the integrated system; create the strategy; financial and budget plan; elements for evaluation and monitoring the system. Each technologic flux has a high complexity but it's very important to see the system like a whole unit. It's really necessary an unit vision, with the possibility to preview all causes for block the system, then we must remark the zone with high-risk possibilities. It's preferable to use an integrated system, where can use intensive, minimum an available element (raw material source, the personal land, equipment for processing, personal network marketing, other). [2]

To more easily understand the concept of the compatibility of integrated food production with traditional peasant household must mention some characteristic elements proven in many literary works and analyzes the evolution of Romanian culture. For the Romanian peasant household is not a simple house, but usually consists of the house itself, its associated structures which serve different needs and activities of daily living, land that belongs to the landowner and, not least, his family. The household is the center of social, family, economic and spiritual Romanian peasants. Being thrifty (Slavic word, meaning "lord, master" who has the qualities of "diligent, skillful, who knows how to manage his own family") in his household is a man's responsibility

to nature and source of the sense of dignity and self-respect. [9]

For to be more close to traditional peasant household business conditions in agro system that responds to the needs expressed by prospective beneficiaries urban embedded systems must be defined as the systems that require a certain assimilation, an amalgamation of all parties in a whole fully harmonized. From a functional perspective, the integrated systems may already be complete, providing closed circuit elements, with input and output function in order to achieve something useful or to accomplish a goal.

The traditions of the Romanian people are frequently proven constancy ambitions to own property and trust, sometimes even blind forces, essential features for followers of integrated production. The integrated production system may include both buildings and land, as well as the technical basis necessary, consisting generally of aggregate, equipment for agricultural - used to purchase raw materials, processing, based on selected technologies and product sales network food obtained. It also must to take into account the experience gained in several European countries in terms of family farms. There is a high diversity of family farms in the EU, in terms of their size, activities they engage in, availability of resources, degree of market integration, competitiveness, etc. They operate in different economic, agro-ecological and social contexts, ensuring food security while meeting rising societal expectations for food safety, quality, value, origin and diversity of food, and thus contribute to smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. [6]

For the case of transformation of the peasant from Secusigiu in a truly integrated system for agro food, are the following measures:

- One of the houses will redesign after one line modern furnishings and amenities in a living space and bathroom, but with rustic elements specific to tradition;
- Court to have an area for relaxation (with a gazebo at a well -well, place with various flowers, vine, a walnut, a lime, and other;
- In the fenced area, to be free poultry, with simple systems of feeding, watering, with the possibility of access to the pigsty, stable of the two horses, at least two cows, goats, sheep.
- The garden is surrounded by various fruit trees, minimum 20), and in one of the corners, 8-10 Paulownia trees, the area will be put and 8-10 beehives;

- Closer to a well drilled for water, will arrange a small greenhouse with an area of about 30-40 square meters, equipped with minimum heating possibilities for preparing seedlings , and grow out of spring.

- Garden will be provided with well-defined paths to ensure easy access for tourists and those who maintain cultures;

- Cultures are very different, not too much focused on the production, but the variety of vegetables and herbs, even small areas sown with corn especially for cooking, sunflower, sorghum, etc.

- Also in the side areas will cultivate strawberries, currants, gooseberry, blackberry, and certain herbs, such as mint, chamomile, etc.

House owners will be equipped with a kitchen with opportunities for complex food preparation including hearth; In the basement, a cellar furnished, compartmented which can be kept in good condition and pickles, some fruit (apples, pears, grapes, walnuts, etc.), 2-3 barrels lower for brandy, sand boxes for vegetables, keeping spaces smoked dry Offer tourists and visitors to both the possibility of hosting CD comprises a certain period, and household choice of different products available, with payment on the spot, at negotiated prices, below market price. It will consider energy issues, using the perspective of renewable resources by harnessing biomass from crop operation, capturing and harnessing solar energy, wind to. Cash provided with computers and access to Internet communications. For to simplify communication with customers, including the ability to promote services.

Also, will be following the integration in local tourism programs and in relation with the supply possibility of agricultural products in the actions taken in the local community.

4. Conclusions

The prospect of more intensive support for the family agriculture will be much clearer after FAO European Regional Conference, which will be organized this year in Romania, in Bucharest, which will draw attention to the importance of family farming, with a lot of challenges and priorities key for the future, and addressing the best ways to support family farms.

Reorganization rural area in the context of current progress and civilization, involves the fitting in the sanitary and hygiene conditions,

endowments which must be consistent with the current technique.

From the economic point of view it is necessary to respect the principle of "win-to-win". It is also necessary a real financial and logistic support for entrepreneurs.

Application of such projects will contribute to the development of a more sustainable and more resilient agriculture in Europe and worldwide.

References

1. Kyle McEnroe, *Public Education of Integrated Farm Systems Using Agri-tourism*, Lambert Academic Publishing, 2012
2. Mnerie, D.: *The integrated systems for agrofood production sources for nourishment. In: Opportunities of Integrated Systems for Agrofood Production*, Ed. Orizonturi Universitare, 1999, pg.17-20.
3. Mnerie, D.: *Specific management features for integrated systems of production*, Proceedings of Conferința Internațională de inginerie integrată, Timișoara, 25-26 aprilie 2002, Ed. Politehnica, Timișoara, pg.162.
4. Mnerie, D., Mnerie, G. V. *Management strategies in food production in integrated current european context*, Proceeding of 7th International Conference, Integrated Systems for Agri-Food Production, SIPA2011, Nyiregyháza (Hungary), November, 10-12, 2011, Editura Bessenyei György Nyiregyháza, Editura Eurostampa, pag.328-331.
5. <http://agritourism.eu/>
6. http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/family-farming/index_en.htm
7. <http://www.landtourismus.de/>
8. <http://www.primariasecusiguar.ro/>
9. <http://www.revista-satul.ro/articol.php?id=85>
10. <http://ruraltourismmarketing.com/2013/04/agritourism-small-family-farmers/>

THE RULES OF ICT IN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT RELATED TO THE AGRI-FOOD AND TOURISM SECTORS

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Abstract: *Although the role of multifunctional agriculture, structural changes, the widening of production chains, co-operative efforts, tourism as an alternative source of income, and other economic clichés are in the forefront of our research. The present situation shows that “rural poverty” has formed as a result of a long and multifactorial process. It is obvious that the greater the social differences in a region compared to other regions the greater the lag of the region. Information and communication technologies (ICT) are a powerful driver for economy-wide productivity, growth and jobs – and are arguably Europe’s best-bet investment for the future. The regional innovation performance is different in regions and lower in rural areas. The ICT acts play more and more important role in innovation processes in rural areas. The new requirements for developing new application and services are to increase the wireless and broadband services. Access to broadband infrastructure is a particular issue for the rural economy. Broadband can provide ready access to international markets for enterprise in remote locations. Extension and take up of broadband facilities in rural areas is, therefore, an important policy objective. We studied the main factors of broadband network readiness in different regional levels and dimensions. Regarding to our results there are differences between regions on European and national level end sectors. The main reason can be the lack of knowledge and skills, the low level of openness to change which are particularly present in the rural areas. That is why we need to make efforts to reduce the gaps by increasing the human research development.*

Keywords: *ICT, rural development, broadband, education.*

1. Introduction

The development of the given region can only be performed in a complex way, building upon a complete social cross-section. It has become clear, that we should overstep the limits of the agricultural sphere and we should reveal the social asymmetries and concentrate on treating them from economic and other aspects by incorporating or associating former research programs and results. It is indisputable that the presence on digital platforms, i.e. the online presence and the speedy transmission of information became crucial for all economic sectors and for the society. In parallel with the development of digital technology a so-called digital ecosystem is emerging (Péntek and Herdon, 2009), in which all areas of living and business are supported by digital solutions.

Currently the rural development policy has been acquiring a stronger role in the strategy of the European Union and its Member States, since the social and economic role of rural areas is very important. These areas constitute more than 91% of the EU’s territory and here is the place of residence of the 56% of EU’s population. The

66% of Hungary’s territory is classified as a rural area, where 48% of the population lives. In addition Hungary has a significant agricultural and food industry which is the typical sector of rural regions. Consequently, for network developments the analysis of the aspects of rural development has become essential. The correlations between broadband networks and social and economic characteristics should be considered not only at macro-economic level, for the creation of national strategies but also at different regional levels. In the current strategy of the European Union and Hungary the reduction of digital divide has unequivocal priority which can be partially reached by the development of micro-regions.

Bottlenecks in broadband services are to be expected to materialize in poor social strata, rural, areas and small enterprises in countries facing the greatest efforts (Struzak, 2010). Making ICT products and services more accessible, including in Europe’s less-developed regions, is an economic, social, ethical and political imperative. NGN are seen as important instrument to bring competition and dynamism in the broadband sector in rural areas (Ruhle et al.,

2011). There are increasing returns to broadband telecommunications investments, which are consistent with the persistence of network effects (Koutroumpis, 2009). One important factor for growing is that the Internet plays a great role in spreading knowledge in an economy (Choi – Yi, 2009). Therefore, economic growth is positively related to the use of the Internet. The growing availability of high bandwidth is likely to enhance business growth opportunities for service providers (Picot and Wernick, 2007), furthermore it can enhance economic opportunities in rural areas by stimulating the development of home businesses and telecommuting and by facilitating access to education and training (LaRose et al., 2011).

2. ICT for regional development

The dynamic development of information technology tools and applications and the convergence of the different areas have started radical social and economic changes in the world. No matter what economic strategy is followed, the effects arising from the development and application of information technology should be taken into account.

Research on agricultural development, rural development and handling of the incorporated environmental protection knowledge, and on the support of innovation processes cannot be performed without the application of information technologies.

- The characteristics of the development of information technology applications are technology-oriented development, vertical and horizontal increase of application technologies, the determining role of the network applications and the Internet, the increasing importance of information technology as an innovation factor.

- The agricultural peculiarities, of course, have also a determining role in the application of information technology. Such factors are the differences in agricultural characteristics between the countries and the characteristics of the different application fields.

Regional Information Society Strategies of regions for the next period considers the spread of the application of information and communication technologies a key element of closing up. This strategy adapts to the European system of values and the developed international strategies, programs and action plans, but it also

takes into account Hungarian conditions and regional specificities and possibilities.

The Hungarian Information Society Strategies determined the areas where intervention is necessary, within these, it states the major directions and tasks to be implemented. The tasks were based upon the modernization of processes and services. The application of information and communication technologies is of determining importance in both cases. The necessary steps are divided into the following areas by the strategy:

- Content and services
- Infrastructure,
 - Establishment of broadband networks,
 - Development of access,
 - Ensuring data, standards and software for public use.
- Knowledge and skills,
- Legal and social environment.

When planning the strategy, the chapters of the regional development concept, strategic and operative plans of regions dealing with infocommunication should also be considered. These plans set the following five priorities:

- Development of the economy,
- Agricultural and rural development,
- Technical infrastructure, environmental protection and nature conservation,
- Human resource development,
- Development of the sector-independent areas.

Within this last priority, the ensurance of information and communication technologies and access to the Internet is of major importance. Special emphasis is laid on the ICT infrastructure of small- and medium-sized enterprises and the application of e-business applications.

ITC and some new IT such as mobile Internet, RFID or GRID, Future Internet can provide important opportunities, economic advantages for enterprises and organisations and support their more efficient operation as they can use them anytime and anywhere (Szilágyi, 2012). We can make their widespread usage, innovation effect and advantages in an economical way, if we consider the effect system of technologies and services. The technological, social and economic complex effect system puts pressure on the spread of business applications. Four player groups can be named according to social aspects: manufacturers, enterprises, customers and workers. If we study the business process, the expenses, advantages, disadvantages can be seen well. Today these applications are successful abroad and in Hungary as well as in the following areas: agriculture, different parts of the food

industry, extension services, precision agriculture and logistics. This system can contribute to the development of agriculture, enterprises and rural areas, and can support production, commerce, services and product tracing.

3. Methods and data

EU regions

Based on different data sources our research data base have been created which includes economic, social and ICT data at national and regional level, especially for the period from 2008 to 2012. Since for some indicators there were several data sources available, at the selection we considered the method of statistical review (representativeness), and its availability from territorial and interval aspects. Based on secondary source data the assessment of the situation and the comparative analysis of 27 Member States of the European Union and of NUTS 2 region of 13 Member States have been performed.

For indicators showing the development of broadband infrastructure and usage of Internet 2008 as a basic period and 2012 as a required period was selected in order to determine the extent of development. For some indicators and countries there was no data available for 2008 and 2012. In these cases data of previous or subsequent years were used.

A regional level study has been also performed, whilst in recent years the modelling and analysis for smaller territorial units are more important in our studies. The analysis included 123 regions of 13 EU Member States. 5 Danish, 17 Dutch, 9 Austrian, 11 Belgian, 8 Swedish, 18 Italian, 19 Spanish, 7 Portuguese, 8 Czech, 4 Slovakian, 7 Hungarian, 8 Romanian and 6 Bulgarian. The data of countries can that not be divided in regions (Malta, Luxembourg, Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia) and countries which have no data available for the selected indicators in a number of regions exceeding the half of the country were not been considered

Analyse Micro-Region

A questionnaire-based study was performed for the assessment of network preparedness and usage characteristics of the business segment, among the small, medium and micro-enterprises in Hajdúböszörmény as a rural area center.

106 business organizations were involved in the study they have been selected by stratified sampling based on area statistics of the

Hungarian Central Statistical Office. The basis of sampling was the distribution of staff employed and business activity of the enterprises. The sample well represents the distribution of the SME-s in the town, since the majority is composed of service and trade enterprises, or those connected to agriculture in any way. Our questionnaire-based study included only those enterprises which have subscribed to any landline Internet services as my research is mainly related to the use of optical upstream and access networks. Hajdúböszörmény is an adequate city from another aspect of the study, because in the period from 2006 to 2008 the broadband network implemented only with investments of service providers was integrated with an NGA infrastructure realized. So we could analyze a town where the total network coverage has been reached with the participation of the EU and the state.

The data collection was performed in the first quarter of 2012. The questionnaires were completed by the managers of enterprises in all the cases, as within the enterprises they are the decision makers in relation to the application of ICT. The test method is essentially considered a closed, guided interview, but in accordance with the questions of the questionnaire an interview was performed with the owners and in case of bigger business organizations with professionals responsible for IT functions, since their opinion can be decisive for the conformation of future company ICT trends. The information obtained during the interviews have facilitated the explanation of the results formulated based on the questionnaire's data.

The data collection, applied during the questionnaire-based study included 4 question groups as follows: Q1: Contained general questions in relation to the respondent business organizations. Q2: Concerned the characteristics of basic Internet infrastructure, the use of telecommunication tools and Internet use. Q3: Has been drawn up for the survey, review and assessment of Internet use. For the review the factors related to satisfaction, utility and importance have been indicated. Q4: Assessed the network characteristics of computers used by the enterprise and the attitudes related to the use of network services (outsourcing of services, remote data access and cloud computing services).

In case of indicators originating from secondary data sources, for the simple comparison of territorial units' percentage

qualitative criteria were applied. In case of countries and regions a correlation analyses has been performed for the data series of the selected indicator. The aim of the study was to determine the economic and social factors which are or could be connected to the development of broadband networks. For the correlation calculation according to the data types of variables the Pearson's correlation coefficient was determined, by two-tailed test. The correlation was evaluated on 0,01 and 0,05 significance level.

For the assessment of the questionnaire, descriptive, statistical method with one or more variables was applied. In the questionnaire in relation to the use, the importance of the factor had been assessed in 23 questions. First the internal reliability of questions' variables has been analyzed by Cronbach-Alpha test. The result of the test is that the variables are suitable for further analysis.

The variables were subject to a principal component analysis. This was necessary for the grouping of the 23 variables in some background variables. The principal components have been used also for cluster analysis, and the aim of the analysis was to determine how the activities of the enterprises affect the views regarding utility of network services. In case of clusters the average value of the principal components has been evaluated. The aim of the cluster analysis is to classify the observation units in relatively homogenous groups based on the variables involved in the analysis. The process is successful when the units are similar to the other components of the group but are different from the elements of other groups. In the cluster

analysis the fundamental task is to determine the variables which cause the difference between the groups, therefore the cluster analysis is frequently performed with variables produced during factor analysis. For my studies the Ward's method was applied because it minimizes the loss of information caused by the combination of groups. The Ward's method is favorable because of the use of scale variables and there was no extreme value. The deviation of the groups was nearly identical, and the correlation between variables was eliminated during the principal component analysis. The Ward's method calculates the average of all elements for each cluster, than the Euclidean squared distance for all observation units shall be calculated. The Euclidean squared distance was selected because it is suggested by the main scientific literature for Ward's method. The characterization of created clusters was made based on variables measured on grouping, not metrical scale, by cross tabulation analysis.

4. Results

At regional level

Two related Internet usage were analyzed by regions in detail. Regular purchases on the Internet and Internet access indicators were closely related to each other. The purchases on the Internet are very low in the Central and Southern European countries. According to the basic indicators such as broadband access the same clusters can be identified. Significant differences were observed by the various indicators between countries and regions within the country (Fig 1).

Fig 1. Differences among regions in EU

Based on the connection analysis performed by the secondary data base we have found that there are indicators between the countries and smaller territorial units which have a similar strict correlation with each other, but it was also revealed that there are some indicators which are strictly connected at national level, but there is no strict connection at the level of smaller territorial

units. For regions the network indicators are in connection with unemployment, rate of graduates from tertiary education, GDP per capita and the rate of employment. In Hungary it has been concluded that the additional aids are very important to reduce the differences between regions (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2: Hungary's NGA coverage in 2011 at NUTS 3 territorial level

The Next Generation Network penetration is below 35% in 5 counties, in 12 counties it is between 35% and 65% and in two counties (Baranya and Tolna) it is between 65% and 100%. The results of tenders have been compared to coverage and usage indicators. In the eastern part of the country rather the tenders for the local governments, while in the western part the tenders for SME-s were popular. Comparing the results of the map to the above mentioned network characteristics it is evident that while in Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg county many of tenders have been realized, the average NGA coverage has remained under 35%. Respect to the other regions the South Great Plain region has better results not only at infrastructural, but also at usage level, and in our opinion the tenders have largely contributed to these results. From the three tenders for e-services, in two cases the amount of the aid reached the highest value in the South Great Plain region.

Micro-regional level

Based on 23 variables of questions a principal component analysis has been performed. According to the result of this analysis the five

principal components have been ranked in five groups of indicators. These represent how much the company decision makers recognize the utility of Internet in relation to the single activities.

- 1.Function supporting internal and external Internet relations
- 2.Importance of online presence
- 3.Function supporting purchasing activity
- 4.Importance of online advertising
- 5.Sales promotion function

These groups of indicators are intended to express the views of company's decision makers. The reduction of the number of application characteristics was important for developing the model of assessment index in order to avoid the involvement of too many factors in the application component.

The variables were further studied by cluster analysis. The aim of the analysis was to determine how the activities of the enterprises affect the views regarding utility of network services. In case of these clusters the average value of the principal components has been evaluated, and the result is shown on Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The Clusters

To determine whether or not the differences between the clusters are significant, variance analysis (ANOVA) was made on the principal components. The result of it, that there is a

significant difference between the clusters ($P < 0,001$). Table 1 shows the distribution the number of enterprises in the clusters by their activity.

Table 1

Type of sector of enterprises	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
Agricultural production and service	-	4	21	23
Agricultural commercial	1	3	-	5
Other commercial	4	8	1	3
Service	7	7	1	1
Building trade	1	6	-	1
Tourism and hospitality	7	2	-	-

The decision makers in the 1st cluster evaluated very positively all the components except for the third one. The members of the cluster consider really important and useful the services available on Internet. Mainly the enterprises on tourism and catering and service are ranked in this group. Considering the importance of the sector in the town this is a very good result, as the presence on Internet is a crucial factor to take advantage of development possibilities. It is crucial that - based on the results - the enterprises of the sector are aware of these possibilities. In the case of the 2nd cluster all of the components are positives, but the difference respect to the 1st cluster consists in lower component scores. The score of 4th and 5th components are much lower but the 3rd one is much higher. This cluster contains several types of enterprises, but most of the commercial, service and building trade enterprises are in it. The 3rd and 4th cluster

contains mainly members of agricultural activities and some enterprises with other activity. The component scores are the lowest in this cluster.

Based on the questionnaire it was concluded that the situation of agricultural enterprises, especially of farmers is very serious, they have a significant lag in the use of broadband services. They don't use and do not consider necessary the use of these services, referring to the nature of their work. The company managers have recognized the advantages of network services only very slightly, and they have given a positive assessment mainly in relation to purchasing activities. The use of ICT applications is the slightest among the agricultural enterprises. These services are not necessary for their activities, the contact with their partners and clients is maintained in person. The purchases are realized only from a few suppliers and selling is

targeted to only a few clients. The trust and personal contact are the most important for them. The most of factors were considered important or expressly important by the decision makers of service and commercial enterprises, regardless from the application.

Based on the above mentioned result on one hand the relevant role of agricultural sector many farms operate in the town, having similar attitudes. But it must be underlined that service and catering enterprises provide substantially better application characteristics. On the other hand the micro-environmental impact is less important, because in multiple cases the use of online services is obligatory in order to contact public institutions. This includes uniformity.

At the respondent enterprises the majority of decision makers rejects the use of network services. Neither the reduction of cost represents a motivation. The main reasons can be the lack of knowledge and skills, the low level of openness to change which are particularly present in the rural areas. In many cases these services obviously are not needed (farmers), here the main problem is the serious lag in the use of Internet.

Based on the results of the questionnaire we have concluded that the IT closing up of small, middle and micro enterprises is a very slow process, and we would like to underline two reasons. It shall be started from a level much lower than the average which will be restrained by the IT attitudes of decision makers. In relation to software and remote data access we detected poor performance results. The 60% of the enterprises does not use specific software for the activities, and the 29% does not trust in remote services. Only the 10% of the enterprises represents a potential development, notwithstanding that there are specific, cost-saving solutions also for small enterprises. The situation is more serious for remote data access. The 92% of the enterprises consider secure when the data are stored in place, on own devices. Only the 8% of the enterprises considers secure this solution, while in reality the data are stored more safely at a company specialized in data storage than on a computer used by collaborators. At 48% of the respondent enterprises more employees use the same computer, therefore there is a greater chance of Internet attacks.

5. Results and consequences

Based on the results of my primary research we have concluded that the network characteristics

should be assessed separately both for infrastructure and usage, in case of companies with agricultural economics activity. It can be explained by the fact that its attitudes are significantly different from other operators of the SME sector. The current and future need for agricultural informatics researches and developments is justified by the same conclusion.

By the analysis of primary and secondary data we have proved that the assessment of development of smaller territorial units is necessary for supporting network development decisions, and a model has been formulated which - contrary to national development studies - contains suitably fewer components in order to facilitate the survey, but which are enough to create a reliable result.

The attitudes of the business sector have been studied globally on a rural settlement, and we have concluded that the current result of network investments is principally the creation of the possibility and right of accessibility, and equal opportunities. The business SME sectors do not take enough advantage of business opportunities provided by networks.

The Faculty of Applied Economics and Rural Development at the University of Debrecen has both the potential and experience to work on different training levels, research in agriculture economics, rural development and informatics. We are working in the center of the largest region in Hungary with wide-ranging relationship to farms, companies, institutes and government administrations. Our aims to support the region with human resource developments (education and trainings) and research. Our degree programs cover agribusiness, rural development, agricultural public administration and agro-informatics, tourism, accounting and finance, sport management, marketing, logistics, human resource development.

We introduced the five year "Informatics Agricultural Engineer" course in the 2002/2003 academic year. In the 2010/2011 academic year the last group was finished their comprehensive agro-informatics studies. The Hungarian agro-food sector, Governmental offices demanded to start this course. The rate of informatics knowledge were approximately 40 percent during the courses. During this time the higher education reform was started according to the Bologna declaration. The new Hungarian Higher Education system was introduced in the 2006/2007 academic year (parallel with the traditional five years courses). From this date

two-tier (separate bachelor-and-master-level) programs were introduced on the 3 + 2 model in certain disciplines. In 2013 we established a new

MSc education program in agro-informatics. The development process can be seen in the Fig 4.

Fig.4. Roadmap of the development in advanced IT agro-informatics education

References

1. Choi, C., Yi, M. H. The effect of the Internet on economic growth: Evidence from cross-country panel data. *Economics Letters*. Volume 105. Issue 1. October 2009. pp. 39–41.
2. Koutroumpis, P. The economic impact of broadband on growth: A simultaneous approach. *Telecommunications Policy*. Volume 33. Issue 9. October 2009. pp. 471–485. ISSN: 0308-5961
3. LaRose, R., Stover, S., Gregg, J. L., Straubhaar, J. The impact of rural broadband development: Lessons from a natural field experiment. *Government Information Quarterly*. 2011, 28. pp. 91-100. ISSN: 0740-624X
4. Péntek, Á., Herdon, M. Digital Business Ecosystem for Rural Areas. *Joint International Conference Proceedings*, Prague, Life Science University, 2009. pp. 191-196.
5. Picot, A., Wernick, C. The role of government in broadband access. *Telecommunication Policy*. 2007, 31. pp. 660-674. ISSN 0308-5961
6. Ruhle, E., Brusic, I., Kittl, J., Ehrler, M. Next Generation Access (NGA) supply side interventions – An international comparison. *Telecommunication Policy*. 2011, Vol. 35. Issues 9-10. pp. 794-803. ISSN: 0308-5961
7. Struzak, R. Broadband Internet in EU countries – Limits to growth. *IEEE Communication Magazine*. 2010. pp. 52-57. ISSN 0163-6804
8. Szilágyi, R. New information and communication technologies in agriculture - factors, drivers and application possibilities. *Journal of Agricultural Informatics*, 2012 Vol. 3, No. 1 pp. 10-18. ISSN 2061-862X

ECONOMETRIC STUDY OF THE EVOLUTION OF BRASOV LODGING INDUSTRY AND TOURISM MARKET

Gabriel-Justin FLORESCU

Abstract: *Given the contribution of tourism industry in the Brasov County economy, local authorities, hoteliers and all other stakeholders have to have a vast view to increase Brasov destination market share of the tourist arrivals. Therefore, this study attempts to investigate the short run demand from domestic tourists by using an econometric model. Empirical studies on tourism field for Brasov County have illustrated little attention in modelling properly the demand function for tourism and identifying the main basis for tourism flows, including the supply factors, as accommodation capacity, which might influence substantially the tourism performance, and this is the objective of this study.*

Keywords: *tourism demand, accommodation capacity in operation, forecast, regression, econometric model.*

1. Introduction

Tourism is an important economic sector of Brasov County, generating a considerable amount of exports, income from fees and taxes, under the ownership of a significant proportion of the employed population. In 2013, Brasov County was visited by 835,044 tourists, of which 708,775 Romanian and 126,269 foreign. However, it should be noted that the number of visitors has dropped steeply in 2009, as direct consequence of the economic crisis.

Tourist arrivals represent the starting mechanism of the Brasov hotel industry. The higher the number of tourists in Brasov County, the greater the benefits generated by the tourism activity.

The objective of this study is the analysis of Brasov Tourist market after the year 2000, in order to assess its evolution and trends and to identify solutions for the sustainable development of the hotel industry in the area of Brasov. The operators of hotels need to observe the increase of the inter-regional competition and the demands of the current generations of tourists regarding the new meanings of the hotel comfort and quality services in the Internet era.

2. Working method

An econometric model is proposed in the content of the article to determine the number of

tourist arrivals in Brasov County according to the simultaneous influence of two main factors, acting as explanatory variables. Furthermore, the multiple regression model allows the analysis of correlations between variables, the explanatory variables significance testing, determining the validity of the multiple regression model and its use for forecasting.

3. Results and discussions

Accommodation capacity has grown very rapidly in the period after 2001, even during the crisis. The tourist offer, i.e. the number of bed nights available in accommodation structures has been much higher than the tourism demand throughout the whole period analysed, and the economic crisis has boosted the excess capacity.

The evolution of accommodation capacity in operation in Brasov County, compared to tourist arrivals and the number of overnight stays in 2001-2013, shown in Figure 1 as a chart, highlights the imbalance between the supply of rooms for accommodation and the tourism demand, as well as the intensification of this imbalance in recent years. Accordingly, the average occupancy level dropped dramatically after 2008, reaching under 19.67% in 2013. This occupancy percentage demonstrates a moment of unsustainable development of tourism in Brasov.

Fig. 1. Market developments in Brasov County between 2001 and 2013

The operators of hotels in Brasov County responded to the crisis by reducing the rates for accommodation, in hopes of maintaining the interest of potential tourists, even if their discretionary income was reduced. However, the inelastic demand in the sector as a whole led to lower revenue of operators of tourism establishments and to substantially reduced profits or even to registering losses.

This process was emphasized by the actions of non-viable long-term hotels, which have reduced rates for accommodation down to unsustainable levels, because of the overriding need to free up cash flow under any conditions.

Investments in recent years were due to some passionate decisions on behalf of the investors, and not to professional analyses regarding the sector's perspective.

Grants funding has supported investments in tourist accommodation capacities, but nobody pulled a wake-up call about the potential impact of the rapid increase of the accommodation capacity, of the excess offer of rooms for accommodation on the viability of recently opened or older hotel businesses and the local tourism sector in general.

The situation was aggravated by the high prices of resources from the Romanian economy: energy prices 50% higher than in Bulgaria for instance, high costs of the staff because of the high level of labour taxation, loan interest rates

substantially higher than in other European countries.

Hotel operators have been caught in the trap of low tariffs for the services rendered, seconded by high costs. Not to forget the action of political actors interested solely in the short-term effect of the decisions made. All of these are detrimental to the general evolution of the tourism sector of Brasov.

The evolution of tourist arrivals and overnight stays looks sinusoidal, with successive increases and decreases. The minimum value of arrivals is recorded in 2002, when Brasov County received 290.3 thousand tourists, and the maximum level of 835.0 thousand arrivals was reached in 2013. The general trend is ascending over the analysed period.

The delay of almost a year of the manifested effects of the economic crisis in Romania in relation to Western States decisively influenced the evolution of demand for tourist accommodation capacity in Brasov County too, the steepest decline taking place in 2009, when the number of tourist arrivals was 451.7 thousand, 22% lower than in the previous year. The dynamics of the number of overnight stays was similar, as one may see in the chart shown in Fig. 1.

Unlike the tourist demand indicators taken into consideration, the accommodation capacity in operation – the indicator selected to emphasize the dynamics of the tourist offer - has increased

continuously and quickly during the years of economic crisis too.

The number of bed nights available was 82% higher in 2013, compared to the situation in 2008, as shown by the data presented in Table 1.

In consequence, the indicator which characterizes the relationship between tourist

demand and supply-average degree of accommodation capacity in function - was also a sine wave, but at a very low level, oscillating between 19.56% and 26.07% over the analysed period.

Tabel 1. Market developments in Braşov County between 2001 and 2013

Year	Tourism supply			Tourism demand		Average occupancy rate (%)
	Number of accommodation capacities	Accommodation capacity (beds)	accommodation capacity in operation (thousands bednights)	Tourist arrivals (thousands)	Overnights (thousands)	
2001	323	10,276	3,670.3	328.3	884.6	24.10
2002	338	9,528	3,297.1	290.3	779.3	23.64
2003	370	9,611	3,649.9	324.8	823.3	22.56
2004	431	11,380	3,900.5	421.8	960.8	24.63
2005	403	12,037	4,219.0	448.1	1,000.3	23.71
2006	489	13,883	4,527.0	484.0	1,054.9	23.30
2007	471	12,634	4,704.7	556.8	1,191.5	25.33
2008	493	15,729	4,907.8	582.0	1,279.6	26.07
2009	482	14,728	5,034.8	451.7	985.0	19.56
2010	474	16,742	5,221.1	510.2	1,078.3	20.65
2011	526	17,795	5,903.9	642.8	1,329.8	22.52
2012	646	21,699	7,327.9	737.8	1,486.5	20.29
2013	750	25,524	8,916.5	835.0	1,754.3	19.67

The evolution of tourism flow is influenced by a complex of factors, some essential, others with less significant influence, many of them being unpredictable.

The tourism demand forecast raises some specific problems:

- The emergence of the new hospitality capacities, of new forms of sales and marketing, can influence current trends;
- Tourism has the handicap of a lack of historical compatible data;
- There is a large number of social, political, economic variables, majorly affecting tourist flows;
- Tourism is highly vulnerable to terrorism, epidemic diseases, natural disasters and political changes.

Knowing the range of future development of the tourism demand should provide sufficient information for the policy management of the Brasov County, as a tourist destination, limiting

the uncertainty and limiting the risk of investments.

According to Archer (quoted by Norbert Vanhove in *The Economics of Tourism Destinations*, 2011), the estimation of tourism demand requires both rigorous scientific analysis, and practical experience, and the accuracy of the information relating to the history of the tourist phenomenon is the starting point.

Causal analysis methods of the tourism phenomenon, such as the regression analysis, seek to explain why the dependent variable changes over time, starting from the assumption that the changes involved are the effect of the influence of one or more independent variables. Tourism demand is such a complex phenomenon that, in most cases, several factors have impact simultaneously on the dependent variable.

In most cases, dependent variables in regression models in tourism are: tourist arrivals, overnight stays or expenses of tourists in a certain destination.

Regarding independent variables, Frechtling (quoted by N. Vanhove in *The Economics of Tourism Destinations*, 2011) distinguishes between: (a) momentum factors, also named push factors: those home market characteristics which encourage people to go on trips, such as family income; (b) factors of attraction, the pull factors: those attracting tourists to a specific destination, such as the existence of accommodation facilities at destination and the comfort level; (c) resistance factors, such as terrorism or prices.

4. Forecasting the number of tourist arrivals using the multiple regression model

The multiple regression analysis allows the estimation of the parameters of the econometric model to determine the number of tourist arrivals in Brasov County according to the simultaneous influence of several factors, acting as explanatory variables. Furthermore, the multiple regression model allows the analysis of correlations between variables, the explanatory variables significance testing, determining the validity of the multiple regression model and its use for forecasting.

Taking into account the particularities of the tourism demand according to the basin of origin of tourists (Romanians or foreigners), this work analyses the Romanian tourist flows in Brasov County, considering the following variables:

- Dependent variable: number of tourist arrivals;
- Explanatory variables: (1) number of accommodation establishments in Brasov County - attraction factor; (2) GDP volume of the national economy - push factor.

The data regarding the evolution of the explanatory variables and the explained variable is shown in Tabel 2.

Data on the number of tourist arrivals and the number of accommodation establishments in Brasov County between 2001 and 2013 was obtained by consulting the website of the National Institute of Statistics www.insse.ro; the data on the volume of GDP was obtained by consulting the website of the World Bank www.worldbank.org

Tabel 2. Multiple regression indicators dynamics

Year	Number of accommodation establishments	GDP (Millions \$)	Observed number of arrivals (Thousands)
2001	323	40,586	260.0
2002	338	45,985	219.1
2003	370	59,466	251.1
2004	431	75,795	329.5
2005	403	99,172	359.3
2006	489	122,696	401.3
2007	471	170,755	452.6
2008	493	205,790	480.4
2009	482	164,948	376.7
2010	474	164,781	422.1
2011	526	183,561	538.3
2012	646	169,177	626.9
2013	750	189,682	708.8

The features of the econometric model associated with the relationship between the

dependent variable selected and the two independent variables are presented in Table 3:

Table 3. Table of regression model with two explanatory variables

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.977110436
R Square	0.954744803
Adjusted R Square	0.945693764
Standard Error	33.86445423
Observations	13

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	2	241939.6268	120969.8	105.485	1.8982E-07
Residual	10	11468.0126	1146.801		
Total	12	253407.6394			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	-117.385861	42.65447579	-2.75202	0.02041	-212.425955	-22.3457662
X Variable 1	0.963475583	0.128750472	7.483278	2.1E-05	0.676601656	1.25034951
X Variable 2	0.000580477	0.000258232	2.247888	0.04835	5.09975E-06	0.001155855

Quality adjustment was calculated as the ratio between the variance explained by the model and the total variance of the dependent variable. The value of the quality adjustment is $R^2 = 0.9457$, which means that the total variance is almost entirely explained by the model; the model is well chosen.

The multiple correlation ratio $R = 0.9771$ shows a very strong intensity of the simultaneous correlation between the endogenous variable "number of tourist arrivals in Brasov County" and the exogenous variables „ number of accommodation establishments in Brasov County" – x_1 , "volume of GDP in Romania" – x_2 .

The expectations regarding positive coefficients for the explanatory variables, were confirmed: the purchase desire of the Romanians for tourist consumption in destinations in Brasov County increases in direct proportion to the number of accommodation establishments in operation (which implies comfort diversity and high competition between hoteliers to attract tourists, thus a favourable quality/price ratio), as well as to the evolution of the GDP volume (indicator giving a real picture of the performance of the Romanian economy and, finally, of the people's welfare).

The regression shown in Table 3 is globally significant because the theoretical value $F_{2,10}^{\alpha=5\%} = 4.10$ is lower than the calculated value $F^* = 105.48$, for a significance threshold of 0.000019%.

The analysis of the individual tests of significance of the coefficients for each explanatory variable in the model, based on Student ratios, compared to the theoretical value Student for $\alpha = 5\%$ and 10 degrees of freedom $t_{10}^{\alpha=0,025} = 2.23$ leads to the following conclusions:

- $|t_{\hat{a}_1}^*| = 7.48 > 2.23$, hence $\hat{a}_1 \neq 0$, so variable x_1 contributes to the expansion of the variance of variable y ;
- $|t_{\hat{a}_2}^*| = 2.25 > 2.23$, hence $\hat{a}_2 \neq 0$, so variable x_2 contributes to the expansion of the variance of variable y .

The *P-value*, the lowest value from which the estimator coefficients are significantly different from zero, is less than 5% in the case of each explanatory variable of the selected model, with a probability of at least 95%.

Also, the claim is valid for the coefficient \hat{a}_0 , for which the calculated Student ratio $|t_{\hat{a}_0}^*| = 2.75$ is bigger than the theoretical one, and the *P-value* shows that the estimator \hat{a}_0 becomes

significantly different from zero starting with a significance threshold of 2%, compared to the acceptable level of 5%.

Confidence intervals for the constant estimator and for the two estimators of the explanatory variables coefficients are:

- $IC_{\hat{\alpha}_0}$: [-212.426 ; -22.3458] does not contain the zero value;
- $IC_{\hat{\alpha}_1}$: [0.6766 ; 1.2503] does not contain the zero value and has the sign „+” of the direct connection between the explained variable and the explanatory variable „number of

accommodation establishments in Brasov County”;

- $IC_{\hat{\alpha}_2}$: [0.000005 ; 0.0012] does not contain the zero value and has the sign „+” of the direct connection between the explained variable and the explanatory variable „volume of GDP in Romania”.

The model identified is: $\hat{y}_t = -117.3859 + 0.9635 \cdot x_1 + 0.0006 \cdot x_2$. The theoretical values \hat{y}_t obtained by applying the model are presented in Table 4:

Table 4. The observed values of the variables, and the theoretical amount of tourist arrivals determined by the regression model

Year	Number of accommodation establishments	GDP (Millions \$)	Observed number of arrivals (Thousands)	Theoretical number of arrivals \hat{y}_t (Thousands)
2001	323	40,586	260.0	218.1762
2002	338	45,985	219.1	235.8681
2003	370	59,466	251.1	274.7887
2004	431	75,795	329.5	343.3596
2005	403	99,172	359.3	330.4078
2006	489	122,696	401.3	427.3832
2007	471	170,755	452.6	438.8756
2008	493	205,790	480.4	481.0936
2009	482	164,948	376.7	445.9899
2010	474	164,781	422.1	438.1817
2011	526	183,561	538.3	499.5517
2012	646	169,177	626.9	606.5413
2013	750	189,682	708.8	719.0483

The evolution of the theoretical values \hat{y}_t is presented in Figure 2, on the same chart with the values observed. One may notice that the two

curves have the same shape. The distances show there are other possible explanatory variables:

Fig. 2. Evolution of tourist arrivals in Brasov County from 2001 to 2013 and their adjustment

This statistical analysis shows that the model closely approximates the variance of the endogenous variable and, therefore, is used for the development of forecasts for 2014 and 2015. In order to forecast the number of tourist arrivals in 2014 and 2015 we need to know the prognosis of the evolution of the two explanatory variables next couple of years:

- the number of accommodation establishments will increase to 786 in 2014 and 821 in 2015 respectively, according to the author's estimates, based on the absolute average modification method applied to the data published by the National Institute of Statistics;
- gross domestic product will grow with 2.2% in 2014 and with 2.5% in 2015, according to the forecasts of the Romanian government.

By substituting the explanatory variables with the estimated values for the years 2014 and 2015, we obtain the following values of the explained variable:

- $\hat{Y}_{2014} = 755.837$ thousands of Romanian tourists;
- $\hat{Y}_{2015} = 793.029$ thousands of Romanian tourists.

Therefore, the forecast of the number of tourist arrivals in Brasov County seeks further growth trend, as to approach the threshold of 800 thousand arrivals of Romanian tourists by the end of 2015, which is plotted in Figure 3.

The econometric model could be improved by refining the explanatory variables and by introducing dummy variables to take into account the influence of economic and political events such as the conflict of Ukraine and the running of Brasov international airport.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the number of tourist arrivals in Brasov County in the period 2001-2013, adjustment and their forecast in 2014-2015.

Conclusions

The econometric model used highlights that between the number of Romanian tourist arrivals in the County of Brasov and the accommodation capacity there is a very strong relationship, in both directions.

The statistical analysis proves that the tourist offer in Brasov County grew strongly in the period 2001-2013, while tourism demand has not kept pace despite the strategy adopted by tourism operators to diminish tariffs aggressively. At the same time, the increased dependency of the tourist activity on domestic tourism is obvious. Research shows the inelastic demand to price reductions, the hotel revenue decreasing even if the number of overnight stays increased over the period. This approach of the hoteliers has clear adverse implications on profit rates and on the viability of the local tourism business.

Accordingly, the majority of accommodation establishments in Brasov County are going through serious financial difficulties.

Resolving the situation by sharply increasing tourist demand, so that the current excess capacity is covered, is improbable, as shown by the above analysis. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the main indicators of tourism demand and supply, as well as the average level of occupancy in the period 2001-2013 and the estimation for 2014 - 2015, taking into account the conclusions of this review and the following assumptions:

- Average length of stay will be maintained to 2.1 days;
- The number of arrivals of foreign tourists will increase by 2% in each of the coming years, according to the average rate of growth of the past decade.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the main indicators of tourism activity in Brasov County between 2001 and 2013 and their estimation in the period 2014-2015

Whereas, it is impossible that this level of occupancy enables the support of the activity for all structures existing at this time on the Brasov market, it is expected that the phenomenon of insolvency and bankruptcy will manifest worse in the coming years in the tourism sector. The question is to what extent the local tourist offer will be affected by this phenomenon?

If we start from the premise that an occupancy rate of around 40% ensures sustainability of a business in the hotel industry,

it would result that in the next two years approximately 42% of the current accommodation capacity in Brasov County will become inactive, in various forms: bankruptcy, voluntary reduction in accommodation capacity, the change of the profile activity etc. The graph in Figure 5 highlights the fact that such an assumption would lead to a tourist offer similar to the one of the year 2008, the first year of the economic crisis.

Fig. 5. Evolution of the average occupancy rate in Brasov County in the period 2001 – 2015, under the scenario of an accommodation capacity similar to 2008

On the one hand, we can estimate that the existence of the black or grey economy will make this process of adjustment of the tourist offer to the manifested demand less dramatic, and on the other hand it is necessary for the process to be followed by a forum of rationality, that could be a local Association of operators of accommodation establishments.

The conclusion therefore is that the unsustainable development of Brasov tourism will continue in the following period, in the absence of active policies aimed at rebalancing the relationship between tourist demand and supply in the market, including the controlled reduction of the rate of growth of the accommodation capacity.

References

- Anghelache C., Anghelache G. V., „Modele macroeconomice utilizate în analiza structurală a Produsului Intern Brut”, Revista Română de Statistică, Nr. 6/2013, pag. 8-14;
- Bălăcescu A., Zaharia M., „Analiza statistică a circulației turistice și a capacității de cazare în funcțiune în perioada 2000 – 2009 în județul Brașov”, Analele Universității „Constantin Brâncuși” din Târgu Jiu, Seria Litere și Științe Sociale, Nr. 3/2012, pag. 1-9;
- Cristureanu C., „Strategii și Tranzacții în Turismul Internațional”, Editura C. H. Beck, București, 2006, pag. 166-207;
- .
- Duguleană L., „Metode de previziune economică”, Editura Universității Transilvania Brașov, 2011, pag. 110-120;
- Gruia R., (2013): „Managementul activității hoteliere”, note de curs, Universitatea Transilvania Brașov, Facultatea de Alimentație și Turism.
- Vanhove N., „The Economics of Tourism Destinations”, Elsevier Ltd., Second edition, 2011, pag. 193-211;
- *** www.worldbank.org;
- *** www.bnr.ro;
- *** www.insse.ro

DEVELOPMENT OF BIOTECHNOLOGY COMBINED FOOD SYSTEMS ENRICHED WITH PLANT COMPLEXES ON THE BASIS OF ANIMAL ORIGIN

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Abstract: *Optimizing the combination of plant systems for the polyunsaturated fatty acids, and administering the best combinations in a food system.*

Key words: *Optimizing the combination of plant systems, polyunsaturated fatty acids in nutritional administration system.*

1. Introduction

Currently particularly relevant scientific substantiation of technological principles to create balanced foods with directionally controlled functional properties based on a combination of animal and vegetable raw materials that improve performance in chemical properties of macro-and trace element composition. Vegetable raw materials - food industry perspective. Russian research centers are actively working in the field of study and implementation of vegetable raw materials to industry. Especially important is the practical application of the results in: bakery, confectionery industry, in the production of dietary therapeutic and prophylactic purposes, baby foods in oil industry. Amaranth bagasse contains from 33 to 35% of the protein balance from 5% to 9% oil, depending on the technological conditions of pressing. Rare component in its composition is squalene. There is 100 grams of the product of its content ranges from 8-10%. Pumpkin cake is not only a valuable protein (45% crude protein) supplement, but also an excellent means of stimulating the digestive system and promotes restoration of the gastrointestinal tract, due to a significant proportion of fiber (20%) and oil. Wheat germ oil cake is a source of complete protein and biologically active substances is rich in essential

amino acids, unsaturated omega-3, 6 - fatty acids, vitamins E, B1, B2, B6, PP, pantothenic and folic acid, carotenoids, and is also rich in macro and micronutrients, among which should be allocated, such as phosphorus, calcium, potassium, magnesium, selenium, zinc. Comparative characteristics of the test materials on the physico-chemical properties, macro-and microelement composition shown in picture 1,2,3.

Statistics on Russia show that approximately 80% of our population consumes insufficient essential fatty acids. Daily demand for them is 10-20% of total calories derived. Lack of these nutrients is a serious threat to health. The greatest attention of specialists in the field of preventive nutrition attracts the use of Ω -3 and Ω -6 fatty acids. It is known that the immunomodulatory effect of PFA alimentary Incoming implemented in accordance with their amounts in the diet, ingredient composition, the ratio of polyunsaturated fatty acids and saturated fatty acids, PFA Ω -6 and Ω -3 PFA, but also the presence of antioxidants. One of the stages in the transformation of the traditional product in a product with high biological efficiency is changing the composition of the fat phase by selecting balanced by the number and ratio of PFA fat base.

Fig. 1 - Comparative characteristics of the test materials

Currently active work on blending vegetable oils with the aim of developing products designed to supply a healthy person. Examples of experimental balanced ratio Ω -6: Ω -3 fatty acids consisting of two or three kinds of vegetative raw material, the experiments shown below. Experience number 1 - consists of three components: WG: AS: PS - 4,5:4:1,5. Experience number 2 - WG: AS = 5:5; experience number 3 - AS: PS = 6:4; experience number 4 - WG: PS = 9:1.

Fig. 2 - Comparative characteristics of the test materials

The picture below shows the amino acid composition of food products with optimized plant raw material for in quantity and ratio of PFA fat base.

Fig. 3 - Comparative characteristics of the test materials

Fig. 4 - Comparative characteristics of the test materials

As a result of experimental studies, it can be concluded that the introduction of plant components to be formulated in the assigned amount does not reduce the protein content and energy value of biological products. Thus, the experimental samples are balanced by the number and ratio of PFA fat-content and significantly large amounts of micronutrients, which contains plant material, enriched culinary

product control and in many respects satisfy the daily physiological need. Because of the low cost of plant materials - cost of experimental samples decrease by 3-5%.

References

1. A collection of recipes for dishes and culinary products. Regulatory documentation for catering: textbook/compl. Alexander Rumyantsev, 3 ed., revised. and extras. -M.: publishing house «business and service ".
2. Dubtsov G.g. cooking technology: Stud. Manual for the media. Prof. Education-2 Ed. rubbed off. -M.: Publishing Center "Academy"; Skill, 2002.
3. Voyutsky, V.V. Colloid chemistry course [Text] / V.V. Voyutsky. - M.: "Chemistry", 1975.
4. The chemical composition of food products. Reference tables of content of major nutrients and energy value of food and culinary products. - M.: Light and food industry, 1984.
5. Laboratory workshop on colloid chemistry [Text] / T.S. Kornienko, S.I. Garshina, T.V. Mastukova and others. - Voronezh, VSTA, 2001.5. Pinchuk, L.G. Biochemistry: Textbook. / L.G. Pinchuk, E.P. Zinkevich, S.B. Gridina; Kemerovo Technological Institute of food industry. - Kemerovo, 2011. - 364 p.
6. Laboratory workshop in physical chemistry [Text] / N.M. Podgornova, T.S. Kornienko, S.I. Garshina and others - Voronezh, VSTA, 2005.
7. Nekryach, E.F. Heats of wetting and hydrophilicity of some high-molecular compounds [Text]: abstract of the thesis of Cand. Chem. Sc. / E.F. Nekryach. - Kyiv, 1954.

ON A NEW RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND PARTICLE SIZE IN A PROCESSES OF CRUSHING AND GRINDING

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Abstract: *We consider the problem of the relationship between the energy consumption and particle size in a processes of crushing and grinding. We show that experiments agree with the theoretical estimation of the energy consumption in a processes of crushing and grinding.*

Key words: *grinding, energy consumption.*

1. Introduction

It is well known that in a processes of crushing and grinding, a working parts of a machine act against the molecular interaction forces in the particles, which results in appearing of new surfaces [1], [2], whose area depends on the strength of the environment, type of the mechanical impact, and the way it is applied [3], [4]. The known theories (by Kirpichev and Kick, Aphanasiev and Rittinger, Bond, Rebinder, Tanaka, et al.) usually just try to describe the nature of the process. They do not take into account all the variety of the phenomena taking place in the material, and, hence, can not be used for precise calculation of the parameters of a particular process [5].

Besides, all these theories are based (explicitly or implicitly) on the assumption that the material strength is a physical constant, though in fact it can change as much as up to $10^3 \dots 10^4$ times and depends on the material properties, mill design, and a working parts of a machine working condition [3]. That is why the desired relationship is usually found experimentally, with the material properties, desired product size, and type and design of the a working parts of a machine taken into account.

2. Problem statement

According to Rittinger's law (1867), the unit energy E required for crushing is proportional to the new surface area appeared in the process. It is given by:

$$E = k \left(\frac{1}{x_2} - \frac{1}{x_1} \right), \quad (1)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the linear sizes of the original particles and the resulting product respectively, and k is a constant.

It is assumed that Rittinger law holds for fragile materials, which have destruction planes and are characterized by new clefs appearing.

$$E = k_1 \lg \frac{x_1}{x_2} \quad (2)$$

Both (1) and (2) show that infinite energy is required only when particles are crushed to certain minimal size $x_2 = x_{\min}$, which is

If crushing of a solid immediately results in one class of particles, no matter what the original size x_1 is, Kick's law (1883) holds:

determined by technological reasons so that further crushing does not make sense.

For this reason, T. Tanaka [6] suggested the following crushing law:

$$\frac{dS}{dE} = k(S_\infty - S), \quad (3)$$

where S is the material surface area per unit, and S_∞ is the limit area, after which the process practically stops.

The above consideration suggests a correction to Rittinger's (1) and Kick's (2) are based on the assumption that the crushing unit energy consumption depend only on the linear

sizes of the original particles and the product, i.e., $E = f(x_1, x_2)$.

Considering the latter statement, it seems more reasonable to assume that, in fact, the unit energy depends on the deviation of the linear sizes from their minimal limit value. Then Rittinger's law takes the form:

$$E = k \left(\frac{1}{\Delta x_2} - \frac{1}{\Delta x_1} \right), \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta x_1 = x_1 - x_{\min}$ and $\Delta x_2 = x_2 - x_{\min}$.

Similarly, Kick's law changes to:

$$E = k_1 \lg \frac{\Delta x_1}{\Delta x_2} \quad (5)$$

From (4) and (5) one can see that, when x_1 increase, the unit energy grows at the rate $V_E = k/x_2^2$ to its limit value k/x_2 , but not more. On the other hand, experiments show that unlimited increase of the original product linear sizes results in also unlimited growth of the unit energy required for crushing to the size

$x_2 = x_{\min}$. That is why it is reasonable to suggest a dependence of x_1 on and x_2 which would give linear energy consumption. Among such mathematical function the most suitable seems to be the following:

$$E = k^* \left[\left(\frac{x_1}{x_2} \right)^{\alpha^*} - \left(\frac{x_2 - x_{\min}}{x_1 - x_{\min}} \right)^{\beta^*} \right], \quad (6)$$

where k^* , α^* , β^* are some parameters which depend on the material to be crushed and its strength and mechanical characteristics. They are to be found in an experiment.

$\frac{x_2 - x_{\min}}{x_1 - x_{\min}}$ - amendment to the existent scientific hypothesis.

Values of making dependences (6) hesitate in next ranges:

$$1 \leq \frac{x_1}{x_2} \leq \frac{x_1}{x_{\min}}, \quad 1 \geq \frac{x_2 - x_{\min}}{x_1 - x_{\min}} \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

$$0 \leq E \leq k^* \frac{x_1}{x_{\min}}, \quad \frac{k^*}{x_2} \geq V_E \geq \frac{k^*}{x_1^2} \quad (8)$$

It is necessary to establish that on the sizes of parameters, it is possible to pick up values and, at that specific energy arrives at a minimum in a range (8).

Conclusion

Possibility of development of recommendation of the most rational (effective)

use of grinding down machines of certain having a special purpose construction appears thus.

Given k^* , α^* , β^* , one can find the values x_1 and x_2 which minimize the unit crushing energy.

This enables one to work out certain recommendations on the most rational usage of a mill of a particular design.

References

1. Гу т и я р . ЕМ об'ємної теорії дроблення //Журнал «Izvestia Moscovskoi selskohoziastvennoy akademii im. Timireazeva», 1961, vyp. 4. – с. 163-166.
2. Kupriř Ia. I. Fizico-himicheskie osnovy razmola zerna. M., Zagotizdat, 1964 – s. 27-54.
3. Akunov V.I. Elementy kiberneticheskoy teorii mel'nit. Trudy NII Tsement. M., 1976, vyp. 36. – s. 130-154.
4. Kachanov L.M. Osnovy mehaniki razrusheniy. M., Nauka, 1974 – с. 711.
5. Ospanov A.A. Tehnologiya izmelchenia pishchevyyh materialov (uchebnik), Almaty, KazHAU, 2013 – s. 59-63.
6. Tanaka T. Otpavnaya tochka sovremennyh issledovaniy v teorii izmelchenia. PM GFNTB-1-23. Biuro perevodov VINITI, 1964.

VACUUM-SUBLIMATION DRYING OF NATIONAL MILK DRINKS – SHUBAT AND KOUMISS – WHEN IMPOSING MAGNETIC AND SUPER HIGH-FREQUENCY FIELDS

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Abstract: *One of the most effective methods of conservation of perishable foodstuff is sublimation drying in vacuum.*

Rather high cost of a received product belongs to the main obstacle in a way of widespread introduction of such drying. Therefore the process intensification at the fullest preservation of natural properties of an initial product will be the main objective in this area that, eventually, can lead to reduction in cost of cost of production.

It is especially important for the products possessing medical properties, for example, for such national milk drinks of health and youth, as shubat and koumiss.

In this direction we developed and investigated a new way of vacuum-sublimation drying of dairy products in which preliminary magnetic processing of initial raw materials and super high-frequency heating is used.

Key words: *milk drying, vacuum, high frequency field.*

1. Introduction

Object of research – the national milk drinks possessing medical properties – shubat and koumiss.

The work purpose – an intensification of processes of vacuum-sublimation drying of milk drinks – shubat and koumiss – when using super high-frequency heating and preliminary magnetic processing of processed raw materials.

Methodology of carrying out work: detailed scientific pilot study of influence of magnetic processing and super high-frequency heating on heat physical properties of drinks and intensity of stages of processes of drying with the critical analysis and comparison of the received results with known data in scientific and patent literature. Check of the received results in industrial conditions.

During the conducted researches the following results are received.

2. Problem statement

Prospects of use for drying of popular national milk drinks – shubat and the koumiss possessing improving and medical properties – with imposing of magnetic and super high-frequency fields are shown a vacuum-sublimation way.

The device design for magnetic processing of liquids is developed and tested [1].

The device for magnetic processing of liquids effectively works at considerable fluctuations of an expense that is very important for working conditions.

It is established that magnetic processing of milk drinks reduces time of their freezing (on the average by 16 %) and drying (on the average for 15 %), increases activity of water, coefficient of diffusion of moisture and a hydrogen indicator p H. The greatest effect of magnetic processing is reached at intensity of a magnetic field $1,2 \cdot 10^5$ A/m.

At smaller values the effect of magnetic processing decreased, and at great values indicators of magnetic processing remained at one level, but energy consumption on carrying out magnetic processing increased.

Frequency of a field of the super high-frequency heating, excluding ionization of the discharged steam-gas mix in the camera made 2450 MHz, the power of the radiation of 750 W.

Regularities of course of processes of freezing and drying at the drinks processed and raw by a magnetic field, nature of change of activity of water, coefficient of diffusion of moisture and a hydrogen indicator p Hn drinks are studied.

On the basis of physical modeling the equations for calculation of duration of freezing, drying, and also the empirical equations for calculation of activity of water, coefficient of diffusion of moisture and a hydrogen indicator p H are received.

The new high-intensity way of vacuum-sublimation drying in which in uniform technological process magnetic processing and super high-frequency heating are at the same time used is developed [2].

Table 1. Chemical composition of dairy products

Indicators	Shubat				Koumiss			
	the natural	the dry	the restored	difference (in %)	the natural	the dry	the restored	difference (in %)
Proteins, g / 100 g product	3,89	31,72	3,78	2,83	2,96	32,48	2,90	2,03
Fats	4,30	32,90	4,21	2,09	2,10	25,97	2,13	1,41
Carbohydrates	3,08	23,01	3,03	1,62	2,43	28,89	2,38	2,06
moisture	87,83	3,70	88,01	0,20	91,91	4,07	92,01	0,11
ashes	1,00	8,67	0,97	3,00	0,60	8,59	0,58	3,33
Power value, kcal / 100 g	67	509	64	4,48	48	646	46	4,17
Vitamins, mg / 100 g product	9,57	65,73	9,347	2,33	10,42	68,80	10,232	1,80
thiamin	0,07	0,53	0,068	2,86	0,03	0,46	0,029	3,33
Riboflavin	0,06	0,54	0,058	3,33	0,04	0,64	0,039	2,50
Niacin	0,20	1,55	0,195	2,50	0,11	1,75	0,108	1,82
Vitamin C	9,10	62,03	8,89	2,31	10,2	65,04	10,017	1,79
Vitamin E	0,14	1,08	0,136	2,86	0,04	0,91	0,039	2,50
Irreplaceable amino acids, g / 100 g product	1,714	12,583	1,650	3,73	1,291	14,027	1,247	3,49
Replaceable amino acids, g / 100 g product	2,135	19,014	2,104	1,45	1,576	18,236	1,554	1,39
Saturated fatty acids, % to the sum of fatty acids	47,1	47,25	47,39	0,66	42,1	42,69	43,05	2,21
The monounsaturated fatty acids, % to the sum of fatty acids	48,7	48,54	48,39	0,90	47,7	47,21	46,99	1,49
The polynsaturated fatty acids, % to the sum of fatty acids	4,2	4,21	4,22	0,24	10,2	10,10	9,96	2,35

Trial tests of the developed way were carried out [3].

They confirmed results of laboratory researches and showed that the general duration of drying at the drinks processed by a magnetic field was reduced on 20÷25 %.

On new technology the high-quality dry product with almost full preservation of properties of a natural product was received, namely: colors, smell, taste, nutrients and vitamins.

The assessment of quality of products of sublimation drying was carried out in laboratory of quality control and safety of food of JSC "Kazakh Academy of Food".

As criteria of an assessment the chemical composition and organoleptic indicators of the initial (natural) and final products of processing served. Chemical compositions of products in three of their states were investigated: fresh (natural); the dry ambassador of vacuum and sublimation drying with use of magnetic processing and super high-frequency heating; the restored.

Food components (proteins, fats, carbohydrates), the power value, vitamin, amino acids and fatty acids structures of the studied dairy products were defined. Results of analyses are given in the table.

Comparison of the recorded results shows that application of magnetic processing and super high-frequency heating don't change a chemical composition of processed products, but significantly intensify freezing and drying processes that raises economic indicators of technology.

The received products of processing – dry shubat and koumiss – from the point of view of a chemical composition slightly differ from initial (natural) and the most important, in the final products almost their medical (vitamin) components completely remained.

Dry products at restoration were quickly dissolved, getting a consistence and the aroma not different from a fresh natural product.

It was confirmed and at an organoleptic assessment of dry products by carrying out tasting of properties of products on five-point system. The shubat and koumiss samples subjected to influence of a magnetic field, and also control samples of shubat and the koumiss, not passed processing by a magnetic field were tasted.

Tasted samples were frozen at a temperature of -18 °C and dried up by a sublimation method with use of super high-frequency energy in semi-working conditions, and then before tasting are flooded in the ratio: 1 h. dry product: 10 h. the boiled water cooled to 45 °C.

Acts of tasting note lack of any changes of the organoleptic indicators caused by action of a magnetic field and super high-frequency heating.

Conclusions

The developed way can be used when drying milk drinks – shubat and koumiss – and other liquid foodstuff.

Expected assumptions of development of object of research: further researches for the purpose of definition of possibility of use of the developed way are necessary for drying of milk, vegetable and fruit juice and precisely to install the theoretical mechanism of action of a magnetic field on liquid solutions.

References

1. No. 7130 Patent RK. The device for magnetic processing of liquid // Shingisov A.U., Timurbekova A.K., Timurbekov E.K. It is published 15.02.1999.
2. No. 13851 Patent RK. Way of sublimation drying of milk // Timurbekova A.K. It is published 15.01.2004.
3. Chomanov U.Ch., Kaziyev M.T., Timurbekova A.K. Industrial tests of a new way and installation for vacuum-sublimation drying of shubat and koumiss // The Messenger of agricultural science of Kazakhstan. – 2005 . – No. 4. – Page 53-54.

STUDY ON THE COMPLIANCE WITH EU FOOD LABELING REGULATIONS IN ROMANIA

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Abstract: *The paper presents the label analysis of food products collected from 8 supermarkets, 4 residential markets and 3 food products warehouses, representative for the city of Sibiu. The analysis was performed taking into account the requirements of European Legislation in the field, respectively the rules 432/2012, 1169/2011, 1924/2006. A number of 200 food labels were analysed and the graphical results are shown in this paper*

Keywords: *nutritional labeling, legislation, food products.*

1. Introductions

Nutritional labeling can help consumers to understand the relationship between certain nutrients and diseases, for choosing healthy food and/or adequate ingredients for different diets. Unfortunately in the most of the cases, only the individuals with health problems are paying attention to nutrition labeling.

The paper work contains studies as well as documentary analysis and theoretical documentations, research and experimental investigations, results and obtained conclusions regarding the labeling process of products in tight relation to the requirements imposed by the national and European legislation.

The main purpose of this work is the improvement of consumer's access to complete and correct information regarding the content and composition of the products, for the protection of their health and interests. [1] The experts in this field, frequently accentuate the necessity of regulation improvement regarding the labeling of the food products [2]. Also, is important that the consumer could be able to buy the products while being completely informed. This work presents informations on food nutrients, legislation, food composition and their influences in human diet, with the mission to identify and examine how nutritional labeling in Romania and out of country, fulfills the actual legislation requirement.

This article aims to analyze a database containing 200 food labels accordingly with following regulations:

- REGULATION (EC) NO. 1924/2006 refers to nutrition and health claims made on foods, general principles, purpose and is applied in EU Member States from 1 July 2007. For ensure a high level of protection for consumers, products put on the market, should be safe and adequately labeled. This Regulation complements the general principles in Directive 2000/13/EC and lay down specific provisions concerning the use of nutrition and health claims concerning foods. Consumers can rely on clear and accurate information on food labels, enabling them to be properly informed on the food they choose. According to European Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006, health claims should only be authorised if they are well understood by the average consumer, to equalize legislation in the EU by providing food clear rules and to help protect innovation, by ensuring that manufacturers, are not competing with false or inaccurate claims.
- REGULATION (EU) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers, refers on nutrition labeling for foodstuffs, the labeling of food ingredients, the net quantity of certain ingredient and the food, the indication of the country of origin or of the place of origin of a food, the presence of energy and certain nutrients in foods, the indication of alcoholic strength by volume in the labeling of alcoholic beverages for sale to the ultimate consumer and durability. Also very important, the Regulation No 1169/2011 mentions the obligativity of labeling of substances or products causing allergy or intolerance, any special storage condition or condition of use, instructions for use and the

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name or name of the business and address of food business operator.

- REGULATION (EU) No 432/2012 establishing a list of permitted health claims made on foods, other than those referring to the reduction of disease risk and to children's development and health, includes nutrients, substances, foods or food category, conditions of use of the claim, conditions and/or restrictions of use of the food and/or additional statement or warning. For example on the list of permitted health claims, are founded informations about fat, proteins, carbohydrates, saturates, sugar, salt, polyols, starch, fibre, MUFA, PUFA, vitamins and minerals.

2. Materials and methods

Marketing research use different investigation methods based on the obtained information both directly and indirectly, but also qualitative and quantitative methods. Among them: the method based on documentation and observation, the comparative analysis of collected data and information, the survey method, the inquiry method, the interview method and various combinations of the above mentioned methods. There are also different statistical processing methods of the collected data, taking into account the objectives of the study.

Taking into consideration the approached problematic, the following investigation methods have been selected out of the multitude of methods presented above, regarding the information presented on the labels of the food products, referring to the content and composition of products: the method based on documentation and observation, the comparative analysis of the collected data and information.

The method based on documentation and observation has been used for the establishment of the food products, from Sibiu market retailers, during the 1st of January and the 1st of December 2013, as well as the informations founded on the labels. The research was conducted by using this method consisted of two stages:

A. The first stage was the establishment of the locations. 15 observation points have been established in Sibiu, 8 supermarkets and hypermarkets, 4 residential markets and 3 alimentary products warehouses, representative for the city of Sibiu.

B. The second stage was the establishment of the main data categories, significant for the health and interests of the consumer, like: food category, the name of the food, country of food origin (location producer), the list of ingredients, observations about languages, the net quantity of the food, country of label acquisition, substances or products causing allergies or intolerances (annex II Reg. 1169), the date of minimum durability or the 'use by' date, any special storage conditions and/or conditions of use, instructions for use where it would be difficult to make appropriate use of the food in the absence of such instructions, the energy value, per portion or %, kkal and kJ.

The comparative analysis of the collected data and informations was presented. This method is an investigation technique consisting of direct information collection from the label, pursuing the presence or absence of one or more of the 29 categories in study. By processing and analysing the resulted data, the degree in which the labeling requirements stated in the specific disposition of the E.U.

3. Results and discussions

The products evaluated during the survey have origins in different countries. Fig. 1 presents the percentage of products from different countries. The products from Romania represent the highest proportion (35%) but didn't represent a majority among the evaluated products. The products from Germany, Italy and France were in high number.

The products evaluated during the project were included in eleven categories. This study did not evaluate product from the category of Fruits (Fr) and Eggs and derivatives (Eg). The product's distribution among these category are presented in

Fig. 2. The highest number of products evaluated was from the category of Vegetable (Vg) – 19%, followed by Cereal products (Ce) – 16%.

The obtained data have the following percentage: bakery products (Bd) -15% and fishery (Fh) – 14%. The smallest number of products was for the category of Drinks (Dr) – 2%. This category doesn't contain any alcoholic beverages.

Fig. 1. The product distribution by country of origin

Fig. 2. Evaluated food category

Fig. 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 present the distribution of products from Romania, Germany, Italy, France and, respective, Poland in different food category. From these figures can be observed that, with the exception of products from Romania and Poland, the highest proportion of products were from the category of cereal products (Ce) together to bakery products (Bd). The highest proportion was observed for the case of Italian products, were these category

represented 64%, with 40% for the products from the bakery products (Bd) category. Between the German products the most numerous products were from the category of dairy products (Mk). The most numerous food products from France were vegetables. The Polish products were from only two categories, fishery products (Fh) and spices, coffee and tea (Cd), 64 and, respective, 36%.

Fig. 3 Distribution of Romanian products in food category

Fig. 4. Distribution of German products in food category

Fig. 5. Distribution of Italian products in food category

Fig. 6. *Distribution of French products in food category*

Fig. 7. *Distribution of Polish products in food category*

The list of ingredients is one of the most important information about the food because it specifies all the ingredients used during the manufacture, so the consumers could choose among the products, they could avoid or prefer one or other products. The consumers may avoid some ingredients because of their believe, of health point of view and they must have the possibility to choose. The Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament specified that the list of ingredients must be present on the

food's labels (Chapter IV. Section I, Article 9, Aliniate 1, Point b).). The food products evaluated has the list of ingredients presented on the labels in 89% of cases (Fig. 8). Within the food products without specific list of ingredients only one has a complex composition (Flakes with raisins). Other food without list of ingredients were sugar, brown sugar, milk, fermented cream, cheese, butter, mineral water.

Fig. 8. The presence of the list of ingredients on the food labels

Due to the increasing of incidence in food intolerances and allergies, the law stipulates the obligation of producers to indicate the presence of allergens in food products. Within the products evaluated 36% of them present inscriptions related with the presence or absence of allergen

in products. Within the labels which contain some references to allergens 5% of them indicates the absence of some allergens (gluten, lactose, egg, etc.) and 58 of labels indicated the presence of one or more allergens (fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Type of specifications present on the food label

In 37% of cases the label had warning which contained the formulas: “the product **may contain**” or “the product **contain traces of**”. Within the products from the categories “Cereal products” and “Bread and bakery products” only 62% of them indicates the presence of allergens. We analysed the list of ingredients and in 89% of cases these products contained gluten but in 66%

of all cases the presence of gluten wasn't specified, despite on some labels were specified other allergens. We observed also one product called Premix for biscuits with oat BIO without gluten (Premix biscuiti cu ovaz Bio fara gluten) with the specification “without allergen”.

The REGULATION (EU) No 1169/2011 specified that the labels should provide to the

consumers informations about the quantity of certain ingredients or category of ingredients if appears in the name of the food or is usually associated with that name, is emphasised or is essential to characterise a food. These information is provided in 36% of labels analysed (Fig. 10) and usually appear in form of percent.

All the evaluated products have on the label or on the package the net quantity of product in units specified by EU regulation (Fig. 11).

Between the evaluated foods, only three of them didn't have any indication about the availability of the product. These products were: green tea, peppermint tea and agave syrup. All of these products have a low microbiological risk due their low water activity.

The quantity of certain ingredients or categories of ingredients

- With quantity of certain ingredients or categories of ingredients
- Without quantity of certain ingredients or categories of ingredients

Fig. 10. The quantity of certain ingredients or categories of ingredients

Fig. 11. The measure units for quantity

In fig. 12 is presented the percentage of the product with instructions about storage condition or conditions of use. Some of the products without any indications didn't required such information, like maize flour, biscuits premix, agave syrup, biscuits, honey, canned fish or

spices. Some food products didn't have information about their conditions of storage or use, despite, in our opinion, these informations were important for products like soured cream, cream (UHT), sauces, freeze vegetables.

Other important information for the consumers and for the product traceability is the name of the producers. For the 31% of the products we didn't manage to identify the producers neither on the label nor on the package. This percentage is very high.

Only 10% of the labels had informations for use. It is quite difficult to say if it is necessary to specify how must be used some products like vegetables or pasta. Many of the products could be consumed as it is (biscuits, bread) while other must be prepared (wheat or maize flour, beans, vegetables, pasta). Because the many possibilities to prepare it and a long consume of these during the ages it is no necessary to specify how to be

used. For the new or unusual products it is necessary to specify how must be consumed or prepared. Between these types of products were premixes for biscuits or muffins, bulgur, deserts from soy bean, green tea, freeze vegetables.

Specified health claims were very few, only three for tea from plants and another one for mineral water (nonsparkling, natural oligomineral water – recommended for preparations of new-born food. Special notes were on only three products: one acacia honey (ideal for children) and another two mineral water (microbiological pure).

Fig. 12. Special storage conditions and/or conditions of use

For a good understanding of the informations provided by labels the languages must be the same as the official language of the countries were the products are sold. In fig. 13 are presented the percentage of the products with the languages of the label. In one case (maize flour)

the informations were presented only in other languages than Roumanian.

Labels analysis regarding the E.U. regulation no. 1924/2006 are presented in figure 14, 15 and 16.

Fig. 13. Languages used on food labels

During our study, the nutrition parameters indicated on the products label was centralized in a data bases. As we can see in the figure 14, regarding the vitamin and mineral content, most of the manufactures do not respect the necessity

of presenting this information on the product and this is the responsibility of individual organizations to ensure their compliance with the law.

Fig. 14. Analysis of the labels regarding the indication of the fat, energy, proteins, vitamins, minerals and salt on the products

Under the law, the food company whose name is on the packaged is responsible for the accuracy of nutrition information. Regarding the MUFA and PUFA content, as we can see in the figure 15, most of the products aren't able to offer this

information. The products are sold without this main nutritive information's, a negative impact on consumer. The same results are presented in figure 16, regarding the poliols and starch content.

Fig. 15. Analysis of the labels regarding the indication of the fat, saturates, MUFA and PUFA on the products

Fig. 16. Analysis of the labels regarding the indication of the carbohydrates, sugars, polyols, starch and fibers on the products

4. Conclusions

European legislation provides a series of recommendations and obligations regarding food labeling through Regulation 432/2012, 1169/2011, and 1924/2006.

None of the analysed labels contain all the informations required by these regulations.

References

1. Ene, C.: *Securitatea alimentară – coordonate și implicații*. Ploiești, Editura Universității Petrol-Gaze din Ploiești, 2009.
2. Stănescu, D., Voicu, O.L.: *Bazele merceologiei*, București, Editura Universitară, 2009
3. Regulation 432/2012
4. Regulation 1169/2011,
5. Regulation 1924/2006.

INTEGRONIC FOOD CONCEPT

ROMULUS GRUIA

Abstract: *The study analyses the food and the alimentary act as a whole, from the perspective of multiple integrations, as a consequence of the coexistence of integrated alimentary systems, that manifests itself in concomitance both at the level of whole body in relation with the environment, and at intra body level up to the molecular level. The paper puts into evidence the nutritional systemic and dynamic complexity by defining the concept of integronic alimentation, respectively by analyzing a matrix system that may bio structurally include nutritional and environment factors, and functionally base itself on the process of emergent integronics. This approach proposes itself a profound understanding of the nutritional profile of simple, complex and composite aliments in relation to metabolic stress specific to modern feeding.*

Key words: *alimentary act, food matrix, integronics, nutrition.*

1. Introduction

In the alimentary act, aliments are carriers of **utilities** that serve or do a disservice to man through: entrances of nutritive substances -S- (with plastic role and organism growth and recovery role), entrances of energies -E- (energy brought by aliments, being in fact an essential element of metabolism, but also of energy necessary to society), as well as reception of information -I- (by sensorial values of aliments etc). In other words, aliments constitute for organism “machinery” producers of bio energy, of constructive substances and utile information coming through sensorial channels that assure a psychological satisfaction of alimentary needs. It is practically combined nutrition with metabolism especially from **epigenetic** perspective, respectively at DAN level, aspects that are directly or indirectly influenced by environment factors [Uekawa A. et al., 2009], especially through the **food profile** at the aliment level as well as at the level of integration on *man-food-environment* axes. All these are possible under the conditions in which in fact man is an informational open system, with self regulation, self reproduction and anti entropic evolution, that processes exogenous and endogenous information [Barnea and Calciu et al, 1979; Bertalanffy, 1962; Choi and Frisco Simonetta, 2010; Gruia et al, 2002; Keyes MK. et al, 2007].

Under this context, starting from the idea of the relation between **nutrition and metabolism**, one may analyze the totality of biochemical and

energetic transformations that take place in the organism bio structures [Macovschi, E., 1984] by the complex process of nutrition, in relation with multiple integration: with environment factors and, respectively, with the organism itself. "The Actors" taken into consideration are the main biochemical groups of macro and micronutrients, having energy as a "common factor", all these being in interconnection between them, but also with the environment. The natural result is nutritive equilibrium and emergent dynamics [Emmeche, 1997] in order to maintain life, estimated at level of alimentary matrix.

The energy, necessary to biosynthesis processes, mostly comes from undoing macro ergic links of different compounds. In function of the capacity to produce energy, **heterotrophy** organisms (which ensure their food using substances synthesized by other organisms), are those that *de facto* apply an **integrionic food**. We refer to a system of nutritional processes, of different types of foods, to multiple integration, to metabolism, respectively to catabolism and anabolism that goes on through a succession of numerous chemical reactions: hydrolyze, hydrogenation, dehydration, decarboxilation, dezamination, transamination, etherification, condensation, polymerization and others [Cristea-Popa Elena et al 1991, Mencinicopschi et al, 2012].

The chemical substances with energetic contribution from the composition of aliments are

well known and characterized as chemical structure, biochemical and physiological function and, therefore, one can appreciate their **nutritive value**. Warming substances are limited at *proteins, lipids* and *carbohydrates*. Associating to these ones *pro vitamins, vitamins*, certain *peptides, fat acids* and *essential amino acids*, together with *mineral substances*, it comes out the general panel of components that give aliments nutritive value.

On the other hand, a number of certifications made all over the world have proved the direct link between alimentation and the stress phenomenon, as well as between alimentation and the incidence of degenerative metabolic illnesses, "civilization illnesses" in fact, such as: cancer, cardiovascular illnesses, diabetes, rheumatism etc.[Barnea and Calciu et al, 1979; Cristea-Popa Elena et al, 1991].

Taking into consideration those mentioned above, as well as taking into account exterior and interior to organism factors concerning the feeding process, the complex notion of „**alimentation**” extends in fact on the axes "*agriculture – alimentary industry – culinary production*", but also in relation with the natural environment and demographic and social evolution over the following decades. All these induce the hypotheses of solving a complex system, by taking into consideration the phenomenon of food integration in relation with the organism, but also with the environment, at all levels and in all directions. We thus refer to the coexistence of integrated alimentary systems, that concomitantly manifest, both at the level of the whole organism in relation with the environment and at intra organismic level up to molecular level.

As a general objective we propose to ourselves, there is the elaboration of a concept that may systemically regard alimentation and the alimentary act also in an integrative dynamics and synthesize, through a new approach, a profound understanding of this complexity. The concrete aim is to understand the dynamics of these connexions through an integrative concept capable to differentiate by distinct matrixes the feeding problem with aspects referring to processes from the inside and outside of the organism and to quantify the complexity of this process in order to harmonize and equilibrate nutritional factors. The steps of the research first of all impose to elucidate aspects of alimentary profile through the system of alimentary matrixes at organism level and of integration in

the environment and then those linked to intimate level on epigenetic principles. The first step constitutes the object of the present paper.

2. Work Method

Methodologically speaking, by harmonizing nutrition with individual metabolism, with food characteristics of different populations and the impact of environment factors, we base ourselves on systemic approach techniques and on integronic dynamics [Gruia, 2000, 2002].

The analyses of such complex systems presupposes to take into consideration Substance (matter), Energy and Information, both in the relation environment - economy (including the production of aliments), and the relation man-environment and man-aliment. These interconnexions may be done by considering integration dynamics as a methodology in itself, which becomes an application of the *Theory of Ecoemergent Integronics* [Gruia, 2009]. Thus, emergent integration (in expression of *integronic eMergy*), being in relation with Information (I) associated to Energy (E) is capable to induce complementary tridimensional processes: synchronic, syncretic and synergic (S^3) ones in systems, having emergency as a resultant (emS^3) and, at systemic level, ecoemergency (eco_{emS^3}).

Therefore, the principle of *ecoemergent integronics* (eco_{emS^3} -I) may describe the coexistence of alimentary systems and the study of integration processes as a form of change of evolutive and integrative type, of interrelations between food making and environment, between living organisms and their life environment etc. There are put into evidence the relations with natural, economic and biologic environment (nutrition, metabolism), having as a resultant the achievement of something totally new and the appearance of new properties, of a superior order, translated by harmonization and nutritional equilibrium with a minimum dysfunctional and pathogenic impact.

3. Results and discussions

The nutritive equilibrium in order to maintain life presupposes pulling together and harmonizing environment factors with nutritive factors. A model we are describing in the paper here is sustained by defining a matrix system that includes the mentioned structural factors, and functionally to base itself on the process of emergent integronics.

Thus there becomes necessary the nutritional profile of the aliment that may be expressed by different parameters: nutritional density, warming density, glycemic index or charge, antioxidant score, aterogenic index, biochemical alkaline or acid profile [Mencinicopschi et al, 2012]. But in the case of processed composite food, nutritional profiles are completely modified and different from nutritional profiles of integral natural aliments. The last ones presuppose another type of analyses, based on matrix structuring with components of nutritional and environment factors.

At the basis of the **food matrixes** analyses are grouped nutritive factors in order to assure life, respectively: proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, mineral salts and vitamins. If we take into account that these ones are formed by simpler substances, the number of well individually characterized and necessary to organism compounds raises to approximately 70 – 80, from which 23 – 25 amino acids, 20 fat acids, 6 oozes, 15 – 20 mineral elements, 12 – 13 vitamins [Cristea-Popa Elena et al, 1991]. There are nutritive factors, that do not exist in nature under pure form, neither singular, but only in certain associations that constitute aliments.

The index of nutritional density is expressed by natural content –equilibrated in macronutrients, i.e. proteins (equilibrated in amino acids profile); lipids (profile equilibrated in fat, saturated, mono no saturated, poly no saturated acids); carbohydrates with rapid release, slow release (with glycolic index –GI

and moderate-small glycolic charge–GL), recommended daily consumption under 40 GL. At the same time, equilibrium may be analyzed at the level of micronutrients: macro elements (Ca, P, Mg,K, etc.) and microelements (Se, Zn, Cu, etc.), hydro and lip soluble vitamins, as well as phytochemical non-nutrients: tannins; carotenoids; flavonoids; phytoestrogens; glucosinolats [Cristea-Popa Elena and al, 1991; Mencinicopschi and al, 2012; Uekawa A. and al. 2009].

It becomes thus extremely important to study these associations necessary to ensure population with covering alimentary products as for nutritive factors. The harmonization of all these may be analyzed by **food matrix** specific to every type of aliment, matrix of an ever larger complexity, starting from agricultural aliments, then industrial ones and up to composite ones from gastronomy. The matrix represents the means through which alimentation is structured and defined from the perspective of nutritive integration and harmonization. We are referring to **integronic dynamics** of alimentary act processes, taking into account its nutritive, metabolic, genetic and ecologic components specific to complex systems.

One may thus define feeding of a holistic type, particularized nutrition and different impacts of the alimentary process, through a unitary and coherent concept of integronic alimentation. Integronic food has forms of manifestation both at super individual level and at organism level (fig.1).

The concept of integronic food is the scientific demarche that studies integrated alimentary systems (consequently to their coexistence) and processes of integration in the idea of dynamic equilibrium, having in view epigenetic and of alimentary profile elements at individual or population level, considering the dynamics of alimentary act synchronic and syncretic, based on emergent integration and synergy.

Fig.1 - Levels of action in integronic food

Complex connexions between biochemical elements of food in relation with interaction between environment, food and organism induce the idea of multiple systemic integration, forming what we could call an **integroneic matrix** necessary in nutritive equilibrium in order to maintain life of animal organisms, through processes of fundamental metabolism. In other

words, this matrix may have different(multiple) levels of integration both at super individual level, where it takes the complex form of *integroneic matrix environment-food-organism / IMEFO* (fig.2) as well as at individual level, where it constitutes itself into a *food organism matrix / FOM* (fig.3).

Fig.2. - *Integroneic matrix environment-food-body (IMEFO)*

Where,

E.F. - environment factors;

N.F. - nutritive factors from food;

FOM - Food Organism Matrix

From fig.2 it is indicated the fact that major progresses have been registered in understanding system biology, at the impact of environment factors and especially of nutritive ones, upon organism, mainly of complex interaction between

its components: genome, transcriptom, proteom and metabolom [Barnea, M., Calciu, AI, 1979; Dunn and Ellis, 2005; Gilbert and Sarkar, 2000; Lei et al, 2011; Patti et al, 2012; Veenstra, 2012].

From figure 2 it results the fact that if it is taken into consideration the principle of complementarity and that one of emergent integration one may appreciate that the idea of matrix at **population level** has a behavior similar to the genetic parameter of *heritability*, i.e. any value of the "integronic matrix environment-food-body" may have a valuable value for a certain population and generation, under certain circumstances (it can also be affected, of course, by a test error). Being a parameter of population, the *integronic matrix environment-food-organism* must be cautiously applied to individual in order to estimate nutritive equilibrium, at least until nutrigenomic studies will be sufficiently relevant in this direction.

Within the concept of integronic food and of biostructurality one may observe that individual variations, as a result of the impact of integronic dynamics, are in principle totally given by environment (E), the genotype (G) remaining practically unchanged [Gruia, 2000; Keyes and al, 2007]. The nutritive equilibrium changes more often because of temporary environment differences. Thus, *the integronic matrix environment-food-organism* may be affected by numerous factors of environment, from which more important are those linked to the intensity of activity, to age, sex, health state, the size of the analyzed group and, of course, the type of food taken into consideration (for example: agricultural or primary aliments, industrial aliments or those coming from processes specific

to food industry, composite aliments or complex dishes and drinks).

At organism level the matrix from fig.3 is based on the macronutrient trinomial (proteins, carbohydrates, fats) and the micronutrient binomial (vitamins and minerals). The metabolism of these elements is linked to the complementarity of energetic dynamics, as integrating and regulating elements, both on biunivocal links (CE₁, CE₂ and CE₃) and on interconnection with micronutrients, specific to integronic dynamics (CE_V și CE_M).

In order to harmonize all these elements, with impact on every organism, it is known that to make a menu in conformity with the principles of scientific alimentation means in fact to find, at super individual level, a modality covering the physiologic necessary for a certain category of consumers. Thus, the menu is made of alimentary products or nutritively corresponding, varied, with psycho sensorial characteristic preparations that may attract the consumer through a taste harmony, with satiety potential and that may prevent hunger sensation to appear for 4-5 hours. The menus are meant for a human population, respectively either a type group of consumers (for ex. school canteens, restaurant canteens), or to adult consumer with an average physical effort, as reference type.

The quantity of culinary preparations daily consumed must include all groups of aliments under certain proportions in order to achieve nutritive equilibrium. There may be made *izocaloric* substitutions (between aliments of the

same group) and *izotrophinic* ones (between aliments of different groups, but equivalent as for the nutritive value). The percentage share *recommended* for different groups of aliments in the daily energetic necessary is notified in table 1.

Table 1 The structure of daily energetic necessary of a type menu, on groups of aliments and macronutrients

Nr. Crt.	Group of aliments	Share in menu (%)	Carbohydrates	Fats	Proteins
1	Cereals and derivates	35	35	-	-
2	Fats	18	-	18	-
3	Vegetables - fruit	17	17	-	-
4	Milk and dairy products	2	-	-	2
5	Meat and meat products	8	-	-	8
6	Sugar and sugar products	8	8	-	-
7	Eggs	2	-	-	2
TOTAL		90	60	18	12

It may be observed, as a recommendation on integronic principles, that the share in macronutrients should be of the **60-18-12** form, respectively a menu with 60 % carbohydrates, 18% fat and 12 % proteins. This is in fact the traditional diet: 60-30-10, with recommended limits up to: 50-30-20. It is obvious that, in function of a number of mentioned factors, the share in the macro nutrient trinomial differ, i.e. it

"slips" towards one or another, in function of the demands of the consumer goal and in relation with micronutrients (vitamins and minerals), but especially in relation with food energy, the receipt or the menu as a whole. This huge variation imposes to make a different food matrix, as a complex system that may cover the integronic dynamics of all nutritive requests (fig.4).

						Fats 0-100%-0					
				20 -80-0	6	6-88-	0-80-20				
			40 -60-0	26 -68-6	14-72-14	6-68-26	0-60-40				
		60-40-0	46 -48-6	34 -52-14	26-48-26	14-52-34	6-48-46	0-40-60			
	8 0-20-0	66-28-6	50 -32-14	46 -28-26	34-32-34	26-28-46	14-32-54	6-28-66	0-20-80		
Carbohy drates 100%-0-0	8 6-8-6	70-10-20	66 -8-26	54 -12-34	46	46-8-	34-12-54	26-8-66	20-10-70	6-8-86	Protei ns 0-0-100%
		80-0-20		60 -0-40			40-0-60		20-0-80		

Fig. 4 - The matrix of the complementarity of micronutrient trinomial, with the resultant of energetic dynamics of alimentary ratio

From figure 4 results the pyramid to be found at the basis of the calculation of the caloric relation of receipts and menus, as well as the location of the recommended relation (the zone marked with three lines). On the other hand, the integration of alimentation may have multiple action and integration directions, in function of

the sustained alimentary philosophy. Among these ones, one may mention :

- the philosophy of equilibrated diet: 40-30-30 (zone marked with interrupted line) ,
- the diet with reduced(low) fats:

86-8-6	70-10-20	66-8-26	54-12-34	46-8-46	34-12-54	26-8-66	20-10-70	6-8-86
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- the diet with low carbohydrates:

6-88-6	6-68-26	6-48-46	6-28-66	6-8-86
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There must be mentioned that the model complicates itself if there is taken into consideration the micronutrient group, that represent in fact the continuation of the research. Practically speaking about the tendency of actual alimentation evolution towards low nutrient diets, i.e. the ever emphasized lack of nutritive food and the necessity to complete it with nutritive supplements. In order to avoid the paradox situation when people will eat quantitatively sufficient, but will be hungry by using nutritively "diluted" (especially in micronutrients) aliments or food, the idea of **integronic food** lays the conceptual basis for harmonizing the quantity-quality relation. The concept may then generate technologies that lead towards harmonizing the relation of aliment production, both in impact with nutritive equilibrium and satiety, and in the impact with the environment, by avoiding pollution (the known example being linked to high level in CO₂, which may increase harvest with approximately 10 %, but reduce nutritive elements with 5-10 %).

4. Conclusions

The concept of integronic food is the scientific step that studies integrated alimentary systems (consequently to their coexistence) and the integration processes, in the idea of dynamic equilibrium, having in view epigenetic and of alimentary profile elements at individual or population level, considering synchronic and syncretic the dynamics of the alimentary act, based on emergent and synergic integration.

The matrix model represent the means by which alimentation is structured and defined from the perspective of integration and nutritive harmonization, made through the integronic dynamics of alimentary act processes, taking into account its nutritive, metabolic, genetic and ecologic components, characteristic to complex systems.

The alimentary matrix may have different (multiple) levels of integration, both at super individual level, where it takes the complex form of *integronic matrix environment-food-organism*, and at individual level, where it constitutes into an *organism food matrix* and which characterizes itself by ever more profound integration stages: macronutrients, micronutrients, non-nutrients, of complementary energy etc.

References

1. Barnea, M., Calciu, Al.(edited) et al (1979): *Ecologie umana*, Editura Medicala Bucuresti, 14-28, 75.
2. Bertalanffy, Ludwig von (1962): *Modern Theories of Development. An Introduction to Theoretical Biology*, New York: Harper, pp. 21, 28-46, ASIN: B0007E65IK.
3. Cristea-Popa Elena, Aurora Popescu, E. Trutia, Veronica Dinu (1991): *Tratat de biochimie medicala*, vol. I si II Ed. Medicala, Bucuresti, 33-72.
4. Choi, S.W., Frisco Simonetta (2010): *Epigenetics: A New Bridge between Nutrition and Health*,
5. *Advances in Nutrition – an international review* - journal doi: 10.3945/an.110.1004 Adv Nutr November 2010 Adv Nutr vol. 1: 8-16.
6. Dunn WB, Ellis DI (2005): *Metabolomics: current analytical platforms and methodologies*, *Trends Analyt Chem*, 24: 285-294
7. Emmeche C. (1997): *Explaining Emergence: towards an ontology of levels*. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science* available -online.
8. Gilbert, SF; Sarkar, S. (2000): *Embracing complexity: organicism for the 21st century*". *Developmental Dynamics* 219 (1): 1-9. doi:10.1002/1097-0177(2000)9999:9999<::AID-DVDY1036>3.0.CO;2-A. PMID 10974666.
9. Gruia, R. (2000) : *Genetica si ameliorare*, Ed.Universitatii Transilvania Brasov, ISBN 973-9474- 73- X, 48-82.
10. Gruia, R. (2002) : *Ecoemergetic theory in sustainable development*, Ed. Universităţii Transilvania Braşov, ISBN 973-635-022-3, 16-29.
11. Gruia, R. (2009): *Theory of Ecoemergent Integronics (General Theory of Ecological Emergence Integration)*, The 2nd International Conference on Environmental and Geological Sciences and Engineering – directed by World Scientific and Engineering Academy and Society – WSEAS, Proceedings ISSN: 1790-2769, ISBN: 978-960-474-119-9, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, September 24-26, 168-172.
12. Gruia, R. (edited), Brătucu Ghe., Geamăn V., Cofaru C. (2002) : *Aspecte actuale ale ingineriei mediului în agricultură* Ed. Universităţii Transilvania Braşov, ISBN 973-9474-48-9, 54-78.

13. Keyes MK. et al .(2007): Older age and dietary folate are determinants of genomic and p16-specific DNA methylation in mouse colon. *J Nutr.*,137:1713–7.
14. Lei Z, Huhman DV, Sumner LW (2011): Mass spectrometry strategies in metabolomics, *J BiolChem*, 286: 25435-25442
15. Macovschi, E. (1984): Conceptia biostructurala si teoriile moleculare ale materiei vii, Editura stiintifica si enciclopedica, Editie trilingva.
16. Mencinicopschi, G, Atudosei,N, Mencinicopschi Claudia (2012): Informația matricei alimentare indicator esențial al calității alimentelor, Conferinta internationala BIOATLAS, mai 24-26.
17. Patti GJ, Yanes O, Siuzdak G, Innovation (2012): Metabolomics: the apogee of the omics trilogy, *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*,13: 263-269
18. Uekawa A. et al. (2009). Change of epigenetic control of cystathionine beta-synthase gene expression through dietary vitamin B12 is not recovered by methionine supplementation. *J Nutrigenet Nutrigenomics*. 2009;2:29–36.
19. Veenstra TD (2012): Metabolomics: the final frontier?, *Genome Med.*, 4: 31.

**UNIVERSITY RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE
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***ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGIES
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